

Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan

for

Naval Base Ventura County
San Nicolas Island, California

December 2010 updated 2015

FINAL
Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan

**Naval Base Ventura County,
San Nicolas Island, California**

December 2010
Updated December 2015

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San Nicolas Island
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Contract No: N62470-08-D-1008 TO 81

INRMP ACCEPTANCE PAGE

This Integrated Natural Resource Management Plan (INRMP) (November 2015) has been prepared in accordance with regulations, standards, and procedures of the Sikes Act, as amended (16 United States Code [U.S.C.] 670a *et seq.*), U.S. Department of Defense Instruction 4715.03, Chief of Naval Operations Instruction 5090.1D, *Environmental Readiness Program*, and in cooperation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, the California Department of Fish and Wildlife, and the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration National Marine Fisheries Service. This INRMP provides for the management and stewardship of all natural resources present on Naval Base Ventura County San Nicolas Island.

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INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PLAN
Naval Base Ventura County
Naval Outlying Landing Field, San Nicolas Island, California

APPROVAL

This Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) was prepared and reviewed in coordination with the U.S. Department of the Interior, Fish and Wildlife Service in accordance with the 2006 Memorandum of Understanding for a Cooperative Integrated Natural Resource Management Program on Military Installations. The U.S. Department of the Interior, Fish and Wildlife Service concurs that the INRMP will provide a framework to manage natural resources on Naval Base Ventura County Naval Outlying Landing Field San Nicolas Island.

For Plan Period: 2016 - 2021

Concurring Agency - U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service

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Date

INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PLAN
Naval Base Ventura County
Naval Outlying Landing Field, San Nicolas Island, California

APPROVAL

This Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) was prepared and reviewed in coordination with the National Marine Fisheries Service West Coast Region (Service). This document was adequately revised to satisfy comments and concerns presented by Service representatives. The Service concurs that this INRMP will provide a framework to manage natural resources on Naval Base Ventura County Naval Outlying Landing Field San Nicolas Island.

For Plan Period: 2016-2021

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10 March 2016

Date

INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PLAN
Naval Base Ventura County
Naval Outlying Landing Field, San Nicolas Island, California

APPROVAL

This Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) was prepared and reviewed in coordination with the Department of the Navy and the California Department of Fish and Wildlife South Coast Region in accordance with the 2006 Memorandum of Understanding for a Cooperative Integrated Natural Resource Management Program on Military Installations. The California Department of Fish and Wildlife concurs that this INRMP will provide a framework to manage natural resources on Naval Base Ventura County Naval Outlying Landing Field San Nicolas Island.

For Plan Period: 2016 - 2021

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Naval Base Ventura County (NBVC) San Nicolas (SNI) Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) addresses terrestrial and adjacent waters of the nearshore environment with which the Navy interfaces. Submerged lands and resources, including Begg Rock, within the 300-foot (91-m) isobaths or 1.0 nautical mile distance from shore, whichever is greater, are considered under this INRMP. In 2014, this INRMP was updated to incorporate data and changes in resources, U. S. Department of Defense (DoD) and Navy INRMP guidelines, and resource goals and objectives. In addition, the SNI INRMP incorporates changes in federal regulations and associated habitat conservation provisions, such as the de-listing of the island night lizard (*Xantusia riversiana*) under the Endangered Species Act and the establishment of the Southern Sea Otter Military Readiness Areas (National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2016 Sec. 312 § 7235).

An INRMP is a long-term planning document to guide the installation commander in the management of natural resources to support the installation mission, while protecting and enhancing installation resources for multiple use, sustainable yield, and biological integrity. The Sikes Act, as amended, requires DoD to prepare and implement an INRMP for each installation that contains significant natural resources. The U.S. Navy (Navy) is required to ensure ecosystem management is the basis for all management of its lands (Sikes Act, as amended [16 United States Code {U.S.C.} 670a]; DoD Instruction 4715.03). This INRMP provides an adaptive ecosystem-based natural resources program that efficiently supports the DoD mission and provides for the sustainability of installation lands. This INRMP will help installation commanders effectively manage natural resources to ensure the sustainability of all ecosystems within the installation; ensure no net loss of the capability of installation lands to support the DoD mission; conserve and rehabilitate natural resources on military installations; sustain multipurpose use of the resources and public access to military installations to facilitate the use of those resources; participate, as appropriate, in regional ecosystem initiatives; and demonstrate conservation benefits for species listed under the Endangered Species Act.

The National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2004 (Public Law 108-136) amended the Endangered Species Act (7 U.S.C. §136, 16 U.S.C. §1531 *et seq.*) to limit areas eligible for designation as critical habitat. Specifically, Section 4(a)(3)(B)(i) of the Endangered Species Act (16 U.S.C. 1533[a][3][B][i]) now provides: “The Secretary shall not designate as critical habitat any lands or other geographical areas owned or controlled by the Department of Defense, or designated for its use, that are subject to an Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan prepared under Section 101 of the Sikes Act (16 U.S.C. 670a), if the Secretary determines in writing that such plan provides a benefit to the species for which critical habitat is proposed for designation.” The benefits provided by this INRMP for each federally listed species at NBVC SNI are addressed in Appendix D (INRMP Benefits for Threatened and Endangered Species). Federally listed species known to occur at NBVC SNI are the federally threatened western snowy plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*), Guadalupe fur seal (*Arctocephalus townsendi*), and southern sea otter (*Enhydra lutris nereis*), and the federally endangered black abalone (*Haliotis cracherodii*) and white abalone (*Haliotis sorenseni*).

The 2014 NBVC SNI INRMP established planning and management strategies; identifies natural resources constraints and opportunities; supports the resolution of land use conflicts; provides baseline descriptions of natural resources necessary for development of conservation strategies and environmental assessment; serves as the principal information source for the preparation of future environmental documents for proposed actions at NBVC SNI; and provides guidance for annual natural resources management reviews, internal compliance audits, and annual budget submittals. The INRMP fully integrates and coordinates the natural

resources program with other NBVC plans and activities. Throughout the update of this INRMP, management concerns were identified in a number of natural resource areas. Some of these natural resources concerns could have an impact on the NBVC mission or future planning operations. This INRMP addresses realistic, workable solutions (presented herein as strategies) for each concern, through the identification of goals and objectives. The recommendations presented herein are balanced with the requirements of NBVC to accomplish its mission with the highest efficiency and are discussed in detail in Sections 3 through 6. Appendix C provides a list of projects to be implemented based on the discussions in those chapters. The Navy will implement recommendations in this INRMP within the framework of regulatory compliance, Navy mission obligations, anti-terrorism and force protection limitations, and funding constraints. All actions contemplated in this INRMP are subject to the availability of funds properly authorized and appropriated under federal law. Nothing in this INRMP is intended to be, nor must be, construed to be a violation of the Anti-Deficiency Act (31 U.S.C. 1341 et.seq.).

This INRMP was prepared and organized in accordance with the Sikes Act, as amended, DoD Instruction 4715.03 *Natural Resources Conservation Program*, Chief of Naval Operations Instruction 5090.1C CH-1 *Environmental Readiness Program Manual*, and the most recent series of DoD, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, and Navy guidance on the Sikes Act and INRMPs (DoD 2010, 2011; Navy 2006). Numerous Navy personnel, tenants, and related organizations, as well as federal, state, and city representatives and other external organizations, were invited to participate in development and review of this document. The U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, the California Department of Fish and Wildlife (formerly California Department of Fish and Game), and the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration/National Marine Fisheries Service have reviewed and signed this INRMP, indicating their mutual agreement with the Commanding Officer regarding natural resources management at NBVC SNI.

NBVC SNI is achieving a no net loss to training and testing lands through implementation of this INRMP. Range capacity (in terms of weapons testing facilities) is increasing on SNI. On land, due to the de-listing of the island night lizard, SNI has increased land area for operations. The change in protected status for the southern sea otter population at SNI poses no loss of operations given current mission needs. Due to the number and distribution of protected species on SNI, natural resources management strategies will continue to be necessary to support current and future training facilities projects.

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1.0 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

In general, the purpose of an Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) is to help installation commanders manage natural resources more effectively so as to ensure that installation land and waters remain available and in good condition to support the military mission. Designed to facilitate both stewardship and compliance with natural resource laws in the context of military mission requirements, this INRMP integrates natural resource components of existing San Nicolas Island (SNI) plans, environmental documents, and the requirements of all applicable U.S. Department of Defense (DoD), U.S. Department of the Navy (DoN), and installation regulations and guidelines.

The purpose of this INRMP is to provide a viable and implementable framework for the management of natural resources at Naval Base Ventura County (NBVC), California, SNI. Required by the Sikes Act, as amended (16 United States Code [U.S.C.] 670a), an INRMP is the primary means by which natural resources compliance and stewardship priorities are set, and funding requirements are determined. A commitment to implement priority projects, as funding permits, comes with the signatures in the front of this INRMP.

The Sikes Act stipulates that this INRMP provide for:

- Conservation and rehabilitation of natural resources;
- Sustainable, multipurpose use of resources;
- Public access that is necessary and appropriate for the use described above, subject to safety and military security requirements;
- Specific natural resource goals and objectives, and time frames for acting on them;
- Fish and wildlife management, land management, and forest management;
- Fish and wildlife habitat enhancement or modifications;
- Wetlands protection, enhancement, and restoration where necessary for support of fish, wildlife, or plants;
- Integration of and consistency among various activities conducted under the INRMP;
- Sustainable use by the public of natural resources to the extent that use is not inconsistent with needs of the fish and wildlife resources;
- Enforcement of natural resource laws and regulations;
- No net loss in the capability of the military installation lands to support the military mission of the installation; and
- Such other activities as the Secretary of the Navy (SECNAV) determines appropriate.

By direction of the Office of the Undersecretary of Defense Memorandum of 08 August 1994, *Implementation of Ecosystem Management in the Department of Defense*, INRMPs are required to ensure that ecosystem management is the basis for all future management of DoD lands and waters. Based on an ecosystem approach, this INRMP takes a large geographic view to ensure the overriding purpose of protecting the properties and functions of natural ecosystems (DoD Instruction [DoDINST] 4715.03, *Natural Resources Conservation Program*). Terrestrial resource management of SNI is a unique scenario where the ecosystem boundary is synonymous with Navy property ownership. However, marine resource management of SNI's nearshore waters is interrelated with regional management issues for the Southern California Bight. When installation managers are confronted with the challenges and opportunities of regional ecosystem issues, they are encouraged to form cooperative partnerships with resource management agencies, as

appropriate, and take part in public awareness initiatives in an effort to manage ecosystems more successfully. The Office of the Undersecretary of Defense Memorandum provides principles and guidelines for implementing ecosystem management on DoD lands. This includes participation in regional ecosystem initiatives.

INRMPs, as formalized under the Sikes Act, are developed jointly by the U.S. Navy (Navy), fish and wildlife agencies such as the California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW), U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS), National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS), and other resource agencies as appropriate. Mutual agreement from these agencies is sought for the fish and wildlife component of natural resources management identified in the INRMP, and an annual review with the agencies discussing Navy-wide natural resources is mandatory.

The 2010 revision (Tierra Data, Inc. 2010) was undertaken primarily due to the need to update the resource goals and objectives of NBVC SNI identified in the previous INRMP (DoN 2005). Some legal requirements had changed, such as guidelines for complying with the Magnuson-Stevens Fisheries Conservation and Management Act and associated habitat conservation provisions for Essential Fish Habitat (EFH). Other regulatory changes which were not addressed in the 2005 INRMP were the Final Rule listing the black abalone (*Haliotis cracherodii*) as “Endangered” under the Endangered Species Act (ESA) (74 Federal Register [FR] 1937), and the Final Rule removing the brown pelican (*Pelecanus occidentalis*) from the Federal List of Endangered and Threatened Wildlife (74 FR 59443). Further changes occurred in the way water quality matters are managed in nearshore waters of SNI, and in DoD guidance on INRMP content.

In 2014, this INRMP was updated to incorporate data and changes in resources since 2010. The most significant changes were the de-listing of the island night lizard (*Xantusia riversiana*) from list of protected species under the ESA, and the official cease of the sea otter (*Enhydra lutris nereis*) translocation project.

The Navy and SNI will implement recommendations in this INRMP within the framework of regulatory compliance, national Navy mission obligations, anti-terrorism and force protection limitations, and funding constraints. All actions contemplated in this INRMP are subject to the availability of funds properly authorized and appropriated under federal law. Nothing in this INRMP is intended to be nor must be construed to be a violation of the Anti-Deficiency Act (31 U.S. Code [USC] 1341 *et seq.*).

1.2 Authority

The Sikes Act directs the DoD to take the appropriate management actions necessary to protect and enhance the land and water resources on all installations under its control. DoD Directive (DoDDIR) 4700.4 *Natural Resources Management Program*, and DoDINST 4715.03, *Natural Resources Conservation Program*, have been implemented to establish fundamental land management policies and procedures for all military lands to preserve the military mission while simultaneously protecting natural resources. Naval Facilities Engineering Command (NAVFAC) MO-100.1 (Maintenance Operating Manual, *Natural Resources Land Management*) provides basic technical guidance for land management practices of all DoD land and water resources. Naval Operations Instruction (OPNAVINST) 5090.1D *Environmental Readiness Program* (DoN 2014a), and *Environmental Readiness Program Manual* (OPNAV M-5090.1, 10 January 2014) *Chapter 12, Natural Resources Conservation* (DoN 2014b), further establish program responsibilities and standards for complying with resource protection laws, regulations, and Executive Orders (EO), to conserve and manage natural resources on Navy installations in the U.S. and its territories and possessions. Finally, the Navy Chief of Naval Operations (CNO) *Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan Guidance for Navy Installations* (April 2006), supplies guidelines on the process and procedure for developing an INRMP (DoN 2006).

Federal and state legal requirements that are the primary drivers for natural resources management are listed in Appendix B (USC, Public Laws [PL], EOs, and Code of Federal Regulations [CFR]).

The content of this INRMP is consistent with the CNO INRMP Guidance (April 2006) and OPNAVINST 5090.1D (2014).

1.3 Location and Planning Footprint

The most isolated of the eight major Channel Islands, SNI is located in the Southern California Bight (SCB), a recessed curve in the southwestern California coastline from Point Conception in Santa Barbara County to just south of the Mexican border. San Nicolas Island lies 68 miles (109 kilometers [km]) south-southwest of Ventura, California, and about 62 miles (98 km) southwest of Point Mugu, California. It is in the southern Channel Island subgroup of four islands (San Clemente, Santa Barbara, Santa Catalina, and San Nicolas).

San Nicolas Island is separated by deep ocean channels from the other Channel Islands in the chain. The island is oriented west-northwest to east-southeast, is oval-shaped, and is about nine miles (14 km) long and 3.6 miles (5.8 km) wide (Map 1-1). San Nicolas Island presents a low, table-like profile with topography dominated by a broad terrace or mesa with no distinctive peaks. The Navy owns the island to the mean high water mark (MHW), an area that encompasses approximately 14,258 acres (5,772 hectares [ha]) and the highest elevation on SNI is 908 feet (277 meters [m]) at Jackson Peak. In general, the island exhibits sparse vegetation and subsequent erosion. This poor vegetation cover is mostly attributable to past sheep ranching, the island's arid climate, and high winds.

This INRMP will be used to manage all of SNI lands, and adjacent waters of the nearshore environment with which the Navy interfaces. This INRMP includes all waters surrounding SNI and Begg Rock within the 300-foot (91-m) isobaths, or 1.0 nautical mile (nm) distance from shore, whichever is greater (Map 1-1).

Marine species considered in this INRMP include those closely associated with SNI and regularly occurring within the expanded footprint. This includes seasonally occurring marine mammals that haul out or breed on SNI as well as the permanent southern sea otter population. Oceanic species, such as large cetaceans or highly migratory fishes, which may occasionally occur within the expanded footprint, though on a transient or infrequent basis, are not included. Offshore and oceanic species are addressed on an as-needed basis in species specific consultations and permit processes for Navy activities offshore SNI.

1.4 Real Estate Summary

In 1933, SNI was transferred to the Navy by an EO of President Hoover. In November 1942, the U.S. Army was given temporary jurisdiction over the island and intended to base an air observation squadron, however, the U.S. Army never stationed such a squadron there (S. Schwartz, *personal communication [pers. comm.]*, 2010). SNI was returned to the Navy following the end of World War II and in 1947, the island came under the control of the Naval Air Station at Point Mugu as part of the Naval Air Missile Test Center (De Violini 1974; Schwartz 1994). In the 1990s, Point Mugu was redesignated Naval Air Weapons Station Point Mugu. In October 2004, SNI was transferred to NBVC.

The Naval facilities at SNI support the mission of the Naval Air Warfare Center Weapons Division (NAWCWD) Point Mugu Sea Range (PMSR), which controls 36,000 square miles (mi²) (93,240 square kilometers [km²]) of Special Use Airspace over the Pacific Ocean. The PMSR parallels the California coastline for about 200 miles (322 km) and extends seaward for more than 180 nm (333 km).

OPNAV-M 5090.1 requires the Navy to identify areas that may be suitable and available for agricultural outleasing or commercial forestry. More specifically, the Military Construction Authorization Act provides for the use of DoD lands under a lease to an agency, organization, or person, for the purpose of agricultural outleasing or the production of and sale of forest products with commercial value. At SNI, there are no forestlands suitable for timber production.

The Navy owns and operates SNI and has one lease with the Department of Homeland Security U.S. Coast Guard (USCG), to support USCG rescue programs.

1.5 Achieving No Net Loss to the Military Mission

Operations at SNI occur in the PMSR and support Research Development Acquisition Testing and Evaluation (RDAT&E) for air warfare systems. There are five general categories of tests to evaluate sea, land, and air weapons systems conducted in the PMSR: (1) air-to-air tests; (2) air-to-surface tests; (3) surface-to-air tests; (4) surface-to-surface tests; and (5) subsurface-to-surface tests. The PMSR also supports four categories of training: (1) fleet exercise training; (2) littoral warfare training; (3) small-scale amphibious warfare training; and (4) aircraft training operations. These RDAT&E and training activities occur in waters surrounding SNI, and instrumentation on the island is used to record and evaluate RDAT&E operations.

The military mission, derived from Title 10 of the USC, requires the Navy to “maintain, train and equip combat-ready naval forces capable of winning wars, deterring aggression and maintaining freedom of the seas.” In keeping with the principal use of military installations to ensure the preparedness of the U.S. Armed Forces, the Sikes Act mandates that the INRMP shall provide for no net loss of the capability of the installation’s lands to support the military mission.

There are several important points regarding the military mission and natural resources at SNI:

- Navy use of land is not particularly intensive, since in general the island is used as a staging area for RDAT&E operations.
- Existing test sites are routinely re-used, which takes advantage of existing infrastructure and avoids additional resource conflicts and costs associated with establishing new areas.
- Large areas remain undisturbed for the specific purpose of natural resource protection, safety, and security buffer zones.
- Most high value resource areas are in locations not intensively used for ground-related military activities.

- The island is still recovering from resource damage that occurred when livestock grazing was intense.

The NBVC SNI installation is achieving a no net loss of training and testing lands through the implementation of this INRMP. Range capacity (in terms of weapons testing facilities) is increasing on SNI. National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) documentation and consultation under Section 7 of the ESA, and consultation under the Marine Mammal Protection Act (MMPA), have preserved and in some areas increased access to operational areas. On land, due to the de-listing of the island night lizard, SNI has increased land area for operations. Recent legislation (50 CFR Part 17) terminated the southern sea otter translocation program and extended ESA protections to the SNI southern sea otter population. However, the 2016 National Defense Authorization Act Section 312 amends Chapter 631 of Title 10 USC § 7235 by establishing the Southern Sea Otter Military Readiness Areas at SNI (including Begg Rock) and the adjacent and surrounding waters, and Naval Base Coronado, San Clemente Island and the adjacent surrounding waters. Incidental takings under Sections 4 and 9 of the ESA and Sections 101 and 102 of the MMPA shall not apply with respect to the incidental taking of any southern sea otter in the Southern Sea Otter Military Readiness Areas in the course of conducting a military readiness activity. It also states that southern sea otter within these areas shall be treated for the purposes of Section 7 of the ESA, as a member of a species that is proposed to be listed as an endangered or threatened species. For activities that do not support military readiness, sea otters residing at SNI are still considered part of the federally threatened population and treated as such. With the 2016 National Defense Authorization Act the change in protected status for the southern sea otter population at SNI poses no loss of operations given current mission needs. Due to the number and distribution of protected species on SNI, natural resources management strategies will continue to be necessary to support current and future training and facilities projects.

1.5.1 Mission Sustainability and the INRMP “No Net Loss” Requirement

The common principal between national security and public land stewardship is the concept of sustainability. Sustainability is a relative condition of the ecosystem and the military mission that can be measured; however, measures of sustainability are scale-dependent. The most widely used definition of sustainability and sustainable development was developed by the World Commission on Environment and Development (also known as the Brundtland Commission [1987]): “[Sustainable resource management is]...the capacity to meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.” Given the strategic significance of SNI and the Navy’s investment in its ranges, the sustainability and “no net loss” of the resources that support it are considered further in *Section 5: Sustainability and Compatible Use at San Nicolas Island*.

Sustainability may be considered as having at least several measurable components in the context of this INRMP – military use facilitation, soil and water resource protection, ecological integrity, cultural resource protection, and range safety for current and future use. For the purpose of this INRMP, an impact to mission accomplishment has occurred when any of the above are constrained or when one of the following conditions occurs:

- Quality of military training is impacted by natural resource restrictions.
- Training qualification objectives to deploy are not accomplished without significant delay or conflict.
- Environmental issues hamper scheduled operations.
- Conflict resolution impacts training intensity or tempo and the target resource condition is impacted.

- Soil and water resources are impaired such that compliance has become a problem and the irretrievable damage has occurred. Protection of soil and water resources will protect the capacity of the ecosystem to recover from disturbance, and sustain its natural carrying capacity to support plants and animals and provide a realistic training environment. Soil surface stabilization is needed to minimize erosion, and maximize opportunities for soils to self-stabilize after disturbance. Water supply, natural hydrologic processes, and water quality are essential to most ecological functions including recoverability from disturbance. Managing for sustainability means preventing damage that will eliminate an area from use for the foreseeable future, or for which restoration or mitigation is excessively costly. The threshold beyond which an area loses its capability to sustain its original training load is loosely termed the carrying capacity.
- Ecological integrity is irretrievably harmed. Compliance under the Sikes Act for mission sustainability (“no net loss”) is also defined in this Plan to include the ecological integrity of training lands, since this integrity will carry these lands into the long-term future with all the elements that allow self-recovery to remain intact. Keeping all the pieces (habitats and species) that allow the ecosystem to function at various scales and at the highest level possible, given the mandate for land and water use, is the third component to protecting sustainability.
- Cultural resources compliance is impaired. Long-term strategies include cultural resources surveys of areas that are not targeted for immediate use. Some of these areas may be opened to training in the future. Under Section 110 of the National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA), federal land managers are directed to inventory cultural resources on lands under their control even when no activity or undertaking is planned. This inventory is usually accomplished through sample surveys designed to characterize the resource base and make projections. Such investigations aid in long-term planning and contribute to the archaeological context that is developed to evaluate resources.
- Range Safety for Current and Future Use. Ability to keep the range clean of hazardous material and unexploded ordnance aids in assuring the safety of the range not just for current training purposes but also potentially for an alternate future use.

San Nicolas Island is situated in a remote offshore location with no public or private in-holdings or fee use areas, which allows for unencumbered land uses to sustainably accomplish its military mission while conserving environmental resources.

The strategic importance of SNI and NAWCWD PMSR is characterized by its ability to provide a safe, highly instrumented volume of air and sea space in which to conduct controlled tests and operational training while maintaining environmental resources. The PMSR is used by U.S. and allied military services to test and evaluate weapon systems associated with air warfare, missiles and missile subsystems, aircraft weapons integration, and airborne electronic warfare systems. A unique combination of attributes make it a strategically important range complex for the Navy by providing realistic training opportunities to maintain operational readiness and to test and evaluate processes critical to the successful assessment, safe operation, and improvement of the capabilities of current and future weapon systems.

Because of its strategic geographic location and proximity to other military installations, SNI can be used to mimic shipboard launches of missiles and targets. Island facilities support all aspects of range operations, such as missile and target launches.

Under the Sikes Act, SNI must ensure mission sustainability and see that there is no net loss to the military mission due to implementation of this INRMP. To do this, the link between land use and the mission of supporting testing, training, research and development operations at NAWCWD PMSR must be maintained by identifying and partitioning the requirement of resource protection and the military missions of the landowner and its tenant users.

1.6 INRMP Vision, Goals, and Objectives

The vision for this INRMP is to institutionalize a Navy conservation ethic and fully comply with regulatory requirements by maintaining the continued ability of the Navy at SNI to support mission requirements while improving the conditions for long-term certainty and permanence through applying the principles of ecosystem management, adaptive management, and cooperative management in an integrated approach.

INRMPs have goals that are shaped by DoD guidelines and directives, pertinent laws and regulations, public needs, public values, ecological theory and practice, and management experience. The planning terms used in this document such as “goal,” “objective,” and “strategy” cover a gradient of specificity and durability, ranging from a very broad, enduring goal to specific strategies. Management strategies are developed and presented using a step-down approach, using the planning definitions in Table 1-1 (see *Section 4: Natural Resource Management Objectives and Strategies* and *Section 5: Sustainability and Compatible Use at San Nicolas Island* for examples).

Table 1-1. Planning definitions used in this Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan.

Hierarchy	Definition
Goal	Broad statement of intent, direction, and purpose. An enduring, visionary description of where you want to go, an end outcome. A goal is not necessarily completely attainable. It does, however, describe a desired outcome related to the mission, rather than an activity or a process.
Objective	Specific statement that describes a desired future end-state or successful outcome that supports an INRMP goal or Navy policy. Can be quantitative. Should be followed by a “standard,” which is an observable indicator by which successful attainment of a condition stated in the objective is measured. "How do we know we are making progress or we have attained the desired end-state or successful outcome?"
Strategy/Project	Specific step, practice, or method to get the job done, usually organized sequentially with timelines and duty assignments. These go out of date quickly and should be updated annually.

The goals of the SNI INRMP are to:

- Utilize adaptive management to maintain long term ecosystem health and minimize impacts to existing habitats consistent with the operational requirements of DoD’s training and testing mission.
- Facilitate sustainable military readiness and foreclose no options for future requirements of DoD.
- Conserve the full suite of native species and restore ecological communities to self-sustaining levels.
- Achieve ecosystem resilience to mission impacts.

Specific Concerns: The discussion of specific concerns identifies management concerns or issues specific to SNI. These specific concerns may describe any aspect of the status and trend of the resource that may be a concern to its health, abundance, or stability or address what controlling factors are involved. Other questions that specific concerns address include:

- Are there known threats to the health of the resource?
- Does the resource have any particular vulnerability (e.g. small breeding area in few locations)?
- Does the expansion of the resource create a problem for other resources or the military mission?

- Is there uncertainty about the status or trend of the resource such that environmental documentation (NEPA, etc.), adaptive management, or ecosystem management is impaired (i.e. is there sufficient inventory and monitoring)?

Current Management: The discussion of current management states how the resource is currently managed under the NBVC Environmental Division (ED), directives of natural resource laws and regulations, Records of Decision, Biological Opinions, permits, zoning, policies, the NEPA site approval process, and inventory or survey reports. Details specific to the installation should include the type of management approach used to carry out the natural resources program, such as ecosystem, adaptive, or cooperative management (DoD 2013).

The purpose of the current management discussion is to describe the tools and plans used for natural resource management at NBVC Point Mugu and Special Areas, specific to each INRMP topic.

Assessment of Current Management: The discussion of the assessment of current management at SNI relates the specific concerns to management adequacy for each INRMP topic. This discussion states the installation's findings with respect to data gaps, military mission conflicts, the ability to support avoidance and minimization of impacts, or the sustainability of natural resource uses. This discussion also considers the relationship between risks, vulnerabilities, uncertainties, costs, and benefits to develop objectives and management strategies that support adaptive management.

Management Objective and Strategy: The objectives and management strategies developed to support these goals are included in *Section 4: Natural Resource Management Objectives and Strategies* and *Section 5: Sustainability and Compatible Use at San Nicolas Island*. The objectives and management strategies were developed for each INRMP management topic through expert interviews conducted with installation managers. These previous discussions lead to the identification of an objective and management strategy for each INRMP topic. For the purposes of this INRMP, an objective describes the desired outcome in terms of the structure and function of what is being protected.

Objectives should be specific, measurable, achievable, and realistic in time frame and budget. Objectives and strategies should be based on the principles of adaptive management, whereby management actions are treated as scientific hypotheses to be tested.

A list of each project or action developed to support each management strategy is included in Appendix C. All management strategies developed in this INRMP support projects that pertain to each respective INRMP topic. A management project may be supported by a single management strategy or may be supported by multiple strategies that are categorized in various INRMP topics. For example, a project related to terrestrial invasive exotic species control may be supported by management strategies discussed in terrestrial vegetation communities as well as in the terrestrial invasive exotic species section. Thus, all the projects included in this INRMP will support an ecosystem based management approach if fully implemented, funded, and enforced.

1.7 Roles and Responsibilities for the INRMP

1.7.1 INRMP Working Group

A working group consisting of both internal Navy and external stakeholders was formed to develop this INRMP. This collaborative and interactive process facilitates the following: identification of specific concerns; documentation of current management practices and assessment of their effectiveness at addressing specific concerns; and development of objectives and management strategies to guide future practices to reconcile deficiencies and ensure that specific concerns are addressed. INRMP signatories meet annually to review natural resource metric focus areas, projects, and the efficacy of the INRMP.

1.7.2 Navy Stakeholders

The following is a list of internal stakeholders and their role in supporting the installation and the development, revision, and implementation of this INRMP. Policy leadership and liaison with non-Navy partners is provided through the Commander, Navy Region Southwest (CNRSW) N40, and NAVFAC Headquarters. Personnel from Naval Facilities Engineering Command Southwest (NAVFAC SW) have natural resources programming and technical support roles in developing this INRMP. Both NBVC natural resources staff and natural resources business line team specialists (N45) provide technical support.

Chief of Naval Operations—The Chief of Naval Operations provides policy, guidance and resources for the development, revision, and implementation of the INRMP and associated NEPA documentation. The Chief of Naval Operations evaluates and validates Navy Environmental Program Requirements Web (EPR-Web) project proposals (DoN 2006).

Commander of Navy Installations Command—The Commander Navy Installations Command reviews the INRMP. Their role is to ensure installations comply with DoD, Navy, and Chief of Naval Operations policy on INRMPs and their associated NEPA documentation. They also ensure the programming of resources necessary to maintain and implement INRMPs, participate in the development and revision of INRMPs, and provide overall program management oversight for all natural resources program elements. The Commander Navy Installations Command reviews and endorses projects recommended for INRMP implementation prior to submittal for signature, and evaluates and validates Navy EPR-Web project proposals (DoN 2006).

Commander Navy Region Southwest— Regional Commanders ensure that installations comply with DoD, Navy, and Chief of Naval Operations policy on INRMPs and their associated NEPA documentation. They ensure that installations under their control undergo annual reviews and formal 5-year evaluations. They ensure the programming of resources necessary to maintain and implement INRMPs, which involves the evaluation and validation of EPR-Web based project proposals and the funding of installation natural resources management staff. The Commander Navy Region Southwest maintains close liaison with the INRMP signatory partners (USFWS, NMFS and CDFW) and other INRMP stakeholders EPR-Web (DoN 2006).

Installation Commanding Officers— Installation Commanding Officers ensure the preparation, completion, and implementation of INRMPs and associated NEPA documentation. Their role is to: act as stewards of natural resources under their jurisdiction and integrate natural resources requirements into the day-to-day decision-making process; ensure natural resources management and INRMPs comply with all natural resources related federal regulations, directives, instructions, and policies; involve appropriate tenant, operational, training, or testing commands in the INRMP review process to ensure no net loss of military mission; designate a Natural Resources Manager/Coordinator responsible for the management efforts related to the preparation, revision, implementation, and funding for INRMPs, as well as coordination with subordinate commands and installations; involve appropriate Navy Judge Advocate General or Office of the General Counsel legal counsel to provide advice and counsel with respect to legal matters related to natural resources management and INRMPs; and approve INRMPs via Commanding Officer signature.

Public Affairs Office—The Public Affairs Office is involved in aspects of the environmental program at NBVC. This includes being informed of, and when applicable, implementing the public notice process required in various NEPA analysis processes.

Office of Counsel—The Office of the General Counsel, Commander Navy Region Southwest, and Judge Advocate General' Region Environmental Counsel provide legal services to NBVC on a variety of environmental matters. Particularly pertinent to natural

resources management, is their review of NEPA documentation and legal interpretations involving compliance with natural resources laws as they pertain to base operations.

Naval Facilities Engineering Command Southwest: NAVFAC SW is responsible for providing support for natural resources management at SNI. NAVFAC SW is currently providing funding and contractual oversight support for the preparation of this INRMP, wildlife surveys, plant surveys, and non-native plant treatment efforts.

Public Works Department—The NBVC Facilities Planning Office, Public Works Department, is responsible for the comprehensive oversight and planning of all land use issues relating to NBVC. Public Works Department personnel provide document review to confirm that this INRMP describes compatible land uses.

Environmental Division—The NBVC ED, as delegated by command directive, is responsible for the preparation and implementation of this INRMP. Acting through the Natural Resources Manager, NBVC ED is responsible for the management of natural resources as part of the overall NBVC environmental program. NBVC natural resources staff provides technical support. This INRMP is the direct “vehicle” for accomplishment of many of the responsibilities of the Commanding Officer and Natural Resource Manager. The Installation Environmental Program Director communicates directly with the NBVC Commanding Officer.

Business Line Team Leader (N45 NAVFAC SW) — Natural resources business line team specialists (N45) provide technical support and contractual oversight in the development, revision and implementation of this INRMP. In addition, NAVFAC SW is responsible for providing support for natural resources management at NBVC when requested. NAVFAC SW personnel such as the NEPA and INRMP coordinators, have natural resources programming and/or technical support roles in developing this INRMP.

Other Installation and Tenant Organizations, and Partners — In addition to the directorates and offices mentioned above, INRMP implementation requires assistance from, or in coordination with, a variety of other installation organizations, tenants, partners, and contract personnel.

Morale, Welfare & Recreation (MWR) —The mission of MWR is to support a variety of recreation, social, and community support activities on Navy facilities. MWR manages installation morale, welfare, and recreation activities for the NBVC community. The MWR has a primary role in managing the installation’s recreational resources at NBVC. MWR works with Environmental Division to ensure compliance with environmental laws.

Naval Air Systems Command (NAVAIR)/ Naval Air Warfare Center Weapons Division (NAWCWD) — NAVAIR’s NAWCWD provides unique engineering, development, testing, evaluation, in-service support, and program management capabilities to deliver airborne weapons systems that are technologically superior and readily available. Using a full-spectrum approach, the command delivers optimal capability and reliability for the sailor and the marine. NAVAIR is the principal provider for the Naval Aviation Enterprise, but contributes to every warfare enterprise in the interest of national security. NAVAIR and the NBVC ED coordinate to minimize conflicts between mission requirements and stewardship/compliance aspects of natural resources management and to effectively use natural resources management to support the military mission.

1.7.3 Non-Navy Stakeholders

The following details external stakeholders and their role in supporting the installation and the development, revision, and implementation of this INRMP.

INRMP Signatories: As required in the Sikes Act, as amended (Section 2904[a][2]), INRMPs are to be developed in cooperation with the USFWS, state wildlife agency, and other appropriate federal agencies. Through a Tripartite Agreement (herein referred to as an MOU) signed January 2006, the DoD, U.S. Department of Interior, USFWS, and CDFW have a statutory obligation to coordinate preparing, reviewing and implementing INRMPs. The desire is for "synchronization of INRMPs with existing USFWS and state natural resource management plans" and "mutually agreed-upon fish and wildlife service conservation objectives to satisfy the goals of the Sikes Act." The MOU is in Appendix H.

The external stakeholders participating in this INRMP are:

- USFWS—Ecological Services: The primary mission of the USFWS (2006 MOU signatory [Appendix H]) is working with others to conserve, protect, and enhance fish, wildlife, and plants and their habitats for the continuing benefit of the American people. The USFWS provides the Navy technical assistance with botanical and wildlife issues. In addition, the DoD and Navy consult formally and informally with the USFWS on the impacts of Navy activities on federally listed species and designated critical habitat.
- NOAA/NMFS Habitat Conservation: NOAA/NMFS is responsible for protecting habitat for fish, marine mammals, and federally listed species and other natural resources within the coastal zone. Though they are not a part of the MOU (Appendix H), NOAA/NMFS is a signatory partner for the INRMP. The DoD and Navy consult formally and informally with the NOAA/NMFS on the impacts of Navy activities on federally listed species, marine mammals, and essential fish habitat.
- CDFW—Habitat Conservation, Marine and Terrestrial: The CDFW (2006 MOU signatory [Appendix H]) is responsible for management of most fish and wildlife in the state. Nothing in this INRMP affects any provision of a federal law governing the conservation or protection of fish and wildlife species, or enlarges or diminishes California's responsibility and authority for the protection and management of fish and resident wildlife. The CDFW and other state fish and wildlife agencies were represented by the International Association of Fish and Wildlife Agencies.

Mutual agreement among the agencies is formalized on the signatory pages at the front of this INRMP.

1.7.4 Other External Organizations and Partners

In addition to the external organizations mentioned above, INRMP implementation requires assistance from, or coordination with, the following entities:

- U.S. Department of the Interior, National Park Service (NPS)—Channel Islands National Park (CINP)
- U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, Los Angeles District
- U.S. Geological Survey (USGS)
- Bureau of Land Management (BLM) California Coastal National Monument (CCNM)
- The Nature Conservancy

1.8 Ecosystem Approach

The DoD and the Navy have adopted a policy of ecosystem management for INRMPs. The DoD (DoDINST 4715.03, *Natural Resources Conservation Program*) describes ecosystem management as, “a process that considers the environment as a complex system functioning as a whole, not a collection of parts, and recognizes that people and their social and economic needs are a part of the whole.” The DoD goal with regard to ecosystem management is “to ensure that military lands support present and future training and testing requirements while preserving, improving, and enhancing ecosystem integrity. Over the long term, that approach shall maintain and improve the sustainability and biological diversity of terrestrial and aquatic (including marine) ecosystems while supporting sustainable economies, human use, and the environment required for realistic military training operations.”

DoD and Navy Instructions mandate an ecosystem framework and approach for the INRMP (DoDINST [2011] and DoD Manual, *INRMP Implementation Manual* [2013] 4715.03, and OPNAVINST 5090.1D [2014] and OPNAV M-5090.1 *Environmental Readiness Program Manual* [2014]). Ecosystem management in DoD draws on a long-term vision of integrating ecological, economic, and social factors. This approach takes a long-term view of human activities including military uses and biological resources, as part of the same environment. The goal is to preserve and enhance ecosystem integrity, and to sustain both biological diversity and continued availability of those resources for military readiness and sustainability, and other human uses (as defined in OPNAVINST 5090.1D). Managing for sustainability and ecosystem management are both approaches that attempt to integrate long-term goals with short-term project lists.

The ecosystem mandate is accomplished by applying principles of sustainable use at several scales, with emphases on partnerships, public outreach, long-term monitoring, and adaptive management. Consistent with Navy policy, ecosystem-based management shall include (OPNAVINST 5090.1D):

- A shift from single species to multiple species conservation.
- Formation of partnerships necessary to consider and manage ecosystems that cross boundaries.
- Use of the best available scientific information and adaptive management techniques.

An adaptive management approach is a requirement for INRMPs under DoDINST 4715.03, and is defined as: “The process of implementing policy decisions as scientifically driven management experiments that test predictions and assumptions in management plans and using the resulting information to improve the plans” (DoD 2011).

Adaptive management occurs through the INRMP annual review and revision process, described below in *Section 1.9: Revision and Annual Review*, and detailed in *Section 6.2: Adaptive Management: Annual Update, Review, and Metrics*. Installation natural resource managers also practice adaptive management on a continuous, day-to-day basis, in response to a range of environmental or programmatic variables, which may require a change in management strategy. Adaptive management is partly implemented through the Navy’s Environmental Management System (EMS) to integrate environmental considerations into day-to-day activities across all levels and functions of Navy enterprise. Executive Order 13423, “Strengthening Federal Environmental, Energy, and Transportation Management” (24 January 2007), required each DoD component to adopt an EMS. An EMS is a formal management framework that provides a systematic way to review and improve operations, create awareness, and improve environmental performance. Systematic environmental management as an integral part of day-to-day decision making and long-term planning processes is an important step in supporting mission readiness and effective use of resources. The most significant resource for every organization is their senior leadership’s commitment and visibility in EMS implementation and sustainability. A robust EMS is essential to sustaining compliance, reducing pollution, and minimizing risk to mission. The Navy’s EMS has a concerted focus on preventing pollution, consistent regulatory compliance,

and reducing environmental impacts, including environmental practice for energy and transportation functions, using a “plan-do-check-act” management model (OPNAVINST 5090.1D [DoN 2014a]). It conforms to the International Organization for Standardization 14001:2004 EMS standard.

1.9 Revision and Annual Review

DoD policy requires installations to review INRMPs annually in cooperation with the two primary partnering parties to the INRMP: USFWS and the state fish and wildlife agency. Annual reviews facilitate adaptive management by providing an opportunity to review the goals and objectives of the plan, and establish a realistic schedule for undertaking proposed actions. Section 101(b)(2) of the Sikes Act (16 U.S. Code [U.S.C.] 670a[b][2]) requires that INRMPs be reviewed for operation and effect regularly (no less than every five years) by the installation, the USFWS, the state fish and wildlife agency (CDFW), and the NMFS. The Office of the Undersecretary of Defense Memorandum for Implementation of Sikes Act Improvement Amendments (17 May 2005) guidance states that joint review should be reflected in a memorandum or letters.

Recent guidance on INRMP implementation interpreted that the five-year review would not necessarily constitute a “revision”, that this would occur only if deemed necessary. The annual review process is facilitated through a tripartite agreement (Appendix H), and broadly guided by the following DoD and OPNAV instructions and manuals: DoDINST 4715.03 *Natural Resources Conservation Program* (2011) and *INRMP Implementation Manual* (2013); and OPNAVINST 5090.1D *Environmental Readiness Program* and OPNAV M-5090.1 *Environmental Readiness Program Manual* (2014). See *Section 6.2: Adaptive Management: Annual Update, Review, and Metrics* for further detail.

According to *Public Comment on INRMP Reviews Legislative Language Section 2905 of the Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997* [16 USC 670a note] and OPNAV M-5090.1, the Secretary of each Military Department is required to provide the public an opportunity for the submission of comments on the initial draft INRMPs or on that of a significant revision that requires NEPA analysis. The installation shall provide the public with a meaningful opportunity to review and comment on the initial draft INRMP and initial draft INRMP revision (other than minor technical amendments) (OPNAV M-5090.1, January 2014).

There is no legal obligation to invite the public either to review or to comment upon the parties’ mutually agreed upon decision to continue implementation of an existing INRMP without revision (OPNAV M-5090.1). If the parties determine that substantial revisions to an INRMP are necessary, public comment shall be invited in conjunction with any required NEPA analysis.

1.10 Integrating Other Plans

The INRMP provides guidance and direction for natural resources management activities and provides a framework for plan implementation. Table 1-2 lists Navy plans and reports referenced and incorporated into the development of this INRMP. The list is not exhaustive; many other plans are discussed throughout this document. Considering the Navy’s sole ownership of SNI and its relative isolation from adjacent land masses, the majority of regional use near SNI relates to the marine environment. Within the SCB, and in particular the Channel Islands area, significant regional uses include recreational activities, Marine Protected Areas, ecological conservation, shipping channels, commercial fishing, and oil drilling. Jurisdiction and regulation of nearshore waters is dependent upon both the individual resources and their geographical location. The CDFW regulates commercial and recreational fishing in conjunction with the NMFS in certain instances such as EFH, ground fishing (quotas), and other highly migratory fish species. Adjacent Channel Islands are managed by the NPS. Surrounding waters are managed

by the National Marine Sanctuaries Program or other conservation organizations that focus on preserving and protecting natural and cultural resources unique to the region. Resource stewardship and integrated management practices currently implemented by the Navy at SNI are complementary to SCB regional marine and land use owners and regulators, allowing for the development of beneficial partnerships in resource management.

During the development of this INRMP, many different planning processes such as the USFWS recovery plans, state wildlife action plan, and NPS's general management plan, are considered and reviewed for consistency. These plans are listed in Table 1-3 and referenced in Chapters 3 and 4. The INRMP's consistency with the plans listed in Tables 1-2 and 1-3 has been assessed to determine if certain related or neighboring planning processes may affect natural resources management on SNI.

Table 1-2. Navy planning documents considered in the Naval Base Ventura County San Nicolas Island Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan.

Authoring Agency	Title	Date
U.S. Department of the Navy	<i>Naval Air Warfare Center Weapons Division Point Mugu Sea Range Environmental Impact Statement/ Overseas Environmental Impact Statement</i>	2002
U.S. Department of the Navy	<i>Naval Base Ventura County Naval Outlying Landing Field San Nicolas Island Master Plan for Nicktown and Public Works Areas</i>	2003
U.S. Department of the Navy	<i>Naval Base Ventura County Comprehensive Land Use Management Plan</i>	2005
U.S. Department of the Navy	<i>Naval Outlying Landing Field San Nicolas Island Emergency Response Action Plan</i>	2006
U.S. Department of the Navy	<i>Naval Outlying Landing Field San Nicolas Island Oil and Hazardous Substance Integrated Contingency Plan</i>	2006
U.S. Department of the Navy	<i>Naval Air Warfare Center Aircraft Division/ Weapons Division Strategic Plan</i>	2008
U.S. Department of the Navy	<i>United States Navy Pacific Fleet Southern California Range Complex Environmental Impact Statement/ Overseas Environmental Impact Statement</i>	2008
U.S. Department of the Navy	<i>Naval Base Ventura County Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan</i>	2010
U.S. Department of the Navy	<i>Naval Base Ventura County San Nicolas Island and Fort Hunter Liggett Activity Overview Plan</i>	2010
U.S. Department of the Navy	<i>Naval Base Ventura County San Nicolas Island Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan</i>	2010
U.S. Department of the Navy	<i>Naval Base Coronado San Clemente Island Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan</i>	2013
U.S. Department of the Navy	<i>Naval Base Ventura County Point Mugu and Special Areas Island Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan</i>	2013
U.S. Department of the Navy	<i>Naval Base Ventura County San Nicolas Island Bird/Wildlife Aircraft Strike Hazard Plan</i>	TBD
National Renewable Energy Laboratory	<i>San Nicolas Island Renewable Community Plan Outline, Baseline Development, and Initial Renewable Assessment</i>	2008

Table 1-3. Other planning documents considered in the Naval Base Ventura County San Nicolas Island Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan.

Authoring Agency	Title	Date
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	<i>California Channel Islands Species Recovery Plan</i>	1984
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	<i>United States Shorebird Conservation Plan</i>	2001
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	<i>North American Waterbird Management Plan</i>	2002
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	<i>Final Revised Recovery Plan for the Southern Sea Otter</i>	2003
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	<i>North American Waterfowl Management Plan</i>	2004
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	<i>Regional Seabird Conservation Plan Pacific Region</i>	2005
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	<i>Recovery Plan for the Pacific Coast Population of the Western Snowy Plover</i>	2007
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	<i>Post-Delisting Monitoring Plan for the Brown Pelican</i>	2009
Partners in Flight	<i>Partners in Flight North American Landbird Conservation Plan</i>	2004
National Park Service	<i>Channel Islands National Park Recovery Strategy for Island Foxes on the Northern Channel Islands</i>	2003
National Park Service	<i>Channel Islands National Park General Management Plan</i>	2015
National Atmospheric and Oceanic Administration	<i>Channel Islands National Marine Sanctuary Management Plan</i>	2009
Bureau of Land Management	<i>California Coastal National Monument Resource Management Plan</i>	2005
California Department of Fish and Game	<i>Marine Life Management Act Nearshore Fishery Management Plan</i>	2002
California Department of Fish and Game	<i>Abalone Recovery and Management Plan</i>	2005
California Department of Fish and Game	<i>Wildlife Action Plan</i>	2007
California Department of Fish and Game	<i>Marine Life Protection Act Master Plan for Marine Protected Areas</i>	2008
California Department of Fish and Game	<i>California Aquatic Invasive Species Management Plan</i>	2008
California Department of Fish and Game and California Environmental Protection Agency	<i>Ocean Action Plan</i>	2004
State Water Resources Control Board	<i>Marine State Water Quality Protection Areas, Areas of Special Biological Significance</i>	2003
Regional Water Quality Control Board	<i>Los Angeles Region Basin Plan</i>	1994

2.0 Military Mission and Operations

2.1 Historical Overview

Over the years, human inhabitants and visitors utilized various marine and terrestrial natural resources that significantly altered the ecological conditions of SNI prior to military use. The preservation and management of existing natural resources requires an understanding of current and historical conditions, their impacts, and resulting ecological status.

2.1.1 Pre-Navy Land Use

Human occupation of SNI is believed to have started around 8,500 years before present (BP). The Native Americans inhabiting the island, the Nicoleño people, left over 550 archaeological sites as evidence of their occupation (DoN 2005b). The Nicoleños formed a subsistence strategy where the primary protein source was fish, with shellfish being a major secondary source, followed by marine mammals (Bleitz 1993; S. Schwartz, *pers. comm.*, 2009). Evidence of marine harvesting on SNI includes the remains of fish, marine mammals, and shellfish, as well as the tools required to harvest them.

Evidence from midden sites (discard locations for shells, urchins, and bones) suggest that birds were also a food source. Marine mammals provided a rich food source when available while abundant fish and intertidal invertebrates (primarily abalone, urchins, mussels, and limpets) provided a more consistent food supply. One of several competing archaeological theories suggest that excavations of middens show that the Nicoleño people utilized the largest invertebrates first collecting the smaller individuals and species as supplies dwindled, eventually moving on to new locations or species (S. Schwartz, *pers. comm.*, 2009).

Subsistence hunting and gathering by the Nicoleño people required skill and ingenuity. Fishing by shell fish hooks and lines, and the use of nets were documented later during their occupation of the island (S. Schwartz, *pers. comm.*, 2009). The Nicoleño's intensive extractive use of marine resources did not likely affect the local ecology because the population was never high enough for their extractive practices to place any type of limit on the size of their population (S. Schwartz, *pers. comm.*, 2009).

San Nicolas Island was first discovered by Europeans in 1543 by the Spanish explorer Bartolome Ferrer, and received its present name when sighted by Spanish explorer Sebastián Vizcaino on Saint Nicolas's Day, 06 December 1602.

European use of the island began during the early 1800s when sea otter hunting became a profitable industry at the island (Schwartz 1994). Russian fur traders began using the island in the early 1800s for sea otter hunting and brought in Aleut hunters, who were very efficient at the "surround-hunting" technique. In 1811, a group of 25-30 Kodiak hunters from a Russian camp in Sitka, Alaska landed on the island to hunt otter and seal (California Mission Resource Center [CMRC] 2010). By the time the Russian Kodiak hunters were finally removed, there were less than one hundred Nicoleño people left on the island (CMRC 2010).

By the early 1800s, the Nicoleño population had decreased due to diseases introduced by Europeans which resulted in a decline of the occupation of Nicoleño villages on the island (S. Schwartz, *pers. comm.*, 2009). By the early 1830s, with the Nicoleño population in decline, the Franciscan missionaries organized the removal of all remaining Nicoleño people from SNI

(CMRC 2010). The Peor es Nada, captained by Charles Hubbard, landed on the island in 1835 and conducted the removal of the Nicoleño people from SNI (Ellison 1937; CMRC 2010). One Nicoleño woman was unknowingly left on SNI and lived alone on the island for 18 years until she was discovered and removed in 1853 (Martz 2003).

San Nicolas Island, like many of the other Channel Islands, was not granted to an individual, but rather became the property of the U.S. government following the Mexican-American war in 1848 (under the terms of the Treaty of Guadalupe Hidalgo in 1848). Initially the U.S. government's jurisdiction over the island was limited. According to the terms of the Treaty of Guadalupe Hidalgo the acquisition of SNI by the U.S. government included a reservation of two 20-acre (8-ha) parcels on the southern ends of the island for lighthouse purposes (Junak 2008). Thus, in the mid-1800s other economic pursuits by various individuals occurred while the U.S. government began exercising its limited jurisdiction on the island.

European sea otter hunting groups are known to have brought in Kanakas (Hawaiians) and Mission Indians to hunt sea otters. The hunting of sea otters for their pelts was so profitable that American sea captains also began to enter the trade (Schwartz 1994). In the 1860s, Chinese abalone fishermen began fishing in SNI's tidal areas, setting up camp at the northwest end of the island (Schwartz 1994). At first, abalone were taken for their meat, but later became popular for their shells (Schwartz 1994).

Aside from the lone Nicoleño woman left on SNI, the island was unoccupied from 1835 until 1857. Sheep ranching became the main economic pursuit on SNI starting around 1857 (Schwartz 1994). Ranching on the Channel Islands did not have the same limitations as ranching on the mainland. Island ranchers did not need to fence in their flocks to prevent straying or encroachment. There were no threats from predators, such as bears, mountain lions, and bobcats, nor did ranchers face raids by Native Americans or poaching (O'Malley 1994). This allowed early ranchers to let sheep roam freely over SNI. This early practice, together with an excessive number of sheep, quickly caused the removal of most of the island's vegetation (Schwartz 1994; Junak 2008).

Martin Kimberly was the first large-scale grazing operation on SNI. Kimberly established his operation during the Era of Wool (1870–1880), the "heyday of the California sheep industry" (O'Malley 1994). Kimberly had around 800 sheep on SNI in 1860 which had increased to 3,400 sheep in the 1870 agricultural census. The number of sheep on SNI is said to have increased to around 15,000 after the 1860 count, but a two-year drought saw the flock size decrease to the 1870 count (O'Malley 1994). Kimberly's operation on SNI ended in the 1870s, and though he tried to remove his sheep from SNI, an estimated 4,000 sheep are thought to have been left on the island (O'Malley 1994).

The most notable owner of SNI following Kimberly's departure was the Pacific Wool Company, which also operated on San Miguel Island and Anacapa Island. Pacific Wool Company operated on SNI for about a decade (1870s–1880s), but the operation failed in the end (O'Malley 1994).

In 1901 President Roosevelt increased the federal government's jurisdiction over the island by reserving the entire island for lighthouse purposes under the administration of the Lighthouse Bureau (Junak 2008). This change represented the first time that the U.S. government had acquired full jurisdiction over the island during its history of occupation and use of SNI.

The next large-scale ranching operation was in 1919 with E.N. Vail, who brought both experience in managing livestock and sensitivity to the island's natural resources (O'Malley 1994). Vail operated on SNI until 1934 under leases from the Lighthouse Bureau. During his operation, Vail moved his center of operations to the northeast shore, between the east end and Corral Harbor (Brooks Landing); he also built a pier and established a rest rotation system to protect SNI's vegetation (O'Malley 1994). Even though the Navy took up ownership of SNI in 1933, sheep ranching continued on the island until World War II under Roy Agee and L.P. Elliott (O'Malley 1994).

In the 1920s or early 1930s, the Civilian Aviation Authority built two emergency dirt landing strips 2,300 feet (701 m) and 2,100 feet (640 m) long. In January 1933, the Civilian Aviation Authority relinquished the airstrips as the Navy took over ownership of SNI.

2.1.2 Historical Navy Land Use

In 1933, control of SNI was transferred to the Navy by an EO of President Hoover. In August of 1933, The Navy set-up a weather station at the Brooks Landing sheep ranch. The U.S. Army was given temporary control of SNI in November 1942. During the Army's occupation, it was intended to be used to base a squadron of early warning aircraft and an airstrip was built near today's airfield to support that intended use (Junak 2008). However, the U.S. Army never stationed such a squadron there. In 1944, SNI was returned to Navy control, and in 1947, the island was placed under the control of the Naval Air Station at Point Mugu as part of the Naval Air Missile Test Center (Schwartz 1994; Junak 2008). In the 1990s, Point Mugu was redesignated Naval Air Weapons Station Point Mugu, and functioned as the principal test and evaluation site for the newly created Naval Air Warfare Center. In October 2004, SNI was transferred to NBVC.

2.1.3 Summary of Human Use and Change

A large body of research exists on the biology, climatology, geology, human history and natural history of the Channel Islands. Much of this work is either found or referenced in the proceedings from a set of multidisciplinary symposia dedicated to the study of the islands (Philbrick 1967; Power 1980; Hochberg 1993; Halvorson and Maender 1994). According to Schwartz's analysis of the ecological ramifications of historic occupation of San Nicolas Island, the current environment is far from "pristine" (Schwartz 1994). Past land uses (including overgrazing by sheep) have affected the composition and distribution of plant communities and individual species on SNI. The full extent of the changes is unknown because of the lack of biological monitoring or periodic biotic surveys. It is assumed (and anecdotal evidence supports the hypothesis) that the island biota is slowly recovering from the grazing damage (Halvorson *et al.* 1996). The terrestrial ecosystem has been affected by sheep ranching, military facility construction, the introduction of plants for erosion control, and miscellaneous grading activities (Schwartz 1994; Junak 2008). Since the early 1960s, 110 new records of non-native plant taxa have been documented (Junak 2008). The flora of SNI has the highest percentage (46%) of non-native plants of all the California Channel Islands. The non-native plants contribute significantly to the plant coverage on the island (Junak and Vanderwier 1990; Halvorson *et al.* 1996). These introductions have been associated primarily with disturbances caused by sheep grazing and military activities. Several are potentially invasive species and have recently been introduced to SNI and threaten the well-being of the sensitive native species. Based on his analysis, Schwartz recommends that historic factors should be addressed in plans to "restore" the island; especially decisions as to what time period and what type of ecosystem to use as a restoration goal (Schwartz 1994).

The introduction of non-native plants on SNI has increased dramatically since the Navy took over the island in the 1940s (Junak 2008). While it is likely that sheep were to some degree controlling emerging non-native plants during peak grazing periods many new introductions have been associated with gravel and other construction materials that have been brought to the island unintentionally during the Navy's occupation and use. By 1969, 63 non-native plant species had been recorded on SNI and by 2005 that number had increased to 141 (Junak 2008). Currently the Navy environmental staff has been making a concerted effort to control and/or eliminate new introductions but staffing and funding levels have been limited.

Some components of SNI's native vegetation have recovered dramatically since the sheep ranching era. Woody plants that were documented as rare by Blanche Trask in 1887 are now common on the island (Junak 2008). The island landscape has been transformed since the 1800s from years of sheep grazing and subsequent erosion of top soil. The recovery of native plants and their associated communities are variable based on localized conditions and exposure; however, adaptive management focused on minimizing soil disturbance and avoiding non-native plant introductions has contributed to the expansion and colonization of many native plants into new areas.

The marine ecosystem has been affected by marine mammal hunting, kelp harvesting, and shellfish collecting (Schwartz 1994). According to the California Wildlife Action Plan for the Marine Region, the direct effect of overfishing has become evident through the harvest of millions of fish every year (Bunn *et al.* 2007). The Southern California commercial passenger fishing-vessel fleet alone, caught an average of 4.25 million fish a year between 1963 and 1991; notably, despite a consistent fleet size of approximately 200 boats since 1991, this figure has decreased to 2.5 million fish a year (Dotson and Charter 2003). Regulations placed on fisheries were often not precautionary, and commercial and recreational fishermen had the equipment and technology to catch whatever the regulators would allow. As of 2003, 36 percent of United States' commercially harvested stocks (those for which we have enough information with which to assess their status) are officially categorized as overfished; another 21 percent are classified as "experiencing overfishing" (NMFS 2004). In the 1990s, state and federal governments began to realize that some populations of species caught off U.S. coasts, including California, were in decline. In addition, the overall fishing capacity of some commercial fleets was too large compared to the stocks that they were harvesting. In response to these conditions, California began implementing restricted-access policies in some commercial fisheries. Other management actions taken in recent years due to declining stocks have included area closures, such as prohibiting bottom fishing over much of the continental shelf to allow several species of depressed rockfish to recover, which has resulted in significant economic hardship to both commercial and recreational sectors.

2.2 Current Regional Navy Land Use

2.2.1 Point Mugu Sea Range

Southern California is home to the nation's largest concentration of naval forces. The Point Mugu Sea Range (PMSR) is composed of ocean areas, including surface and subsurface area and military airspace covering 27,278 nm² (93,561 km²). The primary mission of PMSR is supporting naval RDAT&E activities. The PMSR includes sophisticated range instrumentation centered on SNI and extended over-ocean range areas that are utilized for specialized RDAT&E activities. These extended ocean areas cover approximately 221,000 nm² (758,000 km²). Other military bases also benefit from electronic monitoring capabilities and availability of large expanses of controlled air and sea space including Vandenberg Air Force Base and NBVC.

2.2.2 Naval Base Ventura County

NBVC is a major aviation shore command and a Naval Construction Force mobilization base providing airfield, seaport, and base support services to fleet operating forces and shore activities. NBVC hosts NAWCWD at Point Mugu and provides the land, facilities, and other services to support the military mission throughout the PMSR. The PMSR encompasses facilities at Point Mugu, Laguna Peak, SNI, and portions of the northern Channel Islands.

Several of the northern Channel Islands are either owned by the Navy or provide Navy instrumentation sites that are critical to PMSR operations. These islands are SNI, San Miguel Island and associated Prince Island, Santa Cruz Island, and Santa Rosa Island. San Miguel, Santa Cruz, Santa Rosa, Santa Barbara, and Anacapa Islands also form the Channel Islands National Park (CINP).

SNI, one of the Channel Islands owned by the Navy, is an integral part of the PMSR. The NAVAIR Range Department holds responsibility for developmental and operational activity associated with SNI. Thus, NBVC is the land owner and manager of SNI. The Commanding Officer, NBVC is responsible for implementing policies and instructions of the DoN, in accordance with OPNAV M-5090.1.

The Navy also owns San Miguel Island and associated Prince Island. The National Park Service (NPS) manages natural and cultural resources on San Miguel Island and Prince Island as part of the CINP, under a Memoranda of Agreement between the DoN and the U.S. Department of the Interior, entered into on December 1974. There are no naval facilities on San Miguel Island except for an unmanned, remotely interrogated solar powered automatic weather station (NAWCWD 2002).

The majority of Santa Cruz Island is owned by The Nature Conservancy and NPS. However, the Navy has a 10-acre lease from The Nature Conservancy on Santa Cruz Island, at a radar site that serves as an instrumentation facility for the PMSR (NAWCWD 2002). Use and management of the bunkhouse facility and utility systems at the radar site on Santa Cruz Island are accomplished through an interagency agreement between the Navy and NPS (CINP 2010).

Santa Rosa Island is owned by NPS. There are no naval facilities on Santa Rosa Island except for a tracking antenna (NAWCWD 2002).

2.2.3 Naval Air Systems Command

NAVAIR is a Navy command headquartered in Patuxent River, Maryland, with military and civilian personnel stationed at eight principal continental U.S. sites, and one overseas site. NAVAIR provides unique engineering, development, testing, evaluation, in-service support, and program management capabilities to deliver airborne weapons systems that are technologically superior and readily available. Using a full-spectrum approach, the command delivers optimal capability and reliability for the Sailor and the Marine. NAVAIR is the principal provider for the Naval Aviation Enterprise, but contributes to every warfare enterprise in the interest of national security.

2.2.4 Naval Air Warfare Center, Weapons Division

The NAWCWD is an organization within NAVAIR, dedicated to maintaining a center of excellence in weapons development for the DoN. NAWCWD has two locations in southern California: China Lake hosts the land test range and Point Mugu hosts the sea test range.

2.3 Overview of San Nicolas Island Operations

San Nicolas Island's primary mission is to support the RDT&E of air weapons and associated aircraft systems into strike, anti-surface, and anti-air warfare aircraft within the NAWCWD PMSR (NAVFAC SW 2010a). In support of this mission, SNI serves two primary functions: as a launch platform for short and medium missile testing, and as an observation facility for missile testing (Naval Outlying Landing Field [NOLF] SNI 2003).

The PMSR is used by U.S. and allied military services to test and evaluate weapon systems associated with air warfare, missiles and missile subsystems, aircraft weapons integration, and airborne electronic warfare systems, to provide realistic training opportunities and to maintain the operational readiness of these forces (NAWCWD 2002). This test and evaluation process is critical to successful assessment, safe operation, and improvement of the capabilities of current and future naval weapon systems.

Military training, testing, and evaluation operations directed by NAWCWD PMSR utilize an array of locations and areas including developed facilities, remote launch pads, beaches, air space, and nearshore waters on and around SNI (Map 2-1).

Requirements for specific training and testing exercises can involve the integration of multiple facilities and locations expanding the footprint of exercises to several thousand square miles. The majority of SNI operations involve the electronic evaluation of missile systems utilizing various radars and global positioning systems (GPS).

2.3.1 Point Mugu Sea Range Weapons System Tests

Currently, the facilities associated with military land uses at SNI support three general categories of tests to evaluate sea, land, and air weapons systems conducted on the NAWCWD PMSR.

While the operations partitioned into the categories below are not necessarily exclusive to SNI, they represent the PMSR and the complexity of operational training and testing that may occur on SNI at any time. Considering the demands of weapons testing research and development, not every scenario is presented in this section; a brief overview of typical testing logistics that pertain to the military use of SNI is summarized below.

Air-to-Surface Weapons System Testing

Air-to-surface weapons system testing involves weapons using a missile, bomb, inert mine shape, or any other object released from an aircraft designed for attack of an enemy surface target. Targets for the air-to-surface scenario are floating surface targets or the missile impact area on the western tip of SNI (NAWCWD 2002). The air-to-surface scenario involves testing weapons that support the air warfare mission, including testing a ship's defensive weapons systems for defense against an enemy airborne target or threat. Missile impact altitudes for air-to-surface tests are dependent on the type of missile or target being tested; altitudes range from less than 100 feet (30 m) for GQM-163A Coyote targets to 80,000 feet (24,238 m) for AQM-37s (NAWCWD 2002; S. Schwartz, *pers. comm.*, 2009).

Surface-to-Surface Weapons System Testing

Surface-to-surface testing involves missiles fired from a surface vessel against a surface target, which is either another ship or a land target. The test article can be captive-carry using an inert missile, missile with telemetry and a live rocket, or the actual firing of a live missile. Air support is required from the range to provide chase aircraft and safety procedures are implemented to clear the target operational area (NAWCWD 2002).

Subsurface-to-Surface Weapons Systems Testing

Subsurface-to-surface scenario involves a submarine's weapon system to attack a surface or land target. Missiles are fired from a submarine in the PMSR at a surface target (hulk) on the PMSR, similar to those discussed in the air-to-surface scenario. The air support required from the range to clear the target operational area and provide chase aircraft is identical to the surface-to-surface scenario (NAWCWD 2002).

2.3.2 Point Mugu Sea Range Ancillary Operations Systems

Ancillary Operations Systems are those systems that support routine PMSR operations and include systems such as radars, communications, lasers, chaff, and flares that are used in conjunction with the five typical weapons test scenarios discussed previously. Only the Ancillary Operations Systems that are located on SNI are discussed in this INRMP. The Ancillary Operations Systems located on SNI that are used by the PMSR include a variety of radar and communication systems.

Point Mugu Sea Range Radar Systems

The NAWCWD uses a variety of surveillance radars and display systems to detect and track aircraft and surface vessels on or near PMSR, and provide a complete picture of all of the activity within line-of-sight on the range, including both participants and non-participants. Metric radar systems are distinctly different from the surveillance systems by producing electronic data to generate time, space, and position information. Some metric radar systems have over-the-horizon capability through line-of-sight airborne relay with positioning accuracy enhanced by the use of GPS satellites (NAWCWD 2002). The PMSR also employs an extensive array of high-speed photo-optical equipment from both ground based and airborne platforms to record test and training activity (NAWCWD 2002).

Point Mugu Sea Range Communication Systems

SNI communication systems include voice communication systems (telephone), radio communication systems (satellite interfaces), a PMSR connectivity structure, video systems, and range timing system. A full range of communication systems provides the means to conduct effective testing and training activities on the PMSR. The communication services also provide for sea, land, and area clearance, range instrumentation connectivity, missile flight safety, target control, and target recovery operations. Fiber Optics Communications Underwater System connects Point Mugu with SNI via a redundant system of fiber-optic cables, and handles both voice and data transmission needs (NAWCWD 2002).

2.3.3 Point Mugu Sea Range Training

Military training land uses at SNI also support four general categories of training that include: fleet exercise training, littoral warfare training, small-scale amphibious warfare training, and aircraft training operations (NAWCWD 2002). These PMSR training activities occur in waters surrounding SNI and instrumentation on the island is used to record and evaluate the operations.

Fleet Exercise Training

A Fleet Exercise is a generic term which broadly encompasses a variety of Fleet training activities including but not limited to missile exercises, aircraft operations, joint training activities (e.g. Air Force and Navy), tactical training, and Fleet battle experiments. Fleet Exercises are major Naval training events designed to exercise a Battle Group's war fighting capabilities as they are intended to function in actual combat (NAWCWD 2002).

Littoral Warfare Training

Littoral warfare training is conducted by the Marine Corps and by Navy Special Warfare forces involving operations on land and on sea that encompass amphibious operations that include shore assaults, boat raids, airfield seizure, humanitarian assistance, and light-armor

reconnaissance. Environmental criteria associated with littoral warfare training at several SNI beach locations at various times of the year provide criteria used to determine when special warfare operations or small-scale amphibious training can be conducted at the island. Constraints are associated with seasonal marine mammal shore activity and bird nesting behavior. Since the Fleet routinely uses other ranges for littoral warfare and amphibious landing training, units become familiar with the training grounds. Therefore, in order to adequately evaluate their training skills prior to deployment, unfamiliar ground is required. Deployment of personnel is performed by small inflatable boats, helicopters, or aircraft limited to the insertion and extraction of troops to and from the SNI airstrip or other approved areas (NAWCWD 2002).

Amphibious Warfare Training

Amphibious warfare training exercises have been conducted at various locations on and surrounding SNI and are carefully selected to avoid or minimize damage to vegetation, wildlife, or cultural sites. Several alternative sites have accommodated shore landings, boat raids, and combat rubber boat landings including Daytona Beach (where resupply barges routinely land) and Redeye Beach. Additionally, search and rescue missions can be accomplished on beach areas near the old jetty on Coast Guard Beach, the missile impact targets, and the Vandal launch pad (NAWCWD 2002).

Aircraft Training Operations

SNI aircraft training operations typically occur in a supportive role to other training and testing operations because of the limited support services available at the SNI airfield, and the proximity of NBVC Point Mugu. An aircraft sortie consists of a takeoff, the assigned mission, and a subsequent landing. Sorties typically last only a few hours. The PMSR is divided into defined areas to allow for multiple events to occur simultaneously and to afford a safety margin for test and training activities (NAWCWD 2002). The Control Area Extensions are areas through the PMSR that are used by commercial and civil aircraft flying on assigned air traffic control routes. The Control Area Extensions can be requested and closed by NAWCWD Point Mugu when necessary, and standard entry and exit points into the airspace over the PMSR are not used. The Navy has proposed to extend its unmanned aircraft systems to support RDAT&E operations and training capabilities, to include unmanned maritime system operations on the PMSR (NAWCWD 2014).

2.3.4 Point Mugu Sea Range and SNI Operations Areas

NBVC SNI is part of the NAWCWD PMSR, within its southeastern portion (Map 2-1), and provides an isolated, centralized testing and evaluation location. The PMSR is comprised of various training ranges configured to isolate use areas and utilize the geographic diversity of the area to perform testing and evaluation of weapons systems (NAVFAC SW 2009).

The PMSR has established two airspace Restricted Areas over SNI that extend three nm (5.6 km) around the island. SNI also lies within Warning Area 289 airspace (Map 2-1).

Most of SNI is used as a range instrumentation site to support PMSR operations. SNI operations can be grouped into a few key locations: Alpha Launch Complex, B-807 Launch Site, Missile target area, and the Tomahawk soft recovery area.

Alpha Launch Complex

The Alpha Launch Complex is on the island's central plateau at its western end, at an elevation of over 620 feet (189 m) above mean sea level, and accommodates the Vandal launcher and various other concrete pads which are used to launch missiles and targets from mobile or portable launch stands.

B-807 Launch Site

The 807 Launch Site is on the western shoreline at an elevation of over 30 feet above mean sea level, and consists of a number of concrete pads where there is either a permanent 50k launch rail or where portable missile launchers can be bolted down, or portable launchers can be parked (S. Schwartz, *pers. comm.*, 2010). A wide variety of missiles have been launched from the 807 Launch Site over the years, but typical launches today are various missile configurations that use a Terrier booster with differing second stages (DoN 2005b; S. Schwartz, *pers. comm.*, 2010).

Missile Target Area

The only present-day impact area on SNI is a missile target area used for a variety of precision-guided, non-warhead missiles (S. Schwartz, *pers. comm.*, 2009). Specific locations of historic impact areas on the island are poorly documented. Range-related debris including targets, jet-assisted take off bottles, and ordnance debris are scattered throughout the northwest end of the island (NAVFAC 2009).

Tomahawk Soft Recovery Area

A soft recovery area has been established on the eastern end of SNI to support Tomahawk launches on PMSR, to take into account instances when missile flights must be terminated but the missile can be controlled to fly to a designated area. A ground crew can then pick up the missile with assistance of a truck or helicopter (NAWCWD 2002).

2.3.5 Safety Analyses and Planning

Point Mugu Sea Range Safety Analyses and Planning

Safety analyses and planning are integral parts of operations prior to the execution of any event on the PMSR and safety documentation begins with the preparation of either a Range Safety Approval or a Range Safety Operational Plan (NAWCWD 2002). These are similar planning documents, except that a Range Safety Operational Plan applies to missiles requiring a flight termination system controlled by a Missile Flight Safety Officer. Since most missiles fired on the PMSR do not carry live warheads, most impact areas are relatively small (NAWCWD 2002). Computer models are used to determine the size and location of the impact area into which debris may fall. These predictions are calculated based on altitude, speed, mass of debris pieces, angle of impact, and winds. Impact areas for missiles used on the PMSR are generally oval in shape and can be up to 10 nm (19 km) long and 7 nm (13 km) wide (NAWCWD 2002).

The Sea Range safety policy, procedures, and guidance are covered in NAWCWD Instruction 5100.2. This document defines range safety requirements, criteria, the safety planning process, and operational procedures. Although the Commander of NAWCWD has the ultimate responsibility for range safety, the authority for execution of these safety programs is delegated to the PMSR Safety Officer in the Range Safety Office.

Public access and proximity to the PMSR is a principal safety consideration since most of the PMSR is in non-Territorial Waters and open to the public.

San Nicolas Island Safety Analyses and Planning

SNI supports a significant portion of tests conducted within the PMSR and contains expansive safety zones related to surface craft and airspace. NAWCWD implements advance Notice to Airmen and Notice to Mariners as well as range safety clearance prior to conducting any tests that might be hazardous to non-participants. Access is granted for military related activities and for pre-approved, non-military uses, primarily for scientific purposes. The safety policy of NAWCWD is to observe every reasonable precaution in the planning and execution of all operations that occur on the PMSR and SNI, to prevent injury to people and damage to property (NAWCWD 2002).

Surface Restricted Areas

Restricted area regulation at SNI pertains to the waters of the Pacific Ocean that surround the island and that extend seaward about 3 miles (4.8 km) from the shoreline (33 CFR § 334.980). Three Naval restricted surface areas are located around SNI: Alpha, Bravo, and Charlie (Map 2-2). These areas are used on an “as-required” basis only, and public access is restricted only at those times when military exercises are being conducted. Procedures exist for the notification of the commercial shipping and recreational boating communities of potentially hazardous activities on the Sea Range and SNI, through the Notice to Mariners and daily VHF-FM Marine Radio (Channel 16) broadcasts. NAWCWD Point Mugu issues Notice to Airmen and Notice to Mariners 24 hours in advance of Navy activities that require exclusive use of an area.

Surveillance aircraft are regularly used to ensure that surface vessels are not present within safety zones.

The number of closures per year can fluctuate substantially, but there are periods of several months or more with no closures (NAWCWD 2002).

Restricted Air Space

The PMSR has established two airspace Restricted Areas over SNI that extend 3 nm (5.6 km) around the island. The two areas are divided by an imaginary line from the north side to the south side of the island where the Bravo boundaries intersect the shorelines; they extend from the surface to 100,000 feet (30,500 m) (NAWCWD 2002). Map 2-2 also shows warning zones associated with missile and target launches from the west end of SNI. Non-participating aircraft are precluded from entering SNI’s Restricted Area airspace (NAWCWD 2002). The only authorized air traffic into the SNI airfield is that approved by NBVC Point Mugu and generally include aircraft involved in testing and evaluation activities, training on the PMSR, and scheduled contract passenger flights which bring duty personnel, researchers, or other permitted visitors to the island. When Warning Area W-289 is being used in the Sea Range for military testing and training operations, the Navy notifies commercial, civilian, and other military aviation through a Notice to Airmen. Use of civilian air corridors are controlled by the Federal Aviation Authority and its Air Traffic Control agencies. NAWCWD can request closure of one civilian air corridor at a time (S. Schwartz, pers. comm., 2010).

Accident Potential Zones

Due to SNI’s isolation from civilian communities, an Air Installation Compatibility Use Zone study has not been conducted. Air Installation Compatibility Use Zone studies are necessary to analyze air operations, noise zones, Accident Potential Zones, and existing land use encroachments in the vicinity of the airfield. Accident Potential Zones and Community Noise Equivalent Levels have not been determined at SNI and may significantly impact Nicktown and PWD facilities. DoD criteria for airfield safety indicate that many of the Nicktown facilities are inappropriately located within the approach and departure clearance zones (SNI 2003).

Land Restricted Areas

Naval security personnel secure land restricted access zones prior to and during launch activities at the west end of the island, to prevent unauthorized personnel and non-participants from entering the area. Roads into Warning Zone 2 are blocked during launches, and personnel in Warning Zone 2 are required to be in protected blockhouses or shelters during launches. No personnel are allowed in Warning Zone 1 during missile or target launches, or during missile impacts at the missile target site. In addition, clearance areas are cleared of all non-participating civilian commercial fishing or recreational boats prior to launch activities (NAWCWD 2002).

Electromagnetic Radiation Hazards

The Navy operates a variety of equipment and facilities at SNI that generate electromagnetic radiation. Electromagnetic radiation emissions on SNI cause concern in terms of Hazards of Electromagnetic Radiation to Personnel (HERP) and Hazards of Electromagnetic Radiation to Ordnance (HERO). A large concentration of electromagnetic radiation emitting systems can be found on SNI due to its instrumentation involvement with the PMSR (SNI 2003).

There are numerous emitters on SNI that exceed HERP limits from less than a few feet to many hundreds of feet with their illuminated volume. Most of the transmitting systems at SNI can create a HERP condition only if a person were to get sufficiently close to an emitting antennae where the concentrated power would be dispersed over a very limited area. For a HERP condition to exist on SNI, personnel would have to move into a volume of space illuminated by an emitting system. This would require a person to be on a tower, building roof, or suspended in free space 20 feet (6 m) or more in the air. Sources of emissions for HERP arcs include radars, transmitters, relay links, transmitting antennae fields, and a command destruct system (SNI 2003).

There are several sources of emissions for HERO arcs. Within a HERO arc, there is the risk of unintentional actuation of electro-explosive devices or otherwise electrically activating ordnance because of radio frequency electromagnetic fields. This unintended actuation could have safety or reliability consequences (NOLF SNI 2003).

Currently, there are no HERP or HERO zones that extend into Nicktown and PWD areas (NOLF SNI 2003).

Explosive Safety Quantity Distance Arcs

Various munitions and targets are stored and maintained at SNI that are susceptible to the effects of electromagnetic radiation. These include missile warheads, rocket motors, high explosives, and other types of ordnance that are used in the testing or training activities occurring on the PMSR. Munitions arrive on the island either by surface ship or by air transport (NAWCWD 2002).

Explosive Ordnance Disposal (EOD) uses SNI for training operations and open detonation of unexploded ordnance operations in support of the entire PMSR. Open detonation operations are usually conducted on SNI at the EOD Demolition Range atop the ridge. However, unexploded ordnance may be found throughout the island. The SNI EOD site can handle 100 lbs (45 kg) Net Explosive Weight for working open detonation operations and up to 200 lbs (91 kg) Net Explosive Weight for emergency open detonation operations (NAVFAC SW 2010a). Any item is deemed unsafe to move may require subsequent open detonation wherever it is found.

No habitable development should exist within Explosive Safety Quantity Distance arcs. There are no inhabited buildings within the Explosive Safety Quantity Distance arcs on SNI, and no waivers or exemptions are in effect. There are also no ordnance storage or handling facilities within Nicktown or PWD areas (NOLF SNI 2003).

2.4 Facilities

The facilities on SNI include 85 buildings and 71 structures to transport, house, and support personnel and related materials. Infrastructure includes water wells, a desalination plant, water distribution and sewage systems, and a power plant and distribution system. The island has 47 miles (76 km) of roads, 22 miles (35 km) of which are paved (Map 2-3).

The barge landing ramp at the southeast of the island at Daytona Beach is an Open Ocean Roll-on, Roll-off Barge Landing Ramp (NAVFAC SW 2010a). The ramp is important for the

operations and support of SNI because most items transported to the island are too heavy for air transport and are therefore shipped via barge.

The age of existing facilities throughout the installation ranges from 73 years (built in 1942) to recent construction (NAVFAC SW 2010a). SNI has a 10,000-foot (3,048-m) concrete and asphalt runway located on the mesa in the eastern portion of the island. A control tower, hangers, ground control approach capabilities, and a fire station are adjacent to the airfield.

All development on SNI is associated with the military, and land uses and facilities have most recently been categorized and assessed in the *NBVC San Nicolas Island and Fort Hunter Liggett Activity Overview Plan* (NAVFAC SW 2010a). According to the Activity Overview Plan, land uses and facilities have been categorized by their mission criticality as Mission Critical, Mission Support, or Quality of Life.

2.4.1 Mission Critical

Mission critical lands and facilities are those which directly support the mission of the installation and tenants, and are summarized below.

San Nicolas Island Sea Range Instrumentation Facilities

Because of its strategic location, SNI can be used to mimic shipboard launches of missiles and targets. Mission Critical Island facilities support all aspects of Range Operations, such as missile and target launches. SNI houses an array of buildings and complexes for specialized testing and evaluation projects.

Range support facilities at SNI include metric radars, telemetry antennas, receivers and transmitters, a frequency monitoring station, photo-optical tracking instrumentation, range communications facilities, microwave transmitters, missile launching pads, ordnance bunkers, surveillance radars, meteorological measurement systems, and target control facilities.

Airfield Operations Facilities

Because of its isolated location, SNI relies on the airfield operations in order to accommodate daily living on the Island. The SNI airfield is owned, operated, and maintained by the Navy and consists of a single instrument-capable runway able to accommodate the largest military transport aircraft. The airfield consists of a control tower, hangars, lighting, ground control approach systems (Instrument Landing System), and a fire station (NAVFAC SW 2010a). The landing area of the airfield consists of a 10,000 foot (3,050 m) long, 200 foot wide (61 m), concrete and asphalt runway capable of accommodating C-5 aircraft. A 75 foot wide taxiway parallels the runway on the southwestern side of the airfield. Currently, one air cargo flight per week delivers supplies to SNI (S. Schwartz, *pers. comm.*, 2010).

Waterfront Operations Facilities

To support the PMSR and SNI infrastructure, bulk materials and supplies must be transported to the island and waste materials must be removed. Currently, most materials and supplies are transported to SNI by supply barges. The barges are generally loaded at Port Hueneme, California and transported to SNI via tug boat. Port facilities in Long Beach, California have also been used to load barges for projects in the past, but are not routinely used (S. Schwartz, *pers. comm.*, 2010). Approximately 30 to 40 barge operations are required annually; materials shipped include heavy equipment (missiles, targets, launchers, and military hardware), fuel trucks, bulk construction materials, and other items not feasibly transported via aircraft. Barge operations have been ongoing at SNI since 1943, with operations conducted at Daytona Beach since 1976 (Naval Air Weapons Station China Lake 2002).

At present, fuel barges are moored offshore at Coast Guard Beach and offload their fuel to the fuel farm through pipelines on the seafloor (NAVFAC SW 2010a). Water is also barged to the island as needed, and water barges are moored offshore at Coast Guard Beach where they offload their water through supply hoses at the fuel farm mooring site (S. Schwartz, *pers. comm.*, 2010).

Barges transporting other provisions offload at the supply pier at the southeast side of SNI near Daytona Beach. The supply pier near Daytona Beach is equipped with an Open Ocean Roll-on, Roll-off Barge Landing Ramp (NAVFAC SW 2010a). The supply pier and barge landing ramp are extremely important for the operations and support of SNI (NAVFAC SW 2010a).

Natural and Cultural Resource Management Program Facilities

Along with the Sea Range Operations, SNI hosts an Archeology and Biology Laboratory (NAVFAC SW 2010a). Given the vast number and variety of cultural and natural resources found on the Island, these facilities play a very important role. These facilities are located approximately one mile northwest of the Community Support area and Public Works areas, on the northern side of SNI.

2.4.2 Mission Support

Mission support lands and facilities are those which indirectly support the mission of the installation and tenants. Mission support functions aboard SNI include Administration, Communications (non RDAT&E), Circulation, General Maintenance, Public Safety, Supply, Utilities, Vehicle Maintenance, and Weapons.

Administration Facilities

The center of the Community Support Area houses the main administrative functions for SNI. Other facilities with administrative space requirements include Public Works, Morale, Welfare, and Recreation, and the galley (NAVFAC SW 2010a).

General Maintenance Facilities

General maintenance is performed by NAVFAC SW PWD (NAVFAC SW 2010a).

Public Safety Facilities

The fire station and security building are co-located at the airfield. These facilities are located here to meet all response times and meet strategic location goals (NAVFAC SW 2010a).

Storage Facilities

Storage facilities are located within the Community Support Area in Building 63 (housing services and galley storage). Building 66, located at the airfield, is used for air cargo support (NAVFAC SW 2010a).

Vehicle Maintenance Facilities

Vehicle maintenance is provided by Public Works within the Public Works compound. Facilities consist of vehicle maintenance bays and covered storage for construction equipment (NAVFAC SW 2010a).

2.4.3 Quality of Life

Quality of life lands and facilities are those which support the well-being of the warfighter, summarized below.

Bachelor Housing Facilities

There are 11 housing facilities on the Island with accommodations for 162 personnel, both military and civilian, permanent and transient (NAVFAC SW 2010a; S. Schwartz, *pers. comm.*, 2010). All housing is located within the Community Support area.

Community Support Facilities

SNI community support facilities are comprised of mostly outdoor and indoor recreational facilities, but also include the galley and Morale, Welfare, and Recreation facilities. These facilities are located in the Community Support Area also known as “Nicktown”, which is located approximately one mile northwest of the airfield, on the northern side of the Island. The galley provides breakfast, lunch, and dinner to personnel during the day (NAVFAC SW 2010a).

Medical/Dental Facility

The medical facility is located at the southwestern corner of Owen Road and Public Works Circle intersection (NAVFAC SW 2010a).

2.5 Transportation and Utilities

2.5.1 Transportation

As mentioned previously, there are approximately 22 miles (35 km) of paved roads that generally run southeast to northwest along the long axis of the island. Monroe Drive, Beach Road, Jackson Highway, Shannon Road, and Tufts Road, Owen Road, and Skyline Drive are the primary named roadways. The circulation of traffic centers around three general areas: (1) the Community Support and Public Works areas; (2) the airfield; and (3) Test and Evaluation infrastructure on the western half of the island. A secondary traffic focus is the Beach Road access to the supply pier and barge landing ramp on the southeast coast of the island (NAVFAC SW 2010a).

All vehicles on the island are government-owned or controlled. Traffic conflicts only occur when convoys transport ordnance or other hazardous materials. Non-participating vehicles are precluded from operating along roads taken by these convoys while en route. Parking is adequate at all areas. A bus services the Nicktown, PWD areas, and airfield areas several times each weekday (NOLF SNI 2003).

Personnel within the Community Support area or Public Works areas typically walk when their destination is within those areas (NAVFAC SW 2010a).

Transportation to and from SNI is nearly exclusively accomplished through scheduled contract passenger flights which bring duty personnel, researchers, or other permitted visitors to the island. Supplies and materials are transported to the island via C-130 aircraft (scheduled weekly) and barge (scheduled bi-weekly, but often less than monthly due to weather). Military personnel intermittently access the island using military aircraft, including helicopters and fixed wing aircraft, but visits are typically short in duration and related to specific military training operations.

2.5.2 Utilities

Utilities infrastructure at SNI consist of an electrical distribution system, water distribution system, storm drainage system, sanitary sewer system, and communications system. All residential trash, recyclable materials, and industrial waste products are shipped off the island (S. Schwartz, *pers. comm.*, 2009). Utilities functions are confined to two primary locations at SNI. One is south of the Community Support Area near the intersection of Monroe Drive and Owen Road, and the second is at the extreme northwestern end of the central plateau.

Facilities south of the Community Support area include the Electrical Power Plant and water storage tanks (NAVFAC SW 2010a). Water storage tanks are south of the Community Support area (NAVFAC SW 2010a). A Reverse Osmosis (RO) plant located next to Coast Guard Beach supplies potable water to these active tanks where water is distributed to the Island. The sewage treatment plant and ponds are just north of this area.

Other utilities such as septic drain fields are scattered about SNI.

Electrical Distribution System

The electricity used on SNI is generated by the Electrical Power Plant and distributed throughout the island by three 4160 V feeders. The Electrical Power Plant uses JP-5 jet fuel in five diesel generators to produce power for the Island (National Renewable Energy Laboratory [NREL] 2008). This facility houses five, three-phase, 4,160-volt diesel generators with the following capacities: 825 kilowatts (kW), 910 kW, 1000 kW, and two at 1150 kW (NREL 2008; NAVFAC SW 2010a). The average load ranges from 550 kW to 950 kW, with a 150 kW to 200 kW peak (over the average) occurring morning, noon, and evening (NREL 2008). The total capacity, 5,150 kW meets the present peak demand of 1,050 kW (NAVFAC SW 2010a). Fuel for the generators is stored in a 10,000-gallon (37,854-liter) above-ground tank (NAVFAC SW 2010a). The fuel tank is refilled by an underground pipeline. The fuel is barged to SNI and pumped from the Fuel Farm at Coast Guard Beach to the airfield, then to the Electrical Power Plant through an underground pipeline (NREL 2008). A 3,000-gallon (11,356-liter) lube oil tank is located adjacent to the Electrical Power Plant. A pump allows transfer of oil to the engines as needed (NAVFAC SW 2010a). The plant is also provided with an adjacent waste oil collection system. This system includes two 3,000-gallon (11,356-liter) holding tanks, two 500-gallon (1,893-liter) sump tanks, and two sump pumps (NAVFAC SW 2010a).

In addition to the 4,160-volt generators located in the Electrical Power Plant, critical loads in some buildings have back-up power from local emergency generators. (NAVFAC SW 2010a).

The Navy funded the Department of Energy's National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) to provide a plan to outline how SNI can transition into a renewable community and identify a current, energy, water, and waste baseline for SNI (NREL 2008). The NREL assessment findings indicate that on-site renewable energy systems could provide much of the island's energy requirements and that it may be cost effective (NREL 2008). The wind energy facility construction at SNI was completed spring 2015 and will connect to the existing power grid system in April 2016. The wind turbines are located on Skyline Drive and will provide approximately 900 kW of wind power and battery storage, thereby reducing the quantity of JP-5 jet fuel used on the island (NAVFAC SW 2010a; NAVFAC SW 2010b).

Water Distribution System

Fresh water is a limited resource on SNI and is a main concern for future growth. Water distribution is comprised of a network of storage tanks, pumps, mains, valves, and hydrants. Water is distributed from the main tanks to the different areas on SNI. Pressure reducing stations on the water mains serve the low elevation areas such as the Community Support area and the Public Works areas. For these areas, the water pressure for building service is regulated to approximately 60 pounds per square inch gauge. Water is pressurized for high elevation areas and pumped from tanks to serve the Jackson Hill area (NAVFAC SW 2010a).

The primary source of potable water on the island is the water produced at the RO desalination plant installed in Building 50 at Coast Guard Beach. Two RO desalination units were installed in 2003 and the raw water source for the units is seawater, which is pumped from the beach. In January 2009, seven of the ten proposed wells were installed. Water is pumped from the well points to a seawater holding tank prior to treatment. The brine discharge (highly mineralized wastewater) from the RO unit is transferred to a secondary wastewater holding tank, which is located next to the seawater holding tank. When the wastewater tank is full, the brine is discharged to two brine leach fields located on Coast Guard beach. A brine pond is located approximately 660 feet (200 m) from the RO unit, along the upper beach where it disperses through the sand. The brine pond is used as a back-up in the event that the holding tank or leach fields are destroyed during a storm. The amount of brine discharge is monitored and limited by the Ocean Plan-Water Resources Board. The seawater desalination system discharges under an exception and permit into the SNI ASBS, with limitations including flow limits (67,000 gallons [253,623 liters] per day). The ASBS exception was adopted by the State Water Resources Control Board (SWRCB) (Resolution 90-105) in 1990, and the most recent permit (National Pollution Discharge Elimination System [NPDES] No. CA0061794) was re-issued by the Los Angeles Regional Water Quality Control Board (LARWQCB) in 2004 (Merkel and Associates Inc. 2007a). The Navy is in the preliminary stages of evaluating outfall designs in order to relocate the brine discharge outfall offshore.

Additionally, fresh water can be delivered from off-island. A water barge can be moored near the RO desalination plant at Coast Guard Beach. The water is then offloaded through a submarine water line to a storage tank. The second method is to deliver water tankers (trailers) on the freight barge that moors at the supply pier located at Daytona Beach. These two methods are very expensive and are used only as a last resort (NOLF SNI 2003).

Freshwater wells on the northwestern part of SNI are not a source of potable water but rather provide an as needed source of water for construction activities.

Storm Drainage System

SNI is required to comply with federal and state storm water regulations, in particular the NPDES General Industrial Activities Storm Water Permit and the California General Industrial Activities Storm Water Permit (general permit). The general permit regulates storm water associated with industrial activity and sets requirements to reduce pollutants in industrial storm water discharges. A Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan (SWPPP) was revised in July 2010 and has been implemented for SNI (NBVC SNI 2010). The SWPPP was written in accordance with

requirements of the SWRCB Water Quality Order No. 97-03-DWQ and NPDES General Permit No. CAS000001. The general permit authorizes SNI to discharge storm water from the date the Navy submitted a Notice of Intent (17 March 1992). The SWPPP is intended to identify and evaluate potential sources of storm water pollutants and to specify Best Management Practices (BMPs) to control these sources and prevent or reduce pollutants in storm water discharges and authorized non-storm water discharges (NOLF SNI 2003; Merkel and Associates Inc. 2007a; NBVC SNI 2010). Please refer to *Section 5.9: Storm Water Management* for more information regarding this topic.

Sanitary Sewer System

The Community Support area and Public Works areas are serviced by a 40,000-gallon (151,416-liter) per day sanitary sewage treatment system (NAVFAC SW 2010a). Facilities at the airfield and on the remainder of the island are served by individual septic tanks and drain fields (S. Schwartz, *pers. comm.*, 2010).

The sanitary sewer system components include gravity sewer lines, septic tanks and leach fields, and wastewater treatment facility (oxidation ponds). The wastewater treatment facility is located to the north and west of the Community Support area and consists of a series of three aerated stabilization ponds. Due to the large capacity of the stabilization ponds and the small population served by the plant, the primary method of wastewater disposal is by evaporation. The secondary method of disposal is by discharging the wastewater through irrigation. Treated wastewater is discharged via spray nozzles over a six-acre (2.4-ha) area of land which is restricted and off-limits to personnel. As required by its Waste Discharge Permit, the Navy is responsible for reporting effluent discharge (amount and concentration of potential contaminants) for the SNI wastewater treatment facility (Merkel and Associates 2007a). The treatment facility must meet effluent discharge limitations and monitoring reports are submitted quarterly to meet the limitations set forth under the Waste Discharge Permit issued by the water quality control board (NAWCWD 2002).

Two septic tanks and leach fields dispose of the sewage generated by the facilities located at the airfield. Thirty-six septic tanks and leach fields serve the facilities in the outlying areas (SNI 2003). Septic and holding tank locations are necessary due to the size of the island and the remote locations of some of the buildings. The septic and holding tanks are inspected on a quarterly basis and pumped quarterly or as required. The majority of the outlying buildings are used infrequently or during a limited work day schedule; therefore, septic and holding tanks do not appear to pose a significant risk of contaminating the watershed areas.

Communications System

Communications throughout the island and to outlying areas are maintained through telephones, radios, pagers, and the internet. The backbone of communications on the island is supported by two fiber optic telecommunication cables that run 65 miles (105 km) between NBVC Point Mugu and SNI (NAVFAC SW 2010a). PWD personnel maintain contact with each other throughout the island with hand-held radios and pagers. Internet access is available through Navy/Marine Corps Intranet or through a satellite link; dial-up internet access is not used at SNI (S. Schwartz, *pers. comm.*, 2010).

2.6 Future Use Patterns and Plans

SNI Future Range Operations

Future operations at the PMSR and at SNI may include new facilities and target launch systems to support the following additional theater missile defense activities (NAWCWD 2002).

Strategically located multi-purpose instrumentation sites would also be constructed in support of future range operations and SNI facility modernization (NAWCWD 2002). These facilities would increase NAWCWD capabilities through the use of mobile instrumentation and would also increase opportunities for resource sharing. Examples of mobile instrumentation, which could be used at the proposed sites include portable communications vans, portable optics stations, and portable tracking systems (NAWCWD 2002).

SNI Activity Overview Plan and Sustainable Planning and Design

The SNI Activity Overview Plan identified a preferred vision to construct facilities in support of new and expanded mission requirements, create more community support to meet facility requirements, eliminate duplication, and reduce infrastructure costs (NAVFAC SW 2010a). The preferred vision as identified in the Activity Overview Plan is based on the principles of sustainable planning and design and will provide ideal functional relationships to increase operational capacity, promote proper circulation, provide adequate levels of community support, and improve land use efficiencies (NAVFAC SW 2010a). The preferred vision in the Activity Overview Plan describes the SNI 25-year vision for land and facility use and presents an implementation strategy for meeting short-term, mid-term, and long-term planning actions.

Short-term planning actions are those that will occur within a five year period. These actions consist of high priority construction to meet immediate deficiencies, re-use of facilities with minor to no modification, conversion of Navy owned land into training ranges, leased facilities, and minor construction with few development constraints (NAVFAC SW 2010a).

Mid-term planning actions are those that will occur between 5 to 10 years, and consist of projects that typically require a series of actions. Those actions at SNI include projects that must be processed through the Installation Integrated Priority List and actions predicated on prior planning actions such as facility demolitions or user relocation (NAVFAC SW 2010a).

Long-term planning actions occur beyond 10 years, to be implemented by 2030. Long-term planning projects are those that are lower on an installation's Integrated Priority List than other similar projects, are predicated on facilities exceeding their life expectancy prior to 2030, have significant costs precluding mid-term implementation, or are dependent on the implementation of mid-term actions (NAVFAC SW 2010a).

The projects recommended for implementation are identified in the Activity Overview Plan. Each of these recommended projects are cross-referenced to a project number as identified in the Activity Overview Plan and utilize existing land use designations as designated by category code numbers (NAVFAC SW 2010a). Unified Facilities Criteria 2-000-05N defines category code numbers to provide a common planning standard and identify facility uses in a consistent method.

3.0 Current Condition of Natural Resources

3.1 Ecoregional Setting

San Nicolas Island is the outermost of the eight islands comprising the California Channel Islands chain located off of southern California (Map 1-1). The California Channel Islands are notably different from each other with respect to climate, geology, history, landforms, maximum elevation, size, and vegetation. The eight islands have been divided into two major groups: (1) the Northern Channel Islands of San Miguel, Santa Rosa, Santa Cruz and Anacapa; and (2) the Southern Channel Islands of Santa Barbara, San Nicolas, Santa Catalina, and San Clemente. The islands represent emergent portions of a complex system of submarine canyons and ridges in a geomorphic province referred to as the California Continental Borderlands (Vedder and Howell 1980). SNI lies within the SCB on the Santa Rosa-Cortez Ridge, one of several northwest-trending ridges, which characterize the offshore region. The Southern Channel Islands more geographically isolated from each other and the mainland compared to the Northern Channel Islands, which are clustered together and lie with their long axis in an east-west direction.

The Channel Islands are influenced by ocean circulation, insularity, and human occupation. At various times in geologic history, they have been sculpted by tectonic action, changes in sea level, ecological influence from the mainland, and human inhabitation, producing unique ecological settings that include many endemic species.

3.1.1 Insularity and Consequences of Isolation

The Channel Islands have evolved over thousands of years to host a multitude of endemic flora and fauna distinct from adjacent mainland areas. These endemic species have in some cases adapted to narrow island niches of the Channel Islands or an individual island. Existing endemic populations are of high value because they represent adaptations to unique island habitats and provide excellent indicator species to track changes within island ecosystems and assess the status of current and desired conditions. Due to their isolated evolution and distinct habitat associations, the vulnerability of endemic species on SNI, and the other Channel Islands, are subject to decline from direct impact or habitat modification to a much greater degree than mainland species.

3.1.2 Historical Versus Current Conditions

Few detailed descriptions of the landscape of SNI are available prior to the introduction of sheep ranching in the mid-1850s. However, there is an early reference to woody vegetation made by Captain George Nidever, a sea otter hunter, in the fall of 1852. Nidever reportedly found “some high bushes...” on the island (Junak 2008). Ranching began on the island by the middle of the 19th century and continued until June 1943. During the first half of the 20th century, sheep numbers on SNI apparently varied between 1,200 and 3,000 animals, until they were removed during World War II. As a result of ranching activities, the introduction of non-native plants and grazing animals had profound effects on the plant communities of SNI (Junak 2008). Ranching on the Channel Islands changed the land cover of large areas from native scrub to grasslands dominated by alien annual grasses. This conversion of vegetation from one type to another has had grave consequences for some island endemics, which depend upon habitats that are no longer intact (USGS 2003).

Past land uses and fishing practices by Native Americans, transient Europeans, and American occupation (including grazing and fishing) have affected the composition and distribution of terrestrial and marine communities and associated wildlife on SNI. The full extent of these changes are unknown because of the lack of baseline data on historic conditions, biological monitoring, or even periodic biotic surveys. It is not known whether the current trajectory of change is toward historic conditions or some new equilibrium.

The timeline in Figure 3-1 highlights human occupation time frames and some significant land use practices that historically occurred on SNI. Information regarding the Native American use of island resources is described from archeological investigations, and centers primarily on marine resources. Overall anthropogenic changes to the island’s terrestrial and marine habitats are undoubtedly an assimilation of human inhabitation and resource use throughout the timeline. Since the ranching era ended, changes to the island’s biological communities and landscape are most notably from continued wind and water erosion impacts proliferated from historical grazing practices and from Naval operations involving construction, accidental fires, borrow pits, and facilities. The introduction of non-native species both accidentally and intentionally during the human occupation of the island have prompted challenges to the floral and faunal landscape that continue to affect the island’s ecological condition.

Figure 3-1. Timeline of resource use and occupation of San Nicolas Island.

3.2 Climate

The climate of SNI is highly maritime and is included within a broader-scale Mediterranean-type climatic regime characterized by cool, wet winters and warm, dry summers (De Violini 1974; Philbrick and Haller 1977; Moody 2000).

Average monthly temperatures on SNI range from a low of 55.6 degrees Fahrenheit (°F) (13.1 degrees Celsius [°C]) in January, to a high of 64.7°F (18.2°C) in September (WRCC 2010), with an average maximum temperature of 71°F (22°C) in September (Figure 3-2). Freezing temperatures have not been recorded on the island; a record minimum of 33°F (0.5°C) was recorded in January 1949 when light snow fell. Temperatures above 100°F (38°C) occasionally occur on the island; a 25-year maximum temperature of 106°F (41°C) was recorded in September 1955 (De Violini 1974).

As is typical for southern California, the most rainfall on SNI occurs from November through March (WRCC 2010), with very little rain May through September (Figure 3-3). Average annual rainfall on SNI is highly variable. From 1948–2005, an average of 8.2 inches (20.8 centimeters [cm]) of rain fell per year, ranging from a minimum of 2.6 inches (6.6 cm) in 1961 to a maximum of 21.8 inches (55.4 cm) in 1998 (Figure 3-4; Junak 2008). Data from four coastal weather stations (San Diego

Airport 1921–2009, Laguna Beach 1929–2008, Newport Beach 1922–2009, and Oxnard 1924–2003) indicate that SNI receives approximately 4 inches (10 cm) less rain per year on average than the mainland (WRCC 2010). These four coastal stations averaged 11.9 inches (30.2 cm) in the same years available from SNI. The data from the coastal stations are included here to illustrate the drought conditions that have prevailed in the region in recent years. Since SNI tends to average several inches less rainfall per year compared to the mainland, the drought indicated by the coastal weather data is likely to have been even more severe on SNI.

A dominant feature of island weather is the prevailing northwest wind, which averages 16 miles per hour (mph) (14 knots) with an annual mean maximum of 60 mph (52 knots). The island presents an obstruction to the prevailing wind flow.

Cold oceanic water interfacing with warm inland air masses create dense fog during certain times of the year. The interactions between the strong winds, marine fogs, and island topography promote distinct microclimate zones at various island aspects. The northern and western portions of SNI obstruct prevailing wind flow, increasing the interaction of moisture-laden low stratus clouds moving over the open ocean with the island. Considering average annual precipitation of the island is approximately 8.2 inches (20.8 cm), moisture derived from fog and cloud drip contribute significantly to island ecosystems. Precipitation on the island is the only source of fresh ground water on SNI, according to Burnham et al. (1963).

Figure 3-2. Monthly temperature regime on San Nicolas Island (WRCC 2010; NAWCWD 2004).

Figure 3-3. Monthly rainfall on San Nicolas Island (WRCC 2010).

Figure 3-4. Average annual rainfall total for San Nicolas Island (1949–2014) and four coastal weather stations (1949–2014) (WRCC 2010; Junak 2008).

3.3 Physical Conditions

3.3.1 Topography

The topography of SNI was initially formed and subsequently shaped by changes in sea level and differential uplift of the island (Vedder and Howell 1980). SNI is the one Channel Island that is not directly of volcanic origin as it does not have igneous rock formations. SNI rose from the seafloor, being exposed for the last one million years. From the sea, SNI presents a low, table-like profile containing fourteen distinct marine terraces, all of which have been dated and used to establish sea level changes over the last one million years. The island topography is dominated by a broad terrace or mesa with no distinctive peaks (Map 3-1). This mesa covers most of the surface area of the island, being roughly 6.4 miles (10.3 km) long and 2.1 miles (3.4 km) wide (USGS 1:24,000 Topographic Map, SNI California). The main axis of the island runs from northwest to southeast, and the mesa slopes gently to the northeast from the highest points, which are near the south rim of the terrace. The highest point on the island is Jackson Hill at 907 feet (276 m) (HDR 2014).

Cliffs along the northern perimeter of SNI's central mesa lead to seven well-defined marine terraces visible on the north side of the island. Terrace levels range from underwater depths of about 400 feet (122 m) to an elevation of 900 feet (274 m). Terraces are covered by windblown sand (dune) deposits that decrease in depth from northwest to southeast. The average surface elevation is 500 feet (150 m).

3.3.2 Geology

SNI is thought to be underlain by the Franciscan formation, which consists of a variety of rocks including deep-marine sedimentary rocks, as well as metamorphosed igneous rock. Eocene marine terraces on SNI are comprised of sandstone, formed as a result of sand from the sea floor being compressed by the weight of the overlying sea. Changes in sea level and tectonic uplift eventually exposed the sandstone to a variety of erosional processes such as wind, waves, and rain that gradually sculpted SNI into its current state. Underlying dune sands and marine terrace deposits are alternating layers of Tertiary marine sandstone and siltstone. All units have been folded into a broad anticline. The axis of this fold runs parallel to the length of the island, plunges slightly southeast, and is offset by several Pre-Quaternary faults (Vedder and Norris 1963).

According to Vedder and Norris (1963), the exposed Tertiary section on the island consists of nearly 3,500 feet (1,067 m) of alternating marine sandstone and siltstone beds that contain minor amounts of inter-embedded conglomerate and pebbly mudstone. Vedder and Norris divided this sedimentary rock sequence into 35 mapping units, all of Eocene age, and they reported that several small andesitic dikes of Miocene age intrude the sedimentary rocks near the southeastern end of the island. They found that dune sand and fossiliferous marine terrace deposits of Quaternary age cover most of the central and western parts of SNI.

Fossils of Eocene rocks are predominantly foraminifera, which can be correlated with those of other geologic formations throughout southern California. Fossils of marine terrace deposits consist of over 250 species of mollusks and other invertebrates. These assemblages are presumed to occur throughout marine terraces on SNI and are unique in their completeness (Vedder and Norris 1963). The fossils "...represent one of the most complete sequence of fossil assemblages from successive terrace levels in southern California and contain the largest faunas reported from terrace levels higher than 500 feet (150 m)" (Vedder and Norris 1963).

3.3.3 Hydrology

During their investigations, Burnham et al. (1963) found no evidence of any geologic feature that would allow fresh water to move between the California mainland and SNI. They stated that groundwater on the island is recharged by deep penetration of rainfall and runoff into the highly absorptive fresh dune sand at the west end, which gravity moves downward to the main water table or to impermeable zones that divert the water laterally downslope. Groundwater is discharged at the island's surface by a number of intermittent, as well as some perennial, springs and seeps concentrated along the north side of the island (Burnham et al. 1963). The limited sources of groundwater play a vital role in vegetation community structure, contributing to the geographic partitioning of vegetation found on SNI.

The climate and ultimately, terrestrial hydrology of the Channel Islands are also influenced by the general ocean circulation patterns in the SCB. Current dynamics are dominated by convergence of the California Current and the California Countercurrent (Map 3-2) and are modified by complex bottom topography, shoreline morphology and the presence of the islands (Browne 1994). The cold, southward flowing California Current is pushed offshore just west of the northern Channel Islands, at Points Arguello and Conception. The release of the coastal waters from the influence of the California Current, in combination with the California Countercurrent, admits a large-scale, counterclockwise flow (Southern California Eddy) which influences the entire Channel Island system (Browne 1994; Engle 1994). The southward flowing

limb of the Southern California Eddy is held outside the Santa Barbara and San Pedro channels, and brings cold water to the more oceanward islands such as SNI and San Miguel Island. These oceanographic circulation patterns directly affect the formation of low stratus cloud formation and the formation of coastal fog.

The terrestrial hydrology of SNI may also be directly influenced by coastal fog as a summer moisture source. California’s “fog belt” is located along the immediate coast of the mainland and its offshore islands, subjecting these areas to persistent summer fog and overcast conditions (Fischer et al. 2008; Raven and Axelrod 1978). Coastal fog and overcast conditions both result from low stratus cloud formation. The distinction is that “overcast” is a cloud layer above the surface that obscures all (or most of) the sky, while “fog” is in contact with the surface and reduces visibility to below one kilometer (National Weather Service 2007). Both fog and overcast conditions can reduce the severity of plant drought stress during the summer rainless season, through different mechanisms (Fischer et al. 2008). Previous studies in the California fog belt have shown that stratus clouds can enhance the availability of water to the ecosystem during the rainless summer, through fog drip (Fischer et al. 2008; Kennedy and Sousa 2006; Corbin et al. 2005; Cole

2005; Burgess and Dawson 2004; Dawson 1998; Ingraham and Matthews 1995; Jacobs et al. 1985; Azevedo and Morgan 1974). For more information on how summer fog and overcast conditions may affect drought stress and ecological functioning of coastal California endemic plant species refer to Fischer 2008.

3.3.4 Soils and Soil Condition

The central and northeastern parts of SNI are covered by marine terrace deposits, and the western end of the island is covered by deep (up to 75 feet [23 m] thick) dune sand deposits composed of wind-transported medium grain sand (DoN 2005). Marine terrace deposits are composed of unconsolidated clayey, silty sands. Some of these are cemented together by caliche, a cement-like calcium carbonate deposit formed by the downward percolation of rainwater. The rest of SNI is covered with sandy loams. Sandy beaches are scattered along the coast.

The U.S. Soil Conservation Service (now the Natural Resources Conservation Service [NRCS]) (Estrada 1985) mapped 27 soil units on SNI: beach and dune sand; Jehemy clay; several sandy loams and loamy sands; rock outcrops; and eroded, channeled, and gullied complexes. The most common soil types on the island are rock outcrops (3,699 acres [1,497 ha]), Vizcapoint severely eroded land complexes (1,270 acres [514 ha]), dune sand (1,158 acres [469 ha]), and Vizcapoint sandy loam (1,079 acres [437 ha]).

Most island soils are rated as severely limited for construction, are highly susceptible to erosion by wind, and are moderately erodible by water (Estrada 1985; DoN 2005). Map 3-3 depicts the soils of SNI.

Erosional forces from seasonal rainfall and consistent northwest winds, in conjunction with grazing effects, have facilitated the loss of surface soil particles to adjacent nearshore waters, especially along the steep southern edge of the island. The Vizcapoint sandy loam soil layer is virtually nonexistent, presumably eroded away due to these factors.

3.3.5 Water and Sediment

Nearshore waters of SNI are regulated by oceanic circulation and hydrology as reviewed in the “Ecology of the Southern California Bight: A Synthesis and Interpretation” (Dailey et al. 1993). Springs are the only perennial source of fresh water on the island. SNI has limited surface fresh water sources that only persist during seasonal rainfall events. There are no perennial surface fresh water streams that run to SNI’s shoreline. Erosion and sediment input affect streams and nearshore waters. These erosion events occur primarily during seasonal rain fall events. Current conditions and annual monitoring are tracking point and non-point source inputs from SNI. Current and historic sea surface temperatures, predominant winds, and waves are archived in NOAA NWS Los Angeles/Oxnard records.¹

The nearshore waters around SNI to a depth of 300 feet (91 m) or a distance of 3 nm (5.5 km) offshore (whichever is less) are designated as an Area of Special Biological Significance (ASBS) by the SWRCB (San Nicolas Island and Begg Rock ASBS 21). The ASBS designation of SNI nearshore waters, enacted in 1974, established regulations and guidelines pertaining to water quality concerns, and focused on the beneficial uses of water resources related to surface water runoff, point source discharge, and the potential biological impacts for the water input. At the San Nicolas Island and Begg Rock ASBS, discharges incidental to military research, development, testing, and evaluation of, and training with guided missile and other weapons systems, fleet training exercises, small-scale amphibious warfare training, and special warfare training are allowed. Discharges must not result in a violation of the water quality objectives, including the protection of the marine aquatic life beneficial use, anywhere in the ASBS. Beneficial uses for water resources at SNI include consumption, navigation, water contact recreation, commercial and sport fishing, shellfish harvesting, and preservation of terrestrial and marine habitats, and rare, threatened, or endangered species (LARWQCB 1994).

The SWRCB and the RWQCB recognize that most beneficial uses of water resources are to some degree mutually antagonistic; therefore, waste discharge requirements can at best provide relative protection for all beneficial water resource uses. The concept of an ASBS recognizes that certain biological communities, because of their value or fragility, deserve very special protection consisting of preservation and maintenance of natural water conditions to the extent practicable (SWRCB and RWQCB 1970).

3.4 Terrestrial Vegetation and Flora

3.4.1 Overview

The significance of the Channel Islands natural communities stems from the islands’ remote, isolated position at the confluence of two major ocean currents, resulting in a dynamic transition zone between two biogeographical provinces in the ocean: the Oregonian and the Californian. The resulting climate produces a Mediterranean-type island system that sustains high biological endemism. SNI’s position at the southern-most intersection between the California Current and California Countercurrent (see Map 3-2), in conjunction with its isolation from the mainland, and its topography and soil types have manifested distinctive natural communities relative to adjacent islands. Finally, native vegetative communities have been greatly altered by people and the introduction of non-native species, and are in various stages of change.

The vascular flora of SNI has strong floristic affinities with nearby geographic regions including the southern California mainland and the other Channel Islands. The vascular flora of SNI includes 273 species from 172 genera, of which 140 of those species are non-native (Junak 2008). SNI has

¹The NOAA NWS Los Angeles/Oxnard records are accessible at: <http://www.wrh.noaa.gov/lox>.

limited species diversity when compared to the other California Channel Islands, presumably due to its isolation and relative lack of topographic diversity (Junak 2008). The most current Jepson Manual (2012) was used as the authority for plant nomenclature in this report.

Non-vascular plants are also important ecological components of the flora of SNI. The species diversity and ecology of non-vascular plants on the island are poorly understood. Checklists have been compiled for mosses and lichens (Appendix E), and the lichen species list was updated in 2014 (Knudsen 2014). The most important non-vascular plants in the ecology of SNI may be mycorrhizal fungi, soil algae, and blue-green algae (cyanobacteria), which help to form soil crusts, stabilize soils, and may be vital to repopulation and survival of shrubs.

3.4.2 Vegetation Communities

A survey of the SNI plant communities, for the purpose of mapping and describing them, was conducted from February to June 1992 by Halvorson et al. (1996), and revised in 2013 to meet Federal Geographic Data Committee and National Vegetation Classification Standards (HDR 2014) (Table 3-1; Map-3-4; Appendix K). The Halvorson (1996) vegetation communities were classified based on 103 surveyed relevé plots. The description resulting from this work was the first quantitative analysis of the vegetation of SNI. The vegetation classification system used by Halvorson et al. (1996) combines the work of Foreman (1967), Philbrick and Haller (1977), Halvorson et al. (1996), Junak et al. (1996), and Junak (2003). The classification is a physiognomic one (based on vegetation structure or form). The current vegetation community classification and concomitant Geographic Information System (GIS) vegetation map is based on a floristic vegetation classification according to the National Vegetation Classification Standards, and on statewide vegetation classification and mapping standards agreed upon by a state and federal government consortium of vegetation information users. Field sampling protocols for Vegetation Rapid Assessment and Relevé plots used at SNI correspond with the vegetation mapping protocols used by Channel Islands National Park. A total of 17 vegetation categories were identified on SNI. Of these, 16 vegetation categories were mapped on the installation using a 0.25 acre (0.10 ha) minimum mapping unit for a total of 14,225.26 acres (5,600.51 ha) mapped.

The flora of SNI, its relation to other islands and the mainland, its disturbance history, and patterns of endemism were analyzed most recently by Junak (2008).

Table 3-1. Acreage and percent cover of Association-level vegetation communities on San Nicolas Island.

Association-level Vegetation Communities	Acres	Percent of Total Land Area
<i>Salix lasiolepis</i> Association	1.02	>0.01
<i>Baccharis pilularis</i> /Annual Grass-Herb Association	44.68	0.31
<i>Artemisia californica</i> Association	0.43	>0.010
<i>Opuntia littoralis</i> Alliance	7.76	0.05
<i>Leptosyne gigantea</i> Association	2403.43	16.90
<i>Lupinus albifrons</i> Coastal Association	208.62	1.47
<i>Isocoma menziesii</i> Association	281.46	1.98
<i>Isocoma menziesii</i> / <i>Lupinus albifrons</i> - <i>Astragalus traskiae</i> Association	8341.79	58.64
<i>Ambrosia chamissonis</i> - <i>Abronia maritima</i> - <i>Cakile maritima</i> Association	139.25	0.98
<i>Cakile maritima</i> - <i>Ambrosia chamissonis</i> - <i>Carpobrotus edulis</i> Association	36.83	0.26
<i>Frankenia salina</i> Association	4.91	0.03
<i>Frankenia salina</i> / <i>Distichlis spicata</i> Association	0.70	>0.01
<i>Distichlis spicata</i> Association	2.53	0.02
<i>Deinandra clementina</i> – <i>Eriogonum giganteum</i> Provisional Association	152.90	1.07
<i>Carpobrotus edulis</i> or other Iceplants Semi-Natural Stands	104.96	0.74
<i>Ammophila arenaria</i> Stand Type	6.18	0.04
Mediterranean California Naturalized Annual and Perennial Grassland	1355.08	9.53
Open Water	21.09	0.15
Developed	263.93	1.86
Sand dune	242.44	1.70
Beach	168.13	1.18
Barren	268.78	1.89
Ornamental vegetation	14.20	0.10
Eroded cliffs and hillsides	154.15	1.08
Total	14,225.26	100.00

Source: HDR 2014.

Notes: * Vegetation classification percentages were rounded to the one-hundredth decimal; for the small sample areas the results were not reflected in the total percent sampled.

The vegetation community descriptions below are according to alliance, which is one hierarchical level above the associations listed in Table 3-1. The below descriptions are from the “Vegetation Classification and Mapping for Naval Base Ventura County San Nicolas Island” report (Appendix I) (HDR 2014).

Coastal Scrub

Artemisia californica Alliance

California sagebrush (*Artemisia californica*) is the most common and widespread species of southern California coastal sage scrub. California sagebrush is found on all of the Channel Islands, while the closely related island sagebrush (*A. nesiotica*) is found on three of the islands: San Nicolas, Santa Barbara and San Clemente. Both species grow up to 6.5 feet (2 m). This alliance occurs on gentle to steep slopes of variable aspects, at low elevations. One association of this community was mapped on SNI. Island sagebrush is included within this classification because of the close relations between the two *Artemisia* species. The *Artemisia californica* Association occurs on SNI with island sagebrush as the sole dominant species. Other species found in this community include common yarrow (*Achillea millefolium*), Australian saltbush

(*Atriplex semibaccata*), ripgut brome (*Bromus diandrus*), and blue dicks (*Dichelostemma capitatum*). A total of 0.43 acre (0.17 ha) of this association was mapped on SNI and one plot was sampled (Photo 3-1). Several other occurrences of individuals of island sagebrush were found associated with stands of *Opuntia littoralis* Alliance (HDR 2014).

Photo 3-1. *Artemisia californica* Alliance on San Nicolas Island (HDR 2014).

Opuntia littoralis Alliance

The *Opuntia littoralis* Alliance occurs along the coast of southern California. Coast prickly pear (*Opuntia littoralis*) and other cacti occur with other shrubs to form a canopy that is generally <6.5 feet (2 m). Some taller shrubs may be present in sparse cover. The canopy is intermittent or continuous in two tiers; the herbaceous layer is open to continuous (Sawyer et al. 2009). On SNI, *Opuntia littoralis*, *O. oricola* or *Cylindropuntia prolifera* was found in scattered patches primarily on the northern coastal plain, with scattered populations on the north and south escarpments. Most patches consisted of a small number of individual plants while others consisted of populations of more than 50 individuals. The absence of other diagnostic species did not allow for classification of these plots to the association level. Other species within surveyed plots include island sagebrush, common yarrow, Australian saltbush, ripgut brome, blue dicks, yellow sweetclover (*Melilotus officinalis*), red brome (*Bromus madritensis* subsp. *rubens*), island false bindweed (*Calystegia macrostegia* subsp. *amplissima*), Catalina tarweed (*Deinandra clementina*), Menzies' goldenbush (*Isocoma menziesii*), silver bird's-foot trefoil (*Acemispom argophyllum* var. *argenteus*), burclover (*Medicago polymorpha*), common iceplant (*Mesembryanthemum crystallinum*), and slenderleaf iceplant (*Mesembryanthemum nodiflorum*). On SNI, 7.76 acres (3.14 ha) of this community were mapped, and one plot was sampled (HDR 2014) (Photo 3-2).

Photo 3-2. *Opuntia littoralis* Alliance on San Nicolas Island (HDR 2014).

Isocoma menziesii Alliance

Isocoma menziesii Alliance has a discontinuous distribution along the southern California coast. Menzies' goldenbush mixes with other perennial shrubs to form an open to intermittent canopy. The canopy is low, 3.2 feet (<1.0 m), with an open to continuous herbaceous layer (Sawyer et al. 2009). This species is common throughout all areas of SNI. Three associations within this alliance were mapped on SNI: *Isocoma menziesii* Association, *Isocoma menziesii* – *Lupinus albifrons*/*Astragalus traskiae* Provisional Association (non-sparse and sparse). Other species within *Isocoma menziesii* Association surveyed plots include common yarrow, Australian saltbush, red brome, freeway iceplant (*Carpobrotus edulis*), giant coreopsis (*Leptosyne gigantea*), silver bird's-foot trefoil, and common iceplant. On SNI, a total of 281.46 acres (113.90 ha) were mapped and 17 plots were sampled in this community (Photo 3-3).

Photo 3-3. *Isocoma menziesii* Association on San Nicolas Island (HDR 2014).

The *Isocoma menziesii* – *Lupinus albifrons*/*Astragalus traskiae* Provisional Association (non-sparse and sparse) was created based on the strong association of the three species. A similar community, *Isocoma menziesii* – *Lupinus albifrons* Association, has been described on the mainland and could have been applied here, had Trask's milkvetch (*Astragalus traskiae*) not been so abundant and widespread in this community. *Isocoma menziesii* is the dominant species in

this community, with one or both of silver lupine (*Lupinus albifrons*) or Trask's milkvetch subdominant. On SNI, this provisional association is found primarily on the southern escarpment and southwestern ridge. In this area, all species were of very low density with patches of higher density located primarily on ridges and valley floors. Other species within surveyed plots include giant coreopsis, common yarrow, silver bird's-foot trefoil, and red brome. On SNI, this association was the single most extensive association mapped. A total of 8341.79 acres (3375.81 ha) of this community were mapped, with 2364.78 acres (956.99 ha) denoted as sparse; 59 plots were sampled (Photo 3-4) (HDR 2014).

Photo 3-4. *Isocoma menziesii*-*Lupinus albifrons*/*Astragalus traskiae* Provisional Association on San Nicolas Island (HDR 2014).

Leptosyne gigantea Alliance

The *Leptosyne gigantea* Alliance occurs along the coast of southern California, and on the Channel Islands, on bluffs and stabilized dunes. Giant coreopsis commonly occurs with coastal sage scrub species. Different height classes of shrubs may be present, and the canopy can be open to intermittent and two-tiered with an herbaceous layer that is open to intermittent (Sawyer et al. 2009). *Leptosyne gigantea* Association is dominant on the north and northwestern coastal planes as well as in vegetated areas of the northern escarpment, and is becoming common on the northern portion of the mesa and in pockets throughout the remainder of the island. Other species within surveyed plots include common yarrow, ripgut brome, red brome, blue dicks (*Dichelostemma capitatum*), Menzies' goldenbush, silver bird's-foot trefoil, and silver lupine. In several areas on the north escarpment, surveyors noted dense populations of bright green dudleya (*Dudleya virens* subsp. *insularis*); further sampling of these areas should be conducted to investigate the possibility of a provisional association of *L. gigantean* and *D. virens* subsp. *insularis*. On SNI, 2403.43 acres (972.63 ha) of this community were mapped and 23 plots were sampled (Photo 3-5) (HDR 2014).

Photo 3-5. *Leptosyne gigantea* Association on San Nicolas Island (HDR 2014).

Lycium californicum Alliance

The *Lycium californicum* Alliance occurs on coastal bluffs of southern California. California desert thorn (*Lycium californicum*) occurs with other perennial shrubs in a canopy of 13.1 feet (<4.0 m). The canopy is open to intermittent, generally with a continuous herbaceous layer (Sawyer et al. 2009). One association within this alliance was mapped on SNI. Other species within surveyed plots of *Lycium californicum* Association include common yarrow, ripgut brome, SNI buckwheat, Menzies' goldenbush, San Nicolas biscuitroot (*Lomatium insulare*), silver bird's-foot trefoil, and common iceplant (Photo 3-6). Two plots within this community were sampled but not mapped as stand sizes were too small (HDR 2014).

Photo 3-6. *Lycium californicum* Association on San Nicolas Island (HDR 2014).

Lupinus albifrons Alliance

The *Lupinus albifrons* Alliance occurs along the coast and in alluvial fans throughout California. Silver lupine occurs with other small shrubs and sub-shrubs. The canopy is 6.5 feet (<2.0 m) and open. The herbaceous layer is open to intermittent and includes seasonal annuals (Sawyer et al. 2009). One association within this alliance was mapped on SNI. *Lupinus albifrons* Coastal Association is found in scattered, medium-sized patches along the western portion of the island, primarily in sandy soils (Photo 3-7). Other species within surveyed plots include red sand verbena, silver bur ragweed, freeway iceplant, giant coreopsis, Menzies' goldenbush, and

dunedelion (*Malacothrix incana*). On SNI, 208.62 acres (84.43 ha) of this community were mapped and eight plots were sampled (HDR 2014).

Photo 3-7. *Lupinus albifrons* Coastal Association on San Nicolas Island (HDR 2014).

Baccharis pilularis Alliance

The *Baccharis pilularis* Alliance occurs on the coast of California along rivers, streams, stabilized dunes, bluffs, open slopes, and ridges. Coyote brush (*Baccharis pilularis*) occurs with other perennial shrubs. It forms a variably structured canopy that is 9.8 feet (<3.0 m). The herbaceous layer is also variable (Sawyer et al. 2009). One association within this alliance was mapped on SNI (Photo 3-8). The *Baccharis pilularis*/Annual Grass-Herb Association is common in shallow drainages throughout the central mesa, and in drainages on the northern coastal plain. Other species within surveyed plots include common yarrow, Australian saltbush, slender oat, ripgut brome, red brome, giant coreopsis, blue dicks, and Menzies' goldenbush. On SNI, 44.68 acres (18.08 ha) were mapped and eight plots were sampled (HDR 2014).

Photo 3-8. *Baccharis pilularis*/Annual Grass-Herb Association on San Nicolas Island (HDR 2014).

Deinandra clementina – *Eriogonum giganteum* Provisional Alliance

Island tar plant is found on Anacapa Island and the southern Channel Islands. On San Clemente Island, this species forms a provisional association with Island buckwheat (*Eriogonum giganteum*) (Sawyer et al. 2008). On SNI, this species is found scattered throughout several communities but is concentrated on the east portion of the mesa, south of the airfield, where it is strongly dominant over all other species. The *Deinandra clementina* – *Eriogonum giganteum* Provisional Association is dominant at a portion of the eastern mesa, southeast of the airfield (Photo 3-9). Other species within surveyed plots include Menzies' fiddleneck (*Amsinckia menziesii*), Australian saltbush, ripgut brome, red brome, sand pygmyweed (*Crassula connata*), blue dicks, goldentop grass (*Lamarckia aurea*), California goldfields (*Lasthenia californica*), and Russian thistle (*Salsola australis*). On SNI, this community includes 152.90 acres (61.88 ha) where two plots were sampled (HDR 2014).

Photo 3-9. *Deinandra clementina*-*Eriogonum giganteum* Provisional Association on San Nicolas Island (HDR 2014).

Vernal Pools

Several vernal pools totaling 0.8 acre occur on the western and northeastern portions of the mesa (Halvorson et al. 1996). None of the individual pools met the minimum mapping unit of 0.25 acre to be mapped, but they were recorded when encountered (HDR 2014). Vernal pools are landforms that are typically inundated during and after winter rains, and that support unique flora and fauna that have adapted to ephemeral aquatic conditions. These communities flourish in the late winter into the spring, and become dry and dormant during summer months. The dominant species that occurs on the margin of the vernal pools on the central mesa is pale spikerush (*Eleocharis macrostachya*) (Halvorson et al. 1996; Junak 2008). Associates include toad rush (*Juncus bufonius*), sickle grass (*Parapholis incurva*), and Persian knotweed (*Polygonum argyrocoleon*) at some locations (Junak 2008; HDR 2014).

Riparian Vegetation

Riparian communities are mostly isolated on the southern side of the island, in deep drainages within the island's canyon bottoms, associated with intermittent streams, or in low spots on the mesa top where moisture accumulates (DoN 2005; Junak 2008). This habitat has been highly modified by erosion and human activity over the years (Halvorson et al. 1996).

Salix lasiolepis Alliance

Salix lasiolepis Alliance occurs along stream banks, seeps, and drainages throughout California. Arroyo willow (*Salix lasiolepis*) occurs with other shrubs and trees. It ranges greatly in height and can be up to 32.8 feet (10.0 m). As a shrubland community, taller trees may emerge from the

canopy which is open to continuous. The herbaceous layer is variable (Sawyer et al. 2009). One association within this alliance was mapped on SNI. The *Salix lasiolepis* Association is only found in two locations on SNI: Army Springs and Humphrey's Sump. Other species within the surveyed plots include giant reed (*Arundo donax*), island false bindweed, saltgrass (*Distichlis spicata*), three-square (*Schoenoplectus americanus*), and common sowthistle (*Sonchus oleraceus*). On SNI, 1.02 acres (0.41 ha) of this community was mapped and one plot was sampled.

Other plants now found in canyon bottoms and other moist areas include cattails (*Typha* spp.), brass-buttons (*Cotula coronopifolia*), rabbitsfoot grass (*Polypogon monspeliensis*), saltgrass, spear-leaf saltbush (*Atriplex prostrata*), tall fescue (*Festuca arundinacea*), willow dock (*Rumex salicifolius* var. *salicifolius*), curly dock (*Rumex crispus* subsp. *crispus*), mulefat (*Baccharis salicifolia*), myoporum (*Myoporum laetum*), horehound (*Marrubium vulgare*), celery (*Apium graveolens*), and common loosestrife (*Lythrum hyssopifolia*) (Junak 2008; HDR 2014).

Grasslands

The grassland community is a mixture of native and non-native species covering 1355.08 acres (703 ha) (HDR 2014). Large areas on the mesa are dominated by non-native grasses, especially slender wild oats, bromes, and foxtail (*Hordeum murinum*) (Junak 2008). While non-native grasses account for the majority of the grasslands on SNI, there are some small patches with greater proportions of native grasses, primarily needlegrass (*Stipa pulchra* and *S. cernua*). Native annual vernal barley (*Hordeum intercedens*) can be very common in wet years and can dominate small areas (Junak 2008). Small populations of native annuals occur in scattered areas, especially in grassy openings between shrubs on the northeastern coastal flats and in the northeastern portion of the central mesa.

Mediterranean California Naturalized Annual and Perennial Grassland

This description is based on the group level, which is one hierarchical level above alliance. The group level is a useful classification where distinction cannot be made to the alliance or association level. With the exception of *Ammophila arenaria* Semi-Natural Herbaceous Stands, which were found to be strongly dominant over all other species in each stand, several Semi-Natural Stand types were lumped into this category due of the heterogeneity of species in the grasslands, and difficulty distinguishing between types during photographic delineation. The dominant non-native grasses found in this community include ripgut brome, slender oat, and red brome. Other species found in this community include Menzies' goldenbush, common yarrow, Australian saltbush, coyote brush, island false bindweed, and giant coreopsis. On SNI, 19 plots were sampled within this community and 1355.08 acres (548.38 ha) were mapped (Photo 3-10) (HDR 2014).

Photo 3-10. Mediterranean California Naturalized Annual and Perennial Grassland on San Nicolas Island (HDR 2014).

Coastal Marsh

Coastal salt marsh occurs in a very small area on flats near the base of the sandspit at the southeastern end of SNI (Junak 2008). Two alliances were mapped in coastal salt marsh and are described below.

Frankenia salina Alliance

The *Frankenia salina* Alliance occurs in coastal salt marshes, brackish marshes, alkali meadows and alkali playas. Alkali heath (*Frankenia salina*) is dominant or co-dominant in the herbaceous and subshrub layer. The cover is open to continuous with a low canopy cover of 23.6 inches (<60.0 cm) (Sawyer et al. 2009). Two associations in this alliance were mapped on SNI: *Frankenia salina* Association (Photo 3-11) and *Frankenia salina*/*Distichlis spicata* Association (Photo 3-12). For areas mapped as *Frankenia salina* Association, other species within the surveyed plots include Australian saltbush, rippgut brome, San Nicolas Island buckwheat, Menzies' goldenbush, and woolly seablite (*Suaeda taxifolia*). One plot was sampled in this community and 4.91 acres (2.00 ha) were mapped (HDR 2014).

Photo 3-11. *Frankenia salina* Association on San Nicolas Island (HDR 2014).

For areas mapped as *Frankenia salina*/*Distichlis spicata* Association, in addition to alkali heath and saltgrass, other species within the surveyed plots include California saltbush (*Atriplex californica*), Australian saltbush riggut brome, and woolly seablite. Two plots near the desalination plant were sampled in this community and 0.70 acre (0.28 ha) was mapped (HDR 2014).

Photo 3-12. *Frankenia salina*/*Distichlis spicata* Association on San Nicolas Island (HDR 2014).

Distichlis spicata Alliance

The *Distichlis spicata* Alliance occurs in coastal salt marshes and inland habitats including playas, swales, and terraces along washes that are typically intermittently flooded. Saltgrass is dominant or co-dominant in the herbaceous layer with a relative cover of greater than 30-50 percent (Sawyer et al. 2009). One association in this alliance was mapped on SNI. *Distichlis spicata* Association includes other species such as Watson's saltbush (*A. watsonii*), Menzies' goldenbush, slenderleaf iceplant, and alkali heath. One plot was sampled in this community at Rock Crusher Beach, and 2.53 acres (1.02 ha) were mapped (HDR 2014).

Beach and Dune

Sandy beaches and dunes encompass a majority of the coastline around SNI. The beaches are largely unvegetated; the dune areas can be divided into two types, unstabilized coastal dunes and stabilized inland dunes.

Unstabilized dunes (Photo 3-5) total approximately 138 acres (56 ha) (Junak 2008). Plant communities on unstabilized dunes are diverse and scattered, with no species dominating large areas (Halvorson et al. 1996). Sticky sand verbena (*Abronia maritima*) occurs near the water and is the most abundant plant species. Dunedelion, silver lupine, beach sand-verbena (*Abronia umbellata*), silver beach-weed, iceplant, island morning glory, beach primrose, and silver bird's-foot trefoil also occur on the coastal dunes (DoN 2005).

Stabilized dunes account for approximately 783 acres (317 ha) (Junak 2008). Hottentot fig (*Carpobrotus* spp.) and Trask's milkvetch are common, especially on the west end of the island where some areas are dominated by large stands of milkvetch, which is endemic to SNI and Santa Barbara Island (Junak 2008). Other widespread species in the stabilized dune areas include sand verbena, silver beach-weed, brome, sea rocket (*Cakile maritima*), beach primrose, filaree, silver bird's-foot trefoil, silver lupine, and dunedelion (Junak 2008).

Abronia maritima — *Abronia chamissonis* Alliance

The *Abronia maritima* – *Abronia chamissonis* Alliance occurs along sand dunes of coastal bars, river mouths and spits along the immediate coastline. This dune mat consists of the dominant plants along with other perennial herbs, grasses and low shrubs to form a low, sparse to continuous canopy. Emergent shrubs may be present at low cover. The herbaceous layer is <19 inches (<50 cm) (Sawyer et al. 2009). Two associations within this alliance have been mapped on SNI and include *Ambrosia chamissonis*-*Abronia maritima*-*Cakile maritima* Association (Photo 3-13), and *Cakile maritima*-*Ambrosia chamissonis*-*Carpobrotus edulis* Association (HDR 2014).

Photo 3-13. *Ambrosia chamissonis*-*Abronia maritima*-*Cakile maritima* Association on San Nicolas Island (HDR 2014).

Non-native Vegetation

Ammophila arenaria Semi-Natural Herbaceous Stands

These stands are found on dunes, river mouths and spits along the immediate coastline throughout California. European beach grass (*Ammophila arenaria*) is a highly invasive perennial grass; in this alliance it is dominant in the herbaceous layer and occasionally co-occurring with shrubs. The 3.2 feet (<1.0 meter) canopy is intermittent to continuous (Sawyer et al. 2009). One association (Type) within this alliance (Stand) was mapped on SNI. *Ammophila arenaria* Stand Type (Photo 3-14) can be found along Shannon Road on the northwestern portion of the mesa, where it occurs in several monotypic or nearly-monotypic stands adjacent to the road. A total of 6.18 acres (2.50 ha) were mapped on SNI and within that acreage, no plots were sampled. Several small occurrences of this community were not mapped because they did not meet the Minimum Mapping Unit (on the road to Red Eye, also known as Breakers; on the south side of SNI near Army Spring; along Jackson Highway near Rock Crusher; and near Humphrey Sump) (HDR 2014).

Photo 3-14. *Ammophila arenaria* Stand Type on San Nicolas Island (HDR 2014).

Carpobrotus edulis or other Iceplants Semi-Natural Stands

In this Semi-Natural Stand, invasive iceplant, *Carpobrotus chilensis* or other iceplant species are dominant in the herbaceous layer. Iceplant mats are found on bluffs, disturbed land, sand dunes and coastal and alkaline terraces. Iceplant is highly invasive and at least eight different species are found in California. The canopy is intermittent to continuous with a height of 19.7 inches (<50 cm), with emergent shrubs present at low cover (Sawyer et al. 2009). Common iceplant and freeway iceplant were the dominant iceplants found in this community. Other species within the plots sampled on SNI include silver bur ragweed, Australian saltbush, European sea rocket, Menzies' goldenbush, and silver lupine. In 2013, 104.96 acres (42.48 ha) were mapped and 8 plots were sampled in this community (Photo 3-15) (HDR 2014).

Photo 3-15. *Carpobrotus edulis* or other Iceplants Semi-Natural Stands on San Nicolas Island (HDR 2014).

Ornamental Vegetation

This category includes areas that have been physically disturbed and support primarily non-native, ornamental trees, shrubs, and grasses. On SNI, this may include maintained grass lawns around structures, plantings of *Eucalyptus*, myoporum (*Myoporum laetum*), and non-native palm and pine trees. A total of 14.20 acres (5.75 ha) were mapped as ornamental vegetation on SNI (HDR 2014).

Non-Vegetated Communities

Developed

This category includes areas that have been physically altered to the extent of no longer supporting native vegetation. This can include buildings, paved and regularly maintained dirt roads, airfields, and parking lots. A total of 263.93 acres (106.81 ha) were mapped on SNI and within that acreage, zero plots were sampled (HDR 2014).

Sand Dune

These areas typically lack vegetation or have sparse vegetative cover. A total of 242.44 acres (98.11 ha) were mapped on SNI and within that acreage, zero plots were sampled due to the lack of vegetation cover (HDR 2014).

Beach

Beach areas are composed of nearly flat sandy shores exposed and subjected to tidal inundation and wave action. These areas typically lack vegetation. Beach stands are important pupping grounds for marine mammals and critical nesting habitat for state and federally listed threatened Pacific Coast western snowy plovers (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*) (hereafter referred to as western snowy plover). A total of 168.13 acres (68.04 ha) were mapped on SNI and within that acreage, zero plots were sampled due to the lack of vegetation cover (HDR 2014).

Barren

These areas typically lack or consist of less than 1 percent vegetation cover. A total of 268.78 acres (108.77 ha) were mapped on SNI and within that acreage, zero plots were sampled due to the lack of vegetation cover (HDR 2014).

Eroded Cliffs and Hillsides

This classification includes various steep cliff and hillside areas with no vegetation. These were primarily found on the southern escarpment, with a total area of 154.15 acres (62.38 ha). Although barren of most vascular flora, many of the southern escarpment eroded hillsides host microbiotic crusts composed of cyanobacteria, lichens and bryophytes. Microbiotic crusts protect soils from erosion and contribute to soil development (HDR 2014).

3.4.3 Vascular Flora

Approximately 273 vascular plant species have been documented on SNI (Junak 2008). Floristic relationships among the California Channel Islands have been examined and discussed by several notable botanists (see Raven 1967; Wallace 1985; Moody 2000; Oberbauer 2002). SNI shares 86 percent of its native plants with the southern California mainland, 85 percent with the four northern Channel Islands, 84 percent with the other three southern Channel Islands, and 53 percent with islands off the Pacific coast of Baja California (Junak et al. 1996). Compared to the other seven Channel Islands, SNI has a relatively limited richness of native plant species and also has the highest percentage (51 percent) of introduced plant species. At least 141 taxa are considered to be introduced to SNI and most are native to the California mainland that were either intentionally or unintentionally introduced to SNI during the last 100 years. At least ten non-native plant taxa which have become naturalized on SNI have not yet been reported on the other California Channel Islands (Junak 2008; see Appendix E).

Endemics

Approximately 11 percent of SNI's native vascular plant taxa are endemic to the Channel Islands, ranking it in the middle amongst other Channel Islands (Junak 2008). Two vascular plant taxa found only on SNI are the San Nicolas Island buckwheat (*Eriogonum grande* var. *timorum*) and the San Nicolas Island malacothrix (*Malacothrix foliosa* ssp. *polycephala*). SNI has no federally listed endangered or threatened plant species. Special status plants on SNI include one state endangered, one state threatened, one state rare, and five considered sensitive by the California Native Plant Society (CNPS) (Appendix E).

3.4.4 Non-Vascular Flora

The species diversity and ecology of non-vascular plants on SNI are poorly understood; however, checklists have been compiled for mosses and lichens (Appendix E). Microbiotic soil crusts (also called cryptobiotic or cryptogamic crusts) are arid land soil crusts consolidated by a combination of cyanobacteria, eukaryotic algae, fungi, lichens, and bryophytes. A growing body of data suggests that microbiotic crusts play several important ecological roles in arid and semiarid ecosystems. The most obvious and likely the most important role is stabilization of soil surfaces, which effectively controls and reduces erosion (Johansen et al. 1998). Microbiotic crusts are well represented throughout the Channel Islands and are often defined as a group of flowerless and seedless plants that reproduce by means of spores and include ferns, mosses, algae and fungi. Lichens are a fungus, usually of the class Ascomycetes, which grows symbiotically with algae, resulting in a composite organism that characteristically forms a crust-like or branching growth on rocks or woody surfaces. Liverworts are bryophytes of the phylum *Hepatophyta*, growing in wet places and resembling green seaweeds or leafy mosses. In many arid and semiarid areas of the world, soil surfaces are consolidated by complex communities consisting of microorganisms, lichens, and bryophytes. The physical structure of microbiotic crusts varies depending on climate, soil type, and the composition of the biological community. Biological soil crusts are known to have a variety of physical forms. Some crusts are flattened, polygonally cracked, and have a rough, undulating surface, while others are pedicellate and demonstrate a complex vertical microtopography. All soil crust communities contain some combination of cyanobacteria, bacteria, eukaryotic algae, and non-lichenized fungi. More structurally complex soil crusts contain some combination of lichens and bryophytes. The historic diversity and abundance of SNI microbiotic crusts is not well documented and has likely been reduced to some extent, from human occupation and grazing.

Lichens are the most conspicuous forms of non-vascular plants on the island, covering large rocky barren areas on the northeast slopes. Mosses and liverworts are found infrequently around seeps and springs, and in shady microhabitats. Borlander's moss (*Entosthodon bolanderi*) and California hard-stalk moss (*Scleropodium californicum*) represent the endemic Channel Island bryophytes present on the island, and three species of lichens *Niebla ramosissima*, *N. dactylifera*, and *Lecania chalcophila* are found only on SNI.

3.4.5 Jurisdictional Waters

The USACE delineated wetlands at SNI in August 2011. This delineation included the survey of intermittent stream channels that discharge to the ocean, seeps, and a lagoon. The 2011 wetland delineation identified a total of 2.48 acres (1.0 ha) of jurisdictional wetlands on SNI, including riparian and coastal marsh habitats. The wetlands delineated by the USACE are identified in Map 3-5. In addition to the jurisdictional wetlands on the island, there are dry erosional channels that may be considered nexus to Waters of the United States. Determination of channel jurisdiction will be made on a case-by-case basis. The main criteria for channels to be considered jurisdictional is the conveyance of water directly into a jurisdictional wetland or the ocean. Many of the erosional channels found on the upper mesa are relics from a more erosional period and show no signs of conveying water on a regular basis (waterline, debris along bank, a change in

vegetation inside the channel compared to the surrounding area). These channels are considered “paleo-channels” and are not jurisdictional.

3.4.6 Long-Term Monitoring of Plant Communities

In 1993, the Navy contracted CINP to establish 36 vegetation sampling plots to evaluate long-term plant community trends and contribute to the ongoing monitoring program taking place throughout the Channel Islands (see Map 3-4). The methods established for this program were consistent with those utilized on the other islands of CINP to enable the modeling of vegetation change throughout the Channel Islands. The goal of the project was to monitor the distinct assemblages of plant species and vegetation communities that developed on the island as a result of isolation from the mainland and other islands (Halvorson et al. 1996). The objective of this project is to enable the Navy to make proper management decisions pertaining to the recovery of island plant communities (from NAVFAC SW Scope of Work for 2009 monitoring). SNI vegetation is in various stages of recovery from grazing, farming, military use, and introduction of invasive plant species. The monitoring program documents natural vegetation recovery by gathering and

analyzing data on botanical composition, vegetation cover, and ground cover from the long-term sampling transects. The revised long-term monitoring methods were reviewed and reported in the 2009 vegetation monitoring report (Tierra Data Inc. [TDI] 2009).

Summary of 2009 Monitoring

Thirty-six of the 37 plots were resampled in 2009. Total vegetation cover in 2009 on all plots averaged approximately 64.2 percent, compared to over 80 percent in all previous samplings (TDI 2009). This was likely a result of the drought conditions that have prevailed on the island in years prior to the 2009 surveys. This same trend held true for most vegetation communities, with lower average cover in 2009 than in previous years, but there were exceptions. On the grassland plots, vegetative cover in 2009 was lower than in 1995 and 1996, but was similar to 1993 and 1994. On stabilized dunes, vegetative cover in 2009 was somewhat higher than 1995-1996 and lower than 1993-1994. The greatest decline in vegetative cover was seen in the *Isocoma/Baccharis* scrub (68 to 97 percent cover in 1993–1998, only 33 percent cover in 2009) and lupine scrub plots (92 to 95 percent cover in 1993–1998, only 58 percent cover in 2009).

The percent cover of native and non-native plant species varies widely from one vegetation type to another (TDI 2009). Grassland plots have the highest overall non-native cover (67.4 percent) and lowest native/non-native ratio of 0.35. Lupine scrub plots also had a very low native/non-native ratio of 0.52. Giant coreopsis scrub plots have the next highest percent cover of exotics, but a much higher native/non-native ratio of 0.85, with highest percent cover of natives. Most other vegetation types had nearly equal cover of natives and non-natives.

Over the long term, the percent cover of annual forbs has fluctuated greatly from year-to-year, while annual grasses increased over the first two years of the study before leveling off at around 60 percent between 1995 and 1998, followed by a sharp decline in 2009 (TDI 2009). In addition, average shrub cover remained around 25 to 35 percent since 1993. The fluctuations in annual forb cover tend to closely follow annual rainfall patterns, as might be expected (TDI 2009).

3.5 Coastal and Marine Communities

The Channel Islands, including SNI, lie within the greater context of the SCB. The SCB is a 100,000-square-mile body of water and submerged continental shelf that extends from Point Conception, California, in the north, to Cabo Colnett, Baja California, Mexico, in the south (Noblet et al. 2003). The SCB is subject to short-term and long-term temperature fluctuation, depending upon the strength or weakness of the ocean current systems (Dailey et al. 1993). The complex interactions related to the physical topography, current systems, and biological contributors manifested over eons has defined the richness and diversity of marine life in the SCB. Considering the SCB's isolated position at the confluence of two major ocean currents, marine communities garner significant contributions from these two distinct biomes. SNI is situated along the outer (western) edge of the SCB, and is primarily influenced by the cold productive waters of the California Current. Marine habitats and communities associated with SNI represent a wide variety of assemblages including similarities in terms of fish and algal diversity to northern regions like San Miguel Island and the central coast of California. The dominant invertebrate species resemble those prominent at neighboring Santa Barbara Island and San Clemente Island. The complex oceanographic conditions and circulation patterns associated with SNI contribute greatly to its species diversity and richness.

Overlaid on this range of habitats are temporal and spatial fluctuations in primary production that depend on nutrient supply from coastal runoff, seasonal upwelling, and long periods of sunshine. The waters surrounding SNI consist of a depth gradient of marine habitats from coastal intertidal to deep benthic communities. The marine habitat and depth categories presented in this INRMP are based on the classification system utilized by the CDFW Marine Life

Protection Act Initiative (CDFW 2009), developed to help the state of California implement the Marine Life Protection Act. Marine habitats in the nearshore waters surrounding SNI include: intertidal, subtidal, deep water, and offshore rocks and islets. Marine habitat depth and substrate categories at SNI are listed in Table 3-2 and illustrated in Map 3-6. Table 3-2 shows marine habitat substrate categories according to the Coastal and Marine Ecological Classification Standard to “provide a language through which data regarding habitats can be communicated and managed” (McDougall et al. 2007).

Table 3-2. Marine habitat depth and substrate categories at San Nicolas Island.

Habitat and Substrate Categories		Depth in meters (m)
Intertidal	Sandy beaches	Intertidal
	Rocky shores and surfgrass	Intertidal
Subtidal	Soft bottom habitat	Intertidal to 30
	Eelgrass	Intertidal to 30
	Rocky habitat and kelp forests	Intertidal to 30
Deep Water	Rocky habitat	30 to 100
		100 to 200
		>200
	Soft bottom habitat	30 to 100
		100 to 200
		>200
Offshore Rocks and Islets	Sea stacks and offshore rocks	30 to 100

3.5.1 Intertidal Habitats

Coastal Strand

Coastal strands or sandy beaches, dominate significant portions of SNI shorelines similar to Santa Rosa Island and the mainland. In contrast, only 20 percent of the shoreline of the other California Channel Islands are sandy beach (Richards 2004). Macrophyte debris, primarily algal wrack, serves as a major source of energy for the beach communities. High depositional beaches, such as Redeye Beach and Tender Beach on SNI, face northwest into the prevailing winds and swell. Consequently, they receive large quantities of marine debris, carcasses, and macrophyte wrack, primarily giant kelp (*Macrocystis pyrifera*) (D. Lerma, *personal observation [pers. obs.]*, 2009).

Key invertebrate fauna on sandy beaches are sand crabs (*Emerita analoga* and *Blepharipoda occidentalis*), bloodworms (*Euzonus mucronata*), isopods (*Exciorolana chiltoni*), beach hopper amphipods (*Megalorchestia* spp. [*Orchestoidea* spp.]), purple olive snails (*Olivella biplicata*), and Pismo clams (*Tivella stultorum*) (Morris et al. 1980). Surveys performed at SNI in support of an ASBS evaluation sampled several intertidal and subtidal areas where sandy subtidal habitat was the dominant substrate, along the southeastern portion of SNI including Coast Guard Beach, Sand Spit, and Daytona Beach (Merkel and Associates, Inc. 2007a). A qualitative survey of the area in the vicinity of the pier at Daytona Beach documented sand dollars (*Dendraster excentricus*) and purple olive snails as well as some common polychaete worms (e.g. *Diopatra* spp.). Common organisms typically present on coastal beaches were also reported, including beach hoppers and

bloodworms. Kelp flies (Coelopidae), isopods, and beach hoppers occurred in association with kelp wrack. Noticeably absent were sand crabs, although sand crabs were observed at Daytona Beach during past surveys (L. Honma, *pers. obs.*).

Depositional beaches, exposed to prevailing winds and waves, tend to be the most productive beaches as a result of kelp wrack input. Studies conducted at sandy beaches within the northern Channel Islands reported a direct relationship between amphipod abundance and macrophyte wrack cover (Lerma and Richards 2000; Dugan et al. 2000; Richards 2004). Infaunal invertebrates contribute to the overall productivity of beaches on multiple trophic levels.

Sandy beaches provide foraging and resting habitat for a number of shorebirds including western snowy plover, black-bellied plover (*Pluvialis squatarola*), willet (*Tringa semipalmata*), whimbrel (*Numenius phaeopus*), long-billed curlew (*Numenius americanus*), gulls (Family Laridae), and sanderlings (*Calidris alba*). Invertebrates in wrack on the upper beaches attract black and ruddy turnstones (*Arenaria melanocephala* and *A. interpres*), dowitchers (*Limnodromus* spp.), and other shorebirds. Other birds observed at the sandy beaches are black oystercatchers (*Haematopus bachmani*), killdeer (*Charadrius vociferus*), song sparrows (*Melospiza melodia*), western gulls (*Larus occidentalis*), and western sandpipers (*Calidris mauri*). Western snowy plovers nest on several SNI beaches; access to these areas is restricted during the nesting season. Pinnipeds haul out and breed on the majority of beaches.

Rocky Shores and Surfgrass

The intertidal zone is the strip of shore ranging from the uppermost surfaces wetted during high tides to the lowermost areas exposed to air during low tides. The vertical extent of tidal range on SNI can be as high as 10 feet (3 m; +7.9 to -2.0 feet [+2.4 to -0.6 m]) during full or new moon periods. On surf-swept rocky cliffs, the wave splash can extend the marine influence upward another 16 feet (5 m) or more. Low slope rocky benches can result in intertidal regions tens-of-m wide. Bottom substrate within SNI intertidal consists of sand, gravel, cobble, boulders, and bedrock.

The intertidal zone is unique among marine environments in that its inhabitants are regularly exposed to air and must be adapted to extremes of temperature and desiccation, and physical disturbance from waves and tidal action. For intertidal habitats, tidal characteristics represent the most important abiotic gradient at a given location (Dailey et al. 1993), though tidal characteristics and the subsequent periods of tidal immersion vary little from site to site at SNI. The abiotic parameters of greatest geographic importance appear to be (1) substratum characteristics, (2) surface water masses and accompanying temperature regimes, and (3) wave action (Dailey et al. 1993). Additionally, intertidal areas are subject to high degrees of physical disturbance from prevailing winds and waves depending upon aspect. The richness and complexity of intertidal life represent ecological niches from wave-swept open coasts to protected embayments, and span from the upper splash zone to the nearly continuously submerged lower intertidal. Site specific species diversity and abundance is dependent on the various degrees of biotic and abiotic interaction that sculpt the resulting biological communities.

Upper Intertidal

The organisms in this highest zone are most exposed to the air, staying wet mainly by wave splash. The dominant plants are lichens and cyanobacteria. Marine algae is somewhat limited in the high intertidal and consists of primarily green algae where water collects. Large numbers of periwinkles (*Littorina* spp.) graze on the algae as well as several species of limpet (*Lottia* spp.). Few marine predators occupy this area, but it is visited more frequently by land animals, such as shorebirds, foxes, and people. Variations in species diversity and presence/absence among locations vary widely based on the exposure to wave overwash and spray.

Middle Intertidal

The middle intertidal zone is covered and uncovered by the tides on a regular basis. The majority of this zone is dominated by lush marine algae and a broad host of invertebrate species including owl limpets (*Lottia gigantea*) and black abalone (*Haliotis cracherodii*). The higher zones seem relatively barren by comparison with the teeming life of this mid-region, which is exceeded in density only by that of the outer tidelands (Ricketts et al. 1985). One rockweed alga (*Silvetia compressa*) typically dominates this area as well as a diverse assemblage of red alga (*Chondracanthus* spp., *Pyropia* spp., among others). Considering the various exposure types incorporated within island locales, the invertebrate community can vary widely by site. Representational invertebrates of the middle-intertidal include anemones (*Anthopluera* spp.), limpets (*Lottia* spp.), snails (*Tegula* spp.) and various sea stars (primarily the ochre star, [*Pisaster Ochraceus*], but also bat stars [*Patiria miniata*]).

Lower Intertidal

The lower intertidal zone is submerged most of the time. The lower intertidal is dominated by mussels (*Mytilus* spp.), gooseneck barnacles (*Pollicipes polymerus*), various seaweeds, including red, green and brown algae. Sea urchins (*Strongylocentrotus purpuratus* and *Mesocentrotus franciscanus*), sea anemones (*Anthopleura* spp.), and snails are among the many small animals that live among the seaweeds. Most intertidal fishes live in this zone and include gobies, clingfishes, pricklebacks, and sculpins (Cottidae).

Surfgrass

Sand channels interspersed within rocky intertidal habitat support soft bottom communities similar to adjacent subtidal soft bottom habitat and provide important access points for foraging fauna. The sediment is constantly shifting in response to the waves and currents. Surfgrass (*Phyllospadix* spp.) is a highly productive component of this sandy intertidal habitat, with an extensive system of roots and underground stems. This seagrass supports many species of alga (Stewart and Myers 1980) and provides shelter for many fishes and invertebrates (Engle 1979). The challenges of surfgrass intertidal life are similar to those of hard-bottom. As with most intertidal species, surfgrass is susceptible to desiccation and heat stress during low mid-day tides (Raimondi et al. 1999). It is also sensitive to sewage (Littler and Murray 1975) and oiling (Foster et al. 1988).

3.5.2 Subtidal Habitats

The nearshore waters throughout the Channel Islands are comprised of a variety of bottom types and associated biological communities based on the underlying substrate type and the dominant oceanic conditions. They are influenced by the cold California Current and the California Countercurrent, creating a rich assemblage of fish, invertebrates, macroalgae, and marine mammals comprised of species ranging from the northern Channel Islands to northern Baja Mexico. The shallow subtidal waters surrounding SNI are defined by -9.8 feet (-3 m) MLLW to approximately -98.5 feet (-30 m) MLLW and are comprised of soft sand bottom, small low-lying patch reefs, and large high-relief rocky reefs. Habitats can be further subdivided into vegetated and unvegetated as well as into depth gradients.

Soft Bottom

Considering the expansive nature of the SCB and encompassed Channel Islands, the majority of the nearshore habitat is unconsolidated (gravel, sand, or mud) sediments, hereafter referred to as soft bottom sediments. Benthic species can be epifaunal (attached or motile species that inhabit rock or sediment surfaces) or infaunal (those that live in rock or soft sediments). Nearshore soft bottoms support benthic invertebrates and fish in a vertically stratified pattern. In shallow waters the benthic epifauna are dominated by suspension feeders, giving way to primarily carnivores and scavengers below 33 feet (10 m). The segregation of species by depth within the soft bottom habitat is likely attributed to the ability of suspension feeders to avoid

predation by residing in the harsh physical environment characterized by strong wave action. Moving deeper, the epifaunal densities decrease while the infaunal densities increase (Barnard 1963), probably because of the greater stability of the sediment. The zonation along the complex depth gradient that is apparent for higher taxa and trophic groups is also found within genera (Dailey et al. 1993).

The intricate interactions among individual species and the physical environment provide a multitude of niches from the shore to deep offshore areas. Soft bottom habitat allows larger predatory invertebrates (crabs and sea stars) and fish to take advantage of expansive foraging areas within a mostly homogeneous habitat.

Eelgrass

Eelgrasses (*Zostera* spp.), are widely distributed in the temperate and cold waters of the Pacific and occur mostly within shallow protected coastal waters and embayments. Sometimes exposed at low tide and occurring as deep as 98 feet (30 m), eelgrass communities are important biological habitats common throughout the SCB and the Channel Islands. Eelgrasses can grow into thick luxuriant beds that rank among the most productive communities in the ocean (McRoy and McMillan 1977). Their roots and stems help stabilize the soft bottoms, and their leaves reduce wave action and currents. Reduction of turbulence causes greater and finer sediment deposition, thus affecting colonization by other organisms. The structural complexities of eelgrass beds in conjunction with the diverse assemblage of organisms that inhabit them benefit multiple trophic levels.

Information regarding the distribution of eelgrass habitat within SNI waters is limited and only one location, Coast Guard Beach, has been documented to support a persistent community (Engle and Miller 2003), though additional eelgrass communities may occur within other protected areas along the southeast side of the island. Eelgrass communities are characterized as submerged aquatic vegetation (SAV) that affords it special status and protection under federal statues and defines the habitat as a special aquatic site. Protecting and understanding this habitat is important because various invertebrate and fish species depend on eelgrass beds as essential foraging sites and nursery grounds. Wyda et al. (2002) demonstrated a significantly higher abundance, biomass, and species richness of fish assemblages within sites that have high levels of eelgrass habitat complexity, compared to sites without any eelgrass. The dense eelgrasses offer shelter to many invertebrates otherwise exposed to predation, stabilize sediment erosion, and supply important nutrients from detritus material.

Rocky Reef and Kelp Forest

Hard bottom portions of the continental shelf are usually just submerged extensions of rocky shores. These communities are generally rich and productive; their most obvious feature is the abundance of seaweeds. Unlike eelgrasses, which have true roots and can absorb nutrients from the sediments, seaweeds must depend on nutrients dissolved in the water. One of the main problems for seaweeds in this environment is finding a place to attach. Different seaweeds are adapted to different temperature, light, and grazing regimes. They also vary in their life history strategies. Some species grow fast but only for a short time, while others grow more slowly and live longer.

Forests of the macroalgae, giant kelp, sustain one of the most diverse, productive, and dynamic ecosystems on the planet (Mann 1973; Dayton 1985; Barnes and Hughes 1988; Graham et al. 2003). In southern California alone, over 200 species of algae, invertebrates, fishes, and mammals are commonly observed within giant kelp forests (North 1971; Foster and Schiel 1985). The distributions of many of these organisms are known to be linked tightly to the presence of giant kelp, due to a variety of trophic and habitat associations (see examples in North [1971] and Foster and Schiel [1985]). Kelp forests are diverse, structurally complex and highly productive components of cold water rocky marine coastlines (Steneck et al. 2002). Unlike eelgrasses, seaweeds are also subject to a greater number of grazers. Perhaps the most important herbivore in this community is the sea urchin as urchins play critical roles in the

stable equilibrium of kelp forest systems. Large populations of urchins have the ability to destroy kelp forests. Chitons, sea hares, limpets, and abalones are also important grazers on kelp. As in soft-bottom communities, grazers and their predators have a strong influence on composition as they remove residents from the rocks and open space for other organisms.

SNI kelp forests (Map 3-7), are well distributed within the nearshore waters and display temporal and spatial variability between years based on oceanographic circulation, growth conditions, and grazing pressure. Subtidal surveys performed at four separate sites around SNI, as part of an ASBS evaluation, documented giant kelp and other understory kelps present in the subtidal zone at various life stages (Merkel and Associates, Inc. 2007a).

SNI kelp forests occupy a physically challenging environment and subsequently contribute significant quantities of wrack (drift algae), that break off and disperse throughout the subtidal marine environment. Drift algae is important because it provides food to abalone and other grazers that are limited in their ability to directly graze on the highly nutritional fronds of adult giant kelp plants located near the surface. Abalone, specifically red, green, pink, pinto, black, and white abalone are species of special concern throughout their range because of protection status and historical value as commercial fisheries. Red abalone located in the nearshore waters surrounding SNI represent an important portion of the population located south of Point Conception, and are the largest of all abalone species. Black and white abalone are discussed in depth in *Section 3.8.1: Federally Listed Species*. Green and pink abalone are listed as NMFS species of concern.

The importance of kelp bed density, distribution, and species composition to fish abundance is well documented (Carr 1994; Hamilton 2004). Although the persistence and stability of kelp beds

are at least partly determined by suitable space and substratum type (Dayton 1985), the importance of overall habitat complexity (i.e. kelp cover and substrate topography) to kelp-associated fish species is well understood. Hamilton and Konar (2007) found that structural habitat complexity is important to both fish and kelp in that greater physical habitat complexity is associated with greater overall densities of fish in these communities. Fish diversity and biomass increases with structural complexity of the bottom and attached macroalgae. Trophic contributions from rocky reef and kelp forests to the overlying nearshore waters are directly responsible for the associated high species diversity and the cascading support to every trophic level, specifically marine mammals including sea otters. Though substantial portions of the subtidal rocky habitat lie beyond kelp forest depth they provide equally important productivity contributions to various habitats within the nearshore ecosystem.

3.5.3 Deep Water

SNI is located on a sloping shelf, which has an average depth of 350 feet (107 m) at the outer edge. On the south side of SNI, the continental slope is very narrow and drops off rather quickly into the deep sea. At 3 nm (5.5 km) from shore on the south side of SNI, the depth ranges from around 400 m to more than 600 m. Conversely, on the northern side of the island, the continental slope has a more gradual slope with depths at 3 nm from shore no more than 80 to 90 m. The predominant habitat consists of sandy and muddy sediments (Allen 2006). The deep sea can be divided into two primary areas: pelagic (associated with the open water) and benthic (associated with the bottom of the ocean). Deep water can further be divided into the epipelagic, mesopelagic, and bathypelagic zones. The epipelagic zone (down to 660 feet [200 m]) is the sunlit area of the water where nearly all primary production in the ocean occurs. In the mesopelagic zone (660 to 3,300 feet [200 to 1,000 m]), some light is able to penetrate but not enough for photosynthesis; species in this zone make vertical migrations at night to feed on the nutrient rich surface layers. The bathypelagic zone (3,300 to 13,000 feet [1,000 to 4,000 m]) is completely dark with most species surviving on detritus in sediment (polychaetes, arthropods, mollusks, and echinoderms) (Dailey et al. 1993). Information on deep water habitats (100 feet [>30 m]) is limited due to the expense and difficulty of conducting surveys.

Rocky Habitat

Hard substrates occur to depths of 1,600 feet (500 m) in the SCB (Dailey et al. 1993). The ocean floor surrounding SNI is typically characterized as a high relief rocky habitat that is interspersed with sand channels (Allen 2006). It's estimated that 3 percent of the sea floor in the SCB between 80 and 215 feet (25 and 65 m) is rocky substrate. Using this assumption, the total amount of deep rocky habitat in southern California was estimated at 750 acres (752 ha) (Butler et al. 2006). Surveys completed in 2012 indicate areas of deep hard substrate off of the northwest end of SNI (Map 3-6). However, there are no specific studies describing organisms that inhabit the deep rocky habitat around SNI. General similarities of the deep rocky habitat can be drawn between SNI and the San Miguel Island platform (shelf) on the lower slope-sill (950 to 2,050 feet [290 to 625 m]) in the SCB, which has been previously described. The island platform was composed of rocky outcrop and small cobbles, boulders, and slabs (Dailey et al. 1993). Some of the outcrops had vertical ledges of more than 7 feet (2 m) (Parr and Shrake 1989). The bottom was dominated (more than 80 percent) by a low growing turf, anemones, amphipods, polychaetes, and ectoprocts. Larger species included sponges, gorgonians (*Stenellia* sp.), feather stars (*Florometra* sp.), and anemones (e.g., *Stomphia* sp.). A high degree of commensalism was evident among the large sponges, which provided structure and habitat for a variety of animals, such as crinoids, shrimp, and ophiuroids. In contrast to hard substrate assemblages in shallower water (345 to 700 feet [105 to 213 m]), cup corals, anemones, brachiopods, and lithodid and galatheid crabs were much less prevalent.

Soft Bottom

Extensive areas (over 54,000 nm [100,000 km²]) of deep benthic habitats (>100 feet [30 m]) exist in the SCB (Dailey et al. 1993) and are the dominant habitat of the shelf and upper slope (Allen 2006). In general, organism abundance is high and diversity is low in nearshore sandy bottom habitats; in the offshore habitats, abundance decreases and diversity increases with depth. The nearshore area of SNI, where deep soft sandy bottom occurs, is from approximately 100 to 3,000 feet (30 to 900 m) of water depth and includes portions of the island shelf. The greatest differences in species composition and diversity among deep soft substrate benthic assemblages of the region occur over water depth. This most likely reflects decreasing sediment grain size, increasing organic content, and decreasing dissolved oxygen concentrations that occur over depth. The largest change in species composition occurs at mid-slope, about 1,640 feet (500 m) (Dailey et al. 1993). Differences in benthic assemblages in the SCB also exist between nearshore and offshore sites of similar depth. These differences appear to be related to increased productivity, waves, currents, and decreased contribution of terrestrial detrital sediment on the offshore areas. Species will often inhabit both nearshore and offshore shelf areas, however, abundance will change between these areas. Species adapted to fine sediments occur more frequently on the mainland and species that prefer coarse sediments and rock occur more frequently on the island shelves (Wicksten 1980). Nearshore and offshore basins are inhabited by quite different species assemblages. Nearshore basins have the highest sedimentation rates and can experience episodic anoxia that limits the development of a diverse basin fauna. Echinoderms often dominate benthic communities in southern California. All the deep soft substrate benthic assemblages of the region, except those on the nearshore basin floors, are dominated by echinoderms, usually ophiuroids and echinoids (Dailey et al. 1993). Macrofaunal species diversity and biomass decrease over depth from shelf to basins, but megafaunal diversity and biomass increase over depth to their maximum values on the slopes (Dailey et al. 1993).

3.5.4 Sea Stacks and Offshore Rocks

Offshore rock outcrops are important habitat for many species of plants and wildlife. SNI and adjacent nearshore waters encompass a wide variety of offshore rocks that provide important habitat to resident and migratory marine, terrestrial, and avian wildlife.

The majority of SNI offshore rocks are small in size, close to the island, and of low elevation. Many are composed of exposed rock, washed by active seas. A small but important minority is large enough to have soil and low vegetation, but not high enough to allow seabird nesting.

Offshore rocks and sea stacks are unique habitats that can provide protected breeding sites for thousands of seabirds and marine mammals. Remote, undisturbed offshore breeding sites (such as Prince Island, off of San Miguel Island) are extremely important for seabird species (USFWS 2005).

Due to their isolation from the mainland and relative inaccessibility to the islands, offshore rocks serve as prime sanctuaries for birds and marine mammals. The largest rocks host a small complement of plants and often breeding seabirds. Some smaller rocks may have seabird nesting sites as well; isolated pairs of black oystercatchers, pelagic cormorants (*Phalacrocorax pelagicus*), and pigeon guillemots (*Cepphus columba*) will use such suitable sites at other locations. Many rocks that are submerged or overwashed during high tide and heavy sea events are important feeding sites for black oystercatchers and a suite of wintering and migrating shorebirds such as black turnstones, rock sandpipers (*Calidris ptilocnemis*), surfbirds (*Aphriza virgata*), wandering tattlers (*Tringa incana*), and whimbrels (Mad River Biologists 2002).

Adjacent offshore rocks on SNI do not provide habitat for nesting seabirds, as rocks are regularly inundated. When exposed, the rocks provide habitat for marine invertebrates, plants, and for foraging shorebirds. Begg Rock is one of the few named offshore rocks and is approximately 8 miles (13 km) northwest of SNI. This offshore rock is part of the California Coastal National

Monument (*Section 3.5.5 Protected Habitats*) and is designated as an ASBS and a State Marine Reserve.

Underwater, the offshore rocks contain similar intertidal and subtidal communities previously described in this section. Considering the isolated nature and physical factors affecting offshore rocks within the nearshore waters of SNI, the associated biological communities are essentially islands within themselves. Invertebrates including bivalves (mussels, scallops, etc.), echinoderms (sea stars and urchins), and other invertebrate families benefit from the continual inundation of cool productive water to promote growth. Some invertebrate species, primarily mussels and scallops, grow in high densities and to a larger size due to the lack of predators that result from the rock's spatial isolation. Fish congregate near offshore rocks and structures to take advantage of food and protection from predation associated with such structures. Therefore, offshore rocks contribute to the richness of both terrestrial and marine systems on multiple trophic levels and play an important role in sustaining sensitive island populations.

3.5.5 Protected Habitats

No critical habitat designations, as defined under the ESA, occur for SNI.

However, western snowy plover critical habitat was proposed on SNI, but not designated, as the INRMP provided appropriate protection of the habitat which allowed for the military exemption of critical habitat under the NDAA. Additionally, critical habitat was also proposed on SNI for black abalone but was not designated, as the SNI INRMP provided benefits to black abalone.

For information on Jurisdictional Waters of the U.S., refer to *Section 4.3.2: Jurisdictional Waters - Wetlands*.

No Marine Protected Areas currently exist in the vicinity (3 nm [5.55 km]) of SNI, but a State Marine Reserve was established for all state waters below the mean high tide line surrounding Begg Rock (December 19, 2012)), to support the California Marine Life Protection Act.

By Presidential Proclamation on 11 January 2000, all unappropriated or unreserved lands and interest in lands owned or controlled by the U.S. in the form of islands, rocks, and pinnacles above mean high tide within 12 nm (22.2 km) of the shoreline of the state of California were designated as the California Coastal National Monument. This designation includes the portions of the CCNM off of the shoreline of SNI and Begg Rock that are administered by NBVC. The Navy agreed to management and partnership actions in the MOU (Appendix H) between the Navy and the BLM regarding the CCNM (BLM MOU No. CA-939-08-02). Management strategies are addressed in *Section 4.3.3: Coastal and Marine Habitats and Communities*.

SNI resides within one of the Cowcod Conservation Areas within the SCB. The Cowcod Conservation Areas, implemented in 2001 (Section 27.28[d]), prohibit most bottom-fishing deeper than approximately 20 fathoms (36 m). The SCB is the area where cowcod are most abundant, where adult habitat is most common, and where catches are highest.

3.6 Terrestrial Wildlife Populations

Evaluating trends in important fish and wildlife species within a defined boundary, while prioritizing species in need of conservation attention, is an essential step in developing appropriate management strategies and allocating limited financial or human resources. Although many globally threatened species have been identified through standardized ranking systems (e.g. International Union for Conservation of Nature [IUCN] Red List, MBTA), the burden of identifying priority species at smaller geographic scales often falls on agencies or institutions operating within political boundaries much smaller than the geographic ranges of most species. Species within a region can be assessed using two important factors: (1) scale (globally or locally) at which the level of risk is applied and (2) the biological capacity of a region to contribute towards

sustaining populations of a species based on the proportion of the global or regional population. For example, the species diversity of vascular plants within the Channel Islands is low compared to mainland areas of similar size, while endemism is relatively high (Junak et al. 1996; Junak 2003, 2008). Island ecosystems are insular systems that highlight important interspecies relationships and create defined niches and habitats sometimes exclusive to specific regions or islands.

3.6.1 Invertebrates

Relatively few surveys have been conducted on insects and related terrestrial arthropods on SNI. Nevertheless, over 200 species have been documented (Appendix E). Based on the best available data, over a dozen taxa of insects found on SNI are considered endemic specifically to SNI or to the Channel Islands. However, it may be premature to draw conclusions from these data because (1) some of these supposed endemics may eventually prove not to be, and (2) some endemics have not been described and others have probably not yet been collected or recognized in collections (Miller and Menke 1981). Many of the native pollinators may have co-evolved with island endemic flora and be important to habitat and rare plant management.

The status of most invertebrate species on SNI has been largely overlooked with the exception of the land snail fauna that is fairly well understood and particularly rich. Invertebrate surveys are being conducted in 2014–2015 at twelve locations across the island. Invertebrates play ecologically crucial roles in the terrestrial ecosystem and are important food items for many birds, small mammals, and lizards. As pollinators, insects are vital to the reproduction of many island plant species and are also essential for decomposition and soil formation processes. Insects of the Channel Islands are typically associated with mainland forms but differences in insect assemblages exist between the northern and southern Channel Islands. The southern islands tend to have higher numbers of California endemics and greatest affinity with insects of more arid climates, such as the southern coastal and foothill habitats and the desert environs of the Mojave and Colorado deserts (Powell and Hogue 1979).

Thirteen species of snails have been documented on SNI (Appendix E). Perhaps the rarest land snail is the San Nicolas island snail (*Micrarionta feralis*), its entire global range limited to two small cactus patches on SNI. The prickly-pear island snail (*Micrarionta opuntia*), Santa Barbara shelled slug (*Binneya notabilis*) (known only from recent fossil records), and bicolor cactus snail (*Xerarionta tryoni*) are also SNI endemics (DoN 2005). Other Channel Island endemics found on SNI include Durant's island snail (*Haplotrema durantii*), pouch snail (*Physa virgata*), San Clemente Island blunt-top snail (*Sterkia clementina*), and the California vertigo snail (*Vertigo californica*). At least two introduced non-native snail species, the European garden snail (*Helix aspersa*) and the decollate snail (*Rumina decollata*) are present on the island (DoN 2005). The decollate snail is a relatively large snail which preys on other mollusks and hence may pose a serious threat to the small remnant populations of terrestrial land snails on SNI.

3.6.2 Reptiles and Amphibians

Only three reptiles are known to occur on SNI, the southern alligator lizard (*Elgaria multicarinata*), side-blotched lizard (*Uta stansburiana elegans*), and the previously federally listed threatened island night lizard (*Xantusia riversiana*). The island night lizard is discussed in *Section 3.8.2: Other Special Status Species*. Alligator lizards and side-blotched lizards are presumed to have been introduced to the island in recent historical time. The distribution of both species on SNI is limited, but ranges have been gradually increasing. No amphibian species are currently documented to occur on SNI.

Southern alligator lizards are members of the family Anguillidae, a family of lizards found in the Americas, Europe, Asia, and Africa. Southern alligator lizards are generally secretive, tending to hide in brush, under rocks, and human introduced debris, although they are often seen foraging

out in the open or on roads in the morning and evening. The southern alligator lizard eats a variety of small invertebrates, small lizards, small mammals and occasionally bird eggs and young birds (Stebbins 2003). It is unknown if the increase in southern alligator lizards are adversely impacting island night lizards.

The side-blotched lizard is the most abundant and commonly seen lizard in deserts and semi-arid areas. Diurnal in nature and small in size, this lizard is usually the first species out in the morning and is active mostly on the ground, but is also a good climber (Stebbins 2003). It is unlikely these lizards are having any impacts to island night lizards or having any significant impact to SNI's ecosystem. No estimates of abundance are available for these two introduced species, however their range has been mapped.

3.6.3 Birds

SNI provides nesting, roosting, and foraging habitat for over 300 species of resident and migratory birds (Appendix E).

Landbirds (Passerines)

Passerines (including songbirds) are bird species that are small, often live near the ground, and have appendages adapted for perching. Migration for passerines is predominantly over land. They rarely are seen over open water. The Passerine order of birds encompasses more than half of all bird species and inhabits a variety of land cover types including forest, scrub, riparian, and coastal habitats. Table 3-3 lists the landbird species that nest on SNI.

Table 3-3. Common landbird species nesting on San Nicolas Island.

Species (Scientific Name)	Occurrence on San Nicolas Island
American kestrel (<i>Falco sparverius</i>)	Resident, common
Anna's hummingbird (<i>Calypte anna</i>)	Resident, common
Barn swallow (<i>Hirundo rustica</i>)	Summer visitor, rare, known to breed on SNI
Barn owl (<i>Tyto alba</i>)	Resident, uncommon
Chukar (<i>Alectoris chukar</i>)	Resident, abundant
European starling (<i>Sturnus vulgaris</i>)	Resident, abundant
Horned lark (<i>Eremophila alpestris insularis</i>)	Resident, abundant
House finch (<i>Carpodacus mexicanus clementis</i>)	Resident, abundant
House sparrow (<i>Passer domesticus</i>)	Resident, uncommon
Mallard (<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>)	Summer visitor, uncommon
Northern mockingbird (<i>Mimus polyglottos</i>)	Resident, common
Orange-crowned warbler (<i>Oreothlypis celata sordida</i>)	Resident, common
Peregrine Falcon (<i>Falco peregrinus</i>)	Resident, uncommon
Rock wren (<i>Salpinctes obsoletus</i>)	Resident, common
Western meadowlark (<i>Sturnella neglecta</i>)	Resident, abundant

Resident landbirds on SNI are defined as such, depending on the amount of time the species spends on SNI; they are typically present year-round and breed on SNI. Resident landbird species of SNI include three Channel Island endemics (island horned lark [*Eremophila alpestris insularis*], San Clemente Island house finch [*Carpodacus mexicanus clementis*], and orange-crowned warbler [*Oreothlypis celata sordida*]), as well as the western meadowlark (*Sturnella neglecta*), rock wren (*Salpinctes obsoletus*), and northern mockingbird (*Mimus polyglottos*). Northern mockingbirds are year-round residents that are often found within developed areas. Twenty species regularly breed on the island including three non-natives (the house sparrow [*Passer domesticus*], European starling [*Sturnus vulgaris*], and chukar [*Alectoris chukar*]). Of the bird species breeding on SNI, the western snowy plover is the only species that has special status under state and/or federal law. The western snowy plover is discussed in further detail in *Section*

3.8.1: Federally Listed Species. Peregrine falcons have recently been documented nesting on SNI in 2013 and 2014, with two pairs documented.

Island horned larks are ground-dwelling birds of open habitats that prefer short-height vegetation interspersed with bare ground. The breeding season for the San Nicolas Island horned lark is slightly earlier than in the mainland population. Island horned larks are locally common on SNI, and much of the island consists of sparsely vegetated areas of the type horned larks use for breeding and foraging, with the exception of steep slopes and dense vegetation (Wehtje 2000).

San Clemente Island house finches are quite common on SNI and are year-round residents. These finches are very adaptable and have increased their range in the last 60 years (Wehtje 2000). The primary limiting factor on SNI is access to safe breeding sites. Wehtje (2000) indicates the presence of large numbers of nests at the main compound on SNI may suggest that good nesting sites in native vegetation are lacking. House finches range all across SNI and are not affected by most human activities.

A third SNI endemic, the dusky orange-crowned warbler, is a migrant that breeds on all of the California Channel Islands; however, not all individuals leave at the end of the breeding season. This species is associated with tall vegetation, but nests on the ground or in very low vegetation. During the breeding season, these warblers are most common in giant coreopsis scrub, but coyote brush scrub and deep drainages will also support them. This warbler's breeding cycle is strongly correlated with winter rains; as soon as the island begins to dry out, the birds depart, typically in May.

Western meadowlarks breed on SNI wherever the grass or scrub is sufficiently dense. They do not breed in tall vegetation nor on bare ground. They are a California Partners-In-Flight (PIF) focal species for grasslands.

In California, rock wrens are found throughout the state except along the coastal belt north of Marin County. On SNI, rock wrens are common in areas of exposed soil or rock in combination with cracks and cavities where they might breed (Wehtje 2000). Island-wide point counts in 2000 showed a very strong correlation between steep slopes with bare soil and rock wren presence (Wehtje 2000). Dense vegetation is the most limiting factor for this species.

The northern mockingbird has greatly expanded its range and breeds almost contiguously throughout the U.S. and Mexico. On SNI, northern mockingbirds appear tied to the presence of fruiting shrubs, especially myoporum (Wehtje 2000). As a result, the majority of mockingbird territories are located in developed areas (Nicktown) which use myoporum for landscaping and windbreaks. The population is stable and is primarily limited by lack of suitable habitat and nest vulnerability to high winds.

In 1968, the California Department of Fish and Game (now referred to as CDFW) introduced 85 chukar to SNI in order to develop a source population to restock mainland populations and establish a recreational hunting program for Navy personnel. By the time a sizable population was established, the Navy's mission had increased and personal firearms were no longer allowed on the island. In the early 1990s, CDFG also determined it was not feasible to capture them to take to the mainland. Current population numbers for chukar are unknown but are estimated in the thousands (DoN 2005). Efforts were made in 2012 and 2013 to develop trapping techniques to determine feasibility of eradicating or controlling the chukar population. Results showed the difficulty in trapping due to available resources for chukar and the difficulty of excluding foxes from traps (Manley, S.J., and D.K. Garcelon 2013).

Raptors are uncommon visitors to SNI, with the exception of American kestrels (*Falco sparverius*) and barn owls (*Tyto alba*), which are permanent residents. Additional raptors previously observed on SNI include rare occurrences of transient and wintering visitors including sharp-shinned hawks (*Accipiter straitus*), Cooper's hawks (*Accipiter cooperii*), merlins (*Falco columbarius*), and other rare raptors (see Appendix E for a full list). Kestrels are documented predators of western snowy plovers and island night lizards. SNI sustains a regular wintering population of burrowing owls (*Athene cunicularia*), which is considered a California Species of Special Concern.

Although most resident species are adapted to the arid island conditions, neo-tropical migrants rely on the limited riparian areas and water sources for food and shelter. SNI has a multitude of migrant bird species that visit throughout spring and fall migration. As some of the migration routes can be varied seasonally, there is a flux in the species diversity on the island when comparing spring versus fall migration. Refer to Map 3-8 for important locations utilized by land and sea birds at SNI.

Shorebirds

Shorebirds are closely associated with wetland and coastal environments. They utilize beaches, estuaries, wetlands, coastal dunes, islands, and mudflats for nesting, foraging, and as stopover sites during winter and migration. SNI beaches support a variety of winter and summer visiting shorebirds including willets, yellowlegs, whimbrels, curlews, godwits, and turnstones among others. SNI is also the home to several species of plover including the federally threatened western snowy plover.

The black oystercatcher is a long-lived monogamous shorebird that is completely dependent upon the marine shoreline for food and nesting (Andres and Falxa 1995). It is a locally distributed resident on the west coast of North America south to Laguna San Ignacio, including offshore

islands (Jehl 1985). Breeding pairs establish well-defined breeding and foraging territories and will occupy the same territory for years. The American oystercatcher (*Haematopus palliatus*) and black oystercatcher are present year round on SNI and the black oystercatcher has been documented to breed on rocky shelf areas. The dominant prey items of the oystercatchers are mussels and limpets along the rocky intertidal (Lindberg et al. 1987). During the winter, the oystercatcher will often leave their territories and form a large flock in areas of high mussel density (Andres and Falxa 1995).

Seabirds

Seabirds are those species of birds that have adapted to the marine environment and spend a large portion of their life at sea.

Coastal habitats and productive offshore waters are important nesting and foraging areas for breeding and migratory seabirds. The most numerous groups of seabirds within the SCB are shearwaters, storm petrels, phalaropes, gulls, terns, and auklets.

Many of the seabirds roost on islands and offshore rocks around the Channel Islands. The Channel Islands offer nesting sites, some of which have extremely scarce suitable habitat elsewhere in southern California. These offshore islands are readily available to ocean birds and provide protection from human disturbance and predation. The Northern Channel Islands (San Miguel, Santa Rosa, Santa Cruz, and Anacapa) contain the majority of seabird breeding colonies considered special status.

Map 3-8 shows some sites that have been identified on SNI as areas commonly used by resident and migratory seabirds.

Several seabird species are considered particularly important at SNI because of their large numbers, their limited ranges, the rapid decline in numbers, or their use of unique habitats. One species is a candidate for federal listing (Scripps's murrelet [*Synthliboramphus hypoleucus*]), and nine species have either or both state and federal Species of Special Concern listing (ashy storm-petrel [*Oceanodroma homochroa*], black storm-petrel [*Oceanodroma melania*], Caspian tern [*Sterna caspia*], Cassin's auklet [*Ptychoramphus aleuticus*], elegant tern [*Sterna elegans*], Laysan albatross [*Phoebastria immutabilis*], pink-footed shearwater [*Puffinus creatopus*], and royal tern [*Sterna maxima*]). Of the 11 species listed as Birds of Conservation Concern (BCC) (USFWS 2008), four have active breeding populations within the SCB (ashy storm-petrel, Scripps's murrelet, California brown pelican, and Cassin's auklet), two are extremely rare transient (Laysan albatross and black storm-petrel), four utilize primarily bay and estuarine habitat adjacent to the SCB (Caspian terns, elegant terns, royal terns, and black skimmers) and one is a summer visitor (pink-footed shearwater).

Cormorants

Cormorants are considered coastal rather than oceanic birds, with some having colonized inland waters. This type of seabird is a colonial nester, using trees, rocky islets, or cliffs. Cormorants are primarily piscivorous, with at least 93 species of fish from 43 families documented in their diet (Wallace and Wallace 1998); however, they are also observed foraging upon cephalopods and other invertebrates. All three cormorant species occurring within the SCB (Brandt's, double-crested [*Phalacrocorax auritus*], and pelagic) have significant breeding populations within the Channel Islands, located on rocky headlands and isolated offshore rocks. The single largest breeding colony of Brandt's cormorants occurs on SNI (Map 3-8 and *Section 3.8.2 Other Special Status Species*).

Overall, numbers of cormorants have increased in southern California, but regional populations have suffered from gill net and oil-spill mortality as well as human disturbance at several colonies. Pacific coast colonies fluctuate annually, with low reproduction and population numbers influenced by El Niño events (Ainley and Boekelheide 1990).

Pelagic cormorants have a similar distribution to Brandt's cormorants. They breed along the coast and islands from the Chukchi and Bering Seas, south to Japan and northern Baja California. They are the smallest of the North American cormorants and the least gregarious, forming colonies of less than 100 birds per colony on steep cliffs (USFWS 2005). The California population is about 14,300 pelagic cormorants (5 percent of the North American population) (USFWS 2005). There may be 20 to 30 pairs of pelagic cormorants nesting on SNI.

In 2013 a single double-crested cormorant nest was observed at Vizcaino Point.

Other Seabirds

Alcids are marine birds with a stout bill, short wings and tail, webbed feet, a large head and heavy body, and thick, compact plumage. Confined to the northern parts of the Northern Hemisphere, alcids include auklets, guillemots, murrelets, and puffins. True seabirds, they come to breed in large colonies and then disperse to the open ocean for most of their lives. Important southern breeding colonies historically occurred on the Channel Islands of California, and continue to exist at mostly unknown levels.

Auklets and murrelets documented to occur on SNI reflect avian species that may occur in adjacent offshore waters, but have not been documented to breed on the island. Seven species are represented in this group including two extremely rare wintering species: the common murre (*Uria aalge*), parakeet auklet (*Aethia psittacula*), and one extremely rare transient tufted puffin (*Fratercula cirrhata*). The two most important rare resident species include the Cassin's auklet and rhinoceros auklet (*Cerorhinca monocerata*). Additionally, two rare perennial visitors, the Scripps's murrelet and pigeon guillemot are uncommonly observed utilizing the nearshore waters adjacent to SNI. Surveys planned in 2016 will attempt to determine if murrelets, storm-petrels, or other seabird species are nesting on SNI.

Gulls represent a common and recognizable family of seabirds primarily known as ground-nesting carnivores which will take live food or scavenge opportunistically. Ten species of gull have been documented on SNI, with eight of these ten overwintering on the island. Only one species, the western gull, is an abundant year-round resident that breeds on SNI. All gull species and their corresponding abundance and seasonal use of SNI are listed in Appendix E. The gull population has decreased significantly since the 1996, likely attributed to nesting habitat degradation by California sea lions (Carter et al. 2014). Predation by the San Nicolas Island fox (*Urocyon littoralis dickeyi*) was also suggested as a factor; however, as cormorants continue to nest in large numbers at gull nesting areas, it seems predation may not be one of the primary reasons for the decrease.

Grebes and loons are primarily uncommon transients on SNI, with the exception of western grebes (*Aechmophorus occidentalis*) which are common winter residents. All three species of loons known to occur at SNI are migratory visitors and breed in northern latitudes. On SNI, all three of these have been known to winter on the island. The Pacific loon (*Gavia pacifica*) and common loon (*Gavia immer*) are extremely rare summer visitors.

Terns are fast flying pelagic foragers that transit great distances between summer and wintering areas. The majority of tern species hold special status at either the state or federal level. Caspian terns are federal listed as Birds of Conservation Concern, while elegant terns are listed as Birds of Conservation Concern at both the state and federal level. Royal terns have state listing as California Birds of Conservation Concern. On SNI, only royal terns are common winter visitors. Caspian terns, Forster's terns (*Sterna forsteri*), and elegant terns are rare visitors to the island during migration or foraging trips.

Storm-petrels are the smallest of seabirds and feed on planktonic crustaceans and small fish picked from the surface, typically while hovering. Storm-petrels have a cosmopolitan distribution, found in all oceans. They are strictly pelagic, coming to land only when breeding. In the case of most species, little is known of their behavior and distribution at sea. Storm-petrels nest in colonies on remote islands which are attended nocturnally to avoid predators (Bretagnolle 1990). Petrels typically show a high degree of tenacity to the same nest from year to year; once

pairs are established, they would likely continue to breed at the same sites. Several species of storm-petrels are threatened by human activities (IUCN 2010).

Shearwaters are medium-sized, long-winged seabirds most common in temperate and cold waters. Shearwaters come to islands and coastal cliffs to breed. They are nocturnal at the colonial breeding sites, preferring moonless nights to minimize predation (Sibley 2001). Outside of the breeding season, they are pelagic (frequent the open waters) and most are long-distance migrants. Four species of shearwater have been documented to occur at SNI primarily utilize offshore and coastal waters foraging along upwelling boundaries. The sooty shearwater (*Puffinus opisthomelas*) is common in both the spring and fall, and the pink-footed shearwater is a common summer visitor.

A full list of observed avian species is presented in Appendix E.

3.6.4 Mammals

SNI has only two endemic terrestrial mammals, the San Nicolas Island fox and the San Nicolas Island deer mouse (*Peromyscus maniculatus exterus*). The San Nicolas Island fox and the San Nicolas Island deer mouse have evolved into separate subspecies unique to SNI. These two native species of terrestrial mammals warrant special consideration and are discussed in *Section 3.8: Special Status Species*.

There are six subspecies of island fox, each of which is native to a specific Channel Island, and which evolved there independently of the others. Foxes from each island are capable of interbreeding, but have genetic and phenotypic distinctions that make them unique. The foxes are believed to have "rafted" to the northern islands between 10,400 and 16,000 years ago (Wayne et al. 1991a, 1991b). Initially, fox populations were located on the three northern islands which were likely easier to access during the last ice age, when lowered sea levels united four of the northernmost islands into a single mega-island (Santa Rosae), and the distance between the islands and the mainland was reduced. It is likely that Native Americans brought the foxes to the southern islands of the archipelago, perhaps as pets or hunting dogs (Collins 1991a, 1991b). The San Nicolas Island foxes established themselves as an independent group about 2,200 years ago (Wayne et al. 1991a, 1991b). Currently, the San Nicolas Island fox is a state threatened species and is covered in depth in *Section 3.8: Special Status Species*.

The San Nicolas Island deer mouse is the only native rodent species recorded on SNI. Two or three California ground squirrels (*Spermophilus beecheyi*) are the only other rodents that have been recorded on SNI in historic times. These were individuals that had been inadvertently transported to the island in trash dumpsters and promptly removed. Specific surveys for non-native rats (*Rattus rattus*) and mice (*Mus musculus*) have been conducted in likely areas (e.g. the barge landing area, and around warehouse buildings), but no evidence of their presence has been detected. San Nicolas Island deer mice are larger than typical mainland deer mice, and differ in other aspects of measurements, coloration, and molecular genetics (Von Bloeker 1967; Gill 1980). In the past, the deer mice on each of the Channel Islands have been described as separate subspecies: the named subspecies on SNI is *P. maniculatus exterus* (Von Bloeker 1967).

Deer mice on SNI occur across the entire island, in all habitats. They are typically most numerous in shrub-dominated habitats, such as the large coreopsis stands on the island. The abundance of this endemic subspecies fluctuates yearly based on environmental conditions and reproductive cycles. The status of island populations is based on intermittent monitoring events performed by island staff and USGS. San Nicolas Island deer mouse populations have only been generally quantified in terms of abundance and no formal population study conducted. Relative abundance of deer mice on SNI (number of individuals per 100 trap-nights) ranges from lows of 20 to highs of 90 (unpublished monitoring data from SNI, 2005-2010). Compared to some of the other islands, numbers on SNI are moderate, with neither the very high numbers nor the extreme fluctuations seen on Santa Barbara Island (Drost and Fellers 1991). Overall, the deer mouse population on SNI has remained relatively stable and are common across the island despite predation by the non-native cat population which has been removed (G. Smith, *pers. comm.*,

2009). The trap grid surveys and observations of island biologists have documented a healthy and dispersed deer mouse population throughout the island. Ancillary research has primarily focused on genetic studies of biogeography, evaluating relationships with the adjacent Channel Islands and origin of the different island populations.

Deer mice breed in the spring on SNI, corresponding to the flush of plant growth following the winter rains. Pregnant and lactating females, and juvenile and subadult mice have been recorded throughout April and May, but have not been recorded in the fall (unpublished monitoring data). Because of this seasonal breeding pattern, numbers are typically higher in the fall, and lower in the spring. Deer mice on the Channel Islands eat a variety of seeds, fruit, and insects and other invertebrates, and in turn are preyed on (on SNI) by barn owls, American kestrels, other birds of prey, island foxes, and (formerly, at least) feral cats (before they were removed from SNI in 2010). Based on testing of blood samples, the deer mice on SNI have not been found to carry Hantavirus, the causative agent of the serious and often fatal respiratory disease in humans (Orrock and Allan 2008).

Bats appear to be rare on SNI, with a few documentations in recent years using Anabat® recorders. Species of bats documented included the western red bat (*Lasiurus blossevillei*) and the Mexican free-tail bat (*Tadarida brasiliensis*). These were found during the fall bat migration period. A permanent Anabat® recorder was placed in 2014 to better understand the use of SNI for migrating bats. A hoary bat (*Lasiurus cinereus*) was detected in August 2014 (Tetra Tech, Inc. 2015); hoary bats have also been seen migrating through the northern Channel Islands during late summer. Frequency of timing of bat migration will also be helpful to address any impacts to bats from wind turbines installed on SNI in 2014 and 2015.

Historically, the only introduced terrestrial mammal was the feral cat which posed a serious risk to the integrity of various avian and reptile species. Feral cats have been well documented to be responsible for the extinction of many mammal and bird species worldwide, especially within island ecosystems (see Lever 1985; Wolf 2002; Keitt et al. 2005). Cats were introduced to SNI in historic times, probably originally as pets but later possibly for pest control. It is not known when the feral population became established, but Hillinger (1958) reported that large numbers of feral cats were roaming the island by the late 1950s. The size of the population likely fluctuated over time in relation to prey availability and other factors. An extensive island-wide cat removal program occurred in 2009–2010. After the removal of two final cats in June 2010, there have been no detections of additional cats despite continued monitoring which included over 3,000 camera trap nights and over 168 miles (270 km) of sign search (Edmund Pert, *pers. comm.*, 2010). All cats are assumed to be removed. Monitoring to ensure detection of potential re-introduction of cats or other vertebrate species will continue in the future. A full discussion of invasive species is presented in *Section 3.10: Invasive Wildlife Damage*.

3.7 Marine Flora and Fauna

3.7.1 Macroalgae

California kelp forest ecosystems are highly diverse and productive, and are one of the most distinctive features of the California coastline. Kelp forests are important to the physical and biological mechanisms that sculpt the ecological processes of rocky nearshore ecosystems and their inhabitants. They extend from seafloor to surface and form a vertically structured habitat that is the fundamental element to many important ecosystems in southern California (Rodriguez et al. 2001). Southern California's benthic macrophytes are represented by over 700 varieties of seaweeds, red and coralline algae, brown algae, green algae, and seagrasses (Leet et al. 2001). Benthic macrophytes are intensely zone specific and individual species dominate a specific substrate at a specific depth profile.

Natural history studies have described numerous trophic and habitat associations among kelp forest and macroalgal community taxa and the dependence of these multiple trophic levels on the persistence of vegetated ecosystems. Most subtidal macroalgae need a firm anchor and suitable substrate for attachment and eventual growth to maturity. In southern California, five kelp species represent the primary conduit of fixed carbon into the system (Graham 2004). Other subcanopy kelps are abundant at SNI forming a dense understory that provides food and protection for various fish and invertebrates. Below the subcanopy of kelps, or in other suitable areas, highly diverse groups of various non-kelp macroalgae species persist, including members of the brown, green, and red algae families (including coralline algae and crustose coralline algae). Temperature, light, sedimentation, substrate, relief, wave exposure, and biological factors (i.e. grazing, competition with other species) determine the distribution and abundance of macroalgae. The most persistent kelp beds occur on solid rock substrate with moderately low relief and moderate sand coverage; very low relief and abundant sand has less persistent kelp (Deysher et al. 2002).

Wharton and Mann (1981) argue that kelp stands provide shelter and structural complexity in reef environments, resulting in increased abundance and diversity of organisms such as fishes and larger crustaceans. A large number of studies confirm the relationship between the presence of kelp forests and increased abundance and diversity of temperate reef fishes (Bodkin 1988; DeMartini and Roberts 1990; Holbrook et al. 1990; Carr 1991; Anderson 1994). While fishes are typically considered to dominate the upper trophic levels of kelp forests, their dependence on the multitude of supporting trophic levels is imperative. Most communities and their component populations exist along environmental gradients. The vital role of giant kelp in the coastal environment is accompanied by its dependence on the waters in which it inhabits. Optimum growth conditions for kelp and other macroalgae rely on a consistent delivery of cool nutrient rich water supplied from localized or regional hydrodynamic mechanisms. The health and diversity of kelp forests and their associated macroalgae are dependent on the hydrodynamic processes of the SCB on the large scale; however, they, in turn, modify flow conditions in their interior and vicinity that affect a wide range of kelp forest residents on a smaller scale.

SNI macroalgae are a complex assemblage of species typically associated with the cold water ecosystems of central California and the more temperate ecosystems of southern California (Appendix E). Macroalgae regularly observed along intertidal and subtidal rocky reefs of SNI are diverse and robust, supporting a wide array of invertebrate and fish species. Productivity from kelp and associated macroalgae within nearshore waters surrounding SNI benefit multiple trophic levels and support various species of concern both directly and indirectly, including the black abalone, western snowy plover, southern sea otter (*Enhydra lutris nereis*) and others.

Multiple surveys have provided information about the species and distribution of macroalgae at SNI. Merkel and Associates, Inc. (2007a) provided valuable species accounts and density data for macroalgae within the intertidal and subtidal zones. Long-term kelp forest surveys conducted by USGS–Biological Resources Division and UC Santa Cruz have enumerated and measured various kelp species. These data provide the best long-term and comprehensive evaluation of subtidal macroalgae at SNI, and were recently published (Kenner et al. 2013). Finally, information on the distribution of macroalgae in the rocky intertidal habitat is provided in recently established monitoring sites that follow the Multi-Agency Rocky Intertidal Network protocols.

3.7.2 Marine Invertebrates

Invertebrates inhabit nearly every conceivable niche within the marine environment and are typically divided by size (macro vs. micro), locomotion (motile vs. sessile), and habitat (benthic vs. pelagic). Benthic invertebrates inhabit the sea floor during most of their lives, but they may have pelagic gametes or larvae. Habitats are generally the primary classification tool used for partitioning marine invertebrates into functional groups for discussion. Substrate is typically divided into rock or unconsolidated (gravel, sand, or mud) sediments, hereafter referred to as

soft sediment. Benthic species can be epifaunal (attached or motile that inhabit rock or sediment surfaces) or infaunal (those that live in rock or soft sediments) (Dailey et al. 1993). Information about marine invertebrate life histories, characteristics, and range are well documented for the intertidal and subtidal species compared to those of deeper areas (see Smith and Carlton 1975 and Morris et al. 1980).

Vertical zonation is obvious in the distribution of marine invertebrates, especially in the rocky intertidal where rocky surfaces span from the upper splash zone to the subtidal. Zonation is also evident to a lesser degree in sandy beaches and subtidal habitat where depth, circulation, and water movement dictate suitable habitat.

While very little information is available for the majority of SNI marine invertebrates that exist at greater than 98 feet (30 m) depth, a significant amount of scientific research has been published on intertidal and kelp forest ecology that applies to SNI. Published natural history studies have described clear functional ties to the presence of macroalgae (giant kelp, *M. pyrifera* in particular) for many marine invertebrates (Graham 2004). Sea urchins and gastropods (snails) are conspicuous grazers within kelp forests but rarely consume living algae and rely on drift algae as their primary food source. Abalone (*Haliotis* spp.) are common within the intertidal and subtidal waters of SNI represented by several species. The red abalone (*Haliotis rufescens*) is the most numerically dominant of the species. The largest population of the federally endangered black abalone (*H. cracherodii*) within the SCB is documented to inhabit SNI and has shown signs of recovery over the past decade on SNI. The federally endangered white abalone (*H. sorenseni*) was historically reported to occur within the subtidal waters of SNI. Though limited documentation post-1980 exists on the white abalone population at SNI, this species has experienced dramatic declines throughout its range. Marine invertebrate predators include sea stars, crustaceans (crabs, lobster, and shrimp), and several snails. Encrusting invertebrates make up the numerically dominant species within rocky reefs and include bryozoans, sponges, bivalves, tunicates, cup corals and various worms. The majority of the encrusted invertebrates filter food particles out of the overlying water column thus they are dependent on an ample supply of well circulated productive water common to SNI. Few published marine biological surveys have been conducted at SNI. Caplan and Bootloothian (1967) conducted intertidal surveys at two locations, both located on the southern portion of the island between Dutch Harbor and Daytona Beach, and VanBlaricom (1993) studied the distribution of black abalone. VanBlaricom continues to be involved in an annual monitoring of black abalone at SNI in an effort to document population trends; however, recent data have not been published. In addition, the USGS has been monitoring both rocky intertidal and giant kelp populations and the invertebrates that inhabit these ecosystems at SNI since 1980. Findings on the subtidal invertebrates have recently been published (Kenner et al. 2013). In addition to work by Dr. VanBlaricom and USGS, there are several past and present monitoring efforts examining rocky intertidal invertebrates (Appendix K). These surveys provide a comprehensive list of intertidal algal and invertebrate species at these sites.

In June 2013, sea star wasting syndrome was first noted along the coast of Washington state. Since then, sea stars along much of the North American Pacific coast have been affected by this disease and populations have been greatly reduced. Sea star wasting syndrome has been confirmed at SNI in both intertidal and subtidal species.

Currently, the cause of sea star wasting syndrome has been linked to a densovirus (Parvoviridae) (Hewson et al. 2014). In the past, similar die-offs have occurred from the 1970s through 1990s, but never before at this magnitude and over such a wide geographic area.

Sea star wasting syndrome symptoms typically include lesions in the ectoderm, followed by decay of tissue surrounding the lesions, which leads to eventual fragmentation of the body and death. Progression of wasting disease can be rapid, leading to death within a few days. This syndrome has been detected in sea stars of several species in both intertidal and subtidal habitats.

Sandy beaches and subtidal soft bottoms support the majority of the species known to occur at SNI and are dominated by infaunal species. In shallow water, the epifaunal community is well developed and dominated by suspension feeders (Dailey et al. 1993). In water deeper than

about 33 feet (10 m), the abundance of epifaunal animals declines markedly and most of those present are carnivores and scavengers (Morrin et al. 1988). Considering the greater stability of sediments with increasing depth, a shift from infaunal communities dominated by crustaceans to communities in which polychaetes are predominant has been observed (Oliver et al. 1980). Additionally, invertebrates that utilize tubes or burrows, mostly amphipod crustaceans, become increasing abundant at depth. Polychaetes (worms) typically dominate the infaunal assemblages in areas deeper than 66 feet (20 m) (VanBlaricom 1978). The Navy-conducted biological surveys cited in the previous paragraph provide valuable sandy beach and soft bottom species accounts and density data.

The interactions and trophic dependencies of SNI birds, fish, mammals and invertebrates to marine invertebrates are diverse and complex. Marine invertebrates contribute as primary and secondary food sources at many levels and are functionally important from the high intertidal to the deep subtidal. Their contributions and value to the ecology of many of the island's inhabitants and visitors should not be underestimated.

3.7.3 Fishes

Of the 519 recognized California marine fish species, there are at least 481 species within the greater SCB, south of Point Conception (Horn 1980; Cross and Allen 1993; Horn et al. 2006). Geographical variation of both larval and adult fish distribution within the SCB is strongly related to depth preference, warm- or cold-water affinities of each particular fish species, and water mass influences associated with ocean circulation patterns. Fish can be categorized as pelagic (living in the water column), benthic (living on the ocean bottom), or demersal (associated with the ocean bottom, but are often found feeding in the water column). Considering the location of SNI and the predominant ocean circulation patterns fish assemblages more closely resemble the Northern Channel Islands and areas north of Point Conception than neighboring islands, Santa Barbara Island and San Clemente Island (Seapy and Littler 1980; Engle 1994). The cold southerly flowing California Current delivers fish larvae from central California while maintain relatively cool water temperatures around SNI.

Previous studies of the biogeography of marine fishes and invertebrates throughout the southern California Channel Islands have noted three groups of related islands based on the current flow and resulting temperature regimes surrounding these islands (Seapy and Littler 1980; Engle 1994). In Engle (1994), the islands of San Nicolas, San Miguel and Santa Rosa were found to form a cold-water grouping of fishes, Santa Cruz, Anacapa, and Santa Barbara formed an intermediate temperature grouping and the southern islands of San Clemente and Santa Catalina formed a warm-water assemblage. These patterns reflect, in part, the faunal transition between cold and warm that has been observed in the SCB. Pondella et al. (2005) and VRG (2009) reported that in general, the richness, diversity and composition of fish assemblages at the islands were found to reflect previously described biogeographical processes. The rocky reef fish assemblages of all islands surveyed were found to be significantly distinct from one another. Analyses based on the observable similarities and differences between organisms without regard to assumed genealogy revealed two clusters. San Clemente, Santa Catalina and North Coronado clustered as a warm-water assemblage in the middle of the San Diegan Province. The remaining islands Santa Cruz, San Nicolas, San Martin and San Benito grouped together as a cold-water assemblage, despite the geographically disjunct position of the islands within this cluster.

SNI supports a variety of fish species including benthic and demersal groundfishes (e.g. flatfishes, skates/sharks/chimeras, rockfishes, etc.) and epipelagic fishes that are important recreational and commercial species. The epipelagic zone is defined as the portion of the water column between 328 feet (100 m) and the surface that is regularly illuminated and subject to fluctuations in temperature. It is inhabited by small schooling herbivores such as northern anchovy (*Engraulis mordax*), Pacific sardine (*Sardinops sagax caerulea*), and Pacific mackerel (*Scomber japonicus*); large, active, fast-growing, and long-lived schooling predators such as tunas; and large solitary predators such as sharks and swordfish. The small schooling bait

fish fluctuate in abundance seasonally around SNI and take advantage of the elevated primary production associated with the dominant ocean circulation patterns. Pelagic fishes such as tuna, jacks, and other warm water species are less common and tend to migrate offshore to warmer waters.

The shelf and slope demersal rockfishes are the most speciose genus of fishes off the western coast of North America. These fishes are typically the dominant species documented in many fish surveys, in terms of abundance and diversity, especially between the 66- to 656-foot (20- to 200-m) isobaths (Mearns et al. 1980). The rockfish complex of fishes is highly regulated on both a commercial and recreational basis. SNI represents optimal habitat and is regularly targeted by both recreational and commercial fisheries. Fish species observed at SNI by Pondella et al. (2005) include eleven rockfish species (*Sebastes* spp.), greater than twice the number observed at any other surveyed island.

The Bight 2008 program collected observational fish data using SCUBA, in conjunction with macroalgae and invertebrate information, at five sites at SNI targeting four depths: 16-, 32-, 49- and 82-foot (5-, 10-, 15-, and 25-m) contours along primarily rocky reef. A total of 20 species were recorded consisting of common kelp forest and a few rockfish species. The three most commonly observed species were the California sheephead (*Semicossyphus pulcher*), blacksmith (*Chromis punctipinnis*), and señorita (*Oxyjulis californica*) (VRG 2009). CDFW commercial fisheries landings (2004-2009) reported that invertebrates (lobster, market squid, and sea urchins) were the dominant fisheries both in terms of pounds landed and dollars generated. Commercial landings for finfish for the SNI region during the same time period were an order of magnitude less in both categories and primarily represented by California sheephead, white seabass (*Atractoscion nobilis*), rockfish species, and sharks.

Essential Fish Habitat

Many marine fish that are federally managed by the Pacific Fishery Management Council and NOAA/NMFS rely on shallow coastal habitats during part of their lives. The Magnuson-Stevens Fishery Conservation and Management Act (Public Law 94-265; 16 U.S.C. 1801-1884), as amended (Public Law 109-479), provides for conservation and management of fishery resources. The NMFS is given responsibility for identifying Essential Fish Habitat (EFH) for all federally managed marine and anadromous fish species. The Pacific Fishery Management Council and NMFS are responsible for designating EFH for each life stage of federally managed marine fish species.

The Magnuson-Stevens Act defines EFH as those waters and substrate necessary to fish for spawning, breeding, feeding, or growth to maturity. These waters include aquatic areas and their associated physical, chemical, and biological properties used by fishes and may include areas historically used by fishes.

The waters surrounding SNI are considered EFH for the following fisheries: groundfish, highly migratory species, and coastal pelagic species. Since these species span across many jurisdictional boundaries, the aim is to manage the highly migratory species consistently, both regionally and internationally. The EFH designated for the management unit species is broad and varies by species and their life stage (See Pacific Fishery Management Council 2011a, 2011b, and 2014 for more details).

The designated EFH for managed groundfish species includes all waters and substrate within the following areas:

- Depths less than or equal to 3,500 m (1,914 fathoms) to mean higher high water level (MHHW) or the upriver extent of saltwater intrusion, defined as upstream and landward to where ocean-derived salts measure less than 0.5 parts per thousand (ppt) during the period of average annual low flow.
- Seamounts in depths greater than 3,500 m as mapped in the EFH assessment GIS.

- Areas designated as Habitat Areas of Particular Concern not already identified by the above criteria (see Figure 7-2, from Pacific Fishery Management Council 2014).

The Pacific coast groundfish fishery is the largest most important fishery managed by the Pacific Fishery Management Council, in terms of landings and value (Pacific Fishery Management Council 2014); managed species are found within the nearshore waters of SNI. The 89 species managed under the Pacific Groundfish Management Plan are usually found on or near the bottom and include: 62 species of rockfish, six species of groundfish; 12 species of flatfish, six species of sharks and skates; and three other species (ratfish [*Hydrolagus colliei*], finescale codling [*Antimora microlepis*], and Pacific rattail grenadier [*Coryphaenoides acrolepis*]). (See Table 3-1 in Pacific Fishery Management Council 2014.)

In general, the highly migratory management unit species are found in temperate waters along the west coast of the United States. The federally managed species under this unit includes all five species of tuna which are important to commercial and recreational fisheries in the north Pacific (albacore [*Thunnus alalunga*] and bluefin [*T. orientalis*]) and eastern tropical Pacific (yellowfin [*T. albacares*], bigeye [*T. obesus*], and skipjack [*Katsuwonus pelamis*]). Striped marlin (*Tetrapturus audax*) is included because of its importance to the recreational fishery in California. Swordfish (*Xiphias gladius*) is a major target in commercial drift gillnet, harpoon and longline fisheries, and is pursued by anglers. Blue shark (*Prionace glauca*) is an abundant bycatch species in drift gillnet and longline fisheries. It has been the target of some directed shark fisheries in the past, and currently is caught by anglers. Common thresher shark (*Alopias vulpinus*) and shortfin mako shark (*Isurus oxyrinchus*) are important species in the drift gillnet fishery and also are targeted by recreational fishers. Dorado (*Coryphaena hippurus*) is an important component of the suite of species targeted by recreational fishers, especially in southern California (Pacific Fishery Management Council 2011a).

The Coastal Pelagic EFH includes surface waters, or more specifically, waters above the thermocline where sea surface temperatures range between 50 °F to 79 °F. Coastal pelagic species live in the water column, primarily not near the sea floor, and are usually found from the surface to over 3,000 ft (1,000 m) deep (PFMC 2011). The one primary exception to this is market squid (*Loligo opalescens*), which deposit eggs on the seafloor. There are 6 species of coastal pelagics managed under the Coastal pelagic species Fishery Management Plan, including jack mackerel (*Trachurus symmetricus*), krill (Euphausiids), Pacific mackerel (*Scomber japonicas*), Pacific sardine (*Sardinops sagax*), market squid, and northern anchovy (*Engraulis mordax*) (Pacific Fishery Management Council 2011b).

EFH that is considered to be particularly important to the long-term productivity of populations of one or more managed species, or to be particularly vulnerable to degradation, may also be identified by NMFS as Habitat Areas of Particular Concern. Designating areas of EFH that are also Habitat Areas of Particular Concern is a measure to provide those habitats extra management protection, and intended to give the fish species within Habitat Areas of Particular Concern extra buffer against adverse impacts. Habitat Areas of Particular Concern designated for groundfish include all waters, substrates, and associated biological communities falling within estuaries, canopy kelp, seagrasses, rocky reefs, and other habitat areas of interest, detailed below (Pacific Fishery Management Council 2014).

- Estuaries - protected nearshore areas such as bays, sounds, inlets, and river mouths, influenced by ocean and freshwater.
- Canopy Kelp - waters, substrate, and other biogenic habitat associated with canopy-forming kelp species (e.g., *Macrocystis spp.* and *Nereocystis sp.*).
- Seagrass - waters, substrate, and other biogenic features associated with eelgrass species (*Zostera spp.*), widgeongrass (*Ruppia maritima*), or surfgrass (*Phyllospadix spp.*).
- Rocky Reefs - waters, substrates and other biogenic features associated with hard substrate (bedrock, boulders, cobble, gravel, etc.).
- Areas of Interest - this includes specific areas in the federal waters of the Channel Islands National Marine Sanctuary and specific areas of the Cowcod Conservation Area.

NBVC SNI will need to recognize the inter-relationships between and among species managed by the Magnuson-Stevens Act, the MMPA, and the ESA to apply the ecosystem approach to the conservation and enhancement of EFH in general (NOAA 1997). Any project with potential impacts to EFH requires consultation with NMFS. The Navy must incorporate into project plans, NMFS recommendations for conservation practices that minimize, offset, or avoid impacts to EFH.

3.7.4 Marine Mammals

SNI is an important breeding, foraging and haul-out habitat for several species of pinnipeds and hosts a small population of southern sea otter. The relative isolation of the island from the mainland coast, in conjunction with undisturbed sandy beaches and rocky headlands, provide ideal habitat for pinniped rookeries. Productive nearshore waters surrounding SNI support robust populations of the California sea lion (*Zalophus californianus*), northern elephant seal (*Mirounga angustirostris*), and harbor seals. SNI is the most southerly distribution of the southern sea otter and supports a small resident population. Transient observations of Guadalupe fur seals and an array of cetaceans are commonly recorded on a yearly basis. All marine mammal species that occur on or around SNI are protected under the MMPA.

This section describes the three primary pinniped populations documented to breed or haul out at SNI. Southern sea otters are covered in *Section 3.8.1: Federally Listed Species*. The use of SNI coastal areas by transient and resident marine mammals for foraging, breeding, and hauling vary by habitat and time of year and have important implications to island use patterns and management strategies. Figure 3-5 represents the seasonal use patterns of the most common marine mammal species using SNI beaches and headlands.

San Nicolas Island Annual Pinniped Calendar

Figure 3-5. San Nicolas Island annual pinniped calendar for the most common marine mammal species utilizing San Nicolas Island beaches and headlands.

California Sea Lion (*Zalophus californianus*)

The California sea lion is by far the most common pinniped on SNI (DoN 2005). The U.S. stock is not considered a strategic stock under the MMPA. The California sea lion population estimate for the U.S. stock is 296,750 (Carretta et al. 2013). Nearly all of the U.S. stock (more than 95 percent) breeds and gives birth to pups on San Miguel Island, SNI, and Santa Barbara Island. Smaller numbers of pups are born on San Clemente Island, the Farallon Islands, and Año Nuevo Island (Lowry et al. 1992). Map 3-9 shows haul-out locations for sea lions on SNI.

California sea lions utilize offshore waters for foraging to various degrees and tend to concentrate within geographical areas. If California sea lion distribution is determined primarily by prey abundance, these same areas might not be the center of sea lion distribution every year based on prey availability. During summer, the highest densities are found immediately west of San Miguel Island. During autumn, peak densities of sea lions are centered on Santa Cruz Island. During winter and spring, peak densities occur just north of San Clemente Island (Bonnell and Ford 1987). The seasonal changes in the center of distribution are attributed to changes in the distribution of the prey species (Lowry et al. 1991).

The distribution and habitat use of California sea lions also vary with the sex of the animals and their reproductive phase. Adult males haul out on land to defend territories and breed from mid-to-late May until late July. Individual males remain on territories for 27–45 days without going to sea to feed. During August and September, after the mating season, adult males migrate northward to feeding areas as far away as Washington (Puget Sound) and British Columbia (Lowry et al. 1992). They remain there until spring (March–May), when they migrate back to the breeding colonies. Distribution of immature California sea lions is less well known, but some make northward migrations that are shorter in length than the migrations of adult males (Huber 1991). However, most immature sea lions are presumed to remain near the rookeries for most of the year (Lowry et al. 1992). Adult females remain near the rookeries throughout the year. Most births occur from mid-June to mid-July (peak in late June).

California sea lions haul out at many sites of SNI, primarily along the southern and western shores (Map 3-9). Pupping and mating season for sea lions begins in late May and continues through July (Heath 2002). Females nurse their pups for about eight days before beginning an alternating pattern of foraging at sea and attending/nursing pups on land; this pattern may last for eight months (with some pups nursing up to one year after birth). California sea lions haul out during the molting period in September, and smaller numbers of females and young animals haul out during most of the year.

Since 2001 the SNI California sea lion population has remained stable between 43,000 and 57,000 individuals, with the exception of the 2002 El Niño year (NOAA 2007a). SNI pup production between 2003 and 2008 has consistently been reported between 25,000 and 29,000 individuals, which represents nearly 60 percent of the pups born into the population based on the carrying capacity developed by Carretta et al. (2009). In 2011, almost 52,000 total sea lions were documented (Lowry, unpublished data). To date, there is no indication that California sea lions on SNI have reached the carrying capacity of the surrounding habitat, except during El Niño years when sea lions may have to spend more time feeding and may have to forage farther from rookeries. Based on the sea lions life history and dependence on available prey items to sustain pup production and subsequent population stability, regional oceanographic circulation appears to play a significant role in maintaining the current population at SNI.

Northern Elephant Seal (*Mirounga angustirostris*)

Northern elephant seals molt, breed, and give birth primarily on offshore islands of Baja California and California. Rookeries are found as far north as the South Farallon Islands and Point Reyes (Barlow et al. 1993). The California population is demographically isolated from the Baja California population, and is considered a separate stock, although genetically the two populations are indistinguishable (Barlow et al. 1997). About two-thirds of the California population hauls out on San Miguel Island, approximately 30 percent on SNI, and the remaining

seals (1 percent) use Santa Rosa, Santa Cruz, Anacapa, Santa Barbara, and San Clemente islands (Bonnell and Dailey 1993; DoN1998; Carretta et al. 2000). Northern elephant seals haul out on almost all available sandy beaches around SNI (Map 3-9). They are not federally listed endangered or threatened under the ESA, nor are they listed depleted under the MMPA.

Northern elephant seals haul out on land to give birth and breed from December through March, and pups remain hauled out through April. After spending time at sea to feed (post-breeding migration), they generally return to the same areas to molt (Odell 1974; Stewart and Yochem 1984; Stewart and DeLong 1989, 1995). However, they do not necessarily return to the same beach. Adult males tend to haul out to molt between June and August (peaking in July), whereas females and juveniles haul out to molt between March and May (peaking in April). Different age classes of northern elephant seals are found in the SCB throughout the year (Carretta et al. 2000). For much of the year, northern elephant seals feed mostly in deep offshore waters, and their foraging range extends thousands of kilometers offshore from the breeding range into the eastern and central North Pacific (Stewart and DeLong 1995; Stewart 1997; Le Boeuf et al. 2000). Adult males and females segregate while foraging and migrating; females mostly range west to about 173°W, between the latitudes of 40°N and 45°N, whereas males range further north into the Gulf of Alaska and along the Aleutian Islands, to between 47°N and 58°N (Stewart and Huber 1993; Stewart and DeLong 1995; Le Boeuf et al. 2000).

Over the course of the year, about 32,000 elephant seals may use SNI (Lowry 2002; Barlow et al. 1993), representing about 32 percent of the elephant seals hauling out along all California shorelines. The northern elephant seal population has been steadily increasing on SNI, and SNI

is the second largest elephant seal rookery and haul out in southern California (DoN 2005). The NMFS Southwest Fisheries Science Center has performed censuses for northern elephant seals at SNI since 1988. Surveys are conducted during the peak of the breeding season (when numbers ashore will be greatest) in late January to early February, and late in the breeding season in mid-to-late February. From 1988 to 1995 pup counts increased an average of 15.4 percent per year (DoN 2005). Based on trends in pup counts, northern elephant seal colonies were continuing to grow in California through 2005 (Carretta et al. 2009). A generalized logistic growth model of pup counts indicate that the population reached its Maximum Net Productivity Level of 19,000 pups in 1992, but has not reached carrying capacity at 38,200 pups per year (Carretta et al. 2009). Northern elephant seal pup census performed in 2005 recorded the greatest number of pups produced in a single year since surveys began in 1958.

A complete population count of elephant seals is not possible because all age classes are not ashore at the same time. Elephant seal population size is typically estimated by counting the number of pups produced and multiplying by the inverse of the expected ratio of pups to total animals (McCann 1985). Based on the estimated 35,549 pups born in California in 2005 and a 3.5 multiplier, the California stock was approximately 124,000 in 2005 (Carretta et al. 2009).

During the 2005 NOAA census a total of 9,591 pups were reported for SNI, representing approximately 27 percent of the California pup production for that year (NOAA 2007b). In 2010, over 20,000 elephant seals were recorded, with about half of those young of the year.

The California breeding population is now demographically isolated from the Baja California population. The current northern elephant seal population is expanding rapidly based on interpretation of the pup production curve reported in the 2007 USFWS stock assessment. The expansion of the population over the last decade has manifested the use of new beaches as haul-out areas throughout the Channel Islands and Central California creating new management considerations and resource allocation.

Harbor Seal (*Phoca vitulina richardii*)

Harbor seals are considered abundant throughout most of their range from Baja California to the eastern Aleutian Islands. The SCB is near the southern limit of the harbor seal's range (Bonnell and Dailey 1993). These seals do not make extensive pelagic migrations, but do travel 162-270 nm (300-500 km) on occasion to find food or suitable breeding areas (Herder 1986). In California, approximately 400-600 harbor seal haul out sites are widely distributed along the mainland and on offshore islands, including intertidal sandbars, rocky shores and beaches (Hanan 1996; Lowry et al. 2005). SNI harbor seals haul out at several specific, traditionally used sandy, cobble, and gravel beaches (Map 3-9). A few seals haul out at onshore and offshore ledges and reefs, mostly during the pupping and molting seasons (Stewart and Yochem 1994).

Peak numbers of harbor seals haul out on land during late May to early June, which coincides with the peak of their molt. Pupping occurs on beaches from late February to early April, with the nursing of pups extending into May. When at sea during May and June (and March to May for breeding females), they generally remain in the vicinity of haul out sites and forage close to shore in relatively shallow waters. Breeding occurs between late March and early May. Harbor seals are found in the SCB throughout the year (Carretta et al. 2000).

The best estimate of the California stock of harbor seals is 30,196 (Carretta et al. 2013); this estimate was determined by applying Harvey and Goley's (2011) correction factor to the most recent harbor seal counts on shore, 19,608 in May through July 2009 (NMFS unpublished data). In 2010, the total count for the Channel Islands was just under 5,000 individuals (Carretta et al. 2013). Koski et al. (1998) provided the following seasonal estimates of harbor seals in the Point Mugu Sea Range: 914 in winter; 2,860 in spring; 927 in summer; and 2,065 in autumn. Lowry et al. (2008) counted 3,878 and 4,344 harbor seals hauled out at the Channel Islands in 2002 and 2004, respectively.

The California population of harbor seals increased between 1981 and 2004, but this increase has slowed since 1995 (Carretta et al. 2013). The net productivity rate may be decreasing: from 1983 through 1994, the rate averaged 9.2 percent (Carretta et al. 2013).

Lowry et al. (2008) counted with 584 and 784 on San Nicolas in 2002 and 2004 respectively. The most recent published aerial count at SNI reported 754 harbor seals during May 2009 (Carretta et al. 2009), with similar numbers reported in 2012. The actual number of harbor seals using SNI is probably higher than annual counts because not all seals are detected on shore during any one aerial survey. There is no recent published information on the number of harbor seals at specific haul out sites on SNI, but total numbers of seals using the island have remained relatively stable between 2002 and 2009. Counts performed over by NOAA over the last decade have ranged from 584 in 2002 (El Niño year) and 858 individuals in 2007 (Carretta et al. 2009).

3.8 Special Status Species

3.8.1 Federally Listed Species

Animals found on SNI which are listed under the federal ESA as threatened or endangered are described here and listed in Table 3-4. Both terrestrial and marine species are encompassed within this group and include the western snowy plover, Guadalupe fur seal, southern sea otter and the federally endangered black abalone and white abalone.

Table 3-4. Federally threatened and endangered species of San Nicolas Island.

Species Name	Status	Status on San Nicolas Island
western snowy plover (<i>Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus</i>)	FT	Common (~75-100 individuals) year-round breeding resident on sandy beaches; highest concentration on Northwest edge of Red Eye Beach, West of Dutch Harbor to Daytona Beach and Sand Spit. Low nesting success suspected.
black abalone (<i>Haliotis cracherodii</i>)	FE	Fairly common year-round, breeding, within crevice habitat of intertidal rocky reefs.
white abalone (<i>Haliotis sorenseni</i>)	FE	Rare (unknown number of individuals) year-round resident in nearshore marine environment.
Guadalupe fur seal (<i>Arctocephalus townsendi</i>)	FT	Rare use of island, with few records along the southwest shore.
Southern sea otter (<i>Enhydra lutris nereis</i>)	FT	Rare (70-86 individuals) year-round resident in nearshore marine environment, reintroduced population.

(FE = Federally Endangered, FT = Federally Threatened).

Black Abalone (*Haliotis cracherodii*)

The black abalone was added to NMFS's Candidate Species list on 23 June 1999 (64 FR 33466), transferred to NMFS's Species of Concern list on 15 April 2004 (69 FR 19975), and was listed as federally endangered on 14 January 2009 (74 FR 1937), under the ESA.

Black abalone ranged historically from Crescent City (Del Norte County, California) to Cabo San Lucas (southern Baja California), but their current range is thought to extend from Point Arena (Mendocino County, California) to northern Baja California and rarely occurs north of San Francisco (Morris et al. 1980). This species occurs higher in the intertidal zone than any other California abalone from the high intertidal zone to six m depth, rendering it more vulnerable to terrestrial predators but safer from marine hunters (Morris et al. 1980). Small animals dwell in crevices and may move about in search of food; animals over 3.5 inches (90 millimeters [mm]) long occupy more exposed rocks, at least where sea otters are absent, and are quite sedentary. Average black abalone shell length is approximately 4.5 inches (115 mm); however, maximum shell length may exceed 7.9 inches (200 mm) (Morris et al. 1980). Larval black abalone tend to settle into areas

characterized by bare rock and coralline red algae (Douros 1985; Miner et al. 2006). Once settled onto rocky substrata, black abalone juveniles consume rock encrusting coralline algae and diatom and bacterial films (Haaker et al. 1986). Adult black abalone feed primarily on pieces of algae drifting with the surge or current, such as giant kelp, bull kelp, and feather boa kelp (Haaker et al. 1986). Growth rates can vary depending on food availability, water temperature, and other environmental factors (CDFG 2005). Abalone are long-lived (30+ years) and it takes approximately 20 years for black abalone to reach their maximum length (Blecha et al. 1992). Black abalone are preyed upon by a wide variety of marine predators including sea stars, fishes, octopus, the southern sea otter, and striped shore crab (*Pachygrapsus crassipes*).

Historically, sea otter predation and hunting by Native Americans were two primary sources of mortality for large black abalone. Chinese immigrants began harvesting abalone from dense intertidal beds in central and southern California and Baja California in the mid-1800s, and annual harvest reached a peak of 2,000 tons (1,814 metric tons [MT], or 4,000,000 pounds) in 1879 (Howorth 1978; Rogers-Bennett et al. 2002). Commercial harvest was banned in the early 1900s, during which time black abalone populations expanded slightly. However, in 1968 commercial harvest of black abalone resumed. The commercial harvest was greatest around the islands off southern California, particularly San Miguel Island, San Clemente Island, and SNI (CDFG, unpublished data). By the mid-1980s overharvesting, as evidenced by declining trends in fishery-dependent data and eventual closure of the commercial fishery reduced southern California coastal populations of black abalone considerably. In the mid- and late-1980s, black abalone on the Channel Islands suffered massive local die-offs (generally >90 percent losses) from a disease known as withering syndrome (Haaker et al. 1992; Richards and Davis 1993; Lafferty and Kuris 1993). The cause of withering syndrome was confirmed and has been attributed to a Rickettsiales-like pathogen (Friedman et al. 2000). The principal cause of black abalone population decline in southern and central California has been attributed to over-harvesting (Karpov et al. 2000) and/or the onset of withering syndrome in southern California in the 1980s (Lafferty and Kuris 1993). Black abalone populations have declined by over 99 percent in southern California (except for SNI and San Miguel Island).

The SNI black abalone population sustained significant declines between the late 1980s and early 1990s, though to a lesser degree than other geographical locations. The current status of SNI black abalone shows continuous increases in population since 2007 (VanBlaricom unpublished data). The total number of black abalone counted across nine sites in 2014 was 1,712, an increase of 10.3% over 2013. The 2014 count is approximately 7.4% of the mean count for the seven surveys conducted from 1981 through 1991, prior to the first observation of withering syndrome impacts at SNI in spring 1992 (VanBlaricom unpublished data).

White Abalone (*Haliotis sorenseni*)

The white abalone was federally listed as endangered under the ESA on 29 May 2001. The marine invertebrate was historically found from Punta Abreojos, Baja California, Mexico, to Point Conception, California and was commercially harvested throughout its range until the mid-1970s, when stocks declined precipitously. The white abalone is a prosobranch gastropod mollusk that occurs on hard substrate, reportedly in water depths of 65 to 196 feet (20 to 60 m) (NMFS 2008) but have recently been found in more shallow waters. The species prefers a specific type of habitat, consisting of open, low-relief rock or boulders surrounded by sand. Sand may be important in forming channels for the movement and concentration of their primary food, algal drift. White abalone also appear to be restricted to depths where algae will still grow, a function of light and substrate availability (Hobday and Tegner 2000). This species is relatively sedentary and does not form large aggregations. They have separate sexes and reproduce by broadcast spawning, reaching sexual maturity at age four to six years at a size of three to 5 inches (9 to 13 cm). Newly settled individuals feed on benthic diatoms, bacterial films, and single-celled algae found on coralline algal substrates. As they grow larger, white abalone feed on drift and attached algae, including deeper water brown algae such as, *Laminaria farlowii* and *Agarum fimbriatum*. Adult white abalone can reach a shell length of up to approximately 9 inches (21 cm).

While historical accounts describe the occurrence of white abalone throughout much of the SCB, only a few individuals were officially documented at SNI during a CDFG (CDFW) survey in 1974 (CDFG 1974). The majority of the existing white abalone population within the SCB has been documented within the southern Channel Islands and offshore banks. SNI likely represents the northwesterly extent of suitable habitat, but intensive investigations have yet to be performed. Surveys conducted by the CDFG (CDFW) (Haaker et al. 2001) at five California islands and three offshore banks resulted in counting a total of 157 white abalone within 141 acres (0.5 ha) of habitat. The mean density calculated from these data was 6.7 white abalone per acre (range 0 to 24.2 per acre) with densities at Tanner and Cortes Banks being the highest.

Considering the historical abalone landings and requirements for suitable habitat and growth, white abalone populations at SNI are likely rare. No recent focused white abalone surveys have been performed around SNI due to the probability of finding them, difficult logistics, and consequential cost. However, NOAA will be conducting a study in 2016 at SNI to determine white abalone presence.

Western Snowy Plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*)

The Pacific Coast western snowy plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*) is listed by the USFWS as threatened and by the CDFW as a species of special concern (USFWS 2007a). The western snowy plover is a subspecies of snowy plover that breeds and winters on coastal beaches along the Pacific coastline from southern Washington State south to Magdalena Bay, Baja Sur, Mexico. Populations consist of both migrants and year-round residents depending on locality. Snowy plovers breeding in Oregon have been observed wintering in California as far south as Monterey, while snowy plovers breeding in central California have been observed south as far as Guerrero Negro, Baja Mexico (Warriner et al. 1986).

The average life span of western snowy plovers is estimated at 2.7 years, although a bird of 15 years was observed by Warriner et al. (1986). Minimum survival rates of adults have been inferred by individual plover re-sightings by several projects (Warriner et al. 1986; Page et al. 1983; Paton 1994).

The western snowy plover nests on undisturbed, flat areas with loose substrate, such as sandy beaches and dried mudflats along the California coast. Sand spits, dune backed beaches, sparsely to unvegetated beach strands, open areas around estuaries, and beaches at river mouths are the preferred coastal nesting areas of the snowy plover (Page and Stenzel 1981; Powell et al. 1997; Wilson 1980). Nesting generally occurs between March 1 and September 15 of each year, though egg laying in southern California has been documented as early as mid-February, and continues through late July. Two to six eggs, usually three, are laid in a shallow depression scraped into the sand, or other saline substrates. Incubation does not begin until the full clutch is laid and continues for 24 to 33 days with an average of 27 days before eggs are hatched (Warriner et al. 1986). The incubation is performed mostly by the male, although both sexes incubate the eggs, with multiple clutches per season possible (Ehrlich et al. 1988). The scrape usually has small pieces of shell, vegetation or driftwood associated with it. Young fledge and are independent within 29 to 47 days (Ehrlich et al. 1988).

Western snowy plovers breed in loose colonies with the number of adults at coastal breeding areas ranging from 2 to over 300 (Page and Stenzel 1981). Nesting density is apparently dependent on predatory pressure. Page and others (1995) documented nesting density to be one nest per 15 acres (6 ha) at Mono Lake where predatory pressure is high, while 20 nests per 15 acres (6 ha) were recorded at Monterey Bay where predatory pressure is low. Nest success ranges from 0 to 80 percent for coastal snowy plovers (Widrig 1980; Wilson 1980; Saul 1982; Wilson-Jacobs and Dorsey 1985; Warriner et al. 1986). Instances of low nest success have been attributed to predation, human disturbance, and inclement weather conditions. Although the majority of snowy plovers are site faithful, returning to the same breeding location in subsequent breeding seasons, some dispersal occurs (Stenzel et al. 1994; Warriner et al. 1986).

Chicks are precocial and broods rarely remain within the nesting territory after hatching (Warriner et al. 1986). Birds are able to fly within approximately 31 days of hatching. Snowy plovers will re-nest after loss of a clutch or brood (Wilson 1980, Warriner et al. 1986). Double brooding and polygamy have been observed in snowy plovers along coastal California (Warriner et al. 1986). Snowy plover females may abandon chicks as young as six days old to find another mate leaving the male as the only adult to care for the brood (Warriner et al. 1986). Re-nesting may occur in the same scrape, in close proximity to the initial nest, or in a new location distant from the first attempt (Powell and Collier 1994; Powell et al. 1997; Warriner et al. 1986). Females may re-nest 2 to 14 days after nest failure (Warriner et al. 1986). Males attend their young for 29 to 47 days (Warriner et al. 1986).

Snowy plovers forage primarily on the wet sand at the beach-surf interface, where they feed on small crustaceans, marine worms, insects, and amphipods. Both snowy plover adults and young forage on these invertebrates along intertidal areas, beaches in wet sand and surf cast kelp, in foredune areas of dry sand above the high tide, on salt pans, and along the edges of salt marshes and salt ponds.

SNI's population size is closely related to the movements of migrating individuals and success of the breeding population. Numbers are lowest at the beginning of the breeding season and increase in fall as wintering birds arrive. Areas of highest concentration are Tender Beach, Coast Guard Beach, west of Dutch Harbor to Daytona Beach, and Sand Spit. Annual breeding and winter season surveys of adults have occurred regularly since 1994, with only the winter of 2000 and summer of 2015 not surveyed. A larger population of plovers winter at SNI, with a smaller population present during the nesting season (Table 3-5). During the 2009 Summer Window Survey conducted along the Pacific Coast, 69 adult western snowy plovers were recorded on SNI, which comprised approximately 35 percent of western snowy plovers observed in Ventura County during the 2009 Summer Window Survey (USFWS 2009). Nesting success is thought to be very low on SNI, as many nests are lost to extreme high winds, high tides, and depredation by island foxes and gulls.

Table 3-5. Seasonal counts of federally threatened Pacific Coast western snowy plovers at San Nicolas Island.

Year	Winter Season	Breeding Season
1994	89	83
1995	71	116
1996	140	104
1997	156	91
1998	61	90
1999	119	63
2000	-	72
2001	134	62
2002	177	69
2003	114	90
2004	183	79
2005	243	62
2006	212	96
2007	182	68
2008	138	46
2009	86	69

2010	99	50
2011	129	42
2012	159	44
2013	96	68
2014	70	51
2015	69	-

Note: - = Not surveyed

Guadalupe Fur Seal (*Arctocephalus townsendi*)

Prior to the 19th century, the Guadalupe fur seal (*Arctocephalus townsendi*) ranged from Monterey Bay, California, to the Revillagigedo Islands, Mexico (NMFS 2006). Named for the Mexican island it mainly breeds on, the once-abundant Guadalupe fur seal was reduced to near extinction in 1894 due to commercial sealing. The severe population decline led to the designation of the Guadalupe fur seal as threatened under the ESA in 1967. Additionally, Guadalupe fur seals are listed as depleted and a strategic stock under the MMPA. The state of California lists the Guadalupe fur seal as a fully protected mammal in the Fish and Game Code of California (Chapter 8, Section 4700 d), and it is also listed as a threatened species in the Fish and Game Commission California Code of Regulations (Title 14, Section 670.5, b, 6, H). The Guadalupe fur seal is also protected under Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species (CITES) and fully protected under Mexican law. Guadalupe Island (the main breeding location) was declared a pinniped sanctuary by the Mexican government in 1975. Critical habitat has not been designated for this species in the U.S.

Although the population of Guadalupe fur seals has increased significantly since the turn of the century, it was once thought to be extinct until a lone male was found on SNI in the 1950s. Following the lone sighting, an expedition led by Scripps Institution of Oceanography discovered a small breeding colony on Guadalupe Island in 1954. Between 1969 and 1989, 48 sightings of Guadalupe fur seals were made on the southern Channel Islands, including one territorial male that was seen from 1981 to 1990, and a second bull who established a territory from 1989 to 1991 (Reeves et al. 1992). In 1997, a second rookery was discovered at Isla Benito del Este, Baja California, and a pup was born at San Miguel Island, California (Melin and DeLong 1999). Overall, the population has increased at an average annual rate of 13.7 percent from 1954 to 1993 (Gallo-Reynoso 1994; Carretta et al. 2007), and it may be expanding its range (Gallo-Reynoso 1994). The most recent population estimate of Guadalupe fur seals was 7,408 (Carretta et al. 2007).

Guadalupe fur seals have been intermittently observed on SNI since the mid-1980s (G. Smith, *pers. comm.*, 2010). At SNI, a lone adult male Guadalupe fur seal established a territory on the south side of SNI each year between 2006 and 2009, and again in 2012 and 2014 (J. Laake, NOAA *pers. comm.*). A satellite-tagged female Guadalupe fur seal hauled out briefly on SNI in January 2015, but left the island after only a few days (B. Stewart, *pers. comm.*).

Female Guadalupe fur seals give birth from early June through July, with a peak in late June. They mate about a week after giving birth, and then begin a series of foraging trips lasting two to six days. They come ashore for four to six days between foraging trips to nurse their pups. Lactating females may travel a thousand miles or more from the breeding colony to forage. All breeding and pupping occurs from approximately June through late July on Isla Guadalupe and Isla Benito del Este in Baja Mexico (Gallo-Reynoso 1994). There is little information on feeding habitats of the Guadalupe fur seal, but it is likely that they feed on deep-water cephalopods and small schooling fish, similar to their relative the northern fur seal (Seagars 1984). They appear to feed mainly at night, at depths of about 65 feet (20 m), with dives lasting approximately 2.5 minutes (Reeves et al. 2002). Although some information is available on Guadalupe fur seal breeding, researchers know little about the whereabouts of these seals during the nonbreeding season (September-May), but they are presumably solitary when at sea.

Southern Sea Otter (*Enhydra lutris nereis*)

The population of southern sea otters historically ranged from northern California or southern Oregon to approximately Punta Abreojos, Baja California (Wilson et al. 1991). Currently, the southern sea otter's primary range is restricted to the coastal area of central California, from San Mateo County to Santa Barbara County, plus a small translocated population around SNI (USGS unpubl. data).

Sea otters prefer rocky shorelines with kelp beds and waters about 66 feet (20 m) deep (USFWS 2003a). Few sea otters venture beyond 5,200 feet (1,600 m) from shore, and most remain within 1,600 feet (500 m) (Estes and Jameson 1988). They require a high intake of energy to satisfy their metabolic requirements. Sea otters feed on or near the bottom in shallow waters, often in kelp beds feeding on primarily benthic invertebrates such as abalones, sea urchins, and rock crabs. Sea otters also eat other types of shellfish, cephalopods, and sluggish near-bottom fishes, although the consumption of fishes is extremely rare in southern sea otters. The diet varies with the physical and biological characteristics of the habitats in which they live (Estes and Bodkin 2002). Most sea otters in California tend to be active at night and rest in the middle of the day (Ralls and Siniff 1990), but there is extensive variation in the activity of individuals both among and within age and sex classes (Ralls et al. 1995). Sea otters breed throughout their range and have two peaks in pupping, January to March and October (USFWS 2003a).

Harvest of sea otters for their pelts during the 1700s and 1800s reduced the species throughout its range. In 1974, the total California population was estimated to be about 50 animals. The small size and limited range of the sea otter population, along with the otter's vulnerability to mortality from oil spills, were the main factors that resulted in listing it as federally threatened in 1977. Between 1987 and 1990, the USFWS translocated 139 sea otters to SNI (Hatfield 2005).

In 2013, the official population index reported by the USGS (2,941) included the 3-year running average for the mainland population (2,882) and the previous year's high count at SNI (59). The 2011 mainland spring census was not completed due to weather conditions; therefore, the mainland 3-year running average is calculated from only the 2012 and 2013 raw counts (2,719 and 2,865, respectively). The minimum population estimate for the southern sea otter stock is taken as the lesser of the latest raw count or the latest 3-year running average for the mainland population, plus the count for SNI. In 2013, the mainland count was 2,865. The 3-year running average was slightly higher, 2,882. Therefore, the minimum population estimate is 2,865 plus 59, or 2,924 animals (USGS, 2014).²

The sea otter population has been steadily growing on SNI. The population has not increased as fast as what was originally anticipated, however the population is still increasing. Figure 3-6 demonstrates the growth of the population over the last decade. In 2015, USGS biologists counted 86 independent adult otters plus 9 pups, for a total SNI population of 95 animals (B. Hatfield, USGS, *pers. comm.*). Map 3-9 shows sea otter habitat surrounding SNI based on CNDDB records from late 2009.

In 2012, the USFWS declared the southern sea otter translocation program a failure, removing the regulations that governed the translocation program. This effectively changed the status of the population on SNI from a non-essential experimental population to part of the total federally listed threatened population. The 2016 National Defense Authorization Act Section 312 amends Chapter 631 of title 10 USC § 7235 by establishing the Southern Sea Otter Military Readiness Areas at SNI (including Begg Rock) and the adjacent and surrounding waters, and Naval Base Coronado, San Clemente Island and the adjacent surrounding waters. Incidental takings under Sections 4 and 9 of the ESA and Sections 101 and 102 of the MMPA shall not apply with respect to the incidental taking of any southern sea otter in the Southern Sea Otter Military Readiness Areas in the course of conducting a military readiness activity. It also states that southern sea otter within these areas shall be treated for the purposes of Section 7 of the ESA, as a member of a species that is proposed to be listed as an endangered or threatened species. For activities

²The USGS records are accessible at: <http://www.werc.usgs.gov/seaottercount>.

that do not support military readiness, sea otters residing at SNI are still considered part of the federally threatened population and treated as such. Within the 2016 National Defense Authorization Act, ‘military readiness activity’ has the meaning given that term in section 315(f) of the Bob Stump National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2003 (16 U.S.C. 703 note): (1) all training and operations of the Armed Forces that relate to combat; and (2) the adequate and realistic testing of military equipment, vehicles, weapons, and sensors for proper operation and suitability for combat use. The term does not include: (1) the routine operation of installation operating support functions, such as administrative offices, military exchanges, commissaries, water treatment facilities, storage facilities, schools, housing, motor pools, laundries, morale, welfare, and recreation activities, shops, and mess halls; (2) the operation of industrial activities; or (3) the construction or demolition of facilities used for a purpose described in (1) or (2) above.

Figure 3-6. San Nicolas Island sea otter population from 1987–2014.

3.8.2 Other Special Status Species

Special status species of SNI include native and endemic flora and fauna that have been identified by the State of California as endangered or threatened, Species of Concern, or Fully Protected, or recognized by federal agencies and conservation organizations as species of concern (e.g. proposed for federal listing, Bald and Golden Eagle Protection Act, MMPA, BCC, CNPS Rank 1).

Plants

Field surveys for special status plants were conducted March 1999 to March 2003 to determine the distribution, habitat characteristics, and population status of 21 special status plant taxa (Junak et al. 2003). These taxa are restricted to the California Channel Islands, are of local concern, or have been identified as sensitive species by the USFWS, State of California, or the CNPS. Five

surveys were conducted from December 2012 to May 2013 to remap and reassess 12 of these sensitive plant species at 315 historic occurrences where they had been recorded during the 1999–2002 study (HDR 2013a). In addition to these historic occurrences, four additional species were located and mapped based on information provided by NBVC personnel (See Appendix K for report). Sensitive plant occurrences were found at 245 of the 315 previously recorded occurrences, and 118 new undocumented occurrences were mapped. Numbers of individual plants of each species fluctuated greatly between the previous Junak surveys and the 2012–2013 surveys. Fluctuations in population sizes between the two survey efforts could be attributable to a number of factors. Plant populations experience natural fluctuations in size due to variation in climate particularly precipitation and temperature. Additionally, differences in methodology employed by various observers (e.g. timing of 21 surveys, habitats visited, routes selected, etc.) (HDR 2014). Table 3-6 lists 33 native plant species that occur on SNI and are species of concern within some portion of their California range, with information regarding the plants current status with regards to the State of California, CNPS, Global Ranking, and occurrence on the Channel Islands. While some of the plant species are common or abundant on SNI, they remain a species of concern in other portions of California.

Table 3-6. Special-status plant species on San Nicolas Island.

Species Name	State Listing	CNPS Status	Global/ State Rank	Channel Island Endemics, and Islands Occupied	Vegetation Community	Status on SNI	Expected Known Threats on SNI
sticky sand verbena (<i>Abronia maritima</i>)	-	4.2	G4/S3 S4		Coastal dunes	Common, sandy flats, stabilized and unstabilized dunes	Invasive plants on dunes.
San Diego needlegrass (<i>Stipa diegoensis</i>)	-	4.2	G3/S3. 2		Chaparral Coastal scrub	Abundant, canyon walls and sandy slopes	Invasive plant encroachment and activities with a direct or indirect impacts canyon walls. Erosion.
San Diego coastal creeper (<i>Aphanisma blitoides</i>)	-	1B.2	G3G4/ S3		Coastal bluff scrub Coastal dunes Coastal scrub/sandy	Rare, dry slopes, cactus patches	Disturbance in <i>Opuntia</i> sp. patches. Invasive non-native plants
south coast saltscale (<i>Atriplex pacifica</i>)	-	1B.2	G3G4/ S2.2		Coastal bluff scrub Coastal dunes Coastal scrub Playas	Rare, sandy flats, eroded slopes	Disturbance and erosion. Invasive non-native plants
island sagebrush (<i>Artemisia nesiotica</i>)	-	4.3	G3/S3. 3	Santa Barbara Island, San Clemente Island, San Nicolas Island	Coastal scrub (rocky) Valley and foothill grassland	Occasional, gullies, swales, canyon slopes, and flats	Erosion. Invasive non-native plants
Trask's milkvetch (<i>Astragalus traskiae</i>)	SR	1B.2	G3/S3	Santa Barbara Island and San Nicolas Island Endemic	Coastal bluff scrub Coastal dunes Coastal scrub	Abundant, sandy slopes, stabilized dunes, coastal bluffs, eroded caliche slopes, sandy canyon bottoms, and flats	Invasive non-native plants
island morning-glory (<i>Calystegia macrostegia</i> ssp <i>amplissima</i>)	-	4.3	G4G5T 3/S3.3	Santa Barbara Island, San Clemente Island, San Nicolas Island	Coastal bluff scrub Coastal dunes Valley and foothill grassland	Abundant	Invasive non-native plants
Trask's cryptantha (<i>Cryptantha traskiae</i>)	-	1B.1	G2/S2	San Clemente Island and San Nicolas Island	Coastal bluff scrub Coastal dunes Coastal scrub	Occasional; sandy dunes, stabilized flats	Invasive non-native plants
island tarplant (<i>Deinandra clementina</i>)	-	4.3	G3/S3. 3	Anacapa Island, Santa Barbara Island, San Clemente Island, Santa Catalina Island, and San Nicolas Island	Coastal bluff scrub Valley and foothill grassland	Abundant; slopes, flats, barren ridgetops, and canyon walls	Invasive non-native plants
beach spectacle-pod (<i>Dithyrea maritima</i>)	ST	1B.1	G2/S2. 1		Coastal dunes Coastal scrub	Scarce; unstabilized sand dunes	Marine mammals, invasive species encroachment, habitat loss, and erosion.

Table 3-6. Special-status plant species on San Nicolas Island.

Species Name	State Listing	CNPS Status	Global/ State Rank	Channel Island Endemics, and Islands Occupied	Vegetation Community	Status on SNI	Expected Known Threats on SNI
bright green dudleya (<i>Dudleya virens</i> ssp. <i>insularis</i>)	-	1B.2	G2T2/ S2.2		Coastal bluff scrub Coastal scrub	Common	Invasive plants, erosion ,
San Nicolas Island buckwheat (<i>Eriogonum grande</i> var. <i>timorum</i>)	SE	1B.1	G3T1/ S1.1	San Nicolas Island	Coastal bluff scrub	Abundant; dry slopes, canyon walls	Invasive non-native plants, erosion
island poppy (<i>Eschscholzia ramosa</i>)	-	4.3	G3/S3. 3	Santa Barbara Island, San Clemente Island, Santa Catalina Island, Santa Cruz Island, San Miguel Island, San Nicolas Island, Santa Rosa Island, and Isla Guadalupe - Baja	Coastal bluff scrub Chaparral Coastal scrub	Scarce, dry ridgetops, slopes, and flats	Invasive non-native plants and distribution is highly restricted and vulnerable to erosion. Climate change.
Nevin's gilia (<i>Gilia nevinii</i>)	-	4.3	G3/S3. 2	Anacapa Island, Santa Barbara Island, San Clemente Island, Santa Catalina Island, Santa Cruz Island, San Nicolas Island, Santa Rosa Island, and Isla Guadalupe - Baja	Coastal bluff scrub Coastal scrub Valley and foothill grassland	Very rare, last seen in 1901; sandy sites	Invasive non-native plants.
vernal barley (<i>Hordeum intercedens</i>)	-	3.2	G3G4/ S3S4		Coastal dunes Coastal scrub Valley and foothill grassland (saline flats and depressions) Vernal pools	Occasional; flats small depressions	Invasive non-native plants.
decumbent goldenbrush (<i>Isocoma menziesii</i> var. <i>decumbens</i>)	-	1B.2	G3G5T 2T3/S2 .2		Chaparral Coastal scrub (sandy often in disturbed areas)	Common; flats and coastal bluffs	Invasive non-native plants
island jepsonia (<i>Jepsonia malvifolia</i>)	-	4.2	G3/S3. 3	San Clemente Island, Santa Catalina Island, Santa Cruz Island, San Nicolas Island, Santa Rosa Island, and Isla Guadalupe - Baja	Chaparral Coastal scrub	Occasional; Clay slopes and canyon walls	Invasive non-native species.
island mallow (<i>Malva assurgentiflora</i>)	-	1B.1	G2T2/ S2.1	Anacapa Island, San Miguel Island, San Nicolas Island, and Santa Rosa Island	Coastal bluff scrub Coastal scrub/sandy or rocky	Rare; slopes and flats	Invasive non-native species.

Table 3-6. Special-status plant species on San Nicolas Island.

Species Name	State Listing	CNPS Status	Global/ State Rank	Channel Island Endemics, and Islands Occupied	Vegetation Community	Status on SNI	Expected Known Threats on SNI
San Nicolas Island lomatium (<i>Lomatium insulare</i>)	-	1B.2	G2/S2. 1	San Clemente Island, San Nicolas Island, and Isla Guadalupe - Baja Endemic	Coastal bluff scrub	Abundant; open ridgetops, flats, canyon bottoms, and slopes	Erosion Invasive non-native plants
silver lotus (<i>Acmispon argophyllus</i> var. <i>argenteus</i>)	-	-		Channel Islands Endemic except Santa Cruz		Abundant	Invasive non-native plants
California box-thorn (<i>Lycium californicum</i>)	-	4.2	G4/S3. 2		Coastal bluff scrub Coastal scrub	Abundant; eroded slopes, canyon rims, slopes, flats	Non Native Invasive Plants, erosion.
San Nicolas Island box-thorn (<i>Lycium verrucosum</i>)	-	1A	GXQ/S X	San Nicolas	Coastal Scrub	Very rare; last seen in 1898 "arroya cliffs"	Presumed extinct.
San Nicolas Island malacothrix (<i>Malacothrix foliosa</i> ssp. <i>polycephala</i>)	-	4.2	G4T3/ S3.2	San Nicolas	Coastal Scrub	Abundant; stabilized dunes and sandy sites on flats	Invasive non-native plants
dunedelion (<i>Malacothrix incana</i>)	-	4.3	G3/S3. 3		Coastal dunes Coastal scrub	Common; dunes, sandy terraces, and sandy flats	Invasive non-native plants.
island cliff-aster (<i>Malacothrix saxatilis</i> var. <i>implicata</i>)	-	-		Channel		Common; canyons and slopes	Invasive non-native plants
short-lobed broom-rape (<i>Orobanche parishii</i> ssp. <i>brachyloba</i>)	-	4.2	G4/T3 /S3.2		Coastal bluff scrub Coastal dunes Coastal scrub	Common	Invasive plants and disturbance to host plant Isocoma.
woolly seablite (<i>Suaeda taxifolia</i>)	-	4.2	G/S4		Coastal bluff scrub Coastal dunes Marshes and swamps (margins of coastal salt)	Occasional at low elevations, locally common	Sea-level rise. Invasive non-native plants, marine mammal trampling

Table 3-6. Special-status plant species on San Nicolas Island.

Species Name	State Listing	CNPS Status	Global/ State Rank	Channel Island Endemics, and Islands Occupied	Vegetation Community	Status on SNI	Expected Known Threats on SNI
southern island clover (<i>Trifolium palmeri</i>)	-	4.2	G3/S3. 2	Anacapa, Santa Barbara, San Clemente, Santa Catalina, and San Nicolas Islands, and Isla Guadalupe - Baja	Coastal bluff scrub Valley and foothill grassland	Occasional; found primarily on north-facing slopes and grassy flats with clay soils. It is most abundant on coastal flats in the northeastern portion of the island, where it occurs in grassy openings between shrubs. Small, isolated occurrences have also been found on the mesa, on grassy flats	Invasive non-native plants
<i>Trifolium albopurpureum</i> Rancheria clover	-	-	G5		<i>Isocoma menziesii</i> and <i>Leptosyne gigantea</i> communities.	<i>T. albopurpureum</i> occurs in flats on the mesa of SNI in mixed annual grassland, Limited distribution and abundance.	Its limited distribution and abundance make it vulnerable to extinction on the island.
<i>Trifolium microcephalum</i> Smallhead clover	-	-	G5			Rare; found in flats, slopes, and canyon bottoms.	
<i>Trifolium microdon</i> Valparaiso clover	-	-	G4		<i>Leptosyne gigantea</i> scrub community on the north escarpment at elevations of about 60 m (197 feet). On the mesa it is found at elevations between 122 and 152 m (400 and 499 feet).	Occasional; occurs on grassy north-facing slopes and on flats in grassy openings between shrubs.	
<i>Trifolium willdenovii</i> Tomcat clover	-	-	G5			Extremely limited: Found on moist slopes and flats on SNI.	
<i>Lepidium oblongum</i> var. <i>insulare</i> Veiny pepperweed	-	-	G5			Rare: found on Sandy flats, clay flats, gullies, eroded slopes, and open ridgetops.	

Table 3-6. Special-status plant species on San Nicolas Island.

Species Name	State Listing	CNPS Status	Global/State Rank	Channel Island Endemics, and Islands Occupied	Vegetation Community	Status on SNI	Expected Known Threats on SNI
Notes: - = Not listed California Endangered Species Act: SR=State Rare ST=State Threatened SE= State Endangered California Native Plant Society Rankings: 1B=Plants Rare, Threatened, or Endangered in California and Elsewhere 3=Plants about which more information is needed 4=Plants of limited distribution 0.1-Seriously threatened in California (over 80% of occurrences threatened/high degree and immediacy of threat) 0.2-Moderately threatened in California (20-80% occurrences threatened/moderate degree and immediacy of threat) 0.3-Not very threatened in California (<20% of occurrences threatened/low degree and immediacy of threat or no current threats known) (CNPS 2013 http://www.cnps.org/cnps/rareplants/ranking.php NatureServe Conservation Status: State and Global Ranks (NatureServe 2013): S2/G2=Imperiled S3/G3=Vulnerable S4/G4=Apparently Secure S5/G5=Secure. HDR 2013a							

Terrestrial Invertebrates

There are four special status terrestrial invertebrate species on SNI, including one beetle and three land snails (Table 3-7).

Table 3-7. Sensitive invertebrate species on San Nicolas Island.

Species name	CNDDDB RANK	STATE	FED	IUCN
San Clemente Island coenonycha beetle [†] (<i>Coenonycha clementina</i>)	G1?S1?			
San Nicolas island snail [†] (<i>Micrarionta feralis</i>)	G1S1		FSC	VU
San Clemente island snail [†] (<i>Micrarionta gabbi</i>)	G1S1		FSC	VU
San Clemente Island blunt-top snail [†] (<i>Sterkia clementina</i>)	G1S1			NT

Notes: † = endemic to region (Bunn et al. 2007)

CNDDDB RANKING STATUS:

GLOBAL RANKS: worldwide status of a full species: G1 to G5

G1 = extremely endangered: <6 viable occurrences (EOs) or <1,000 individuals, or <2,000 acres of occupied habitat.

STATE RANKS: statewide status of a full species or a subspecies: 1 to 5, same general definitions as global ranks, but just for the range of the taxa within California.

S2 = endangered: about 6-20 EOs, or 1,000 - 3,000 individuals, or 2,000 to 10,000 acres of occupied habitat

? = inexact numeric rank (Note - Uncertainty about the rank of an element is expressed in two major ways: (1) By expressing the rank as a range of values) [e.g., S1S2 means the rank is somewhere between S1 and S2]; (2) By adding a ? to the rank [e.g., S1? represents more certainty than S1S2, but less than S2])

OTHER CODES:

FSC = Federal Species of Concern (former Category 2 species)

VU = IUCN Vulnerable species (A taxon is Vulnerable when it is not Critically Endangered or Endangered but is facing a high risk of extinction in the wild in the medium-term future)

NT = IUCN Near Threatened species (A taxon is Near Threatened when it has been evaluated against the criteria but does not qualify for Critically Endangered, Endangered or Vulnerable now, but is close to qualifying for or is likely to qualify for a threatened category in the near future).

The San Clemente Island coenonycha beetle (*Coenonycha clementina*) is a member of the Scarab Family (*Scarabaeidae*). Scarab beetles are generally herbivores or frugivores, while the larvae are usually soil dwellers where they feed mostly on plant roots. The San Nicolas Island snail was proposed for listing as endangered in 1976 (USFWS 1976), but ultimately was not listed as such. This species is known to occur in a highly restricted range on SNI (1 km southwest of Nicktown). The principal threat to the species was feral goat grazing, but this threat has been eliminated. It remains vulnerable to military activities or other actions which may result in the introduction of exotic species or cause erosion. The San Clemente Island snail (*Micrarionta gabbi*) inhabits temperate shrublands where its principal threat is habitat loss (Nature Serve 2009; IUCN 2010). The San Clemente Island blunt-top snail has a cylindrical shell with somewhat obtuse apex, and is 8 to 9 mm in diameter (Pilsbry 1921). Its color varies from cinnamon to cinnamon-buff. The two *Micrarionta* species have the familiar turban shape of the common garden snail, while the blunt-top snail has a more elongated profile. One species of stiletto fly (*Studia Dipterologica*) is found only on SNI (Holston and Irwin 2005).

Birds

The 1988 amendment to the Fish and Wildlife Conservation Act mandated the USFWS to “identify species, subspecies, and populations of all migratory non-game birds that, without additional conservation actions, are likely to become candidates for listing under the ESA of 1973.” These species, subspecies, and populations are called Birds of Conservation Concern (BCC).

The double-crested cormorant (*Phalacrocorax auritus*) is the most numerous and most widely distributed species of the six North American cormorants. Double-crested cormorants have increased dramatically in coastal regions of California and Oregon because of reduced human disturbance, reduced levels of marine pollutants in southern California, and recent use of artificial nesting areas in San Francisco Bay and Columbia River estuaries (Gress et al. 1973;

Carter et al. 1992). The southern California population has still not recovered to historical levels (Weseloh et al. 1999). The breeding population of double-crested cormorants was estimated to be 1,191 individuals on nearby Santa Barbara Island in 1991 (Carter et al. 1992). In 2012, a single double-crested cormorant nest (and chick) was documented on Vizcaino Point.

Brandt's cormorant is endemic to North America, where it occurs only in marine and estuarine environments. It breeds along the West Coast of North America, reaching Alaska in the north and Mexico in the south. In the main part of its range, from California to Washington, its life history and populations are tied to the rich upwelling associated with the California Current. In the non-breeding season, when the effects of this current diminish, populations redistribute along the coast in concert with changing water and feeding conditions. Current breeding populations within the SCB occur on SNI and Santa Barbara Island. SNI has one of the largest breeding colonies in California, estimated at 5,000 breeding pairs in 2006. In 2013, the Brandt's cormorant population increased to 6,958 nests.

Pelagic cormorants have also recently been identified as nesting on SNI, with 7 nests observed in 2012, approximately 12 nests in 2013, and 18 nests suspected in 2014.

The California brown pelican has been delisted from the federal ESA and the California Endangered Species Act (CESA). A petition to delist the California brown pelican from the list of endangered or threatened species under the ESA was recorded in December 2005, which resulted in a delisting of the brown pelican in November 2009. According to the USFWS, "the population has remained stable for at least 20 years within its entire range" (USFWS 2007b).

The California brown pelican is one of two subspecies of brown pelicans residing in the United States and breeds along the Pacific coast from the Channel Islands to Mexico. Their number has increased recently at the two primary nesting colonies in the Channel Islands (West Anacapa and Santa Barbara Island) in southern California, following severe pre-1975 declines primarily due to eggshell thinning from marine pollutants (Anderson et al. 1975; Anderson and Gress 1983; Carter et al. 1992; USFWS 2007b). Breeding success is still low and limited recovery may involve immigration of birds out of Mexico. Although California populations have recovered substantially from previous declines, they continue to show inter-annual variation in productivity as related to prey availability (Anderson et al. 1982). Approximately 12,000 California brown pelicans breed in southern California and this represents nearly 12 percent of the western subspecies (Kushlan et al. 2002). The SCB provides extensive breeding and foraging territory for the California brown pelican including a large breeding population on Santa Barbara Island. California brown pelicans have not been documented nesting on SNI.

In May 2006, during surveys sponsored by the CDFG (now CDFW), 43 pelican nests were discovered on Prince Island near San Miguel Island. This is the first pelican nesting activity recorded at this location since 1939 (CDFG 2006). In 2006, a nesting colony was found for the first time on Middle Anacapa Island, and breeders were observed on East Anacapa for the second time since 1928 (UCSC CIES 2006). Breeding populations on Santa Barbara and Anacapa islands have increased annually since 2000 and are approaching 7,000 breeding pairs (CINP 2005). Nests have also been found recently on San Clemente Island. The DoN has conducted long-term monitoring on SNI, tracking population trends and roosting habitat; approximately 5,000 birds currently roost on the island (Capitolo et al. 2007). However, surveys have not occurred regularly since the delisting.

Cassin's auklet populations, like other auklets and murrelets in California, have declined and several historic colonies have disappeared altogether, mainly from predation (Manuwal and Thorensen 1993). On SNI, small numbers of Cassin's auklets have been observed in nearshore waters year round, however they are not known to nest on SNI.

Rhinoceros auklets, a medium-sized auk, closely related to puffins (*Fratercula*), breeds along the Pacific coast of North America from the Aleutian Islands, Alaska, south to southern California (Gaston and Dechesne 1996). The current status of southern California breeding populations is not well known and is likely restricted to the northern Channel Islands. California numbers

remain low; the most recent counts estimate approximately 1,700 individuals now breeding in California (Carter et al. 1992). Small numbers of rhinoceros auklets are year round residents in waters adjacent to SNI, however they are not known to nest on SNI.

Scripps's murrelets (previously known as Xantus's murrelets) populations persist in very low numbers throughout their range. About 2,000-5,000 individuals of the breeding population are documented in southern California. The world population of Scripps's murrelets is concentrated in four major breeding colonies. Santa Barbara Island and Islas Los Coronados support the great majority of Scripps's murrelet in southern California and northern Baja California. The species has been extirpated on some of the Baja California islands by introduced cats and other predators, and it is threatened on other islands.

The most recent Scripps's murrelets population estimates for southern California are 1,544 breeding individuals at Santa Barbara Island (Carter et al. 1992). On SNI, Scripps's murrelets are perennial visitors in nearshore waters around the island. Surveys were done for nesting Scripps' murrelets in the 1980s as well as in 2014, with no murrelets identified. Additional surveys will be done in 2015 to survey the southern half of SNI, which was not completed during 2014. However, nesting is not suspected as SNI does not seem to have the appropriate nesting habitat for this species.

The pigeon guillemot is found along rocky coastlines between Alaska and California. This alcid nests in burrows or in rock cavities, mostly on small islands that provide protection from predators. A significant population and new nesting areas have been found recently in southern California, although higher numbers may reflect both better survey techniques and population increases (Carter et al. 1992). Unlike other alcids that fly 32 to 54 nm (60 to 100 km) out to sea to find fish schools, the pigeon guillemot stays close to the rocky coast and searches for fish prey in relatively shallow waters and within approximately 5.4 nm (10 km) of their nest. The estimated population of this species is about 235,000, with the largest breeding concentrations on Farallon Island, California. The most current population estimate for the SCB is 284 breeding individuals at Santa Barbara Island (Carter et al. 1992). This species is not known to nest on SNI.

In the SCB, the ashy storm-petrel is known to breed on Santa Catalina, Santa Barbara and San Clemente Island. The majority of the ashy storm-petrel population breeds in coastal and island areas of central and southern California (McChesney et al. 2000; Ainley et al. 1995). Nearly 1,500 breeding individuals were documented on Santa Barbara Island in 1992 (Carter et al. 1992) and 2,252 breeding birds or about 1,126 nests in 1996. Breeding populations on San Clemente Island and Santa Catalina Island have not been accurately enumerated since Carter et al. (1992), and their current status remains unknown as of the date of this research. The rare sightings at SNI have been of storm-petrels either foraging or resting in nearshore waters of the island, with no nesting documented. Table 3-8 shows the special status avian species and their use on SNI.

Table 3-8. Special status avian species and their use on or offshore of San Nicolas Island.

Common Name (Scientific Name)	Status*	Use of San Nicolas Island
ANATIDAE (DUCK, GEESE, AND SWANS)		
brant (<i>Branta bernicla</i>)	BSSC	Transient, rare spring migrant and extremely rare fall migrant
GAVIIDAE (LOONS)		
common loon (<i>Gavia immer</i>)	BSSC	Winter visitor: Summer visitor, extremely rare
DIOMEDEIDAE (ALBATROSSES)		
Laysan albatross (<i>Phoebastria immutabilis</i>)	BCC	Transient, extremely rare
PROCELLARIIDAE (SHEARWATERS AND PETRELS)		
pink-footed shearwater (<i>Puffinus creatopus</i>)	BSSC, PIF	Summer visitor, common
HYDROBATIDAE (STORM-PETRELS)		

Table 3-8. Special status avian species and their use on or offshore of San Nicolas Island.

Common Name (Scientific Name)	Status*	Use of San Nicolas Island
ashy storm-petrel (<i>Oceanodroma homochroa</i>)	ESA Candidate, BSSC, PIF	Transient, extremely rare
black storm-petrel (<i>Oceanodroma melania</i>)	BSSC	Transient, extremely rare
PELECANIDAE (PELICANS)		
California brown pelican (<i>Pelecanus occidentalis californicus</i>)	Federally and State Delisted, CFP	Resident, abundant, historically breeds on SNI
ACCIPITRIDAE (KITES, EAGLES AND HAWKS)		
bald eagle (<i>Haliaeetus leucocephalus</i>)	BCC, SE, PIF, CFP	Winter visitor, uncommon, extirpated
northern harrier (<i>Circus cyaneus</i>)	BSSC	Winter visitor, uncommon
FALCONIDAE (FALCONS)		
peregrine falcon (<i>Falco peregrinus</i>)	Recovered, BCC, SE, CFP, PIF	Resident, uncommon
prairie falcon (<i>Falco mexicanus</i>)	BSSC, BCC	Transient, extremely rare fall migrant
CHARADRIIDAE (LAPWINGS AND PLOVERS)		
western snowy plover (<i>Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus</i>)	FT, BSSC, PIF	Resident, common, breeds on SNI
mountain plover (<i>Charadrius montanus</i>)	BCC, BSSC, PIF	Winter resident, uncommon
HAEMATOPODIDAE (OYSTERCATCHERS)		
black oystercatcher (<i>Haematopus bachmani</i>)	BSSC, PIF	Resident, uncommon, breeds on SNI
SCOLOPACIDAE (SANDPIPERS, PHALAROPES, AND ALLIES)		
whimbrel (<i>Numenius phaeopus</i>)	PIF	Winter visitor: Summer visitor, rare
long-billed curlew (<i>Numenius americanus</i>)	BCC, PIF	Winter visitor, rare
marbled godwit (<i>Limosa fedoa</i>)	BCC, PIF	Winter visitor, common: Summer visitor, uncommon
red knot (<i>Calidris canutus</i>)	PIF	Transient, extremely rare fall migrant
short-billed dowitcher (<i>Limnodromus griseus</i>)	PIF	Transient, rare fall migrant: Transient, extremely rare spring migrant
LARIDAE (GULLS, TERNS AND SKIMMERS)		
Caspian tern (<i>Hydroprogne caspia</i>)	BCC	Transient, extremely rare
royal tern (<i>Thalasseus maximus</i>)	BSSC	Winter visitor, common: Summer visitor, uncommon
elegant tern (<i>Thalasseus elegans</i>)	BCC, BSSC	Transient, extremely rare
black skimmer (<i>Rhynchops niger</i>)	BCC, BSSC, PIF	Transient, extremely rare
ALCIDAE (MURRELETS AND AUKLETS)		
Scripps' murrelet (<i>Synthliboramphus hypoleucus</i>)	ESA candidate, BCC, ST, PIF	Perennial visitor, extremely rare
Cassin's auklet (<i>Ptychoramphus aleuticus</i>)	BCC, BSSC, PIF	Resident, rare
rhinoceros auklet (<i>Cerorhina monocerata</i>)	BSSC	Resident, rare
CUCULIDAE (CUCKOOS)		
yellow-billed cuckoo (<i>Coccyzus americanus</i>)	BCC, SE, PIF	Transient, extremely rare
STRIGIDAE (OWLS)		
burrowing owl (<i>Athene cuicularium</i>)	BCC, BSSC, PIF	Winter visitor, uncommon
long-eared owl (<i>Asio otus</i>)	BSSC	Transient, extremely rare fall migrant
short-eared owl (<i>Asio flammeus</i>)	BSSC	Transient, extremely rare
APODIDAE (SWIFTS)		
black swift (<i>Cypseloides niger</i>)	BCC, BSSC, PIF	Transient, extremely rare spring migrant
Vaux's swift (<i>Chaetura vauxi</i>)	BSSC	Transient, extremely rare fall migrant
TROCHILIDAE (HUMMINGBIRDS)		

Table 3-8. Special status avian species and their use on or offshore of San Nicolas Island.

Common Name (Scientific Name)	Status*	Use of San Nicolas Island
Costa's hummingbird (<i>Calypte costae</i>)	BCC, PIF	Transient, extremely rare spring and fall migrant
Allen's hummingbird (<i>Selasphorus sasin</i>)	BCC, PIF	Transient, rare spring migrant: Transient, extremely rare fall migrant
PICIDAE (WOODPECKERS)		
Lewis's woodpecker (<i>Melanerpes lewis</i>)	BCC, PIF	Transient, extremely rare
TYRANNIDAE (TYRANT FLYCATCHERS)		
olive-sided flycatcher (<i>Contopus cooperi</i>)	BCC, BSSC	Transient, rare
willow flycatcher (<i>Empidonax traillii</i>)	SE	Transient, rare
vermillion flycatcher (<i>Pyrocephalus rubinus</i>)	BSSC	Transient, extremely rare fall migrant
LANIIDAE (SHRIKES)		
loggerhead shrike (<i>Lanius ludovicianus</i>)	BCC, BSSC, PIF	Winter visitor, rare
HIRUNDINIDAE (MARTINS AND SWALLOWS)		
purple martin (<i>Progne subis</i>)	BSSC	Transient, extremely rare fall migrant
MIMIDAE (MOCKINGBIRDS AND THRASHERS)		
Bendire's thrasher (<i>Toxostoma bendirei</i>)	BCC, BSSC, BLMS	Transient, extremely rare
PARULIDAE (WOOD WARBLERS)		
Lucy's warbler (<i>Oreothlypis luciae</i>)	BCC, BSSC	Transient, extremely rare
yellow warbler (<i>Dendroica petechia</i>)	BSSC	Transient, common
yellow-breasted chat (<i>Icteria virens</i>)	BSSC	Transient, uncommon fall migrant: Transient, rare spring migrant
EMBERIZIDAE (TOWHEES AND SPARROWS)		
green-tailed towhee (<i>Pipilo chlorurus</i>)	BCC	Transient, rare
spotted towhee (<i>Pipilo maculatus</i>)	BCC	Transient, uncommon: Winter visitor, rare
black-chinned sparrow (<i>Spizella atrogularis</i>)	BCC, PIF	Transient, extremely rare fall migrant
Savannah sparrow (<i>Passerculus sandwichensis</i>)	Depends on subspecies	Transient, common fall migrant: Winter visitor, uncommon
grasshopper sparrow (<i>Ammodramus savannarum</i>)	BSSC	Transient, extremely rare
song sparrow (<i>Melospiza melodia</i>)	Depends on subspecies	Transient, rare
CARDINALIDAE (GROSBEAKS, BUNTINGS, AND ALLIES)		
summer tanager (<i>Piranga rubra</i>)	BSSC	Transient, extremely rare
ICTERIDAE (BLACKBIRDS AND ORIOLES)		
tri-colored blackbird (<i>Agelaius tricolor</i>)	BCC, BSSC, PIF	Transient, extremely rare fall migrant
yellow-headed blackbird (<i>Xanthocephalus xanthocephalus</i>)	BSSC	Transient, uncommon
FRINGILLIDAE (FINCHES AND ALLIES)		
Lawrence's goldfinch (<i>Spinus lawrencei</i>)	BCC, PIF	Transient, rare

BCC = Bird of Conservation Concern (USFWS 2008), BSSC = California Bird Species of Special Concern (CDFG 2008c), FT = Federally Threatened, SE = State Endangered, ST = State Threatened (CDFG 2010)

Inventary of species based on Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History September 2000 Birds Species Checklist and 2013 surveys (HDR 2013b).

PIF: DoD Partners in Flight, CFP=Fully Protected;

Mammals

All marine mammal species that occur on or around SNI are protected under the Marine Mammal Protection Act (MMPA). For more information regarding the marine mammals that occur at SNI see *Section 3.7.4: Marine Mammals*.

One special status mammal occurs on SNI, the San Nicolas Island fox (*Urocyon littoralis dickeyi*), listed by the State of California as threatened, and discussed below.

San Nicolas Island Fox (*Urocyon littoralis dickeyi*)

The island fox was listed as state threatened in 1971. It is restricted to the Channel Islands and is endemic to the region (Bunn et al. 2007), where an endemic subspecies occurs on all but two of the islands (Anacapa and Santa Barbara). San Nicolas Island foxes are omnivorous, foraging on insects, vegetation, mice, and seasonally available bird eggs. Island foxes are generally monogamous, and breed only once per year. Pairs are together frequently beginning in January; they mate in late February to early March, and pups are born from late April through early May. Litter size ranges from one to five pups, but two or three is average. Pups emerge from the den at about one month of age and undergo a period of extended parental care.

In early 2000, foxes on SNI (*U. l. dickeyi*) and those on San Clemente Island (*U. l. clemente*) were considered to be the only subspecies maintaining viable populations (Suckling and Garcelon 2000). The four remaining subspecies suffered marked declines in the mid to late 1990s caused by predation and canine distemper, and were listed as federally endangered. Those populations are now recovering.

The San Nicolas Island fox is a fairly common resident of terrestrial habitats across the island. The San Nicolas Island fox population has been monitored annually since 2000 on three permanent grids established by Institute for Wildlife Studies (IWS) (Hudgens and Garcelon 2014) (Map 3-10). The long-term fox sampling (trapping) grids cover three distinct habitat types representing the dominant floral communities on SNI, including coastal scrub and inland dune habitats (Redeye grid), coastal scrub (Tuft's grid), and grassland and coastal scrub (Skyline grid).

Beginning in 2014, the fox population survey method was altered to incorporate the use of mini-ladder grids, such as those used during post-feral cat eradication monitoring (Ramsey et al 2010; Jolley et al. 2012; Hanson et al. 2010). The smaller grids provide more refined information on population status and distribution by accounting for habitat changes that have occurred over time, and by sampling previously under-represented locations such as the coreopsis scrub and beach zones.

Since regular monitoring began in 2000, the population has been mainly stable, often with densities among the highest recorded on any of the Channel Islands, ranging from 15.8 to 26.3 foxes/km² (Schmidt et al. 2007). However, while individual foxes appear to be in good health, the population currently seems to be in the midst of a sustained decline which began in 2010. The island-wide population estimate in 2009 was 619; in 2012, it was 460; and in 2013, it was 341 individuals (Hudgens and Garcelon 2014). The decline may be due to negative density-dependence causing the population to correct after exceeding carrying capacity, or may be a result of extended drought conditions limiting resources. However, a disease outbreak has not been ruled out.

Serology results from 2013 indicated that 62 percent of tested foxes had measurable titers for canine adenovirus; 30 percent were high titers indicating recent exposure. None of the 27 previously unvaccinated foxes tested positive for canine distemper virus, but 7 had titers of 1:8 but <1:16 which were considered "suspect" (Hudgens and Garcelon 2014). Canine parvovirus was not detected in 2013, though it was detected in 16 percent of 2009 samples, and in nearly 99 percent of samples from 2001 through 2003.

While the San Nicolas Island fox population is not currently affected by factors that have caused other fox populations to decline, such as canine distemper disease and predation by golden eagles (*Aquila chrysaetos*), its insular nature, lack of resistance to canine distemper and other diseases, high densities, and low genetic variability increase the vulnerability of this subspecies to decline (Roemer et al. 2004; USFWS 2004b; Clifford et al. 2006; Schmidt et al. 2007).

Reptiles

Island Night Lizard (*Xantusia riversiana*)

The island night lizard (*Xantusia riversiana*) is a medium-sized, cryptically patterned lizard endemic to the Channel Islands, where it occurs on SNI, Santa Barbara Island, and San Clemente Island. The island night lizard is the most morphologically distinct of the endemic vertebrates on the Channel Islands, indicating a long period of isolation from the mainland (Bezy et al. 1980). Island night lizards are sedentary and have small home ranges, averaging about 183 ft² (56 m²). This species is active primarily from March to September, with timing of activities largely dependent on mild to warm temperatures (DoN 2005). The island night lizard is omnivorous, eating insects, plants, and small mammals. The lizards breed in April, and young are born in September (Goldberg and Bezy 1974). Lizard numbers vary greatly depending on available habitat and are typically associated with defined areas (Map 3-11). Grasslands that cover much of the eastern mesa support few or no lizards, while the mixed shrub communities support moderate numbers of island night lizards. The highest island night lizard densities are associated with cacti and boxthorn (*Opuntia* and *Lycium* spp.) (Smith 1993; Fellers et al. 1998).

Fellers et al. (1998) estimated the island night lizard population on SNI to be about 15,300 lizards. A population survey was done in 2012 and 2013, however data is still being analyzed. On the eastern part of the island, they occur from the low beach terraces on the north and south sides, to the highest elevations at the top of the mesa overlooking the southern escarpment. In contrast, island night lizards on the west side of the island are essentially restricted to cobble-driftwood near Red Eye Beach. However, in 2014, island night lizards were found within selected vegetated areas in the Red Eye area. Their distribution on the west side of the island may have expanded from Red Eye, or these small populations may have previously existed and were undocumented. These habitats were surveyed more extensively in 2015. The broad grasslands that cover much of the eastern mesa support few or no lizards. Mixed shrub communities, whether on the low marine terrace on the north and south sides of the island, in some canyons, or on top of the mesa, support moderate numbers of island night lizards. Predators of the island night lizard include the San Nicolas Island fox and feral cats (before their removal from the island). Introduced southern alligator lizards may compete for habitat and food, and may depredate young island night lizards. The USFWS delisted the island night lizard on May 1, 2014. The species will be monitored for nine years post-delisting, to ensure its habitat quality and quantity remains, and the population and recruitment remain stable.

3.9 Invasive Plants

Executive Order 13112 defines an invasive species as “an alien species whose introduction does or is likely to cause economic or environmental harm or harm to human health.” Non-native invasive plants pose a serious threat to native ecosystems. The relatively mild climate throughout much of southern California provides suitable conditions for invasive plants from other areas to invade native ecosystems. Invasive plants can alter ecosystem processes, transport disease, interfere with reproduction, or cause cascading impacts to native animal populations, potentially impacting multiple trophic levels.

Whether introduced unknowingly by early settlers 200 years ago, or more recently by global commerce and travel, the spread of non-native invasive plants throughout California is reaching levels in some cases that pose long-term, far-reaching threats to ecosystems. Without the natural enemies of their original habitats, non-native invasive species can spread rapidly and out-compete California native plant species, thereby degrading natural ecosystem processes. The introduction and spread of non-native plants has profoundly affected the composition of plant communities and has threatened the status of individual species on SNI. Historic land uses prior to Navy occupation have certainly contributed to the majority of non-native invasive plant introductions on SNI, while some have likely been imported inadvertently with materials and equipment used in Navy construction projects. Most of the non-native taxa are native to the Mediterranean region (Europe, North Africa, and west Asia) or Australia (Junak 2008).

In 2008, known flora of SNI consisted of 278 taxa. Of these, 141 had been introduced. Of all the Channel Islands, SNI has the highest percentage (51 percent) of introduced plant species (Junak 2008). In contrast, 19 non-native species were documented during the period from 1890–1899. The SNI non-native plant eradication program is growing in capability to match the demands of controlling rapidly spreading species such as *Brassica tournefortii* and *Euphorbia terracina*. Contracted non-native plant control treatments on SNI have been conducted from 2001 to 2015, with supplemental treatments by Navy staff (Agri Chemical and Supply Inc. 2014a). A weed management plan was developed in 2014 (Appendix K); it replaces a Resource Conservation District Weed Eradication Plan developed with the support of the USSCS, and to supplement an alien (invasive) plant removal plan developed by Navy natural resource staff in the early 1990s. The weed management plan identifies the top invasive species for treatment and will be revised with new information and additional species, as needed.

3.10 Invasive Wildlife Damage

The introduction of non-native rodents, especially black rats, Norway rats, or house mice, could have a devastating impact on the island ecosystem. Invasion by these species could severely impact ground nesting seabirds, resident land birds, and the endemic Channel Islands deer mouse (DoN 2005). Trapping incidental to other activities (hanta virus studies, deer mouse population monitoring, removal of mice from living quarters, site specific rodent trapping for rats) has not revealed any rodents except for the native deer mouse. However, shipwrecks, a known route for introducing rodents on islands, have been documented.

The invasive terrestrial invertebrate species that occur on SNI may include, but are not limited to decollate snails, European garden snails, and Argentine ants (*Linepithema humile*). At least two introduced non-native snail species, the European garden snail and the predatory decollate snail, are present on SNI and may pose a threat to the small remnant population of terrestrial land snails on SNI. Argentine ants also occur on SNI and are an invasive non-native species that are a known threat to endemic wildlife populations and also prey upon other ant species.

The invasive terrestrial vertebrate species that occur on SNI may include, but are not limited to chukar and other non-native birds. Established populations of chukar are present on SNI;

although used for hunting on the mainland, there is no hunting permitted on SNI so it may be considered an invasive species rather than a game species. Chukar may have impacts to sensitive flora and likely facilitate the dispersal of weedy plants.

To protect the island's native fauna, the Navy has funded intermittent efforts to control feral cats since the 1980s. Through funding under the Montrose restoration settlement, cat removal efforts began in June 2009, with the last remaining cats removed in 2010.

Feral cats are among the most detrimental of invasive species, causing population decline, extirpation, and extinction in a diverse array of animals, including insects, reptiles, birds, and mammals (Lowe et al. 2000; Nogales et al. 2004). The effects of feral cats are particularly severe on islands (Whittaker 1998). Cats have had detrimental impacts on SNI vertebrate and invertebrate populations, including various landbirds, seabirds, the federally threatened western snowy plover, the San Nicolas Island deer mouse, the state threatened San Nicolas Island fox, and the island night lizard. Considering the limited resources available for vertebrate predators within an island ecosystem, competition between native and non-native species is a considerable concern. All efforts should be made to ensure cats and other harmful species are not transported to the island in the future. To aid in this effort, a biosecurity plan (Tetra Tech, Inc. 2011) and Naval Instruction (NBVCINST 5090.14 [20 May 2014]) were created to develop and execute measures to reduce the chances of any future introductions.

4.0 Natural Resource Management Objectives and Strategies

4.1 Ecosystem Approach

Specific Concerns

- There are a number of known large-scale threats to both terrestrial and marine environments that are difficult to address for any one jurisdiction in isolation. Examples are: disease, climate change, sea level rise, invasive species, air pollution, and oil pollution.
- Observed and anticipated changes to the environment from these large-scale threats have and will continue to contribute to shifts in habitat and community distribution and structure that require consideration when developing management strategies.
- The complexity of island communities and the difficulty of dealing with this complexity argues for the use of management indicator (emphasis or focus) species to provide a basis for decision-making, and these have not been identified by agreement within the Navy or among agencies. Since it is impossible to measure and monitor the effects of management practices on all species, a suite of processes and species should be identified to serve as ecosystem indicators. The challenge of managers is to determine which indicators characterize the system yet are simple enough to be effectively monitored and modeled.
- Plant community or habitat metrics for SNI are not identified, such as: the mix of expected species when a site is healthy or damaged; soil condition; or the status of a management focus species.
- SNI continues to be in a State of recovery from historic grazing pressure which resulted in evident soil losses and long-term change in plant communities.
- The current long-term marine ecosystem monitoring program is beginning to inform managers on habitat health and threats in intertidal and subtidal habitats, and is progressing in terrestrial habitats, but continued program funding in this area is required.

Current Management

Ecosystem management became a national initiative in the 1990s as a conceptual model in reaction to deficiencies of the more traditional approaches that were too narrow in scope. An interagency MOU was signed by DoD along with 14 other agencies in an attempt to create a more consistent approach to ecosystem management among federal agencies, enhance coordination, and to encourage more regional ecosystem initiatives (CEQ et al. 1995). The DoD's Ecosystem Initiative states that "ecosystem management is a process that considers the environment as a complex system functioning as a whole, not as a collection of parts, and recognizes that people and their communities are part of the whole" (Keystone Center 1996; Benton et al. 2008). This approach shall take a long-term view of human activities, including military uses, and biological resources as part of the same environment.

This INRMP complies with federal guidelines regarding adoption of an ecosystem approach to land and water management. The Navy is required to ensure that ecosystem management is the basis for all management of its land and waters (OUSD Memo of 08 August 1994, *Implementation of Ecosystem Management in the Department of Defense*). In addition, the Sikes Act states that the INRMP goals “shall be to maintain or develop an ecosystem-based conservation program...” DoDINST 4715.03 Environmental Conservation Program (11 March 2011) requires that U.S. Navy installations incorporate ecosystem management’s “ten guiding principles.” These principles and guidelines are generally acceptable to academicians and practitioners alike, and they provide more specific guidelines to installation managers. It also provides a DoD definition of ecosystem management as, “a goal-driven approach to managing natural and cultural resources that supports present and future mission requirements; preserves ecosystem integrity; is at a scale compatible with natural process; is cognizant of nature’s time frames; recognizes social and economic viability within functioning ecosystems; is adaptable to complex changing requirements; and is realized through effective partnerships among private, local, state, tribal, and federal interests.”

Additionally, SNI waters are considered EFH by NMFS for some managed fisheries. The Magnuson-Stevens Fishery Conservation and Management Act assigns NMFS the responsibility for identifying EFH for all species which are federally managed, and for determining whether projects or activities adversely impact EFH zones. According to this Act, EFH is defined as those waters and substrate necessary to fish for spawning, breeding, feeding, or growth to maturity. Around SNI, there are three groups of managed fishes under the Magnuson-Stevens Fishery Conservation and Management Act: groundfish, highly migratory species, and coastal pelagic species.

The ten guiding principles of ecosystem management in DoD are as follows (DoDINST 4715.03, 18 March 2011):

1. Maintain and improve the sustainability and native biodiversity of ecosystems.
2. Administer with consideration of ecological units and timeframes.
3. Support sustainable human activities.
4. Develop a vision of ecosystem health.
5. Develop priorities and reconcile conflicts.
6. Develop coordinated approaches to work toward ecosystem health.
7. Rely on the best science and data available.
8. Use benchmarks to monitor and evaluate outcomes.
9. Use adaptive management.
10. Implement through installation plans and programs.

Finally, the Navy directs through OPNAVINST 5090.1D that ecosystem-based management shall include: a shift from single species to multiple species conservation; formation of partnerships necessary to consider and manage ecosystems that cross boundaries; and the use of best available scientific information and adaptive management techniques.

Natural resources are managed with an ecosystem approach; however, funding (Environmental Program Requirements [EPR]) categories tend to be species-based and generally within annual to three-year budget cycles.

Current natural resource management at SNI includes but is not limited to the following activities:

- Development of the NBVC Point Mugu Range Capabilities Master Plan to examine land use on a broader scale;
- Participate in the Channel Islands symposia;
- Support monitoring and research on seabird populations;

- Support monitoring and research for aerial and land-based marine mammal surveys;
- Collaborate and participate with USFWS for western snowy plover monitoring and landbird surveys;
- Collaborate with the USGS for island night lizard monitoring and development of long-term vegetation monitoring plots;
- Support cooperative agreements with universities for research;
- Support research from non-profit scientific organizations such as the Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History and the Santa Barbara Botanic Garden; and
- Collaborate as a steward with the BLM to manage the offshore rocks of SNI and Begg Rock that are included within the jurisdiction of the CCNM.

Current research and monitoring efforts are also generally driven by the need for impact assessment under the ESA or NEPA. Past management techniques have used single species management with the assumption that protection of one species will act as an umbrella to protect other similar species in the environment.

Assessment of Current Management

A premise of this INRMP is that management on a project-by-project basis is inadequate to manage ecosystem integrity because the scale and time frame associated with projects is unlikely to consider all the resources, processes, and interdependencies that may be affected. At the same time, viewing issues on an ecosystem level may allow some important management concerns to fall through the cracks.

Generally, the idea of an ecosystem approach is to identify a process or a species that indicates the “health” of a system, but there are differing definitions of ecosystem health. Ideally the suite of indicators should represent key information about structure, function, and composition of the ecosystem (Dale and Beyeler 2001). For example, to determine the energy flow of an ecosystem, one might decide that the number of trophic levels would be a good indicator to determine “health” of the system.

One goal of this plan should be to prevent species and processes that are currently healthy from becoming threatened and unbalancing the ecosystem. Thus, some healthy processes and species populations must be monitored and managed.

The general synopsis of the elements to be included in this INRMP to promote an ecosystem approach for natural resource management at SNI is: habitat first, use of focal management species, partnerships, and adaptive management.

Management Strategy

Objective: Conserve ecosystem resources by planning and acting at ecologically meaningful spatial scales and time frames.

- I. Maintain and improve the sustainability and integrity of the ecosystem by planning and managing at key ecological scales: regional, island-wide, by species group and habitat needs, and by management focus species representing different scales used by wildlife or different ecological functions (such as migratory species support versus species that are tied to a very specific and localized set of habitat conditions). Implement an approach to terrestrial and aquatic management based on habitats. Refer to *Section 4.6: Invasive Species* for more information concerning biosecurity and invasive species objectives and strategies.
 - A. Develop, implement, and enforce biosecurity and invasive species objectives and strategies.
 - B. Ensure that habitats are able to sustain viable populations of special status species.

1. Ensure habitats have all essential elements to maintain productivity and soil stability.
 2. Avoid or minimize disturbance outside of a site's natural ability to recover.
- II. Ensure endemic species are self-sustaining in order to protect biodiversity and prevent future listings under the ESA.
- A. Develop a geo-spatial framework of priority management emphasis areas for management focus species. These areas are designed such that threatened and endangered species are provided for with a minimum of conflict with the military mission.
 - B. Define the habitat needs of management focus species, considering the full range of plant community composition and structural conditions found historically in the area, rather than any one set of habitat conditions.
 - C. Investigate use of management indicator species to assist managers in determining that the ecosystem is properly functioning and that natural biodiversity is provided for.
 - D. Work to stabilize soils and slopes to protect remnant habitat or sedimentation of downslope ecosystems.
- III. Support any research on effects from long-term regional change including but not limited to climate change.
- IV. Participate in or ensure consistency with regional monitoring protocols in order to derive additional interpretive power from Navy data sets.
- A. Support cooperative research ventures with schools, universities, and non-profit scientific research organizations.
- V. Rely on the best science and data available to collect and analyze data for SNI's ecosystems.
- VI. Apply sustainability principles to the management of habitats, species, and ecological functions on SNI by identifying resource-specific best practices similar to what has been done for energy and water in the built environment (*Section 5.1.4*) using Sustainable Sites Initiative (SSI) principles and following the SNI landscaping plan.
- VII. Use construction siting, materials, and methods that promote biotic communities to the fullest extent possible.
- A. Ensure for design review by engineers, water quality specialists, and marine biologists at all major phases of intertidal and subtidal construction project development, if proposed.
 - B. The majority of the island is not suitable for shoreline armoring; however, at a few select locations armoring may be warranted to protect coastal infrastructure. Design substrates that are amenable to occupation by intertidal and subtidal biota during the refurbishment and construction of new armored shorelines as implemented in the Military Construction Projects (MILCON) P-793 Navy Lighterage Project.
 - C. Design against the occupation of shoreline stabilizing structures by terrestrial predators that can negatively impact the success of endangered species programs.

4.2 Managing the Physical and Chemical Environment

4.2.1 Water Resources and Water Quality

Specific Concerns

- The inland surface waters and groundwater resources are vulnerable.
- The expansion of the RO plant raised compliance concerns from the brine discharge line into the ASBS.
- Storm water runoff and erosion has the potential to degrade SNI nearshore water quality, and these waters surrounding SNI and Begg Rock are designated as an ASBS by the SWRCB. The ASBS water quality designation is another level of water quality protection for which sedimentation into ocean waters should be considered an important priority.
- SNI's renowned, abundant marine life requires consideration in daily management for compliance with CWA requirements, as well as for NEPA and Magnuson-Stevens Act compliance.
- Development and maintenance of facilities can increase erosion, affect water quality, and disturb sensitive species which inhabit these areas. Storm water management approaches that maintain water quality are most important in the interface between the water and terrestrial resources.

Current Management

The Los Angeles Regional Water Quality Control Board (LARWQCB) has jurisdiction over water quality on San Nicolas Island and Begg Rock. San Nicolas Island and Begg Rock are analyzed as part of the LARWQCB San Pedro Channel Islands Hydrologic Unit (LARWQCB 1994). According to the Basin Plan, the existing beneficial uses for the inland surface waters of SNI are wildlife habitat and rare, threatened, or endangered species. Potential beneficial uses for inland surface waters of SNI include: municipal and domestic water supply, water contact recreation, and warm freshwater habitat. Due to the isolation of SNI, limited access, and island operations, potential contaminants of the watershed are limited; therefore, the LARWQCB has not developed water quality objectives for inland surface waters island watercourses. The existing beneficial use for the groundwater of SNI is municipal and domestic supply. The potential beneficial use for the groundwater of SNI is industrial service supply. The LARWQCB has established the following groundwater quality objectives for SNI: Total Dissolved Solids - 1,100 milligram per liter (mg/L), Sulfate - 150 mg/L, Chloride - 350 mg/L (LARWQCB 1994).

The beneficial use designations for coastal features of SNI include navigation, water contact recreation, non-contact water recreation, commercial and sport fishing, marine habitat, rare-threatened or endangered species, shellfish harvesting, wildlife habitat, and preservation of biological habitats. For Begg Rock they are the same, except for navigation. The wildlife habitat beneficial use for both SNI and the Begg Rock is intended to support pinniped haul out areas. The potential beneficial uses for the coastal features of SNI and the Begg Rock nearshore zone are spawning, reproduction, and/or early development.

The waters surrounding SNI and Begg Rock to a distance of one nautical mile offshore or to the 300-foot isobath, whichever is greater, have been designated as an ASBS. The ASBS designation is intended to protect the species or biological communities, because of their value or fragility, from an undesirable alteration in natural water quality. Natural water quality conditions must be preserved and maintained to the extent practicable (Water Resources Control Board and California Regional Water Quality Control Board Administrative Procedures, 24 September 1970, Sec. XI and Miscellaneous Rev. 7-9/1/72). CDFW is responsible for

management of marine resources in these areas. No site-specific regulations have been established for this ASBS, but the following general regulations apply:

- Discharge of elevated temperature wastes in a manner that would alter water quality conditions from those occurring naturally is prohibited.
- Discharge of discrete, point-source sewage or industrial process wastes in a manner that would alter water quality conditions from those occurring naturally is prohibited.
- Discharge of waste from nonpoint sources, including but not limited to storm water runoff, silt, and urban runoff, will be controlled to the extent practical. In control programs for waste from nonpoint sources, Regional Boards will give high priority to areas tributary to ASBSs.
- The California Ocean Plan, and hence the designation of ASBSs, is not applicable to vessel wastes, the control of dredging, or the disposal of dredging spoil.

The State Board adopted the Water Quality Control Plan for Ocean Waters of California (State Board Resolution No. 74-57) in 1974 and amended this plan in 1988 (State Board Resolution No. 88-111) and 1990 (State Board Resolution No. 90-27). This amended plan, which is referred to as the California Ocean Plan, establishes beneficial uses and water quality objectives for waters of the Pacific Ocean adjacent to the California coast outside of enclosed bays, estuaries, and coastal lagoons. The California Ocean Plan also prescribes effluent quality requirements and management principles for waste discharges and specifies certain waste discharge prohibitions. Prohibitions include discharges of specific hazardous substances and sludge, bypasses of untreated wastes, and discharges. Waste discharges to ASBS are prohibited unless the State Board finds that there would be no adverse impact to beneficial uses. Implementation of the SWPPP, SPCC and a soil erosion program greatly reduces potential for contamination and erosion influences on the water quality within the nearshore waters of SNI that are encompassed by the ASBS designation. The quality of surface and groundwater is also enhanced when soil erosion and contamination are reduced. Management of storm water runoff is addressed in *Section 5.9: Storm Water Management*. At the SNI and Begg Rock ASBS, discharges incidental to military research, development, testing, and evaluation of, and training with guided missile and other weapons systems, fleet training exercises, small-scale amphibious warfare training, and special warfare training are allowed.

Wastewater Treatment Plant

Effluent discharge (amount and concentration of potential contaminants) for the SNI Wastewater Treatment Plant is governed by a Waste Discharge Requirement issued by the LARWQCB. Permanent wastewater operators perform sampling activities and monitor the facility per permit requirements. The primary method of wastewater disposal is via evaporation from a series of three oxidation ponds. Irrigation is the secondary method of disposal. Treated wastewater is sprayed over a six-acre land area, which is restricted and off-limits to personnel. A plan to meet limitations for chlorides, total dissolved solids, and several other water quality parameters as set forth under the Waste Discharge Permit for SNI is in effect.

Water Supply and Use

The seawater desalination system (RO plant), discussed in *Section 2.5.2: Utilities*, discharges under an exception and permit into the SNI ASBS, with limitations, including flow limits. The ASBS exception was adopted by the SWRCB (Resolution 90-105) in 1990, and the most recent permit (NPDES No. CA0061794) was re-issued by the LARWQCB in 2004. The Navy currently disposes of brine through subterranean infiltration fields. The Navy is in the process of assessing alternative discharge options, primarily focusing on the evaluation of an open ocean outfall.

Additionally, fresh water is delivered from off-island. A water barge can be moored near the RO desalination plant at Coast Guard Beach. The water is then offloaded through a submarine water line to a storage tank near Building 196. The second method is to deliver water tankers (trailers) on the freight barge that off loads at the pier. These two methods are expensive and used as a last resort (DoN 2005).

Freshwater wells on the northwestern part of SNI are not a source of potable water but rather provide an as-needed source of water for construction activities. Groundwater is not required to be sampled because it is a source of water for non-potable use.

Assessment of Current Management

Wastewater Treatment Plant

There have been no reported spills or upset events that resulted in the discharge of toxic or otherwise prohibited substances, including untreated or partially untreated wastewater in the SNI ASBS (Merkel and Associates, Inc. 2007b). The Navy is working on upgrading the wastewater treatment plant. Current wastewater monitoring is adequate and supports compliance with permit requirements. Additionally, a recent revision of the SWPPP was completed in 2015 which further strengthens existing BMPs and facilitates new adaptive management strategies (NBVC 2015).

Water Supply and Use

The Navy has installed one new salt water storage tank and seven salt water wells for a total of ten on Coast Guard Beach to provide an adequate supply to the RO plant. The Navy is currently in discussions with the RWQCB and the SWRCB to obtain an updated NPDES permit for brine disposal through an open ocean outfall at the RO plant on Coast Guard Beach. The Navy is also modifying the drinking water distribution system and is assessing the current status of ground water resources.

Management Strategy

Objective: Comply with applicable water quality related regulations or directives to reduce and minimize water pollutants from entering the watershed and nearshore waters.

- I. Protect the water quality of SNI waters.
 - A. Coordinate with the USACE, EPA, and LARWQCB as appropriate, with regard to restrictions or required permits for any Navy actions that may affect water resources.
 1. Continue to support BMPs for SNI that include pollutant source controls, management practices other than source controls, preventative maintenance, spill prevention and response, erosion and sediment controls, identification of storm water pollution prevention personnel, and structural controls for runoff.
 2. Continue to update and implement the SNI 2015 SWPPP and integrate into general management strategies.
 3. Continue to update and implement the SNI 2008 SPCC and integrate into general management strategies.
 4. Continue to update and complete the ASBS exception package with respect to the RO plant intended to supply fresh water to the island.
 5. Continue dry and wet season monitoring of storm drains.
 6. Continue implementation of storm water BMP for pollution prevention.
 7. Continue annual storm water reporting to the LARWQCB.

- B. Habitat protection and water quality monitoring are the primary means SNI implements to provide for marine water quality health.
 - 1. Relate the diversity and abundance of marine life to attributes of the substrate and water quality where they live, and manage substrate and water quality directly.
 - C. Implement watershed-based approaches wherever possible. The Navy has a policy on Watershed Management (OPNAV M-5090.1 [DoN 2014b]): *“Installations should apply a watershed approach when evaluating the impact of their overall activities on the quality of area water resources and address water impacts by reducing pollutant discharges. A watershed approach is an integrated holistic management strategy that addresses the condition of land areas within the entire watershed. It ensures that nonpoint sources as well as point sources of pollution are addressed. Navy water program managers should consult other media experts (e.g. natural resources, RCRA/CERCLA, and air) to fully implement the watershed approach.”*
 - D. Implement BMPs to protect and improve water quality and to prevent erosion and sedimentation from SNI land and roads into sensitive waters.
 - 1. Continue to implement BMPs for construction, training, maintenance, and other ground disturbing activities.
 - 2. Assess and monitor BMPs to ensure they are achieving their stated goals.
 - E. Comply with water quality permit requirements when required by project site size or if a project may affect wetlands or watercourses.
- II. Conserve water. Review military and non-military uses at SNI for ways to contribute to water conservation.
- A. Assess non-military uses at SNI for contributions to water conservation or impacts to water resources.
 - B. Ensure that military BMPs require that potable water not be used for landscaping.
 - C. Conserve groundwater at SNI.
 - 1. Improve the integration of natural resources professionals into sustainability planning for groundwater resources.
 - a. Facilitate early, advance project review through RSIPs, NEPA, site approval, and sustainability action plans (SAPs) for storm water management, landscaping, shoreline and in-water structures.
 - b. Go beyond pollution prevention (P2) and compliance to sustainable operations.
 - c. Expand the incorporation of sustainability principles into project scope and cost estimates, such as that reflected in the DD Form 1391.
- III. Sustain and expand long-term monitoring efforts to evaluate baseline conditions of key water quality parameters at established and representative sampling locations throughout the ASBS, building on the work of Bight 1998, 2003, and 2008.

4.2.2 Soil Conservation

Specific Concerns

- There is evidence of large-scale (island-level) soil losses resulting from historical land use practices, most likely livestock grazing and military construction activity.

- The military mission and preparedness at SNI could be impacted by ongoing erosion, as infrastructure and facilities are potentially threatened.
- Erosion control measures may be eliminated from a project as a cost-cutting measure.
- The role of biological crusts in sustaining the health of island vegetation and soils has not been described sufficiently to be integrated into decision-making.

Current Management

The USSCS (now NRCS) conducted an inventory of soil resources at SNI in 1985 (Map 3-3). Subsequently, Jayne Belnap of the USGS-Biological Resources Division conducted a study on biological crusts in 1989. In 2015, Santa Barbara Botanic Garden and Northern Arizona University collected biological crust to conduct a greenhouse study on the best conditions to increase biological soil crust biomass and growth rates.

Federal agencies must manage lands to control and prevent soil erosion and preserve natural resources by conducting surveys and implementing soil conservation measures. The Sikes Act, the Soil and Water Conservation Act, CWA, DoDINST 4715.03, and OPNAVINST 5090.1D and OPNAV M-5090.1 require BMPs for soil and water resources on federal lands. The Clean Air Act also restricts particulate matter emissions that result from soil disturbance.

Any project that may disturb the soil must go through a screening process with the Site Approval and Project Review Board (SA/PRB) process, codified in NBVC Instruction (NBVCINST) 11010.1B, to receive a site approval from local and regional Navy, and to ensure NEPA compliance. This includes any soil disturbing activities such as digging, grading, stockpiling, dumping, staging, or establishing a laydown area. As necessary, BMPs are required of the project in order to protect the soil from erosion by wind and water. This project screening process is a streamlined means for project sponsors to comply with NEPA, as well as the laws, regulations and guidelines described above.

Assessment of Current Management

Implementation of NBVCINST 11010.1B has been necessary and sufficient to avoid and minimize impacts to soil resources that may result from activities related to the military mission at SNI. The site-specific erosion control provisions as well as guidelines for site revegetation requirements provide the means to control and manage site-specific erosion at SNI. However, military construction projects at SNI need to include BMPs to control erosion as well as better oversight and follow-up to ensure conservation measures are implemented.

Soil conservation is needed to provide the ecological structure necessary for terrestrial habitats and communities to function and perform the ecosystem services that support the Navy's current use of SNI. An assessment of the health of soil resources at SNI will also contribute to further protecting and maintaining soil resources. The existing soil maps could be better integrated into land use and restoration planning. Soil maps also allow for the assessment of land and vegetation conditions and trends, based on ecological site understanding derived from such maps.

The causes of erosion at an island-wide scale are related to historical land use practices rather than current military activities; however, a need continues to develop an island-wide erosion management plan to correct ongoing problems, and to determine if restoration is a possibility.

Management Strategy

Objective: Conserve soil productivity, nutrient functioning, vegetation, wildlife habitat, and water quality by effectively implementing best management practices to prevent and control soil erosion.

- I. The first priority is to prevent, through proper planning, losses of environmental values caused by impacts to soils, biological crusts, sedimentation, or airborne particulate matter.
 - A. Soil conservation shall be considered in all site feasibility studies and project planning, design and construction. Appropriate conservation work and associated funding shall be included in project proposals and construction contracts and specifications.
 1. As per OPNAVINST 5090.1D and OPNAV M-5090.1, ensure incorporation of BMPs in the preliminary engineering, design, and construction of facilities involving ground disturbance.
 - a. Ensure enforcement of the SA/PRB requirements to prevent erosion and repair any damage that occurs during construction or maintenance activities.
 - b. Use the specific guidance for selecting BMPs as presented in the *California Storm Water Best Management Practices Handbook*, including project planning and design guides, SWPPPs, Water Pollution Control Programs preparation manuals, Construction Site BMPs Manual (Caltrans 2000), other specifications in use on island projects, and other proven techniques, with the following strategy:
 1. Minimize site disturbance;
 2. Stabilize site disturbance;
 3. Protect slopes and channels;
 4. Control site perimeter;
 5. Control internal erosion; and
 6. After construction, add source-control BMPs and treatment-control BMPs.
 - B. Minimize disturbance by locating staging areas in disturbed areas only. Staging areas should be prohibited within sensitive habitat areas. Staging areas should be delineated on the grading plans and reviewed by the resource agencies and project biological monitors prior to start of construction.
 1. Continue to ensure that NEPA planners require that construction and road maintenance projects employ BMPs to minimize soil erosion by wind and water.
 2. Evaluate the success of the BMPs that have been utilized at SNI.
 - a. Assess and evaluate storm runoff and wind erosion and its effect on particularly vulnerable areas.
 - b. Monitor BMPs in terms of:
 1. Implementation to expected specifications;
 2. Having the desired management effect; and
 3. Soundness in context of the overall management strategy.
 3. Keep informed and up-to-date on improved methods for preventing environmental impacts during maintenance activities and on revisions in laws, regulations, guidance, and policies.
 - a. Investigate the use of permeable ground cover types (e.g. gravel) to slow runoff and increase percolation.
 - C. Implement roadway improvement recommendations and investigate redirecting runway runoff to the ocean.

II. Control ongoing erosion.

- A. Conduct an island-wide soil erosion and restoration assessment to determine what sites are actively eroding, which are not, and which have potential for restoration. Consider the following:
 1. When erosion control work is deemed necessary because sites cannot revegetate on their own to their native condition, it should be prioritized according to its seriousness and potential impact to the natural resources based on the following criteria:
 - a. Safety or security, as for emergency or military vehicle access on secondary roads;
 - b. Potential for affecting high-value facilities or areas crucial to the military mission;
 - c. Likelihood of affecting a federally listed species (beneficially or otherwise), a jurisdictional Water of the U.S., or significant cultural resource;
 - d. Volume of potential soil or habitat loss due to environmental conditions such as rain or wind; and
 - e. Cost-effectiveness of the repair or control measure.
 2. Revegetation efforts will utilize occasional seed collection and broadcast activities, plantings with potted SNI plant stock, supplemental irrigation, and removal of invasive plant species. Collect native seed to use in revegetation and restoration work as needed.
- B. Assess and implement cost-effective means to reduce gully development or expansion.

III. Restore large-scale erosion as part of a long-term plan that addresses threats to natural and cultural resources island-wide, considers the risk of regulatory non-compliance under the ESA, CWA, and other laws, and examines cost-effective approaches.

IV. In tandem with other monitoring and mapping efforts, assess indicators of soil health.

- A. Soil indicators include native plant cover, litter, rock, bare ground, presence or absence of compaction, and condition of biological crusts.

V. Stabilize disturbed sites with appropriate native erosion control plants or protective materials.

- A. Ripping soils to de-compact them has been found to be a cost-effective means of initiating self-recovery of sites.
- B. As a first resort, prevent dust emissions. Prevention measures including confining the surface area to be disturbed, limiting vehicle traffic to 15 mph, and controlling the number and activity of vehicles on a site at any given time. Construction activities can also be scheduled to minimize exposed areas. Other prevention measures are:
 1. Stabilize disturbed soils with appropriate erosion control methods.
 2. Stabilize key access points prior to construction.
 3. Direct most construction traffic to stabilized road surfaces.
 4. Soil tackifiers should be used with caution, such as only on piles. They have been found to work best only where there is no traffic or other subsequent disturbance. To be effective, tackifiers require a compact soil surface, and sufficient moisture

- holding capacities (such as with the presence of clay, organic matter, or soil structure [clods]).
- C. Plant disturbed sites that are erosion hazard or air quality nuisance with appropriate erosion control or native seed or plants. Adopt locally-proven revegetation practices with standards for:
1. Ground preparation and soil amendment such as:
 - a. Soil shaping to create water catchments by grading, pitting, or other means to create micro-catchments or swales.
 - b. Soil amendments such as mulch with bark chops, local plant litter, straw, rock, and large woody chunks.
 2. Planting techniques and types of plants (native species that easily establish) such as establishing vegetation islands, windbreaks, and protecting volunteer plants.
 3. Seed mixtures of native species collected from the island.
 4. Irrigation.
 5. Timing of planting and irrigation.
 6. Maintenance.
 7. Success criteria or standards for compliance.

Objective: Conserve biological crusts and the ecological functions they provide.

- VI. Map biological crusts.
- VII. Support research on biological crust diversity and function in order to understand conservation needs.
- VIII. Determine environmental conditions required to maintain functioning biological crust - list threats, strategies to restore, salvage, and promote.

4.2.3 Wildland Fire Management

Specific Concerns

- There are risks associated with military mission activities, including the possibility of wildland fire ignitions. For example, the missile launch facilities on the west end of SNI may be regarded as a potential wildland fire ignition source because most fires that have occurred on SNI are associated with the launching of missiles. The disposal of munitions by EOD personnel and live fire training, although infrequent in occurrence, may also represent a potential wildland fire ignition source at SNI.
- Potential wildland fire ignitions may also result from normal human activity, such as maintenance and construction activities, which are indirectly associated with the military mission.
- Separate fire suppression strategies may be needed for different plant communities and different infrastructure support areas on the island, and these have not been identified.
- Security and logistical issues may prevent regular use of cooperating agency firefighting resources due to the lack of regular fires.
- There is limited availability of water sources, wildland fire suppression equipment.
- The potential exists for damage to archeological and natural resources resulting from remote wildland fire suppression activities.

Current Management

Federal wildland fire policy requires that all federal lands with burnable vegetation have a fire plan and resources to safely mitigate losses. This policy was adopted by the DoD Wildland Fire Policy Working Group in 1996 and codified as DoD fire policy through DoDINST 6055.06 Fire and Emergency Services Program.

There is no wildland fire management plan for SNI. Fire suppression assets and resources are largely focused on structural fires that may occur within areas near the vicinity of the airfield or Nicktown. The Federal Fire Department will mobilize and respond to an incident if a fire does occur.

The Federal Fire Department at SNI oversees hazards and activities that may be considered as a potential fire ignition source; this includes activities such as weapons system testing, construction and maintenance, and recreational barbecues and bonfires. Fire suppression units are notified during weapons system testing and missile launches. The NBVC SA/PRB allows the Federal Fire Department to review construction and maintenance projects that include potential ignition sources for fire; furthermore, the Federal Fire Department may issue hot permits for welding activities and fire permits for the use of a recreational barbecue or bonfire pit. In general recreational fires are restricted to specific areas. The recreational fire pit behind the Islander club are a potential wildland fire ignition source and should follow guidelines for fire prevention and control, which includes notifying the Federal Fire Department to request authorization for the use of a recreational bonfire. The SA/PRB also authorizes the burning of piles of invasive plant material and branch trimmings as an economical means of disposal that also assists with management for biosecurity.

Assessment of Current Management

Wildland fire is not a major concern at SNI but it does need to be considered due to federal wildland fire policy, habitat vulnerability, and the presence of the aforementioned potential fire ignition sources. Currently, SNI is not in compliance with DoD fire policy (DoDINST 6055.06 Fire and Emergency Services Program), as a wildland fire management plan has not been developed.

Historic grazing and surface disturbance from feral and domestic ungulates have created disturbed plant communities that favor exotic plants. Invasive plant infestations, particularly exotic grasses, are most pronounced on the upper plateau. The problem is exacerbated by the breaking and continued disturbance of organic and clay soil crusts. The crusts normally help the soil resist penetration by seeds of exotic weeds. The presence of these exotic plants increases the vulnerability of habitats to the occurrence of a wildland fire event. There is a need to develop an island-wide wildland fire management plan given this vulnerability and the aforementioned federal compliance issues.

Adequate measures are in place to communicate with the Federal Fire Department for weapons system testing, construction, and maintenance activities. Recreational bonfires are managed through the SA/PRB. The NBVC ED is authorized to burn invasive plants and branch trimmings in a burn box. A future wildland fire management plan for SNI should reflect the complexity of the problem and the perspective that rather than eliminating wildland fire, an unplanned wildland fire should be controlled so there is no harm to persons or sensitive habitat. In order to accomplish this, fire protection areas should be mapped out in wildland fire management zoning. A fire policy should be written taking into account which areas could continue to involve a "let it burn" policy, or develop a new policy that uses wildland fire as a management tool, and identify those areas that would be impacted by such policies. Currently there is a need to use prescribed burns in restoration efforts on SNI, particularly burning of invasive plant biomass that has been collected. Burning of cut biomass in enclosed containers is also being considered.

Management Strategy

Objective: Protect SNI's human, infrastructure, natural, and cultural resources from harmful impacts of wildfire.

- I. Provide, maintain, and/or upgrade fire management cooperative agreements, memoranda of understanding, and reciprocal agreements to provide maximum protection to natural and cultural resources and infrastructure values.
- II. As a first priority, prevent wildland fire ignitions.
- III. Prevent human-caused fires through education, investigation, and public outreach efforts.
- IV. Develop a wildland fire management plan for SNI.
 - A. Complete a landscape-scale risk/hazard assessment that identifies high values at risk, prescribes preemptive action to protect the values, and sets priorities for implementation.
 1. Develop post-fire rehabilitation guidelines appropriate to SNI and these plant communities.
 2. Identify any fine fuels management areas.
 - B. Emphasize staging of fire suppression and post-suppression rehabilitation resources so that inevitable wildfires may be responded to in a non-crisis atmosphere with proper planning.
 1. For suppression, this includes equipment pools, water, retardant, suppression prescriptions by management area, and funding.
 2. For rehabilitation, this includes equipment pools, site descriptions, treatment prescriptions based on research findings and historic successes, and funding.
 - C. Provide fire suppression efforts commensurate with resource and adjacent property values at risk. Develop specific tactics and initial attack schemes based on buildings occupied by humans, highly valuable infrastructure, presence of sensitive species, historic districts, or unique vegetation communities.
 - D. Train qualified on-island personnel to provide initial response to a wildfire.
 - E. Determine fire frequency within habitats when considering future fire planning.
 - F. Keep up to date GIS delineations of sensitive natural and cultural resources for use in future wildland fire planning.
 - G. Use naturally occurring land features, existing roads as part of the fire break system to contain wildfires.
 - H. Continue to support and increase local firefighting ability to respond to fires in remote or rugged areas.
 1. Implement emergency fire suppression training for range operations personnel.
- V. Develop a database to track all fires, including acres burned, how suppressed and agency or personnel who suppressed the fire.

4.3 Management of Habitats and Plant Communities

4.3.1 Terrestrial Vegetation Communities

Specific Concerns

- Soil erosion, invasive species, human disturbance, marine mammal disturbance, and climate change threaten the condition and biodiversity of terrestrial vegetation communities. This in turn may affect the abundance and diversity of affected wildlife.
- There appear to be vegetation changes on the island that are documented anecdotally or through historic photos that are not detected quantitatively or island-wide through the current monitoring program. It is not known if these changes might have a long-term effect on biodiversity or wildlife habitat.

Current Management

The current management of coastal habitats and associated plant communities is based on mapping and descriptions conducted from February to June 1992 by Halvorson et al. (1996), in which twelve vegetation communities were classified based on 103 relevé plots. Vegetation monitoring plots were placed in representative plant communities on SNI and on other Channel Islands under the jurisdiction of the NPS in a joint effort (Halvorson et al. 1996). Previously, no data had been collected regarding the density and demographics of shrub or sensitive species occurring on the plots. The addition of belt counts allow density data on perennial species and sensitive species to be collected. Distinct coastal habitats were included in the described communities and included coastal marsh and beach dunes. In 1993, 36 permanent vegetation sampling plots were established on SNI by CINP. In 2009, surveys were repeated with some additions to the methods to improve detection of island-wide trends (TDI 2009).

The monitoring of these distinct vegetation communities enables the Navy to make proper management decisions pertaining to the status of island coastal plant communities and habitat. This comes from the recognition that SNI coastal vegetation is in various stages of recovery from grazing, farming, military use, and introduction of invasive plant species.

The focus of the Navy's management of coastal vegetation has been a long-term approach utilizing sustained monitoring and invasive plant control. The Navy's natural resources program has prioritized coastal areas for weed control as they are recognized as being the most at risk for impacts, and because of the possibility and practicality of control. Current management of terrestrial communities at SNI is a long-term, sustained investment in invasive plant control. Invasive plant control is prioritized by the potential of the plant species to spread, its proximity to sensitive species, and by current operations.

The Navy revised the SNI Weed Management Plan (Agri Chemical and Supply, Inc. 2014) (formerly the Weed Eradication Plan for SNI) to proactively support invasive plant management efforts. BMPs for invasive plant management are beginning to be implemented by explicitly adding them to construction and maintenance contracts. Non-native plant control treatments on SNI have been conducted by contractors since 2001 (Agri Chemical and Supply Inc. 2009). The non-native plant control effort focused primarily on fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare*) and short-podded mustard (*Hirschfeldia incana*), although several other target non-native species were treated in 2008, including: arundo (*Arundo donax*), agave (*Agave* sp.), cliff aster (*Malacothrix saxatilis tenuifolia*), smilo grass (*Stipa miliaceum*), and milk thistle (*Silybum marianum*) (Agri Chemical and Supply Inc. 2009). Project BMPs have also been implemented to promote invasive plant control. Consistent efforts towards invasive plant control have occurred. In 2013 and 2014, an increased effort was made to control Sahara mustard (*Brassica tournefortii*) and

carnation spurge (*Euphorbia terracina*) which are rapidly invading areas of SNI. An eradication attempt targeting marram grass (*Ammophila arenaria*) began in early 2015 with scheduled re-treatments to occur in 2016 and 2017; this effort will attempt to return inland dune vegetation to a more natural state.

Beach habitat and communities below the vegetation line are mostly managed through controlled access and limitation of activities stipulated in SNI's NBVC SA/PRB process codified in NBVCINST 11010.1B, the Biological Opinions (BO) with USFWS, and the Letter of Agreement (LOA) with NOAA pertaining to marine mammals (Appendix H). Beach condition and use are managed through regularly performed surveys for western snowy plovers and marine mammals.

Management of living marine resources below the mean high water mark (4.14 feet [1.26 m] for SNI), which are considered *State Tidelands and Submerged Lands*, is the responsibility of the CDFW as confirmed by the federal Submerged Lands Act of 1953 (43 USC 1301 *et seq.*) which granted ownership of lands and resources within this body of water to coastal states such as California (shoreline to 3 nm [5.6 km] offshore). The Navy supports the authority and responsibility of the CDFW to manage marine resources by providing access and information regarding use of the islands marine resources. See *Section 4.3.3: Coastal and Marine Habitats* for additional management information of beaches below the mean high water mark.

Assessment of Current Management

Of the identified known threats to terrestrial vegetation (climate change, soil erosion, altered fire regime, and invasive species), the most urgent to address at SNI is thought to be invasive species. For this reason there has been long-term, sustained effort at invasive species control. In the absence of monitoring that may direct natural resources managers in addressing other threats, or the identification of focal species that could provide managers an indication of a need to change direction, this is a reasonable approach (Hierl *et al.* 2008). The current program has successfully decreased fennel through control measures over the last 20 years. This also true for two species of introduced buckwheat, smilo grass, *Agave* sp., *Washingtonia* sp., *Tamarix* sp., fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare*), and *Opuntia ficus-indica*.

In addition to the revised SNI Weed Management Plan (Agri Chemical and Supply, Inc. 2014b), and BMPs that are added to construction and maintenance projects through the SA/PRB process, BMPs that promote invasive plant control also need to be enforced for any ground disturbing activities and projects. Habitat vegetation restoration efforts could also be more effective if BMPs are enforced. A need exists for management of terrestrial vegetation communities to identify a methodology to ensure no net loss to habitat types and to offset impacts from proposed development projects.

The current vegetation community monitoring program has been successful at providing a baseline description of the floristic composition of vegetation on SNI, and documenting the occurrence of rare and endemic plants through the Navy's partnership with the Santa Barbara Botanic Garden and CINP. This especially benefits comparisons to other Channel Islands and to the mainland.

SNI managers use a vegetation classification system consistent with the approaches of the other Channel Islands and consider their benefits for habitat management at SNI. The 2014 SNI vegetation classification and map was developed in compliance with the California Vegetation Classification and Mapping Program (VegCAMP) guidelines. The VegCAMP system complies with National Vegetation Classification Standards. The application of National Vegetation Classification Standards is mandated by the Federal Geographic Data Committee, for all federal agencies.

The existing field monitoring programs have allowed for documentation of some major vegetation shifts and the provision of some quantitative floristic cover data over time. However, the monitoring plots contribution to natural resources program objectives and management

cues can be improved. The plot data have been insufficient to report on ecosystem health on a range-wide basis or for species that are the focus of management, because there are too few plots; they do not represent the range of surface substrates, landscape position, and geology on SNI; and the field measures collected are not able to detect changes that intuitively and anecdotally appear to be occurring in plant communities.

Finally, Halvorson (1996) noted from his field work in the early 1990s that the island is recovering from past use of natural resources including a grazing history that spans nearly a century and a military use history of over half a century, but that there are many areas of serious soil erosion and impacts from invasive plants. He observed that rehabilitation of the island to a more natural setting will require a complex active restoration scheme that includes soil restoration, enhancement of native species populations, and restoration of natural ecosystem processes. Nearly 20 years later, this is still the case. Restoration and assessing the island's vulnerability to emerging concerns, such as climate change, remain.

Management Strategy

Objective: Reduce threats to native vegetation habitat types while maintaining no net loss to the military mission.

- I. Develop threat analysis for each vegetation community.
 - A. Address the priority threat of invasive species. Maintain the natural quality and integrity of native vegetation and habitats by reducing non-native plant species cover.
- II. Continue to implement and revise the invasive plant species management and eradication program, consistent with the long-term protection of native plant communities.
 - A. Follow the most current Integrated Pest Management Plan (IPMP), including prevention. This IPMP will be applied to invasive non-native species infestations. An IPMP is a long-term plan for managing pest problems, in contrast with the short term approach of relying on chemicals to abate pests, Integrated Pest Management relies on cultural, physical, mechanical and biological methods for controlling pests, with minimal dependence on chemical control.
- III. Construction projects that clear vegetation or disturb soil will conduct post-construction weed control.
- IV. Insert BMPs into contracts and other applicable plans that will reduce the threat to native vegetation habitat types and especially areas that are susceptible to erosion like coastal scrub.

Objective: Restore, enhance, and offset losses of terrestrial vegetation communities.

- V. Continue to update the vegetation classification and map.
 - A. Prioritize vegetation mapping projects by the sensitivity of the vegetation for special status species management, or to expected change in the vegetation due to military disturbance or other recognized threat like fire, invasives, or climate change.
 - B. Ensure each complete vegetation mapping project for SNI includes the following products:
 1. Detailed vegetation report including a documented species list and community descriptions.
 2. Digital vegetation map that incorporates soils and geomorphic attributes.
 3. Vegetation plot data.

4. Accuracy assessment data and analysis.
 5. Photo-interpretation key.
- VI. Develop a comprehensive erosion control and restoration implementation plan which includes ranking system to identify which disturbed areas need to be stabilized from active wind and water erosion.
- VII. Top priority is to avoid losses to the sensitive species habitat to ensure the stability of sensitive flora and fauna populations to exclude SNI from designated critical habitat.
- VIII. Establish criteria for restoration work as mitigation, such as risk of permanent loss of real estate or loss of potential to grow plants at all due to soil erosion. 50 CFR 402 Section 2 under ESA states “all federal departments and agencies shall seek to conserve endangered and threatened species and shall utilize their authority in furtherance of the purposes of the Act.” Thus, restoration work that promotes the recovery of federally listed species can be interpreted as mitigation for habitat loss.
- A. Use vegetation maps to plan recovery strategies for disturbed areas.
 - B. Make project proponent responsible for restoration.
- IX. Avoid and minimize losses and ensure habitat is protected to stabilize sensitive species populations.

Objective: Support monitoring of native vegetation habitat types.

- X. Priorities for monitoring may include areas such as restoration sites, areas of sensitive species, habitats of special concern, and threat prone areas.
- XI. Encourage research that can better define the extent, nature, and value of vegetation resources of SNI, and that helps sort out priority management actions to address risks and vulnerabilities related to these values.

Coastal Scrub

Specific Concerns

- Caliche Scrub is impacted by a tremendous loss of soil, most likely a result of past overgrazing by sheep. It is not known if the soil loss is ongoing or is now stable.
- It is not known if there is a reasonable or cost-effective opportunity to restore Caliche Scrub.
- Coreopsis Scrub and invasive grasslands are expanding on SNI, and it is not known if this may affect future biodiversity.

Current Management

The Coastal Scrub plant communities are currently described, managed, and monitored as a component of vegetation as a whole, rather than separately. Impacts are generally avoided and minimized through the NBVC SA/PRB process codified in NBVCINST 11010.1B. Management of terrestrial habitats take into consideration and coordinate with cultural resource management efforts focused on SNI’s archaeological resources.

Assessment of Current Management

Coastal Scrub is the island’s dominant land cover type and is comprised of five defined scrub habitats including Caliche, Isocoma, Baccharis, Lupine, and Coreopsis scrubs. The Coreopsis

Scrub component of the Coastal Scrub community is changing; for other subtypes it is less clear. There is uncertainty as to how to prioritize efforts targeted at these subtypes because the cost-effectiveness is unclear, and there are no defined objectives or statement of desired outcomes.

Management Strategy

Objective: Protect coastal scrub habitat in its various forms to maintain or expand spatial extent to support natural species diversity, with special emphasis on cover types that support species warranting Navy stewardship.

- I. Maintain the spatial extent and diversity of Coastal Scrub that now exists by controlling exotics and reducing erosion within defined habitats and minimizing anthropogenic impacts.
- II. Define and map the boundaries of all coastal scrub cover types. Compare to historical photographs to evaluate trend and recruitment.
 - A. Monitor the boundaries and condition of coreopsis scrub through the vegetation mapping program.
 - B. Identify the boundaries and condition of caliche scrub through the vegetation mapping program.
- III. Continue to restrict access in sensitive areas, especially by vehicles.
 - A. Enforce general contract requirements for contractors in addition to SNI rules.
- IV. Control ongoing erosion using BMPs.
- V. Establish milestones and success targets for plant community composition and cover of non-natives in each Coastal Scrub community.
 - A. Increase the relative cover of native shrubs and herbaceous plants in relation to non-natives.

Vernal Pools

Specific Concerns

- There is uncertainty as to the natural or anthropogenic origin of vernal pools at SNI.

Current Management

The vernal pool plant communities are currently described and monitored as a component of vegetation as a whole, rather than separately. Impacts are generally avoided and minimized through the NBVC SA/PRB process codified in NBVCINST 11010.1B. Management of terrestrial habitats takes into consideration and coordination with cultural resource management efforts focused on SNI's archaeological resources.

Assessment of Current Management

The origin and historic condition of the current vernal pools is unknown. Currently there is a need to assess the integrity of the SNI vernal pool designation and manage them appropriately.

Management Strategy

Objective: Protect vernal pools that support their natural species diversity, with special emphasis on species such as the fairy shrimp, which are dependent on this habitat.

- I. Protect vernal pools and associated fauna to maintain their existing condition.

Riparian Vegetation

Specific Concerns

- There is a need to identify important isolated areas of riparian vegetation because of its importance to migratory birds.
- There is a need to identify the island-wide distribution of riparian vegetation, such as areas dominated by willows, so as to avoid it when planning for future development.
- Willow habitat that includes riparian vegetation is important for migratory birds.
- Future use of fresh water wells would impact the groundwater supply that supports these systems.
- Invasive plant species pose a threat to riparian vegetation habitat.

Current Management

The riparian vegetation plant communities are currently described, managed, and monitored as a component of vegetation as a whole, rather than separately. Impacts are generally avoided and minimized through the NBVC SA/PRB process codified in NBVCINST 11010.1B. Management of terrestrial habitats take into consideration and coordination with cultural resource management efforts focused on SNI's archaeological resources. Riparian vegetation habitat is also managed by the LARWQCB Basin Plan for surface water quality and ground water quality. Riparian vegetation habitat was mapped by USACE during their wetland delineation of SNI conducted in December 2008. All watersheds on SNI have had *Washingtonia rousta*, *Tamarix*, and *Arundo* treated or completely removed in 2014–2015. These treatments free-up precious water resources for native riparian plants, creating higher quality riparian habitat. Currently (2015–2016), trials are being

conducted on Bermuda grass (*Cynodon dactylon*) removal using monocot-specific herbicide within riparian areas.

Assessment of Current Management

The current status and condition of this habitat is known based on the wetland delineation conducted by the USACE in 2008. Management for riparian vegetation can be proactive by reducing invasive species and improving habitat integrity. It is possible to expand this habitat by removing invasive trees and restoring willow, which also enhances this habitat for use by migratory birds. Benefits to other species, such as migratory birds, have been observed and assessed for this habitat.

Management Strategy

Objective: Protect the riparian vegetation community in order to support natural species diversity, with special emphasis on supporting species warranting Navy stewardship.

- I. Maintain the existing community boundaries, allowing no net loss from anthropogenic activity, by monitoring changes.
- II. Remove non-native plant species in order to reduce competition and facilitate the expansion of associated riparian plants into adjacent suitable habitat.

Grasslands

Specific Concerns

- With the exception of steep north facing escarpment slopes with relic *Stipa diegoense* fields, native perennial grasses do not make up a functional native grassland habitat. The perennial grass component of the grassland habitat appears to be missing.
- In the grasslands habitat dominated by non-native grasses there are small populations of other native and endemic grasses and other plants.
- Native perennial grasses currently exist in various habitats and notably in refugia under *Opuntia*.
- Vegetation and floristic data do not provide sufficient information to establish priorities for recovery, such as locations where a perennial grassland can be managed or enhanced to favor the perennials.

Current Management

The grassland plant communities are currently described, managed, and monitored as a component of vegetation as a whole, rather than separately. Impacts are generally avoided and minimized through the NBVC SA/PRB process codified in NBVCINST 11010.1B. Management of terrestrial habitats take into consideration and coordination with cultural resource management efforts focused on SNI's archaeological resources.

Mowing activities occur in this habitat for fire control, weed abatement, and road maintenance. Four species of native grasses have been integral in habitat restoration efforts from 2014 onward. Seed bulking rows are in planning so that large amounts of seeds can be included in future restoration efforts.

Assessment of Current Management

Maps and survey work have been done for native grasses at SNI. A potential exists to expand native grass populations and increase their visibility in terrestrial habitat management. A desired future condition is to have native grasses as a buffer around other managed habitats.

Management Strategy

Objective: Develop restoration goals for grassland shrub savannah defining specific geographic and plant assemblages.

- I. Investigate the processes needed to sustain grasslands, such as wildland fire.
- II. Reduce invasive non-native species so they are no longer a significant factor in community structure, function, or composition.
- III. Implement grass seed bulking rows to provide native seed for restoration efforts.

Coastal Marsh

Specific Concerns

- Marine mammals impact the vegetation of coastal marsh habitats.
- Sea level rise and increased storm intensity are eroding this vegetation community.
- There is the potential for loss of connectivity for ocean water to support this habitat.

Current Management

The coastal marsh plant communities are currently described, managed, and monitored as a component of vegetation as a whole, rather than separately. Impacts are generally avoided and minimized through the NBVC SA/PRB process codified in NBVCINST 11010.1B. Management of terrestrial habitats take into consideration and coordination with cultural resource management efforts focused on SNI's archaeological resources.

Coastal marsh habitat was mapped by the USACE during their wetland delineation of SNI conducted in August 2011 and during the island-wide vegetation classification and mapping effort in 2013 (HDR 2014). This habitat will be remapped periodically by the USACE when wetland delineations are conducted and during general vegetation mapping updates.

In 2015–2016, coastal marsh plants such as beach morning glory (*Calystegia soldanella*) and woolly seablite will be outplanted in coastal marsh areas to increase occurrences and biodiversity from island-sourced populations.

Assessment of Current Management

The coastal marsh habitat at SNI is its own self-sustaining and functioning system. The most recent USACE wetland delineation and vegetation mapping is sufficient to identify the boundaries of this habitat.

Management Strategy

Objective: Maintain function and diversity of coastal marsh habitat.

- I. Monitor key elements, including invasive species, for changes in trend that may affect the integrity of coastal marsh habitat.

- A. If feasible restore, enhance, or maintain habitat based upon recommendations from monitoring.

Upland Beach and Dune

Specific Concerns

- Dunes are a dynamic component of the coastal landscape at SNI and their location and form may change over time.
- Dunes have the potential to obstruct roads on SNI.
- Dune movement affects the ability to use facilities and infrastructure to support the military mission at SNI.
- Dune management practices have used non-indigenous invasive species to stabilize drifting dunes.

Current Management

The beach and dune plant communities are currently described, managed, and monitored as a component of vegetation as a whole, rather than separately. Impacts are generally avoided and minimized through the NBVC SA/PRB process codified in NBVCINST 11010.1B. Management of terrestrial habitats takes into consideration and coordination with cultural resource management efforts focused on SNI's archaeological resources.

Upland dunes were planted in the 1970s with European beach grass, a non-native invasive species, to stabilize drifting dunes and prevent them from occluding road access. Since then, the native vegetation has stabilized the dunes, and in 2015, European beach grass is being removed to allow native cover to return to the areas of the dunes where it was planted. If drifting dunes start to cross roads, Public Works staff will move the sand to the down-wind side of the road.

Assessment of Current Management

At the west end of the island there is a potential for the drifting dunes to cross roads. Dune drift can be investigated for possible management measures. There is a need to develop a dune drift management plan.

Management Strategy

Objective: Protect the integrity of stabilized dunes with respect to cultural resources, root casts, and the natural abundance and diversity of native species.

- I. Remove invasive non-native plants and replace them with native dune stabilizing plant species.

Objective: Research and develop management measures for drifting dunes.

- II. Investigate dune drift processes on SNI.
- III. Support the development of a Dune Drift Management Plan.

4.3.2 Jurisdictional Waters - Wetlands

Specific Concerns

- Jurisdictional wetlands are regulated under Section 404 of the CWA.
- Non-native invasive species, such as tamarisk, are present in freshwater riparian wetland habitat areas. Invasive plant species can outcompete native species and change the hydrology of wetlands.
- The coastal marsh wetlands on the back beaches are areas where marine mammals occur during the time period when they use haul out locations on SNI.
- Sedimentation from increased erosion can shrink wetlands or impact jurisdictional Special Aquatic Sites.

Current Management

The USACE delineated jurisdictional waters of the U.S. at SNI in August 2011. This delineation surveyed intermittent stream channels that discharge to the ocean, seeps, and lagoon areas. This 2011 jurisdictional waters of the U.S. delineation identified a total of 2.48 acres of wetland habitats on SNI, which includes riparian and coastal marsh habitat.

Under Federal requirements and Navy policy (OPNAVINST 5090.1D), there shall be “no net loss” of waters of the U.S. on SNI. Any action significantly affecting wetlands shall require an environmental review. Placement of fill or movement of earth of any kind is prohibited unless under permit. If it is demonstrated that wetlands impacts are unavoidable, then mitigation shall be required. Loss of wetland function shall be mitigated through wetlands enhancement, restoration, or creation. During normal, or above average, rainfall years, runoff collects in drainages or vernal pools on SNI.

For intertidal habitat other than salt marsh, unvegetated shallows, and deep subtidal habitats in the USACE jurisdiction (below Mean Higher High Water), compliance with EPA Section 404(b)(1) Guidelines is essentially evaluated qualitatively and involves exercise of the judgment of the USACE in each permit application. The USACE is required to deny the permit if the findings show that the proposed discharge, even with mitigation, would result in “significant degradation,” to include consideration of effect of the fill on the water bottom, water flow and circulation, turbidity, the aquatic ecosystem and organisms, contamination of the water, and downstream resources (40 CFR 230.10[c]). The Guidelines apply an additional burden of proof requirement covering special aquatic sites such as mudflats and eelgrass beds—to demonstrate that no practicable alternatives exist that will meet the project purpose (40 CFR 230.10[a]).

Within the restrictions of EPA Section 404(b)(1) Guidelines, the USACE will grant a permit unless the permit is determined to be contrary to public interest. To determine effect on public interest, the USACE is required to balance the benefits expected against the foreseeable detriments of the proposed project. The factors considered in this review are conservation, economics, aesthetics, environmental quality, historic values, fish and wildlife values, flood control, land use, navigation, recreation, water supply and quality, energy needs, safety, food production, and the general public and private need and welfare (33 CFR 320.4).

The Navy coordinates with the California Coastal Commission (CCC) to receive a concurrence letter when proposing development in the coastal zone within wetlands, tidelands, submerged lands (below mean low tide), beaches, estuaries, riparian habitat, and streams. The definition of wetlands used by the CCC differs from that of the USACE in that it includes nonvegetated areas such as mudflats and an additional 100 feet (30 m) wide terrestrial buffer measured from the upland edge of the wetland.

The EO, "Protection of Wetlands," (EO 11990) requires federal agencies to provide leadership and take action to minimize the destruction, loss or degradation of wetlands, and to preserve and enhance the natural and beneficial values of wetlands when:

1. Acquiring, managing, and relinquishing of federal lands and facilities;
2. Providing federally undertaken, financed, or assisted construction and improvements; and
3. Conducting federal activities and programs affecting land use, including but not limited to water and related land resources planning, regulating, and licensing activities.

Since the issuance of this EO, the focus of national policy has shifted from "minimizing" destruction, loss, and degradation of wetlands to "no net loss" of wetlands in carrying out the above federal activities.

Assessment of Current Management

The USACE conducted their wetland delineation for SNI in 2011. The status of those wetland habitats identified during that delineation, which included riparian and coastal marsh habitat, should be monitored. A future wetland delineation conducted by USACE may occur again. Jurisdictional delineations should be performed at each installation to show which wetlands or water bodies are subject to regulatory jurisdiction under Section 404 of the CWA or Section 9 and 10 of the Rivers and Harbors Act of 1899.

The focus of implementation of EO 11990 on SNI should be on the enhancement of non-jurisdictional wetlands and the springs; on freshwater, not salt water wetlands. The coastal wetlands on the back beaches would require excluding marine mammals, which would be a poor use of natural resource management funds.

Management Strategy

Objective: Protect the natural and beneficial functions of SNI waters and wetland vegetation, as part of appropriate permits with the USACE and to ensure no net loss of area, function, or value. Preserve and enhance wetlands as directed under EO 11990.

Commanders shall ensure that boundaries of legally defined wetlands, on all Navy lands, are identified and mapped with sufficient accuracy to protect them from potential unplanned impacts, and that the maps are distributed to all potential users, including facilities planners, operational units, and tenant commands (OPNAVINST 5090.1D).

- I. A current inventory of wetlands shall be maintained and net changes monitored (OPNAVINST 5090.1D; DoDINST 4715.03 Manual).
 - A. Monitor wetland community plant species composition and relative cover on a regular basis to determine if wetland margins are expanding and to ensure no net loss in structure or function.
 - B. Maintain and update GIS database of all wetlands.
- II. Protect the natural ecological integrity, structure, and functional values of the wetlands and floodplains on SNI. The Navy will comply with EO 11990 and the national goal of no net loss of wetlands.
 - A. Continue to comply with water regulations to ensure wetlands are not at risk of pollution.
- III. Remove non-native invasive species, such as tamarisk, from freshwater wetland habitats and those upstream areas that help confer the ecological integrity to those wetland habitats.

- D. Prohibit dumping, filling or other contamination of waters of the U.S. Filling requires a permit from USACE.

4.3.3 Coastal and Marine Habitats and Communities

The coastal and marine habitats and communities surrounding SNI support a diverse and robust community encompassing every trophic level and taxonomic family. The relative isolation of SNI from the California mainland has provided these habitats and communities a certain degree of protection from impacts related to development, extraction, and pollution. Additionally, prohibition of public access to SNI has reduced extraction of marine resources, especially in the intertidal zone. While these communities represent some of the most pristine coastal and marine areas contained within the SCB they have sustained changes and remain vulnerable to both natural and anthropogenic factors.

Intertidal Habitats

Coastal Strand

Specific Concerns

- Coastal strands or sandy beaches are exposed to risks posed by debris, pollution, and invasive species.
- Limited qualitative or quantitative information is available on the biologically productive components of sandy beaches that subsequently support many species of shore birds including the federally threatened western snowy plover.
- Observed changes to the environment from increased populations of pinnipeds have created intra-species competition that may be contributing to shifts in habitat and community distribution and structure that require consideration when developing management strategies.

Current Management

Sandy beaches are managed directly through utilization of the SA/PRB process codified in NBVCINST 11010.1B.

Sandy beaches are managed indirectly by limiting human uses during substantial times of the year due to the occurrence of marine mammals and western snowy plovers. Reducing access to beaches promotes natural interaction between species and reduces potential impacts from disturbance and anthropogenic materials. The Navy conducts removal of iceplant and other invasive species, and propagates and plants rare dune species such as beach morning glory and *Dithyrea maritima* within dunes and salt marshes.

Assessment of Current Management

Utilization of the SA/PRB process in conjunction with access limitations to sandy beaches are necessary but not sufficient to protect and maintain communities that occur in this habitat. In addition to use restrictions for this habitat, sustained efforts to remove invasive exotic species and continued monitoring efforts will contribute to the conservation of this habitat.

Management Strategy

Objective: Maintain and protect the attributes of sandy beaches to sustain a diverse and abundant invertebrate and wildlife community.

- I. Protect and manage populations of the federally threatened western snowy plover on sandy beaches in order to maintain compliance with current BOs.
- II. Establish baseline information and conditions of sandy beach communities.
 - A. Support scientifically recognized methodologies and surveys to evaluate individual beaches with special emphasis on indicator species, endemics, invasives, and protected species.
 - B. Complete GIS delineations of sandy beach habitat throughout the island to identify and conserve valuable habitat and reduce operational conflicts.
- III. Establish acceptable use periods based on the time of year to enhance military training flexibility while maintaining habitat integrity and BMPs.
- IV. Support evaluation of impacts of marine debris and pollution on intertidal habitats.

Rocky Shores and Surfgrass

Specific Concerns

- The rocky intertidal communities are exposed to risks posed by debris, pollution, disease, and invasive species.
- Climate change and related increases in sea surface temperature create shifts in the dominant species assemblages that may contribute to changes in habitat and community structure that require consideration when developing management strategies.

Current Management

Management of rocky intertidal areas is accomplished through a combination of surveys and restricted access to the southern shoreline and limited access to the northern shoreline. These areas are restricted to personnel due to the presence of marine mammals and seabirds during specific portions of the year.

Few published marine biological surveys for the rocky intertidal have been conducted at SNI; however, the various rocky intertidal surveys that have been conducted at SNI provide important baseline information. Caplan and Bootlootian (1967) conducted intertidal surveys at two locations, both located on the southern portion of the island between Dutch Harbor and Daytona Beach. Intertidal biodiversity surveys were conducted on SNI in 2003 and 2007 by the PISCO Coastal Biodiversity Studies program at two locations, Marker Poles and Thousand Springs. In 2009, a new biodiversity site was also established at Tranquility Beach.

Dr. VanBlaricom (1993) has also studied the distribution of black abalone at SNI since 1981. VanBlaricom continues to conduct an annual monitoring effort to document trends in black abalone populations at SNI and this 35-year data set of nine monitored sites represents the single longest dataset on abalone abundance in California. The CDFW also monitored two sites for black abalone recruitment and abundance on the north and west sides of SNI between 1992 and 1996. In 2010, they re-established one of these sites at Corral Harbor and a new site at Phoca Reef, and have monitored annually since then.

Additionally, the USFWS in cooperation with UC Santa Cruz established five permanent intertidal sites around SNI in 1980. The five sites have been sampled twice a year in spring and fall since that time with a few exceptions. The project is currently conducted by the USGS-Biological Resources Division, UC Santa Cruz Field Station. These sites were installed

to monitor sea otter affects in intertidal resources. While these data have not been published, efforts are presently underway to compile and analyze them.

In 2014, four rocky intertidal monitoring sites were established on SNI utilizing the standardized Multi-Agency Rocky Intertidal Network (MARINe) protocols. MARINe is a partnership of agencies, universities and private groups committed to determining the health of the rocky intertidal habitat and providing this information to the public. Currently, MARINe monitoring sites extend from British Columbia to Baja California, Mexico, including sites on all of the Channel Islands. This type of standardized regular survey of the condition and dynamics of rocky shore marine life is critical for detecting and understanding rocky intertidal community dynamics at SNI.

Assessment of Current Management

While existing research on black abalone provides the single largest long-term data set for that species, data on the broader rocky intertidal ecosystem have not been compiled from continuing surveys. A review of existing intertidal studies, compilation and analysis of existing data, and establishment of a series of monitoring sites using a methodology consistent with those employed throughout the California is necessary. The MARINe plots have fulfilled the management goal of collecting data using a methodology that is consistent with those employed throughout California and the elsewhere along the west coast of North America.

Management Strategy

Objective: Utilize existing and new rocky intertidal monitoring data to document baseline conditions and preserve a functional habitat.

- I. Continue intertidal monitoring at SNI using standardized monitoring protocols consistent with those used throughout the other Channel Islands and California to establish regional trends and understand site specific change.
 - A. Support the compilation and analysis of existing intertidal monitoring data from USGS and other sources.
 - B. Support establishment of scientifically recognized protocols for monitoring locations around SNI in intertidal habitats that represent key indicator species.
 - C. Include additional measurements and monitoring of rocky intertidal habitat and organisms to understand and potentially forecast species' responses to climate change.
 - D. Support evaluation and research of disease outbreaks that can lead to habitat-wide impacts to SNI rocky intertidal.
 - E. Support evaluation of impacts of marine debris and pollution on intertidal habitats.
 - F. Support annual monitoring of black abalone populations by continuing to conduct density surveys.
 - G. Support GIS mapping of black abalone densities to establish sensitive areas and document trends in recruitment and depletion.

Objective: Provide access to academic researchers to investigate important community related questions involving recruitment, disturbance, and species diversity that help to assess regional trends.

- II. Continue to support rocky intertidal monitoring and GIS delineations of rocky intertidal habitat in order to provide site specific information on rocky intertidal species diversity and biogeographic distribution patterns.
 - A. Encourage and support independent scientific research and develop cooperative research agreements focused on recruitment of important indicator species or species of concern.
 - B. Monitor an appropriate set of environmental variables (i.e. water and air temp, nearshore current speed and direction) in order to better understand what is driving the patterns of distribution and abundance.

Subtidal Habitats

The nearshore waters of SNI are composed of various habitats that represent subtidal areas and associated habitats from the shoreline to the deep offshore waters. Habitats include unvegetated soft bottom, vegetated soft bottom, and rocky reefs and kelp forests. Many of these habitats can be further subdivided to examine fine scale differences; however, for the purpose of natural resource management and regulatory considerations, these categories are most applicable.

Soft Bottom

Specific Concerns

- Very limited qualitative or quantitative information is available on the, quality, and diversity of soft bottom communities adjacent to SNI that subsequently support many species of commercially important invertebrates and fish.

Current Management

NBVC supports surveys and studies performed by various state and federal agencies that examine the soft bottom habitat and perform regular ASBS monitoring of three areas that contain this community. All potential activities that could potentially interface with soft bottom habitat are reviewed under the NBVC SA/PRB process.

Assessment of Current Management

Continued monitoring of soft bottom habitat in support of ASBS compliance increases the availability of baseline data that allows assessments of the status and trend of wildlife populations that occur within this habitat. Continued support of surveys and studies conducted by various state, federal, and non-governmental partners will also contribute to the development of adequate baseline data.

Management Strategy

Objective: Inventory and protect the attributes of soft bottom shallows that sustain diverse and abundant invertebrate and vertebrate communities.

- I. Encourage and support soft bottom monitoring that is performed at SNI and throughout the SCB.

- A. Support species abundance/diversity surveys to establish general community dominants and baseline conditions.
- B. Implement best management practices to preserve diverse and functional habitat.
- II. Update GIS data of the extent of soft bottom habitat and rocky reef habitat as needed.
 - A. Continue to support multi-beam and Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR) mapping and GIS delineations of subtidal habitat adjacent to SNI to identify habitat types as needed and reduce the potential for operational impacts.

Eelgrass

Specific Concerns

- Comprehensive eelgrass surveys have not been performed to examine the extent, quality, and diversity of this sensitive habitat.
- Deposition from erosion may affect the health, abundance, or stability of these communities.

Current Management

NBVC performs regular ASBS monitoring. All potential activities that could potentially interface with eelgrass habitat are reviewed during the NBVC SA/PRB process. Eelgrass beds are recognized as “Special Aquatic Sites” under the CWA and as such receive special attention from the USACE and the EPA when determining mitigation measures. Eelgrass is also considered EFH under the Magnuson-Stevens Fishery Conservation and Management Act.

Assessment of Current Management

Continued utilization of the SA/PRB process is necessary but not sufficient to maintain and protect eelgrass habitat at SNI. Continued monitoring and analysis of the status and trends of eelgrass habitat that is based on baseline data sets are needed in addition to SA/PRB NEPA planning activities.

Management Strategy

Objective: Maintain integrity of eelgrass habitats.

- I. Encourage the preservation of eelgrass habitat through supporting baseline surveys conducted within SNI waters.
 - A. Comply with regulations to avoid this EFH area and establish buffer zones for protection.
- II. Support mapping of eelgrass beds to inform decision-making and NBVC SA/PRB processes for future projects and operations that may have impacts.

Rocky Reef and Kelp Forest

Specific Concerns

- The rocky reefs and kelp forest communities are exposed to risks posed by pollution, overfishing, and invasive species.
- Information on the extent, quality, and diversity of rocky reefs and kelp forest habitat that subsequently supports a multitude of fish, invertebrates, bird, and marine mammal species

including the federally endangered white abalone and green and pink abalone as federal species of concern has not been made readily available to managers.

- Climate change leading to increased sea surface temperatures create shifts in the dominant species assemblages that may contribute to changes in habitat and community structure that require consideration when developing management strategies.

Current Management

Various rocky reef and kelp forest surveys have been conducted at SNI over the decades by public and private research entities providing some important baseline information. Ongoing cooperative research with the USGS has developed the most valuable long-term site specific data examining giant kelp and sea urchin interaction. Management of rocky reef and kelp forest communities is primarily accomplished by regulations enforced by the CDFW to limit commercial and recreational fishing.

In 2014, a project was funded to establish a long-term monitoring program for rocky reefs and kelp forests at SNI that is comparable with the other Channel Islands, while continuing to add to the 30-year baseline dataset already established by USGS. This project will allow for installation managers to characterize the long-term status and trends for fish communities and populations that occur within SNI's rocky reef and kelp forest habitat.

Assessment of Current Management

Continued utilization of the NBVC SA/PRB process is necessary but not sufficient to maintain and protect rocky reef and kelp forest habitat at SNI. Monitoring using an acceptable methodology and analysis of the status and trends of rocky reef and kelp forest habitat that is based on baseline data sets are needed in addition to SA/PRB NEPA planning activities.

Existing data collection efforts, including the long-term USGS surveys and enhanced protocols implemented in 2014 provide one of the most comprehensive data sets for subtidal ecosystems in California. These data help ensure that rocky reef habitat around SNI is not significantly changing due to anthropogenic change. These surveys are also documenting ecosystem shifts potentially related to the ongoing increases in southern sea otters around SNI. There is a clear need to continue to support these surveys and to ensure they are conducted in a way that is comparable to other efforts in the Channel Islands and throughout California.

In addition to the subtidal surveys, the Navy supports annual mapping of the kelp canopy around SNI. This effort allows for tracking of the overall kelp forest habitat extent and to determine if any significant trends in kelp coverage are present.

Management Strategy

Objective: Enhance the protection and monitoring of subtidal rocky reef and kelp forest attributes that are comparable to other Channel Islands to evaluate community trends.

- I. Support continued kelp forest ecosystem monitoring around SNI that is comparable to other Channel Islands.
 - A. Survey habitats that contain the key indicator invertebrate and fish species associated with kelp forests.
- II. Limit impacts to kelp forests through the NBVC SA/PRB process.
 - A. Utilize scientifically recognized kelp forest ecosystem monitoring protocols to assess long-term trends in community structure and seasonal variations to ensure ASBS compliance.

- III. Encourage state and federal agencies and academic researchers to investigate important community related questions involving recruitment, disturbance, and species diversity that help to assess regional trends.
 - A. Support surveys of the federally endangered white abalone to establish the presence/absence of the species within SNI waters.
 - B. Support continued kelp mapping surveys to examine trends in surface coverage and primary production.

Deep Water Habitats

Rocky Habitat

Specific Concerns

- Very limited qualitative or quantitative information is available on the quality, and diversity of deep water rocky habitat communities adjacent to SNI that subsequently support many species of recreationally and commercially important invertebrates and fishes.
- Several sensitive species may be present in these deep water habitats such as white abalone (*Haliotis sorenseni*, federally endangered), cowcod, and bocaccio rockfish (*Sebastes levis* and *S. paucispinis*, federal species of concern).

Current Management

Management of deep water rocky habitat is primarily achieved by regulations implemented by CDFW to limit consumptive marine resource use from activities such as commercial and recreational fishing. Fishing regulations seek to manage populations at sustainable levels through: area and seasonal closures; gear limitations; and size, catch, and possession limitations.

Assessment of Current Management

Continued utilization of the NBVC SA/PRB process is necessary but not sufficient to maintain and protect rocky habitat at SNI. Baseline monitoring using an acceptable methodology and analysis of the status and trends of deep rocky habitat is needed in addition to SA/PRB NEPA planning activities.

Management Strategy

Objective: Assess and conserve the attributes of deep rocky substrate to maintain the diversity of communities and promote the conservation of sensitive species warranting Navy stewardship.

- I. Update the island-wide map of all deep water rocky habitat as needed.
 - A. Support species abundance and diversity surveys to establish general community dominants and baseline conditions.
 - B. Implement best management practices to preserve diverse and functional habitat.
- II. Continue to support the management of the Begg Rock State Marine Reserve designated in December 2012 (Title 14, CCR, Section 632 (b) (115)).

Soft Bottom

Specific Concerns

- Very limited qualitative or quantitative information is available on the, quality, and diversity of deep soft bottom communities adjacent to SNI.

Current Management

Deep soft bottom habitat is not directly managed at SNI. Nearshore waters of SNI are designated as an ASBS, which provides direct benefits to water quality and indirect benefits to nearshore benthic habitats. Therefore, the Navy's active compliance with the requirements of the ASBS designation benefits deep unvegetated soft bottom habitat and species that use this habitat.

Assessment of Current Management

Baseline monitoring using an acceptable methodology and analysis of the status and trends of deep soft bottom habitat is needed in addition to SA/PRB NEPA planning activities.

Management Strategy

Objective: Conserve the attributes of deep soft bottom substrate to maintain ecosystem function.

- I. Conserve deep soft bottom habitat through the continued use of the SA/PRB process.
 - A. Continue to comply with ASBS requirements.
 - B. Implement best management practices to preserve diverse and functional habitat.

Sea Stacks and Offshore Rocks

Specific Concerns

- Offshore rocks are important as roosting (and sometimes nesting, though not at SNI) habitat for many seabird species.
- Offshore rocks represent an environment that is not well studied and only rudimentary information exists on the extent, quality, and diversity of these communities adjacent to SNI.
- There is uncertainty as to the extent that offshore rocks of SNI support populations of avian species that warrant stewardship or protection.
- No specific issues are currently identified that may affect the health, abundance, or stability of these communities.

Current Management

By Presidential Proclamation on 11 January 2000, all unappropriated or unreserved lands and interest in lands owned or controlled by the U.S. in the form of islands, rocks, and pinnacles above mean high tide within 12 nm (22.2 km) of the shoreline of the State of California were designated as the California Coastal National Monument. This designation includes the portions of the CCNM off of the shoreline of SNI and Begg Rock that are administered by NBVC.

The proclamation specifically identifies the pelagic, nearshore, and terrestrial bird species associated with the CCNM, as well as the importance of this nearshore ocean zone for pinnipeds, general biodiversity, and other species and resources of scientific interest (BLM

2005). In the geographic extent of the monument, there are 12,767 offshore rocks or islands recognized. Of these, 11,507 fall under the jurisdiction of the BLM and therefore, the CCNM. Only 70 of these rocks are larger than one acre and of these, only 11 are greater than five acres in size.

The Secretary of the Interior manages the CCNM through the BLM and under the BLM's existing authorities, subject to the overriding purpose of protecting the resources described in the Presidential Proclamation. The BLM's authority for such activities are directed by the Federal Land Policy and Management Act of 1976, Section 307(b), which provides that the Secretary of the Interior may undertake programs of resource management through cooperative agreements. The BLM is directed by Congress to administer the public lands so that all various land and resource uses and values are managed in combinations that will best meet the needs of the American people.

Through an MOU signed in 2000, the CDFW and the California Department of Parks and Recreation were brought in as managing partners to assist the BLM, who retains the ultimate legal responsibility for the CCNM, in "preserving the [CCNM's] objects of historic and scientific interest...mapping and understanding resources within the Monument [and]...working with the public to explain the values of the Monument." In order to effectively deal with the wide array of partnership opportunities associated with the CCNM, three basic partnership categories have been developed:

- Core-Managing Partner: Each of the three 'core' agencies - BLM, CDFW, and California Department of Parks and Recreation - responsible for collaborating in the overall management of the entire CCNM.
- Collaborative Partner: An organization, governmental or private, that is interested in collaborating with the core managing partners in any of a variety of programs, actions, and management elements associated with the long-term management of the CCNM.
- Steward: A select entity with ownership and/or management responsibility for a portion of the coast that adjoins part of the CCNM and that is interested in serving as the local CCNM BLM point of contact for the adjacent portion of the CCNM.

Each Steward will work with the BLM and other CCNM partners as appropriate, in a cooperative and collaborative management effort to ensure the long-term protection of their specific portion of the CCNM, a portion that is offshore of the Steward's onshore property.

The Resource Management Plan that guides the management of the CCNM was approved by a ROD in September 2005. Further management guidance was developed in November 2007 when the Navy and the BLM entered into a MOU (BLM MOU No. CA-939-08-02) to establish an interim agreement whereby the Navy will serve as a *Steward for those* portions of the CCNM off the shoreline of SNI and Begg Rock that are administered by NBVC. The authority for the Navy to enter into such an MOU is derived from EO 13352 of 26 August 2004, Facilitation of Cooperative Conservation, which requires the Secretaries of Defense and Interior to carry out activities of their respective agencies that relate to the environment and the natural resources in a manner that facilitates cooperative conservation.

Of relevance to this INRMP, the MOU between the Navy and the BLM regarding the CCNM identifies that the Navy agrees to cooperate with the BLM on defining the monitoring and research needs for the CCNM and developing a strategy for implementing the protection, monitoring, and research needs consistent with the Navy's integrated natural resource management plans.

Assessment of Current Management

Implementation of the CCNM Resource Management Plan and the MOU between the Navy and the BLM has not yet been fully realized. The Navy's agreement to act as a Steward for the marine and coastal resources of the offshore rocks surrounding SNI and Begg Rock requires

habitat protection, natural resource inventories, monitoring, and research commitments. Partnerships between the BLM and the Navy and other federal, state and non-governmental partners will facilitate implementation of those commitments. As no specific threats have been identified for these habitats, priority management actions will likely continue to focus solely on habitat protection.

Management Strategy

Objective: Maintain the integrity of the offshore rocks adjacent to SNI to insure a viable community with natural abundance and composition of invertebrates, fish, and wildlife.

- I. Support the MOU between the BLM and Navy (BLM MOU No. CA-939-08-02) for management of the offshore rocks near SNI, including Begg Rock, that are designated as part of the CCNM.
 - A. Serve as a CCNM Steward and work closely with the Core-Managing Partners CCNM and other CCNM partners.
 - B. Designate a contact person to serve as the Navy liaison with the CCNM.
 - C. Cooperate with the BLM on defining the monitoring and research needs for the CCNM and developing a strategy for implementing the protection, monitoring, and research needs consistent with the Navy's integrated natural resource management plans.
 - D. Provide information on existing and future Navy missions, subject to national security concerns, which could impact the CCNM, in order to assist the BLM in developing guidance on managing the CCNM.
 - E. Implement Navy activities to avoid or minimize negative impacts to the CCNM as practicable and consistent with the Navy mission.
 - F. Provide the BLM reasonable access and information, if needed, to the CCNM from San Nicolas Island and Begg Rock in a manner that is compatible with the Navy's activities, actions, schedules, and national security.
 - G. Report to BLM on an annual basis on known impacts to the CCNM, and activities and/or actions related to the CCNM undertaken by the Navy.
 - H. To seek opportunities to share information to enable BLM to carry out its protection, monitoring, research, and/or public education initiatives associated with the CCNM and unique coastal habitats and resource values to the extent Navy resources are available.
 - I. To work together to ensure consistency and coordination in the protection and management of the CCNM.II. Develop a plan for offshore rock habitat conservation.
 - J. Conserve fragile communities by limiting access and reducing human impacts from debris and or structures.
 - K. Limit disturbance and establish guidelines for buffer zones, closure periods, and access limitations.
 - L. Support the management of the Begg Rock State Marine Reserve designated in December 2012 (Title 14, CCR, Section 632 (b) (115).

4.4 Fish and Wildlife Management

4.4.1 Terrestrial Invertebrates

Specific Concerns

- There should be a sufficient inventory and monitoring program developed for terrestrial invertebrates.
- At least two introduced snail species, the European garden snail and predatory decollate snail are present on SNI and may pose a threat to the small remnant population of terrestrial land snails on SNI.
- Argentine ants are an invasive species that are a known threat to endemic populations on SNI.
- The California Wildlife Action Plan (Bunn *et al.* 2007) has identified the San Nicolas island snail as a state endemic special status invertebrate.
- Over a dozen taxa of terrestrial invertebrates and insects found on SNI are considered endemic specifically to SNI or to the Channel Islands.
- Native pollinators may have co-evolved with island endemic flora and be important to habitat and rare plant management.
- Invertebrates play ecologically crucial roles in the terrestrial ecosystem and are important food items for many birds, small mammals, and lizards.
- Insects are essential for decomposition and soil formation processes.

Current Management

A broad terrestrial invertebrate survey that addressed SNI was conducted in the 1970s for Point Mugu by Nagano; this project thoroughly studied the terrestrial invertebrates of Point Mugu and addressed SNI as a side project. Since the 1970s several researchers have also looked at specific terrestrial invertebrate families or genera, including snail studies. The latest terrestrial invertebrate survey for insects was conducted in 2015 by Ken Osborne. Yearly survey efforts for land snails are conducted by USGS employee Charles Drost.

Terrestrial invertebrates are formally managed from a habitat perspective through the utilization of the SA/PRB process codified in NBVCINST 11010.1B. Terrestrial invertebrates are also managed through informal interactions between the environmental staff and pest contractors that work on SNI. The environmental staff also looks out for new invertebrate arrivals during their daily routine while conducting fieldwork throughout the year.

David Holway from UC San Diego was funded in 2015 to conduct a feasibility study for Argentine ant eradication. If results show a fiscally plausible method for eradication, the Navy will pursue eradication efforts.

Assessment of Current Management

A need currently exists to supplement current management activities with educational opportunities to provide pest management contractors with awareness of the threat of exotic invasive terrestrial invertebrates. A formalized educational program may enhance the capacity of the environmental staff to utilize the time that pest management contractors spend in the field in order to detect introductions of invasive exotic invertebrates into habitats on SNI. For more information regarding management of terrestrial exotic invasive species refer to Section 4.6.1: Terrestrial Invasive Species.

Management Strategy

Objective: Conserve intact native invertebrate communities and develop measures to prevent the establishment and spread of invasive invertebrates.

- I. Determine baseline information on the invertebrate community of SNI, with particular emphasis on endemics.
 - A. Consolidate existing information on documented species.
 - B. Add support studies that would inventory insects and also focus on interactions between invertebrates and endemic fauna and flora.
 1. Support completing baseline field surveys for endemic terrestrial invertebrates that focus on understanding endemic invertebrate food resources such as endemic plants and surveys that focus on understanding which endemic invertebrates are utilized by endemic fauna.
 2. Support studies on all federally and state listed endemic plants to determine which invertebrates contribute to their pollination and are essential to their reproduction.
 3. Support completing baseline field surveys that assess interactions between invasive exotic terrestrial invertebrates and endemic flora and fauna.
- II. Develop educational materials that are provided to researchers, personnel, and contractors about the threats posed by exotic invasive terrestrial invertebrates.
- III. Protect cactus patches that contain San Nicolas Island snail from the invasive decollate snail and other threats such as development and erosion.
- IV. Develop biosecurity measures to make sure exotic invasive terrestrial invertebrates are not brought to SNI, and those that are detected early are responded to rapidly.
 - A. Enhance early detection and rapid response capacity by setting traps near the barge and airfield to monitor for new arrivals and screen soil and plants brought to SNI.

4.4.2 Reptiles

Specific Concerns

- The distribution of alligator lizards and side blotched lizards are expanding.
- There is a concern of the effect of a competitive interaction between alligator lizards and island night lizards upon the population stability of island night lizards.
- Potential for high predation pressure if appropriate plant cover is lacking due to non-native species cover or drought conditions.
- Island night-lizard habitat impacts from invasive plant species, habitat conversion, or development.
- Introduction of new predatory species to SNI via cargo plane or barge

Current Management

Since the delisting of the island night-lizard on May 1, 2014, the population on SNI will continue to be managed with an ecosystem approach, but with less emphasis on individuals and specific projects compared to when it was federally listed. There are no other native reptiles on SNI and no amphibians have been documented on SNI.

During the post-delisting time frame, the island night lizard population, habitat availability, and quality are required to be monitored for nine years. These surveys will quantify and assess quality of habitat and the abundance of the population over time. Surveying for the presence of lizards at specific sites will assess survival of known individuals; transects and pitfall trap within monitoring grids may also document population expansion of not only island night lizards, but also the potential expansion of other, non-native lizard species on island

Even though the island night lizard has been de-listed, measures to protect habitat and individual lizards will still occur. For example, some of the previous BO conservation measures require that island night lizards be relocated when doing construction, moving debris, or conducting vegetation management activities. This will continue for most projects, with attempts made to capture and relocate night-lizards in harm's way. All development or disturbance of undeveloped areas will avoid high quality island night lizard habitat.

Assessment of Current Management

Ongoing long-term monitoring of the island night lizard provides the SNI environmental staff an adequate mechanism for tracking population and identifying potential invasive introductions. The 2006 USFWS status review for the island night lizard listed feral cats as a major concern for the species. The recent removal of all of the cats off SNI should provide immediate benefits to island night lizards. While recent fox studies reported that island night lizards do not provide much of a food source to terrestrial island predators, predation pressure remains a potential threat to this resource. Conserving habitat integrity for island night lizards through management of habitat and prevention of habitat loss through implementation of the SA/PRB process and conservation measures provide the greatest contribution to sustaining populations of endemic lizards.

Management Strategy

Objective: Continue programs and collaborative efforts to minimize impacts and protect the federally listed and species warranting Navy stewardship to the maximum extent practicable.

- I. Support regular monitoring of reptiles in addition to island night lizard monitoring.
- II. Conserve the habitat integrity for this species by targeting habitat for protection where there is a higher population density of island night lizards and allowing future development to occur in those areas with lowest population densities.
- III. Continue to use of the SA/PRB process to avoid sensitive areas and minimize potential impacts.
- IV. Fulfill the post-delisting monitoring requirements by monitoring population and habitats for 9 years post-delisting.
- V. Survey habitats on the west side of the island, to determine and map the extent of occupied habitat in areas previously thought to be unoccupied.

4.4.3 Birds

Specific Concerns

- Of the over 300 species identified to utilize SNI, 58 have some special status assigned by government or non-government agencies (ESA, CESA, MBTA, U.S. Shorebird Conservation Plan, and U.S. Seabird Conservation Plan; see Table 3-8 under *Section 3.8: Special Status Species*).

- Bird species of the Channel Islands tend to have smaller populations and smaller breeding ranges, rendering these species to be more vulnerable to ecological stresses (Rich *et al.* 2004).
- There is uncertainty of the spatial extent of the effects of the Navy's management decisions on global populations of island breeding birds, specifically seabirds.
- Expansion of marine mammal populations within coastal habitats threatens the breeding success of several avian species of concern.
- Redistribution of gull nesting areas are affecting other species, such as the special status western snowy plover.
- There is uncertainty of the impact of competition between non-native bird species and endemic resident bird species.
- Weapons testing activities, such as missile launches, occur near a shorebird and seabird colony on the west end of SNI where nesting and breeding activities occur.
- There is uncertainty how the impacts from wildland fire, such as burned habitats that include ground nesting bird breeding areas, affect the reproductive success of those ground nesting bird species; several potential ignition sources for wildland fire exist on SNI (see *Section 4.2.3: Wildland Fire Management*).
- There is uncertainty of the effect of road maintenance and mowing impacts to ground nesting birds.
- Challenges exist for developing enforceable BMPs for road maintenance and mowing activities to minimize impacts to bird populations during breeding season while also minimizing the potential for weed dispersal.
- The operation of wind turbines for electrical energy production to supplement energy needs to support the military mission; antennas, guy wires, and wind turbines are hazards to migratory birds.
- A BASH plan had not been developed at SNI.
- The MBTA's Migratory Bird Rule and other DoD guidance and policies are in the early stages of implementation at SNI; military mission requirements that may affect migratory birds are to be specifically identified and monitoring set up to document whether adverse effects from military use could be significant at the population level.
- SNI lacks a robust standardized method to maintain the current status and long-term trend of migratory and resident bird populations.

Current Management

Migratory Bird Treaty Act

The MBTA of 1918 (16 USC 703-711) is legislation that covers species protected under four international treaties. These treaties are agreements between the U.S., Canada, Mexico, Japan, and Russia and protect most species of birds. The MBTA prohibits the taking or pursuing of migratory birds, their eggs, feathers, or nests. Game birds are listed and protected except where specific seasons, bag limits, and other factors govern their hunting. Exceptions are also made for some nuisance pests, which have standing federal depredation orders (e.g. yellow-headed, red-winged, tri-colored, Rusty and Brewer's blackbirds, cowbirds, all grackles, crows, magpies, rock doves, European starlings, and house sparrows).

The MBTA provides the USFWS the opportunity to comment on projects potentially affecting bird species, and their habitats, that are not protected under the ESA. Violations of the MBTA can result in fines of up to \$2,000 or two years imprisonment. Therefore, if a project has the potential to affect nesting birds or nesting substrate (including the trimming of nest trees) a qualified biologist from NAVFAC SW should be contacted to determine if there will be any

violations of the MBTA. U.S. Department of Defense policy states that migratory bird programs shall be established in support of and consistent with the military mission.

MOU Between the USFWS and DoD

In 2001, President Clinton issued EO 13186, requiring that federal agencies whose actions may affect migratory birds to develop and begin implementing, within two years, an MOU with the USFWS aimed at conserving these birds. It also established a federal interagency Council for the Conservation of Migratory Birds to help agencies implement the Order. In addition, the EO required NEPA evaluations to include effects on migratory birds and that advance notice or annual reports must be made to the USFWS concerning actions which result in the taking of migratory birds. The EO also required agencies to control the establishment of exotic species that may endanger migratory birds and their habitat.

The USFWS/DoD MOU (FR 30 August 2006) that evolved out of the requirements of the EO addresses the conservation of migratory birds on military lands in relation to all activities except readiness. The MOU is a guidance document on how the DoD will conserve migratory birds and does not authorize any take. In April 2007, further guidance was issued by the Under Secretary of Defense for Acquisition, Technology and Logistics on implementing the MOU to Promote the Conservation of Migratory Birds between the USFWS and DoD in accordance with EO 13186. This guidance covers all activities at SNI, including natural resources management, routine maintenance and construction, industrial activities, and hazardous waste cleanups. The guidance emphasizes interdisciplinary collaboration within the framework of the U.S. North American Bird Conservation Initiative Bird Conservation Regions, collaborative inventory and long-term monitoring.

Migratory Bird Rule

In an effort to provide guidance for conflicts arising between military readiness activities and the MBTA, the USFWS issued the final rule on, "Migratory Bird Permits: Take of Migratory Birds by the Armed Forces" (50 CFR Part 21 in FR 28 February 2007, pages 8931-8950), hereinafter referred to as the Migratory Bird Rule. The Migratory Bird Rule authorizes the military to "take" migratory birds during military readiness exercises under the MBTA without a permit, but if the military determines that the activity will have a significant adverse effect on a population of migratory birds, they must work with the USFWS to implement conservation measures to minimize and/or mitigate the effects.

The authorization for take requires an understanding of the definition of the following highlighted terms:

- *Population* is a group of distinct, coexisting (conspecific) individuals of a single species, whose breeding site fidelity, migration routes, and wintering areas are temporally and spatially stable, sufficiently distinct geographically (at some time of the year), and adequately described so that the population can be effectively monitored to discern changes in its status.
- *Significant adverse effect on a population* means an effect that could, within a reasonable period of time, diminish the capacity of a population of migratory bird species to sustain itself at a biologically viable level. A population is "biologically viable" when its ability to maintain its genetic diversity, to reproduce, and to function effectively in its native ecosystem, are not significantly harmed. This effect may be characterized by increased risk to the population from actions that cause direct mortality or a reduction in fecundity. Assessment of impacts should take into account yearly variations, and migratory movements of the impacted species. Due to the significant variability in potential military readiness activities and the species that may be impacted, estimates of significant measurable decline will be determined on a case-by-case basis.

Conservation measures under the Migratory Bird Rule require monitoring and record-keeping for five years from the date the Armed Forces commence their conservation action. During INRMP reviews, the Armed Forces must report to the USFWS migratory bird conservation measures implemented and the effectiveness of the conservation measures in avoiding, minimizing, or mitigating take of migratory birds.

Many questions remain about how to implement the Migratory Bird Rule. Uncertainty remains regarding how the evaluation of significance is to be addressed. Since the impact assessment must be conducted on populations of migratory birds, there will mostly be a need to collect more refined population baseline data.

Monitoring and Surveys

Annual monitoring and regularly scheduled surveys including project or readiness surveys are performed on SNI in compliance with the Migratory Bird Rule for all avian groups and potentially affected bird species.

Biannual western snowy plover surveys are completed during the spring and fall covering the entire island including facilities and recreational areas where plovers may nest. The biannual surveys are in compliance with the existing BO and coordinated with USFWS regional surveys to assess population dynamics and trends. Additionally, western snowy plovers that are located within the sphere of influence of a missile launch are monitored both before and after those launches in accordance with the conservation measures identified in the most current BO. Selected beaches, such as Tender Beach which is among the most used by nesting plovers, are also monitored regularly to determine hatch rates.

Aerial surveys focused on evaluating nesting seabirds, primarily cormorants, are accomplished annually. A minimum of two flights occur over nesting colonies and aerial photographs are used to determine the nesting population. Beginning in 2014, trail cameras programmed to take hourly time-lapse photos were placed in close proximity to nesting cormorants at Vizcaino Point and South Range Markers. Trail camera photos will be reviewed at the end of the nesting season to determine the efficacy of using this new strategy to monitoring nesting activity.

The Montrose Settlements Restoration Program has also funded the analysis of western gull data collected during the 1990s. Carter et al. (2014) concluded that there has been a significant decline in nesting gulls on SNI since the mid-90s, primarily due to impacts to the their nesting habitat from sea lions at Vizcaino Point, as well as, effects of fox and/or cat depredation.

Breeding bird surveys with permanently established point count stations were completed in 2000 (Wehtje 2000), and a bird checklist of species confirmed on SNI was documented in that report and incorporated into Appendix E. In 2012, HDR Inc. conducted point count surveys using a sub-set of the count stations utilized by Wehtje. Since 2013, NBVC has conducted point counts each nesting season at selected point count stations that were monitored by HDR in 2012 (HDR 2013b). These point counts will continue in upcoming years, to determine any changes in breeding land birds on SNI. It is hoped populations will increase due to the removal of cats off the island.

No general shorebird surveys are conducted SNI; existing shorebird surveys are focused on western snowy plovers and oystercatchers. Shorebird surveys for the oystercatchers are done at the same time as western snowy plover surveys. An in-depth study of oystercatchers, a state listed species, was completed in 2008 documenting their current status and breeding locations (Smith *pers. comm.* 2015). Anecdotal observations of rare shorebirds are recorded in a database.

Resident land bird, such as American kestrels and burrowing owls, are surveyed intermittently by SNI staff biologists. Land birds surveys were performed in 2009, in conjunction with the NEPA review of a wind turbine project. Upcoming wind turbine mortality surveys may also provide new data on species occurrence on island.

Nesting peregrine falcon surveys, funded by Montrose Settlements, were completed in 2013 and 2014 by Institute for Wildlife Studies. Two pairs of peregrine falcons successfully nested in 2013 and a total of 5 chicks were banded. Two pairs of peregrine falcons successfully nested in 2014, and three pairs in 2015 (P. Sharpe, *pers. comm.*). These were the first documented peregrine falcons nesting on SNI, although they may have nested on the island pre-DDT decline. Surveys to track this species will likely continue.

Chukar surveys were completed in 2013 to evaluate the population status and determine the feasibility of eradicating the species from SNI in the future. If eradication proceeds, additional intensive surveys may be needed.

Assessment of Current Management

Current management of avian fauna provides baseline inventory and habitat information sufficient to assess current conditions and track potential effects to most of the identified sensitive species. Interaction between SNI biologists and federal and state regulatory agencies have developed effective communication for monitoring strategies related to western snowy plover, cormorants, and other migratory birds.

A database with all bird data, such as the Avian Knowledge Network, would assist managers in determining changes in avian abundance and diversity across the island. A Checklist of the Birds on SNI developed by the Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History in 2000 may be used as a source of baseline data to develop this comprehensive database. New data may be added to this database as subsequent surveys are performed in the future. New survey data may also be added to appendices of this INRMP as part of the INRMP metrics annual update process. The intent of this INRMP is to provide an assessment of historic baseline data in the document while also providing an opportunity to update survey data.

A need exists for general land bird, shore bird, and sea bird monitoring to be done regularly and with a consistent scientifically acceptable methodology in order to document the status and trend of the Island's avian populations. SNI will continue to investigate and assess military use impacts on resident and migratory bird populations, such as nesting seabirds and shorebirds, in order to document any significant adverse effects to those populations and maintain compliance with the Migratory Bird Rule. The monitoring of the Vizcaino seabird colony and Cormorant Rock before and after missile launches should continue to ensure no significant impacts due to the launches. Previous evidence suggests that cormorants tend to stay on the ground whereas gulls take to flight as a group and then settle back down. Uncertainty as to the effects of missile launches upon this colony, requires that the effects of these military uses continue to be monitored.

An emerging management concern is the increase in marine mammal pinnipeds that have displaced habitat for shorebirds and seabirds. Focused studies are needed to document the loss of beach habitat to shorebirds and seabirds as a result of the increased use of those areas by marine mammals. This information will help identify any potential negative interactions that marine mammals may have upon special status avian species or seabirds.

Another emerging management concern is the need to reconcile road maintenance and mowing activities to take into account ground nesting bird breeding seasons while also minimizing the potential to disperse weed seeds. Surveys have occurred in 2014 to determine if migratory birds are nesting along mowed shoulders, however additional surveys are required. Conservation measures, such as those presented as management strategies for this section, are being developed to address this concern.

The NEPA assessment of the Wind Turbine project also led to the development of new conservation measures to protect migratory birds. For example, a recommendation has been made to outfit guy wires and infrastructure with visual deterrence devices (e.g. flappers) to protect migratory birds.

Lastly, the future development of a BASH plan specific to SNI may further contribute to conservation of bird populations at SNI. Especially if BASH plan involves the trapping and removal of non-native avian species, such as European starlings or chukar.

Management Strategy

Monitor populations and maintain, restore, and enhance habitats that provide for the health of migratory and resident populations of birds depending on NBVC SNI habitats to complete their life cycles, emphasizing Birds of Conservation Concern and other special status species.

Objective: Maximize the effectiveness of ongoing monitoring and management efforts for migratory birds that use SNI for breeding, nesting, resting, or feeding.

- I. Comply with the Migratory Bird Treaty Act, 2003 Defense Reauthorization Act Migratory Bird Rule, EO 13186, and other federal laws, regulations, and MOUs regarding the protection of migratory birds.
- II. Inventory and monitor habitat and populations of migratory birds that use SNI to evaluate conservation effectiveness through Navy efforts at SNI and by cooperating with other large-scale efforts.
 - A. Identify migratory bird species of concern for SNI that will be one of the focuses of monitoring (see Table 3-8).
 1. To identify bird species of concern, SNI adopts the species that may use its land and waters listed in periodic reports of Birds of Conservation Concern published by the USFWS Division of Migratory Bird Management¹; priority migratory bird species documented in the comprehensive bird conservation plans (U.S. Shorebird Conservation Plan, Colonial Seabird Conservation Plan, North American Waterbird Conservation Plan); species or populations of waterfowl identified as high, or moderately high, continental priority in the North American Waterfowl Management Plan²; focus species identified in the California PIF plans; listed threatened and endangered bird species in 50 CFR 17.11; and MBTA-listed game birds below desired population sizes.³
 - B. Maximize the effectiveness of ongoing monitoring and management efforts by continuing to implement standardized, scientifically sound survey protocols to collect and analyze population abundance and distribution of birds across water, upland, and transitional habitat types and seasonally. Ensure that survey protocols will establish current local population sizes and also permit credible estimates of population trends at sufficient intervals. By standardizing monitoring techniques, researchers ensure that results can be compared across space and time.
 1. Consolidate existing migratory bird monitoring information.
 2. Maximize the cost effectiveness and value of existing specialized monitoring programs for listed species by collecting standardized data on multiple species (such as point counts) in addition to any specialized protocols aimed at one species.
 - a. Continue efforts to monitor the established point count stations as a long-term standardized population monitoring program.
 3. Inventory birds using methods that can be integrated with the work of regional partners.

¹Available online at: <http://migratorybirds.fws.gov/reports/bcc2008.pdf>.

²Available online at: <http://www.waterbirdconservation.org>.

³Available online at: <http://migratory-birds.fws.gov/reports/reports.html>.

- a. Investigate the compatibility of the USDA Forest Service (USFS) published guidelines for standardized monitoring techniques for monitoring birds (Ralph et al. 1993) for use at SNI.
 - b. Determine how current established monitoring programs might contribute to regional databases and monitoring protocols, including the Breeding Bird Survey, Breeding Bird Atlas, Colonial Waterbird Surveys, International Shorebird Survey, Hawk Migration Surveys, Breeding Bird Census, Winter Bird Population Studies, survey information collected locally by federal and state agencies, and the USGS Bird Banding Laboratory. As appropriate, coordinate with Avian Knowledge Network and DoD e-bird databases to ensure bird monitoring data are submitted.
- III. The transitory nature of many migratory birds complicates assessment of the health of habitats and populations. In support of California PIF bird management plans, consider conducting intensive, long-term monitoring at selected sites for more than five years.
 - A. Collect and assess information on environmental contaminants and other physical or biological stressors having potential relevance to migratory bird conservation. Where such information is collected in the course of agency actions or supported through federal financial assistance, reasonable efforts shall be made to share such information with the USFWS, USGS-Biological Resources Division, and other appropriate repositories of such data.
 - B. To comply with the DRA, SNI should use the best scientific data available to assess through the NEPA process, or other environmental requirements, the expected impact of proposed or ongoing military readiness activities on migratory bird species likely to occur in action areas. Most importantly, ensure no significant population impacts to cormorants from missile launches.
 - C. Regularly monitor infrastructure that may pose a hazard to migratory birds, such as wind turbines, in order to document any significant adverse impact to migratory bird populations.
 - D. SNI should address impacts on species of concern thoroughly and specifically, focusing on the effects of the proposed action on the sustainability of these populations. Special consideration should be given to priority habitats, such as important nesting areas, migration stop-over areas, and wintering habitats.
 - E. Continue to update breeding bird surveys for migratory avian species.
 1. Link this effort with that of other needed surveys to cost-effectively evaluate ecological conditions and trends.
- IV. Include the results of monitoring in the annual review of this INRMP.
 - A. Promote research and information exchange, including coordinated inventory and monitoring (EO 13186).
 1. Increase communication and coordination between land managers and specialists hired to implement specific projects or conduct monitoring. Coordinate with monitoring and research projects targeted at non-avian taxa to maximize the benefits of the protection, management and restoration of riparian habitats.
 2. Continue to use cooperative assistance from wildlife agencies, organizations, and volunteers to help collect needed data. Integrate with regional databases.
- V. Conserve, restore, and enhance migratory bird habitat, as practicable. Improvements to existing habitat include wetland protection, maintenance and enhancement of buffers, and

- elimination or control of invasive species that may be a threat to migratory birds (2003 DRA Proposed Rule).
- A. Avoid detrimental habitat alteration caused by establishment or spread of invasive plants.
 - B. Avoid encroachment into the springs, seeps, and washes by preventing off-road activity and trespass into these areas.
 - C. Support biological research of species, interactions with mammalian predators, and impacts from increasing marine mammal presence.
 - D. Remove unused communication towers, antennas and other structures, which could pose a hazard to migratory birds.
 - E. When operationally practicable, follow the USFWS guidelines for the siting, construction and operation of communications towers.
 - F. Maintain and enhance primary roosting, foraging, and nesting sites.
 - 1. Identify opportunities for maintaining and enhancing primary habitats.
 - 2. Develop a migratory bird protection protocol for routine maintenance activities such as mowing and tree trimming.
- VI. Continue biosecurity measures to reduce any chance of new invasive species arriving on SNI via the barge or aircraft.
- A. Ensure that use, protection, and enhancement of naturally occurring and man-made water sources do not adversely affect use by avian species.
 - B. Continue efforts to ensure no new predators are introduced to SNI.
 - C. Continue efforts to keep island free of feral cats and other predatory species.
- VII. Identify opportunities through mitigation and non-mitigation funding to protect existing, restore degraded, and recover priority bird habitats.
- A. Support cleanup efforts to reduce contaminants and toxic buildup in the ecosystem, including monitoring and reducing nonpoint sources.
 - B. Remove any unused towers, antennae, and guy wires to eliminate these as a hazard to migratory birds.
- VIII. Implement bird conservation principles, measures, and practices through avoidance and minimization measures to protect migratory bird populations.
- A. The principal means of evaluating the effect of actions on migratory birds will be through the NEPA process or other established environmental review processes, with emphasis on species of concern (EO 13186).
 - B. NBVC will prepare NEPA analyses whenever it proposes to undertake a new military readiness activity that may significantly affect the quality of the human environment; make a substantial change to an ongoing military readiness activity that is relevant to environmental concerns; learn of significant new circumstances or information relevant to the environmental concerns bearing on an on-going military readiness activity; or prepare or revise an INRMP covering an area used for military readiness activities.
- IX. Avoidance measures will be discussed at the outset of project planning and followed, such as siting projects to avoid important nesting areas or to avoid collisions of birds with structures, or timing projects to avoid peak breeding activity.
- A. If take is inevitable, minimize the take of species due to military readiness.

1. EO 13186 and MBTA require that SNI provide notice to the USFWS in advance of conducting an action that is intended to take migratory birds and is not directly related to authorized military readiness activities, or annually report to the Service on the number of individuals of each species of migratory birds intentionally taken during the conduct of any agency action, including but not limited to banding or marking, scientific collecting, taxidermy, and depredation control.
 2. Develop standards, protocols, and procedures for such take.
 4. Review and evaluate actions that take migratory birds for means to avoid and minimize such take, with emphasis on activities that may affect the sustainability of migratory bird species at a population level.
- B. Identify areas of unintentional take of migratory birds and minimize such take. EO 13186 states that agencies will identify where unintentional take reasonably attributable to agency actions is having, or is likely to have, a measurable negative effect on migratory bird populations, focusing first on species of concern, priority habitats, and key risk factors. With respect to those actions, the agency (NBVC) shall develop and use principles, standards, and practices that will lessen the amount of unintentional take, developing any such conservation efforts in cooperation with the USFWS. These principles, standards, and practices shall be regularly evaluated and revised to ensure that they are effective in lessening the detrimental effect of agency actions on migratory bird populations.
1. Restrict access into and disturbance of nesting and breeding grounds during critical periods. Incorporate this restriction as a mitigation for proposed projects.
 2. Prevent or abate effects on migratory bird populations caused by pollution.
 3. Reduce pesticide use (see also *Section 5.11: Landscaping and Grounds Maintenance*). Prohibit the use of rodenticides outdoors. Limit its use to within buildings and only when there is a health risk. Properly dispose of any dead or dying rodents from a treated area to prevent the possibility of secondary poisoning through raptor predation of poisoned rodents.
- C. Provide training and information to employees regarding protection of migratory birds in compliance with laws to avoid and minimize take and conserve and restore habitat (EO 13186).
1. Limit disturbance during the breeding season. Promote understory and groundcover quality by postponing mowing until after peak breeding season if birds observed nesting in mowing sites. If mowing must be done during breeding season, maintain a low herbaceous layer of no more than six inches (15 cm) to discourage birds from nesting there. Limit restoration activities and disturbance events such as herbicide application to the nonbreeding season when possible. When such actions are absolutely necessary during the breeding season, time disturbance to minimize its impacts on nesting birds.
 2. Continue educational efforts on biosecurity, to ensure personnel are aware of the importance of not introducing new species to SNI and awareness of the resulting ecological damage of these introductions.
- D. Set guidelines to protect migratory birds such as requirements for towers and guy wires to reduce bird mortalities. Requiring protective measures such as bird flappers to be placed on lines, and the avoidance of guy wires where feasible, to reduce avian strikes.
- X. Reduce bird/animal aircraft strike hazards.
- A. Collect bird/animal aircraft incident data and maintain records of BASH incidents, including time of day, date, species involved, and location.

B. Continue efforts to develop and implement a BASH plan.

XI. Ensure that SNI biologists work closely with aircraft operations and the BASH team.

A. Mow airfield and adjacent areas to discourage use by avian species and manage any other habitat attractants.

B. Remove potential bird perches from the airfield vicinity.

C. Support censuses of the airfield area to determine avian usage patterns.

D. Remove or reduce non-native avian species frequenting the airfield.

Objective: Conserve viable habitat for resident birds that use SNI for breeding, nesting, and feeding. Continue to develop practical strategies that provide for the needs of federally-listed shorebirds and military values of the coastal strand and beach areas.

XII. Monitor populations of resident land birds.

A. Support biannual counts (using established methodology) of western snowy plovers, to determine relative abundance of species during breeding and non-breeding season.

B. Conduct point count surveys to determine changes in breeding land birds within a habitat and between habitats.

C. Support additional surveys to determine the status of American kestrels.

XIII. Support winter surveys to determine numbers and locations of burrowing owls.

XIV. Conduct roadside surveys to determine if migratory birds are nesting along shoulders that are mowed.

A. Investigate breeding bird use areas for land birds through using surveys that require a species-specific research design.

1. Support studies that investigate the habitat use of orange-crowned warblers on coreopsis or willow-patch.

2. Support studies that investigate the habitat use of house finches on cactus.

XV. Protect the sustainability of resident land bird populations and their habitat.

A. Set guidelines and standards for construction of towers and guy wires to reduce bird mortalities.

B. If migratory birds are found to be nesting on shoulders, conduct roadside mowing outside the breeding season of native ground nesting land birds. Mowing in the airfield should occur outside of the nesting season, as nesting in the airfield is likely. Promote understory and groundcover quality by postponing mowing until after peak breeding season. If mowing must be done during breeding season, maintain a low herbaceous layer of no more than six inches (15 cm) to discourage birds from nesting there. Limit restoration activities and disturbance events such as grazing, disking, and herbicide application to the nonbreeding season. When such actions are absolutely necessary during the breeding season, time disturbance to minimize its impacts on nesting birds.

C. Enhance important surface water areas used by resident land birds.

1. Continue *Arundo donax* removal and riparian restoration at Humphrey Sump.

2. Remove invasive non-native species at Humphrey Sump.

XVI. Monitor resident bird populations and breeding colonies.

- A. Develop a standard format and a database to collect and maintain records of shorebird observations on SNI.
 - B. Support studies that document the loss of sandy beach habitat as a result of the increased use of those areas by marine mammal pinnipeds.
 - 1. Support studies that investigate potential negative interactions between special status avian species such as the western snowy plover and increased use of sandy beach habitat by marine mammal pinnipeds.
- XVII. Increase the level of western snowy plover monitoring in order to determine nesting success.
- A. Continue to investigate and assess military activity effects on migratory birds, such as nesting shorebirds and seabirds, in order to comply with the MBTA.
 - B. Determine the status of selected species which nest on SNI, such as the peregrine falcon, black oystercatcher, and the western gull.
 - C. Use cooperative assistance from wildlife agencies, non-governmental organizations, and volunteers to collect needed data.
- XVIII. Protect the sustainability of resident bird populations and their habitat.
- A. Avoid shoreline construction that results in a loss of coastal strand/beach habitat, except for the currently planned improvement to the RO facility at Coast Guard Beach.
 - B. When development is required to support mission (new facilities, staging areas, etc.), all efforts should be made to utilize previously disturbed habitat.
 - C. If it is determined that a non-native species is having a direct effect on a sensitive native resident shorebird species, then take appropriate removal actions for the pest.
- XIX. Monitor resident seabird populations and breeding colonies.
- A. Increase seabird monitoring to capture nesting success, including camera studies if proven successful.
 - B. Continue to monitor at appropriate intervals for new species of seabirds that may begin nesting on SNI, such as Scripps's murrelet.
 - C. Continue aerial surveys of Brandt's cormorants nesting colonies to determine distribution and breeding population size.
- XX. Investigate methods to assess distribution of western gull nest sites and reproductive success.
- A. Support studies that investigate potential negative interactions of the redistribution of western gull nests into western snowy plover habitat.
 - B. Support outside research of seabird biology, interactions with mammalian predators, and impacts from increasing marine mammal presence.
 - C. Continue to investigate and assess military activity effects on migratory birds, such as nesting seabirds, in order to comply with the Migratory Bird Rule.
- XXI. Protect the sustainability of resident sea bird populations and their habitat.
- A. Maintain closure signs and gates around Brandt's cormorant nesting colonies.
 - B. Investigate feasibility of reducing island fox depredation on cormorant colonies.
- XXIII. Continue to provide educational materials regarding SNI's resident birds and management practices. Include information on what personnel can do to help, species lists, and activities detrimental to resident bird populations.

4.4.4 Terrestrial Mammals

Specific Concerns

- SNI has only two endemic terrestrial mammals, the San Nicolas Island fox and the San Nicolas Island deer mouse.
- The San Nicolas Island fox is susceptible to outbreaks of wildlife disease such as canine distemper and rabies, or human activities, such as vehicle strikes, drowning in treatment ponds, or falling into uncovered pipes or vaults.
- Potential for high predation pressure if appropriate plant cover is lacking due to non-native species cover or drought conditions.
- The San Nicolas Island deer mouse is a generalist feeder that is thought to play an important ecosystem role by feeding on larvae and pupae of terrestrial invertebrates that prey upon plant life.
- Rodent pest control practices, such as the use of rodenticide, poses a risk to raptors and the San Nicolas Island fox.
- Small numbers of bats have been observed to pass through and utilize SNI. However, the number of bats using SNI may be underestimated.
- Methods for monitoring for recent arrival of new predators (i.e., rats or mesopredators) should be developed.
- Future introductions through the barge or aircraft of terrestrial mammals such as rats may have significant ecological impacts.
- Potential for SNI deer mice to be transported to mainland through the barge.

Current Management

Terrestrial mammals are currently managed from a habitat perspective through the utilization of the SA/PRB process codified in NBVCINST 11010.1B. The pest management and control program at SNI also contributes to endemic terrestrial mammal management by restricting the use of poison rodenticide bait for rodent control. Prohibiting domesticated dogs (other than Force Protection working dogs) from accessing the Island also contributes to mammal management by avoiding harassment to endemic mammals and controlling a potential vector for wildlife disease.

The San Nicolas Island fox population is surveyed annually by utilizing grids and live trapping to estimate the abundance of this species over time. Additionally, recommendations made in the “Recovery Strategy for Island Foxes on the Northern Channel Islands”, such as a vaccination program that inoculates some of the population against canine distemper and rabies (Coonan 2003), are followed. In 2014, SNI will reinstitute a sentinel program to monitor for disease outbreaks with the use of mortality signal collars. Roadside mowing and education is to reduce vehicle strikes will continue. See *Section 4.5.2: Management for Other Special Status Species* for more details.

Assessment of Current Management

Current management of terrestrial mammals provides adequate capacity for inventory and habitat protection efforts as well as addressing concerns for the threat of an outbreak of wildlife disease. Interaction between the environmental program and the pest management and control program have enabled integrated pest management efforts to be compliant with environmental requirements, such as avoiding rodenticide use in developed areas to minimize the risk of poisoning endemic San Nicolas Island deer mouse populations. There are no threats to the San Nicolas Island deer mouse population given this current capacity and ability to coordinate with pest management activities. Furthermore, monitoring of the endemic deer mouse populations

would be valuable because of their abundance and their twin roles as important plant and seed consumers, and as prey for mammalian and avian predators on the island.

Sentinel monitoring will improve management capacity to detect early and respond quickly to future threats including a potential disease outbreak. To minimize the risk of a disease outbreak, a subset of SNI foxes will continue to be vaccinated for distemper and rabies. Additionally, biosecurity program will continue to monitor for non-native species such as raccoon, opossums, and dogs, all which can be potential vectors for introduced disease.

During 2014, bat populations will be monitored using an Anabat© detector placed at the evaporation ponds to continuously record ultrasonic echolocation calls. Echolocation data will be analyzed once or twice a year for species identification. This will provide additional information on the use of SNI by migrating bats. If bats are found to be more common than previously known, additional Anabat© detectors may be deployed at other strategic locations, such as Humphrey Sump and/or the wind turbine sites.

Management Strategy

Objective: Provide for healthy populations of native mammals by identifying and conserving diverse native habitats and habitat conditions that support mammals and ensuring that trade-offs of all military and biological projects to native mammals are considered in planning.

- I. Support deer mice monitoring programs at SNI that assess status, survival, home range, movement patterns, and prey abundance for mammalian predators.
- II. Support programs that contribute to maintaining endemic populations of the San Nicolas Island deer mouse and the San Nicolas Island fox.
- III. Continue to monitor island fox populations through trapping and sentinel monitoring.
- IV. Support programs to inventory and monitor bat populations on SNI.
- V. Continue efforts to control for the introduction of non-native mammalian species.

4.4.5 Marine Macroalgae

Specific Concerns

- Extractive uses, non-native invasive species, and climate change threaten the condition and biodiversity of marine macroalgae and plant communities. This in turn may affect the abundance and diversity of fish and wildlife.

Current Management

Current management of marine macroalgae below the shoreline to three nautical miles is the responsibility of CDFW. The Navy supports the mission and regulations of the State of California with aerial surveys used to estimate the surface coverage of giant kelp and annual subtidal surveys to examine various habitats. Navy biologists perform intertidal monitoring of marine macroalgae related to ASBS compliance. In 2014, a project was funded to establish a long-term monitoring program for rocky reefs and kelp forests that includes evaluation and characterization of macroalgae. Additionally, associated research conducted by other federal agencies and universities are supported by the installation.

Assessment of Current Management

The current understanding and documentation of marine macroalgae associated with SNI is primarily derived from studies conducted by various state and federal resource agencies and universities examining specific species or community assemblages. Sufficient data sets, pertaining to macroalgae species, exist for waters surrounding SNI documenting dominant species and habitat types. Monitoring of macroalgae achieves compliance with regulatory responsibilities and evaluates vulnerability, avoidance conflicts with the military mission, and assesses ecosystem health. Currently operational activities only indirectly interface with these habitats via storm water runoff; BMPs and the NBVC Site approval and project review board are also in place to avoid or minimize potential impacts to these resources.

Management Strategy

Objective: Support monitoring of macroalgae within intertidal and subtidal ecosystems at SNI for baseline information and integration with existing Channel Islands monitoring programs.

- I. Develop community-level marine macroalgae baseline information.
 - A. Continue monitoring water quality focusing on canyon outflows and those areas used for the ASBS Monitoring Program.
- II. Support continued annual aerial kelp surface coverage monitoring and integrate annual coverages into GIS database.
- III. Survey subtidal and intertidal areas near high use locations (piers and barge landing areas) for the introduction of non-native invasive algal species.

4.4.6 Marine Invertebrates

Specific Concerns

- The population of abalone species on SNI and along the west coast of North America declined dramatically in the mid-1980s due to disease and overharvesting.
- The population of sea stars on SNI and along the west coast of North America declined dramatically in 2014 and 2015 due to a disease event.
- Erosion on SNI and storm water runoff could affect water quality around the island and potentially impact marine invertebrates.
- The introduction of a non-native invasive species could devastate marine invertebrate populations around the island.

Current Management

Commercial fishing for invertebrates and fish species within subtidal waters of SNI has a long history. The island historically contributed significant annual catches of sea urchins, abalone, lobster, squid and finfish over the decades.

Current management of marine invertebrates below the shoreline to three nautical miles is the responsibility of CDFW. The Navy supports the mission and regulations of the State of California by collaborating with various state and federal resource agencies and universities acquiring baseline information on marine invertebrates. Navy biologists support or perform intertidal and subtidal monitoring of marine invertebrates to comply with ASBS regulatory standards. In 2014, two projects were funded to establish a long-term monitoring program for

intertidal and subtidal rocky reefs that includes evaluation and characterization of marine invertebrates in both of these communities.

Assessment of Current Management

Current management of marine invertebrates provides a substantial baseline inventory and habitat information that can provide key information on changes and trends. Long-term intertidal surveys beginning in the 1980s were supplemented with an additional program established in 2014. These surveys will continue to provide data on broad marine invertebrate populations and their associated habitats, document current conditions, and track the trend of key communities.

Management Strategy

Objective: Continue to support collection of baseline information on the status of marine invertebrate populations around SNI.

- I. Continue consistent monitoring program for marine invertebrates at SNI.
 - A. Continue to fund monitoring of SNI intertidal invertebrate populations using standardized monitoring protocols consistent with those used throughout the other Channel Islands.
 - B. Continue programs and collaborative efforts to minimize impacts and protect the federally listed and species warranting Navy stewardship to the maximum extent practicable.
 - C. Promote and discuss current long-term monitoring of black abalone populations established in the late 1970s (VanBlaricom 1993) and ensure that survey information on existing populations and trends are made available to the general scientific community.
 - D. Investigate the potential for remnant populations of white abalone, compile existing information, and document historical occurrences for future NEPA considerations.
 - E. Support evaluation and research of disease outbreaks that can impact marine invertebrates.

4.4.7 Fishes

Specific Concerns

- There is uncertainty if changes in fish populations may negatively impact federally endangered or threatened species or species warranting navy stewardship.
- There is uncertainty how overutilization of fisheries may impact ecosystem health.

Current Management

Current management of marine fishes out to three nautical miles is the responsibility of the State of California. The harvesting of fish and shellfish in SNI waters is managed directly by CDFW. Ocean fishing regulations are drafted by the Marine Region, reviewed in public hearings, revised if needed, and adopted by the Fish and Game Commission.

Harvest regulation seeks to manage sustainable populations through a combination of techniques: area and seasonal closures; gear limitations; and size, catch, and possession

limitations. The Navy supports the mission and regulations of the State of California by collaborating with the development of management and conservation areas (i.e., Cowcod Conservation Areas). The Navy worked collaboratively with the State of California during the Marine Life Protection Act initiative to designate Begg Rock as a State Marine Reserve. The Navy supports monitoring related to ASBS compliance as well as associated research conducted by other federal agencies and universities.

SNI's abundant marine life, including fishes requires consideration in daily management as well as for NEPA and Magnuson-Stevens Act compliance. CDFW currently monitors fish populations in several ways including fishery dependent data obtained by the surveying of commercial and recreational fishing vessels. Fisheries independent data is collected by intermittent surveys performed by CDFW and NMFS and typically focuses on commercially important species assemblages and species of concern.

Assessment of Current Management

Considering the isolated nature of SNI and the distance from the mainland, fishing pressure on SNI is substantially less than the other Channel Islands.

The current understanding and documentation of fishes associated with SNI is primarily derived from studies conducted by various state and federal resource agencies and universities examining specific species or assemblages. Existing datasets pertaining to marine fishes for waters surrounding SNI are focused on commercially important species. Currently operational activities on SNI only occasionally interface with fish and their associated habitat through erosion or storm water runoff and more directly from intermittent take by island personnel. Long-term kelp forest monitoring around SNI fulfills the need to investigate marine fish populations and their associated habitats through the implementation of a scientifically valid methodology able to document current conditions and track the trend of important constituents.

Management Strategy

Objective: Partner in long-term baseline monitoring occurring throughout the Channel Islands and make data available to the scientific community.

- I. Support the continuation of consistent monitoring to evaluate fish species.
- II. Increase environmental education programs for transient and island personnel through signs and other outreach to raise awareness of threats, concerns, and management needs for marine species.
- III. Continue to work collaboratively with state and federal agencies to implement and fund monitoring of existing SNI populations using standardized monitoring protocols consistent with those used throughout the other Channel Islands and California.
 - A. Conserve and protect kelp forest habitat to maintain its function as a food source, nursery, and protective environment for various fish species.

4.4.8 Marine Mammals

Specific Concerns

- There is uncertainty if disturbance of marine mammals from anthropogenic activities may alter their behavior and breeding success.

- There is uncertainty how the effects from global climate change may affect the distribution and abundance of marine mammals species observed in the vicinity of SNI.
- There is the possibility of disease outbreak within marine mammal populations.
- There is uncertainty if the expansion of existing marine mammal populations may reach a threshold that creates conflicts with the management of sensitive coastal habitat or other special status species.

Current Management

The MMPA requires the protection of marine mammals as well as making the take or import of those animals illegal, with specific exceptions. The USFWS is responsible for management of sea otters and NMFS is responsible for cetaceans and pinnipeds, other than walrus. The USFWS and NMFS may authorize and permit take (with limitations and mitigation measures) of marine mammals under their purview. Pinniped and southern sea otter occurrence on SNI is discussed in *Section 3.7.4: Marine Mammals*.

Upon receipt of an application from the Navy, NMFS issued regulations (50 CFR 217.50-58) to govern the unintentional takings of small numbers of marine mammals incidental to missile launch operations from SNI. These regulations allow NMFS to issue LOAs to the Navy in accordance with Section 101 (a)(5)(D) of the MMPA (DoN 2005). These Small Take Regulations address impacts to the northern elephant seal, California sea lion, and harbor seal. The LOA under these regulations is applicable for the entire 5-year regulation period.

Specific effects addressed in the regulations are primarily related to noise, such as startle responses (e.g. stampeding) and physiological stress. A suite of mitigation measures and monitoring and reporting requirements are required by the regulations to minimize these potential harassment-related takes. Current management of marine mammals at SNI is accomplished through the LOA in conjunction with the NMFS and is overseen by Navy biologists.

Other management includes the closure of beaches during pinniped breeding and pupping seasons. Additionally, the south side of SNI and Vizcaino Point are permanently closed to all recreational activity to reduce disturbance to pinnipeds. Navy operations are limited in these closed areas to reduce disturbance. Biologists escort most personnel requiring access to ensure pinniped disturbance does not occur.

Researchers are provided access to the island to conduct a variety of research on pinnipeds, with research providing valuable information to help manage and understand the populations both on island and across their ranges. Individual pinnipeds (usually elephant seals) are also moved on occasion when in harm's way, such as when seals move onto Beach Road.

NBVC funds aerial surveys to determine numbers of breeding pinnipeds. These surveys are conducted by NOAA, which has been surveying SNI and the other Channel Islands for decades. These surveys provide valuable information on the numbers and distribution of pinnipeds across SNI.

Sea otter surveys are also conducted by USGS twice a year. These are conducted from shore utilizing a telescope. These surveys provide the Navy with updated information on the numbers and distribution of otters in the nearshore waters.

Assessment of Current Management

Current management of marine mammals provides adequate capacity for resource and habitat protection efforts. Interaction between the SNI environmental program, NOAA, USFWS, and other researchers enables adaptive management to ensure island operations remain compliant with regulatory requirements. There are no current threats to the SNI marine mammal populations given the current status of individual species and their increasing numbers.

Management Strategy

Objective: Maintain compliance with MMPA mandates.

- I. Continue to monitor marine mammal populations and evaluate interactions related to island activities.
 - A. Ensure that activities that affect marine mammals are accomplished in accordance with the MMPA.
 - B. Apply for required authorizations as early in the project planning process as practicable for actions that may impermissibly impact marine mammals.
- II. Comply with conditions contained in regulations or authorizations granted to the Navy by the NMFS or the USFWS.
 - A. Continue the year-round closure of the south side and Vizcaino point to non-essential activities.
 - B. Maintain compliance with the MMPA by seasonally closing beaches when breeding pinnipeds, pups, or pregnant females are present.
- III. Monitor and protect island-wide pinniped breeding and haul out sites.
 - A. Maintain minimum flight level of 1,000 feet (305 m) over shoreline when pinnipeds are present, if operationally feasible, in accordance with the Small Take Regulations.
 - B. Continue aerial surveys for northern elephant seals, harbor seals, and California sea lions in cooperation with the NMFS to gather data on distribution, abundance, age structure, pup production, and reproductive phenology.
 - C. Maintain closure signs around breeding and haul out sites.
 - D. Continue educational instruction on marine mammal issues and individual responsibility for island personnel.
 - E. Continue to provide support for pinniped research by outside agencies or universities.
- IV. Continue to support USGS surveys of sea otters.
- V. Maintain adaptive management strategies to address complex issues related to marine mammal resource conflicts and occurrence.
 - A. Comply with Navy marine mammal stranding notification policy to address scientific evaluations of rare or unusual occurrences.
- VI. Maintain the educational kiosks and display boards on SNI and update if needed.
 - A. Update the educational kiosk on SNI.

4.5 Special Status Species Protection

4.5.1 Federally Listed Species and Critical Habitat

Specific Concerns

The ESA was revised via the NDAA of 2004 (PL 108-136) to recognize INRMP conservation measures and species benefit that could obviate the need for critical habitat designation on Navy lands. All Navy installations with federally listed threatened or endangered species, proposed federally listed threatened or endangered species, candidate species, or unoccupied habitat for a listed species where critical habitat may be designated, must structure the INRMP to avoid the designation of critical habitat. The INRMP may obviate the need for critical habitat if it specifically addresses both the benefit provided to the listed species and the provisions made for the long-term conservation of the species. The species benefit must be clearly identifiable in the document and should be referenced as a specific topic in the INRMP table of contents.

The USFWS and NMFS use a three-point criteria test, to determine if an INRMP provides a benefit to the species. An installation is strongly encouraged to use these criteria, listed below, when structuring its INRMP to avoid the need for critical habitat designation.

1. The plan provides a conservation benefit to the species. The cumulative benefits of the management activities identified in a management plan, for the length of the plan, must maintain or provide for an increase in a species population, or the enhancement or restoration of its habitat within the area covered by the plan (i.e. those areas deemed essential to the conservation of the species). A conservation benefit may result from reducing fragmentation of habitat, maintaining or increasing populations, insuring against catastrophic events, enhancing and restoring habitats, buffering protected areas, or testing and implementing new conservation strategies.
2. The plan provides certainty that the management plan will be implemented. Persons charged with plan implementation are capable of accomplishing the objectives of the management plan and have adequate funding for the management plan. They have the authority to implement the plan and have obtained all the necessary authorizations or approvals. An implementation schedule, including completion dates, for the conservation effort is provided in the plan.
3. The plan provides certainty that the conservation effort will be effective. The following criteria will be considered when determining the effectiveness of the conservation effort. The plan includes: (1) biological goals (broad guiding principles for the program) and objectives (measurable targets for achieving the goals); (2) quantifiable, scientifically valid parameters that will demonstrate achievement of objectives and standards for these parameters by which progress will be measured are identified; (3) provisions for monitoring and, where appropriate, adaptive management; (4) provisions for reporting progress on implementation (based on compliance with the implementation schedule) and effectiveness (based on evaluation of quantifiable parameters) of the conservation effort are provided; and (5) a duration sufficient to implement the plan and achieve the benefits of its goals and objectives.

Current Management

Activities relating to and management of federally threatened and endangered species on SNI are primarily guided by the terms and conditions of the BO for Activities on San Nicolas Island,

California (1-8-01-F-14). Annual BO reports are provided to the USFWS to discuss impacts from activities to the western snowy plover (and previously the island night lizard).

The current management of federally threatened and endangered species populations of SNI are addressed through the INRMP at both the individual and community level by avoidance, minimization, and monitoring measures developed to achieve conservation benefits. Conservation efforts and strategies at SNI have been implemented with approval and funding from the SNI command and follow recognized monitoring methodologies. Annual INRMP metric updates provide a formal means to utilize adaptive management and review progress made for protecting and conserving the federally threatened and endangered species at SNI.

Assessment of Current Management

SNI is in the early stages of documenting and reporting its achievements under the three-point criteria for avoiding critical habitat designation for the western snowy plover. Other than this, current management of threatened and endangered species on SNI is adequate to maintain compliance responsibilities, identify threats, and minimize potential impacts. Current communication and partnerships with federal and state regulatory agencies is providing an adaptive management framework able to sustain the military mission while insuring long-term conservation of the species. The Navy participated as a member on NMFS black abalone critical habitat committee and continues to work directly with NMFS to ensure protection of black abalone on SNI.

Management Strategy

Objective: Protect and maintain viable populations of threatened and endangered species and maintain compliance with ESA requirements.

- I. Ensure that land use plans and activities in or near threatened or endangered species habitats are accomplished in accordance with the ESA.
 - A. Conduct formal and informal consultations with the USFWS and NMFS as early as practicable in the project planning process for actions that may affect listed species in accordance with ESA Section 7 Consultation Handbook (USFWS/NMFS March 1998).
 - B. Comply with requirements of species or site-specific consultations and with terms and conditions of Section 7 Consultation BOs. Consider Conservation Recommendations provided in Section 7 Consultation BOs.
- II. Comply with the Incidental Take Statement in the USFWS 2001 BO (USFWS 2001).
 - A. Consider Conservation Recommendations (USFWS 2001) regarding San Nicolas Island fox, domestic pets, feral animal removal, and listed species research permits.
- III. Monitor and conduct censuses of the listed species covered under a BO for Activities on SNI (USFWS 2001), for the purpose of monitoring the effects of Navy activities on these species in accordance with the Terms and Conditions listed in the BO.
 - A. Monitor the barge landing area and other areas of concentrated human activity for non-native species and remove any such species found in accordance with the Terms and Conditions listed in the USFWS 2001 BO (USFWS 2001).
 - B. Provide the USFWS an annual report containing the number of western snowy plovers killed or injured by Navy activities, and a summary of Navy activities and their effects on listed species in accordance with the Reporting Requirements in the USFWS 2001 BO (USFWS 2001).

IV. Review all existing and new structures to determine which shall be fitted with materials to prevent their use as perches by predatory birds in accordance with the Terms and Conditions listed in the USFWS 2001 BO (USFWS 2001).

Western Snowy Plover - Federally Threatened

Specific Concerns

According to BO for Activities on San Nicolas Island, California (1-8-01-F-14) and the western snowy plover recovery plan (USFWS 2007a) current threats to the recovery of the western snowy plover include:

- Habitat loss and fragmentation from development.
- Mortality, injury, and disturbance resulting from overutilization due to military and human activities.
- Displacement from preferred nesting areas as a result of increasing pinniped populations, disturbance by humans, and predation.
- Natural and anthropogenic factors, such as inclement weather, oil spills, and management of other special status species that may have an affect on the quality and quantity of western snowy plover habitat.

Current Management

Consistent biannual western snowy plover monitoring has been conducted since 1995. After the implementation of a BO in 1997 monitoring and annual surveys for the western snowy plover became a required natural resource management action.

Continued implementation of the discretionary conservation measures and reasonable and prudent measures, and the non-discretionary terms and condition identified in the BO for activities on San Nicolas Island, California (1-8-01-F-14) and other SNI management measures has been sufficient to preclude the designation of critical habitat as well as provide adequate detail to the status and trend of the western snowy plovers at SNI for over fifteen years. SNI management measures include but are not limited to the following activities:

- Bi-annual population surveys (window surveys);
- Nest monitoring near launch areas and selected beaches;
- Beach closures to recreational use and human access during breeding season;
- Permitting only necessary activities to take place in coastal habitat in order to avoid impacts to breeding habitat; and
- Scheduling routine maintenance for coastal facilities outside of breeding season.

Exclusion of the general public to SNI in conjunction with beach specific access and use limitations of island personnel and activities reduces the potential for incidental impacts and develops resource awareness. Island resource managers have developed detailed maps of important habitat areas and continue to document threats from increasing populations of marine mammals.

Assessment of Current Management

Current management of western snowy plovers, in the context of the federal ESA, provides adequate capacity for inventory, habitat protection, and avoiding and minimizing impacts from military activities.

Interaction between the environmental program and regulatory agencies is compliant with environmental requirements, such as reporting the status of the population and the effectiveness of implemented conservation efforts. Concerns regarding the SNI western snowy plover population is primarily related to interspecies habitat competition and anthropogenic threats.

Management Strategy

Objective: Protect, monitor and maintain a viable population of western snowy plovers.

- I. Protect western snowy plover populations and habitat.
 - A. Maintain compliance with the ESA by closing nesting areas to recreational activity during the March 1 - September 15 breeding season for beaches commonly used for nesting, closing other areas when nests are present. Alternative measures to ensure compliance will be evaluated periodically.
 - B. Maintain signs around breeding sites to alert personnel of closures.
 - C. Conduct an invasive plant control program in western snowy plover habitat.
 - D. Remove unnecessary structures in snowy plover nesting areas in accordance with the Terms and Conditions of the BO (USFWS 2001) and attach avian excluders to essential structures, if feasible.
 - E. Conduct amphibious training exercises on beaches not harboring nesting western snowy plovers.
- II. Monitor western snowy plover populations and habitat.
 - A. Conduct island-wide snowy plover censuses twice annually, once during the breeding season and once during the winter season. Alternative monitoring programs may be implemented if they are determined to provide adequate monitoring data.
 - B. Monitor snowy plover nests prior to missile launches, general operations, and other activities that may disturb nesting behaviors in accordance with the Terms and Conditions listed in the BO (USFWS 2001).
- III. Conduct site-specific western snowy plover surveys in potential or known breeding habitat prior to disturbance activities as required by the BO (USFWS 2001).
 - A. Continue efforts to determine nesting success of snowy plovers on high bird use beaches such as Tender Beach.
- IV. Support research to explore the effects of increasing pinniped populations on nesting success of western snowy plovers.
- V. Educate island personnel regarding protected species regulations and responsibilities.
- VI. Develop and maintain a computer database for storing information on locations of nesting sites, incidental sightings and size and results of surveys for resource management purposes.
- VII. Support recovery plan efforts to establish stable western snowy plover populations and eventual delisting.
 - A. Continue to participate with recovery planning and other efforts to help establish stable snowy plover populations.

Black Abalone - Federally Endangered

Specific Concerns

- Disease (i.e. withering syndrome) and predation.
- Natural and anthropogenic factors (i.e. toxins).
- Suboptimal water temperatures associated with effluents, El Niño Southern Oscillation events, and long-term climate change.

Current Management

Ongoing long-term black abalone research, performed by Dr. VanBlaricom and supported by the island's command since the 1970s, provides one of the most important population studies on the species within the SCB. Dr. VanBlaricom began studying the distribution of black abalone in 1981 and continues to conduct annual monitoring to document trends in black abalone populations at SNI. The total SNI black abalone population has been increasing since 2001. In addition, Dr. VanBlaricom has been systematically mapping black abalone habitat around SNI. This mapping effort will provide detailed GIS layers with black abalone habitat quality. Dr. VanBlaricom's studies provide valuable trend data on the status of the black abalone as well as identifying sensitive areas and potential vulnerabilities from both natural and anthropogenic impacts. This work also has implications for larger scale recovery of the species throughout its range. The CDFW also conducted black abalone surveys at Corral Harbor annually from 1992-1996. An additional site was established to the west of Corral Harbor in 2010 and both sites have been sampled annually since.

The island's rocky intertidal habitat along the shorelines of SNI are restricted access to the general public which partially protects the population. Cooperation with the CDFW in enforcing the restricted areas and support of USGS studies evaluating rocky intertidal habitat has developed data on existing conditions and promotes natural resource stewardship.

Certain areas of SNI are also are restricted to access by Navy staff and SNI personnel. The southern shoreline is one area where all access is restricted due to marine mammal and seabird protective measures. This access restriction also ensures that any anthropogenic disturbance or impacts are avoided to black abalone habitat in the rocky intertidal zone. Due to the rugged terrain, limited access, signage and oversight by security, compliance with these area restrictions is high.

Impacts to black abalone habitat are also generally avoided and minimized through the NBVC SA/PRB process codified in NBVCINST 11010.1B.

Assessment of Current Management

Current management through ongoing monitoring efforts at multiple locations on SNI in conjunction with long-term monitoring at the other Channel Islands provides federal and state regulators invaluable data on the trend of the black abalone population over the central portion of its range. The listing of black abalone as a federally endangered species in January 2009 requires that the Navy consider this species as a management focus species and support surveys and other conservation measures for the protection and maintenance of this population. The current black abalone monitoring efforts conducted by Dr. VanBlaricom provide a sufficient baseline of information, but should be integrated into the standardized regional protocol used within the other Channel Islands and supplemented with community ecology studies to examine habitat associations. Continued implementation of the NBVC SA/PRB process for projects that will impact the rocky intertidal zone will help avoid and minimize impacts to SNI's black abalone population.

Management Strategy

Objective: Protect black abalone habitat and existing populations on SNI.

- I. Continue to support population surveys.
 - A. Complete mapping of abalone habitat around SNI.
- II. Continue to support surveys to provide additional information on current conditions and establish regular monitoring intervals.
 - A. Continue to support the monitoring of rocky intertidal sites on SNI using accepted scientific methodologies to provide complementary data sets documenting trends of key rocky intertidal species assemblages.
 - B. Support scientific studies to investigate recruitment and predation.
 - C. Support the monitoring of key environmental variables that may play an important role in modulating population dynamics.
- III. Develop educational materials for personnel and visitors informing them of black abalone issues and their role in helping to preserve the species.
- IV. Continue to support appropriate closures at SNI.
 - A. Continue the SNI south side area closures, limiting access to and protecting habitat for the largest known black abalone population sites.
- V. Continue to review all military activities to ensure compliance with ESA and avoid or minimize impacts to black abalone.
- VI. Integrate historical monitoring data sets into SNI databases for management consideration.
- VII. Support recovery plan efforts to establish stable black abalone populations.
 - A. Support Channel Islands-wide review of population status of the species.

White Abalone - Federally Endangered

Specific Concerns

- There is uncertainty of the status and trend of white abalone populations at SNI.

Current Management

Prior to the listing of white abalone under the ESA, the State of California closed the white abalone fishery in 1996 and subsequently closed all abalone fisheries in central and southern California in 1997 (NMFS 2009). The NMFS published a final rule listing the white abalone as an endangered species under the ESA on 29 May 2001 (66 FR 29046) (NMFS 2001). In October 2008, the NMFS White Abalone Recovery Team published the final recovery plan for the white abalone (NMFS 2008a) and announced that Plan in the Federal Register (73 FR 62257).

Currently, surveys have not been conducted specifically to identify white abalone population baseline levels at SNI. Rather, white abalone management is accomplished through nearshore habitat management and compliance with ASBS conservation measures. Surveys are planned in 2016 that will search potential white abalone habitat around SNI to determine if they continue to exist in the area.

Assessment of Current Management

White abalone populations in the nearshore waters surrounding SNI are managed by the CDFW and the NMFS. Nearshore habitat management and compliance with ASBS conservation measures may be sufficient to protect and maintain white abalone populations at SNI. Lack of data on the presence, location, and abundance of white abalone around SNI limits the ability to understand potential impacts to the species.

Management Strategy

Objective: Protect and maintain viable populations of white abalone in suitable rocky substrate habitat at SNI.

- I. Support efforts to identify white abalone habitat and densities of individuals around SNI.
 - A. Support targeted surveys and integrate historical data sets into SNI databases for management consideration.
- II. Implement complementary baseline surveys to provide more obtainable information on current conditions.
 - A. Support scientific studies to investigate recruitment and predation.
- III. Support recovery plan efforts to establish stable white abalone populations.
 - A. Support Channel Islands wide review of population status of the species.

Guadalupe Fur Seal - Federally Threatened

Specific Concerns

- There is uncertainty if there is a sufficient monitoring program to observe the presence of Guadalupe fur seals on SNI, since any occurrence will likely be very few individuals, and may be for short periods.
- There is uncertainty if current military uses harass Guadalupe fur seals and reduce the probability that individuals will haul out and breed on SNI, if they are more sensitive to disturbance than California Sea Lions.
- Occurrences of sightings of Guadalupe fur seals are very rare on SNI.

Current Management

On 16 December 1985 (50 FR 51252) the NMFS determined that the Guadalupe fur seal should be listed as a threatened species under the ESA. Concurrent with this rule, the USFWS amended the U.S. List of Endangered and Threatened Wildlife by adding the Guadalupe fur seal as a threatened species. The designation of the Guadalupe fur seal as a threatened species under the ESA automatically qualifies this species as a depleted and strategic stock under the MMPA. Critical habitat was not established because the only areas that are essential to the conservation of the species and may require special management consideration or protection are outside of the jurisdiction of the U.S. The State of California has also listed the Guadalupe fur seal as a fully protected mammal in the Fish and Game Code of California (Chap. 8, sec. 4700, d), and it is listed also a threatened species in the Fish and Game Commission California Code of Regulations (Title 14, sec. 670.5, b, 6, H).

The Navy currently supports aerial and land-based surveys that help determine presence of fur seals on SNI. During these surveys, photographs are taken and any fur seals would be identified. A variety of pinniped researchers and other marine biologists frequent coastal areas

of SNI. Therefore, any use of the islands by fur seals may also be observed and documented by marine researchers. Any new observations will likely result in an increased effort to monitor that site or individual, to determine how long it remains.

Assessment of Current Management

Current management is adequate to document any increase in use of SNI by fur seals. However, if use by fur seals continues to be very rare and by few individuals, they may be undocumented. If population increases, surveys would increase to ensure monitoring is adequate to monitor this population.

Sandy beach habitat management and compliance with ASBS conservation measures support marine mammals by protecting habitat quality and reducing disturbance, such as the Guadalupe fur seal, which occasionally haul out and use sites at SNI. Marine mammal monitoring activities are generally related to the surveys used to support compliance with the NMFS LOA. There is uncertainty if these surveys that target northern elephant seals, California sea lions, and harbor seals may be sufficient to identify population baseline levels for the Guadalupe fur seal individuals that haul out on SNI. The Navy will continue to support surveys with other federal partners such as NOAA. Management must balance any additional monitoring of the Guadalupe fur seal with the fact that focused surveys may harass other marine mammals present at haul out locations. If sightings of Guadalupe fur seals become more prevalent on SNI then other management measures will be taken.

Management Strategy

Objective: Resolve baseline biological data gaps for Guadalupe fur seal populations at SNI.

- I. Support ongoing and new research on distribution and ecology of the Guadalupe fur seal. Encourage academic institutions to facilitate resource data collection.
- II. Record all sightings of Guadalupe fur seals and develop a database to track numbers of individuals, time of year, and location.
- III. If individuals are sighted, revisit site to determine how long individuals remain and document if breeding occurs.

Southern Sea Otter – Federally Threatened

Specific Concerns

- USFWS terminated the southern sea otter translocation program by declaring the program a failure. This effectively designated the translocated SNI experimental sea otter population as threatened.
- Navy exemption from the ESA and MMPA for the southern sea otter population at SNI was reinstated with the 2016 National Defense Authorization Act.

Current Management

The Secretary of the Interior determined on 14 January 1977 (42 FR 2968) that the southern sea otter was a threatened species for the purposes of the ESA. On 15 August 1986 (51 FR 29384) the USFWS proposed the establishment of an experimental population of southern sea otters. This experimental population represents a different population than that designated as threatened under the ESA. In August 1987, the USFWS developed a final rule (52 FR 29754) to establish this experimental population and began translocating this population of southern sea otters to SNI in the SCB as part of the recovery action for these

animals (Riedman and Estes 1990; USFWS 2003a). On 27 September 1988 (53 FR 37577) the USFWS published technical amendments to the sea otter translocation regulations as a final rule.

The last sea otter in the experimental population was released at SNI in July 1990, for a total of 140 sea otters (USFWS 2003a). Of the 140 sea otters released, the fate of 70 is known. At least 13 sea otters are thought to have remained at SNI after their release (USFWS 2003a). The number of otters at SNI has varied since the population was translocated, however, as of 2005 the population has been steadily increasing and in 2015 the population was estimated at approximately 95 individuals (Hatfield *pers. comm.*).

The 2016 National Defense Authorization Act Section 312 amends Chapter 631 of Title 10 USC § 7235 by establishing the Southern Sea Otter Military Readiness Areas at SNI (including Begg Rock) and the adjacent and surrounding waters, and Naval Base Coronado, San Clemente Island, and the adjacent surrounding waters. Sections 4 and 9 of the ESA and Sections 101 and 102 of the MMPA shall not apply with respect to the incidental taking of any southern sea otter in the Southern Sea Otter Military Readiness Areas in the course of conducting a military readiness activity. It also states that southern sea otter within these areas shall be treated for the purposes of Section 7 of the ESA, as a member of a species that is proposed to be listed as an endangered or threatened species. For activities that do not support military readiness, sea otters residing at SNI are still considered part of the federally threatened population and treated as such. Within the 2016 National Defense Authorization Act, 'military readiness activity' has the meaning given that term in section 315(f) of the Bob Stump National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2003 (16 U.S.C. 703 note).

Assessment of Current Management

The Navy continues to support semi-annual surveys by USGS to assess the resident population of southern sea otters at SNI and facilitate research and adaptive management strategies. Nearshore habitat management and compliance with ASBS conservation measures may be sufficient to protect and maintain southern sea otter populations at SNI.

Management Strategy

Objective: Support population surveys for the southern sea otter population at SNI.

- I. Continue to support on-going and new research on distribution and ecology of the southern sea otter at SNI. Encourage academic institutions to facilitate resource data collection.
- II. Conduct monitoring and research within the Southern Sea Otter Military Readiness Areas to determine the effects of military readiness activities on the growth or decline of the southern sea otter population and on the nearshore ecosystem. Monitoring and research parameters and methods shall be determined in consultation with the USFWS.
- III. Prepare reports every three years for the Secretary of the Navy.

4.5.2 Management for Other Special Status Species

Specific Concerns

- The effects of invasive species on several species of special status vascular plants on state lists, CNPS lists, or that are island endemics for which SNI has suitable habitat or known occurrences.

- The effects of invasive species on special status terrestrial invertebrate species on SNI: the San Clemente Island coenonycha beetle, the San Nicolas Island snail, San Clemente Island snail, and San Clemente Island blunt-top snail.
- The Scripps's murrelet was listed as a federally threatened and endangered candidate species in 2004 (FR Vol. 69 No. 86). Surveys were attempted most recently in 2014, but did not occur due to weather. Acoustic surveys are planned for in 2016 and potentially 2015. Spotlight surveys may also occur in 2015 and 2016. There is a very low potential for use by the island now or in the future, but the Navy should conduct an adequate presence/absence survey to confirm their absence. If the population is very small, use may be harder to document. If no Scripps's murrelets are found during surveys, additional surveys should occur a minimum of once every 10 years to monitor for any future colonization of the island.
- The ashy storm-petrel was proposed to be listed as a threatened and endangered species. However, on 22 October 2013, the USFWS determined listing was not warranted at this time. There is a very low potential for use by the island now or in the future by storm-petrels, but the Navy should survey for them to confirm their absence. If the population is very small, use may be harder to document. If no storm-petrels are found during surveys, additional surveys should occur a minimum of once every 10 years to monitor for any future colonization of the island.
- There is not much information regarding the island's endemic orange-crowned warbler. More information is needed on its nesting success and preferred habitats.
- The San Nicolas Island fox was listed under the ESA as a species of concern (59 FR 58982). This species may be at risk due to the spread of disease or arrival of novel predators (such as the golden eagle).
- Deer mice are one of two native terrestrial mammals on SNI. A disease outbreak or introduction of other rodents may threaten their population.

Current Management

The Navy recognizes the value of maintaining diverse ecosystems. The Navy also recognizes that it is prudent to protect rare species as a proactive strategy to prevent future federal listings. To the extent that resources are available to support the management of these species, NBVC intends to implement the following objectives and strategies. The Navy complies with the laws pertaining to regulated species by avoiding and minimizing impacts to those species and their habitat.

- Snail surveys have been done and will continue to determine distribution of native and non-native snails.
- Storm-petrel and murrelet surveys will be done a minimum of every 10 years, unless individuals are identified nesting during planned surveys in 2015 or any other future documented sighting, in which case monitoring will frequency will increase.
- Navy will support any research on sensitive species.
- Sensitive plant surveys are programmed to occur every five years.
- Island fox surveys occur each year, including an inoculation program and sentinel program to manage for and monitor for disease outbreaks.
- Nesting peregrine falcon surveys occur at a minimum, every other year.
- Deer mice surveys are done once or twice a year at established study sites.

Assessment of Current Management

The habitat based and species specific management measures proposed in this INRMP in conjunction with the NBVC SA/PRB process provide a sufficient level of natural resource management to protect and conserve species warranting Navy stewardship at SNI.

Management Strategy

Objective: Species warranting Navy consideration and the habitats which support those species, will be protected to the extent practicable by giving them consideration during the land use planning processes.

- I. Provide for the recovery, enhancement, and protection of species warranting Navy stewardship, as a proactive strategy to prevent federal listings.
 - A. Maintain contact with regional specialists and regulatory agencies regarding the listing status of unique species known or thought to occur on SNI.
 - B. Continue to participate in the USFWS/NMFS review and listing process for species known or thought to occur on SNI that are being considered for listing under the ESA.
- II. Stay updated on agency decisions, published material, and meetings that change the listing status of species.
 - A. To the extent practical, avoid or minimize impacts from military activities to species warranting Navy stewardship.
- III. Continue to resolve baseline biological data gaps.
 - A. Support ongoing and new research on distribution and ecology of species warranting Navy stewardship. Encourage academic institutions to facilitate resource data collection.
 - B. Continue to inventory and map existing species warranting Navy stewardship.

Special Status Plants - State Endangered, State Threatened, State Rare, and CNPS Rare, Threatened, and Endangered

Specific Concerns

The relative distance of SNI from other landmasses has resulted in the development of reproductively isolated populations of unique plants. Flora that may warrant stewardship are those which fall into any one of the following categories:

- Federally listed
- State listed
- Proposed for federal listing or a former Category 2 or 3 species
- Are considered rare
- Are taxonomically undescribed
- Are an endemic species
- Are on the CNDDDB lists
- Occur on CNPS Inventory of Rare Plants with a status of 1B or rarer
- Identified as being of scientific interest

There are no federally listed or proposed for federal listing plant species that are known to occur on SNI. However there are several species of vascular plants on state lists, CNPS lists, or that are island endemics for which SNI has suitable habitat or known occurrences. All plants that have a CNPS listing of 1B or rarer, which includes all state listed species here on SNI, are regarded as valuable natural resources. Measures to ensure their survival and healthy rebound should be considered when discussing management issues.

One of the most effective ways to preserve unique plant species is by assembling and evaluating the available information, and then utilizing that information during the land planning stages of projects and activities. By doing so, a list of specific concerns can be developed and from that a prioritized strategy approach can be created. Generally speaking, the current State of the special status plants that either are known to occur or have the potential to occur on SNI has yet to be identified. Beyond that, there are some environmental conditions that do not favor the recovery of certain species.

A list of specific concerns that if addressed would likely result in an increased knowledge base as well as suitable conditions for species survival is as follows:

- Navy operations and facility development and maintenance activities contribute to loss of suitable habitat.
- There are soil erosion conditions that are destructive to sensitive plant communities.
- There is uncertainty of pollinators for sensitive endemic plants.
- There is uncertainty of increased competition from invasive non-native species.

Current Management

The focus of current management has been a long-term, sustained investment in invasive plant control. Invasive plant control is prioritized by the potential of the plant species to spread, its proximity to sensitive species, and by current operations (see *Section 4.6: Invasive Species*). BMPs have been implemented to prevent invasive plant introduction and spread.

The current management of vegetation communities and special status plants is in compliance with the OPNAVINST 5090.1D plan for the conservation of natural resources. All plans for building and activities follow the established SA/PRB process developed for DoD properties.

Sensitive plant surveys for special status plants were conducted by Steve Junak between 1999 and 2003; a total of 21 sensitive plant taxa were included in the study and sixteen of the study taxa were found (Junak 2003). The special status plants that have been identified for SNI are identified in *Section 3.8.2: Other Special Status Species* and Table 3-6. Sensitive plant taxa on SNI were also mapped during surveys conducted on the island in the early 1990s (Junak *et al.* 1995, 1996) and again in 2013. These earlier surveys were conducted to support establishment of vegetation monitoring plots that were placed in representative plant communities on SNI and on other Channel Islands under the jurisdiction of the NPS in a joint effort. These plots were monitored annually from 1993–1996 (Junak *et al.* 1995, 1996) and resampled in 2009 (TDI 2009).

Assessment of Current Management

SNI is able to accomplish stewardship of special status plant populations through the use of the NBVC SA/PRB process in conjunction with construction BMPs. SNI is also able to assess the current status and trend of special status plant species through the vegetation monitoring program that utilizes established monitoring plots and sensitive plant surveys.

Scarce resources are available for the development of an island herbarium, which may be considered to improve the management of special status species and their populations that occur on SNI.

Management Strategy

The habitat or ecosystem (rather than individual species) focus of this INRMP is expected to result in integrated recommendations which will serve to protect SNI and target communities as a whole. The key is to strike the acceptable balance between natural habitat values and SNI's military mission. Current constructive management efforts will be sustained while

adopting more up to date research tools and adaptive management approaches. Initially this will greatly increase the amount of data specific to SNI. In doing so and continuing to do so valuable accurate datasets will assist in the development of resource conservation programs. Furthermore, systematic surveys will prove valuable in better understanding the island as a whole and how the military mission at SNI can be upheld.

Objective: Protect the natural diversity and long-term viability of the ecological and evolutionary processes in all natural communities and habitats consistent with DoD ecosystem management policy, including no net loss in the capability of SNI lands to support its military mission.

- I. Continue to support efforts to conduct an inventory of special status plants on SNI.
 - A. Support vegetation surveys that use the established vegetation monitoring plots.
 1. Coordinate a terrestrial invasive non-native species assessment with re-occurring vegetation surveys.
- II. Investigate habitat and reproductive requirements for sensitive endemic plants species that occur on SNI.
- III. Conserve special status plant species habitats and populations.
 - A. Conserve habitat that has known species occurrences or has the potential based on habitat characteristics.
 - B. Support population specific programs that are specific to each special status plant species population that identifies threats and develops solutions based on the particular situations at hand.
- IV. Perform erosion control efforts under their specific management plan.
- V. Restore natural habitat with rare plants whenever the environment is suitable (if necessary).
- VI. Control invasive non-native species as detailed within their specific management plan.

Terrestrial Invertebrates

Specific Concerns

- There is one beetle and three land snail special status terrestrial invertebrate species on SNI: the San Clemente Island coenonycha beetle, the San Nicolas Island snail, San Clemente Island snail, and San Clemente Island blunt-top snail.
- The three snail species are highly restricted in range.
- The San Nicolas island snail is vulnerable to military activities or other actions which may result in the introduction of exotic species or cause erosion.
- The principal threat to the San Clemente Island snail is habitat loss.

Current Management

Terrestrial invertebrates are formally managed from a habitat perspective through the utilization of the SA/PRB process. Terrestrial invertebrates are also managed through informal interactions between the environmental staff and pest contractors that work on SNI. The environmental staff also looks out for new invertebrate arrivals during their daily routine while conducting fieldwork throughout the year.

Assessment of Current Management

A need currently exists to supplement current management activities with educational opportunities to provide pest management contractors with awareness of the threat of exotic invasive terrestrial invertebrates. A formalized educational program may enhance the capacity of the environmental staff to utilize the time that pest management contractors spend in the field in order to detect introductions of invasive exotic invertebrates into habitats on SNI. For more information regarding management of terrestrial exotic invasive species refer to *Section 4.6.1: Terrestrial Invasive Species*.

Management Strategy

Objective: Protect special status native invertebrate species and develop measures to prevent the establishment and spread of exotic invasive invertebrates.

- I. Determine baseline information on the special status native invertebrate species of SNI.
 - A. Consolidate existing information on documented special status species.
 - B. Support studies that focus on interactions between invertebrates and endemic fauna and flora.
 1. Support completing baseline field surveys for insects, focusing on special status endemic invertebrate food resources such as endemic plants and surveys that focus on understanding which special status endemic invertebrates are utilized by endemic fauna.

Scripps's Murrelet - Federal ESA Candidate

Specific Concerns

- On SNI, Scripps's murrelets are perennial visitors in nearshore waters around the island but are not documented to nest or breed on the island or its offshore rocks.
- Threats to populations include predation, oil spill, and lack of available prey items.
- There is uncertainty if there is a sufficient monitoring program to observe the presence of Scripps's murrelet on SNI.
- There is uncertainty if current military uses harass Scripps's murrelet and reduce the probability that individuals will rest and breed on SNI.

Current Management

The Scripps's murrelet was listed as a federally threatened and endangered candidate species in 2004 (FR Vol. 69 No. 86). SNI's implementation of the SWPPP contributes to ensuring that nonpoint source storm water discharge does not impact the Scripps's murrelets population. ASBS water quality compliance also contributes to ensuring that impacts to water quality do not affect the offshore foraging activities of Scripps's murrelets.

Regional seabird surveys have been conducted by USGS and NOAA over the past two decades to help understand the foraging ecology of murrelets. A survey for Scripps's murrelet occurred in 1980, with no murrelets observed and habitat deemed as inappropriate. Acoustic and potentially spotlight surveys are planned for in 2015 and 2016. An attempt was made to conduct a spotlight survey in 2014 but could not be completed due to weather constraints.

Assessment of Current Management

The Navy supports seabird monitoring efforts through regional avian research partnerships. The Navy also records current sightings of this species at SNI and adjacent nearshore waters. The Navy continues to support efforts to identify and monitor population baseline levels and trends in their population.

Management Strategy

Objective: Support the monitoring of Scripps's murrelets populations at SNI.

- I. Provide for the recovery, enhancement, and protection of Scripps's murrelets as a proactive strategy to prevent federal listings.
 - A. Support seabird surveys identifying species warranting Navy stewardship known or thought to occur on SNI.
 - B. Support survey of offshore rocks adjacent to SNI to confirm the presence/absence nesting habitat of Scripps's murrelets.
- II. Stay updated on USFWS decisions, published material, and meetings that change the listing status of species.
 - A. To the extent practical, avoid or minimize impacts from military activities to Scripps's murrelets.
- III. Continue to resolve baseline biological data gaps.
 - A. Support ongoing and new research on distribution and ecology of Scripps's murrelets. Encourage academic institutions to facilitate resource data collection.
 - B. Record all sightings of Scripps's murrelets and develop a database to track numbers of individuals, time of year, and location.
- IV. Survey intermittently offshore for foraging Scripps's murrelets.

Ashy Storm-Petrel – previously proposed as a Candidate Species

Specific Concerns

- Ashy storm-petrels have been confirmed to breed at 26 locations (on islands and offshore rocks) with breeding concentrated in two population centers at the Farallon Islands and in the California Channel Islands (Carter et al. 1992).
- On SNI, ashy storm-petrels are perennial visitors in nearshore waters around the island but are not documented to nest or breed on the island or its offshore rocks.
- Threats to populations include predation, oil spill, and lack of available prey items.
- There is uncertainty if there is a sufficient monitoring program to observe the presence of ashy storm-petrel nesting on SNI.
- There is uncertainty if current military uses harass ashy storm-petrel and reduce the probability that individuals will rest and breed on SNI.

Current Management

Surveys for storm-petrels just offshore of SNI are planned to occur in 2015 and/or 2016 (while searching for Scripps's murrelets), with future surveys done approximately every 10 years (unless individuals are found nesting, in which case monitoring frequency will increase). There are no current offshore surveys to determine frequency of use offshore, however it is likely

storm-petrels use surrounding waters. The Navy also records anecdotal sightings of this species offshore of SNI. In the event storm-petrels begin using SNI, then additional management will occur to protect nesting areas from disturbance and to aid in nesting success. SNI's implementation of the SWPPP contributes to ensuring that nonpoint source storm water discharge does not impact the ashy storm-petrel population. ASBS water quality compliance also contributes to ensuring that impacts to water quality do not affect the ashy storm-petrel's offshore foraging activities.

Regional seabird surveys have been conducted by USGS and NOAA over the past two decades to help understand the foraging ecology and distribution of storm petrels.

Assessment of Current Management

As storm-petrels are not known to nest on SNI and SNI does not have what is considered appropriate nesting habitat, infrequent surveys are adequate to monitor for storm-petrel use, as long as monitoring increases if sighting increases and/or nesting is confirmed. The Navy also supports seabird monitoring efforts through regional avian research partnerships.

Management Strategy

Objective: Support the monitoring of ashy storm-petrel populations at SNI.

- I. If found to nest on SNI in the future, provide for the recovery, enhancement, and protection of ashy storm-petrels, as a proactive strategy to prevent federal listings.
 - A. Support seabird surveys, identifying species warranting Navy stewardship known or thought to occur on SNI.
 - B. Support surveys a minimum of every 10 years to monitor for adults use of near-shore environment around SNI during the nesting season.
- II. Stay updated on USFWS decisions, published material, and meetings that change the listing status of species.
 - A. To the extent practical, avoid or minimize impacts from military activities to ashy storm-petrels if they are found nesting on SNI.
- III. Continue to resolve baseline biological data gaps.
 - A. Support ongoing and new research on distribution and ecology of ashy storm-petrels. Encourage academic institutions to facilitate resource data collection.
 - B. Record all sightings of ashy storm-petrels and develop a database to track numbers of individuals, time of year, and location.

San Nicolas Island Fox - State Threatened

Specific Concerns

- The island fox, which includes all six subspecies on all six islands, was listed under the CESA as a state threatened species on 27 June 1971.
- A Recovery Strategy for island foxes on the northern Channel Islands was published by the CINP in August 2003.
- The San Miguel Island fox (*Urocyon littoralis littoralis*), Santa Rosa Island fox (*Urocyon littoralis santarosa*), Santa Cruz Island fox (*Urocyon littoralis santacruzae*), and Santa Catalina Island fox (*Urocyon littoralis catalinae*) were all included in a final rule that listed them as federally endangered species under the ESA on 05 March 2004 (69 FR 10335).

- The San Nicolas Island fox was listed under the ESA as a species of concern (59 FR 58982).

Current Management

Management of the San Nicolas Island fox population consists primarily of maintaining population levels through protection of habitat and reduction of human-caused impacts. Habitat protection on SNI is accomplished through implementation of the SA/PRB process.

The San Nicolas Island fox population has been monitored annually since 2000. The population currently appears to be in the midst of sustained decline. The island-wide population estimate was 619 in 2009. As of 2013, the population estimate was 341 individuals.

Assessment of Current Management

Management and monitoring of the San Nicolas Island fox is sufficient. If a sudden disease outbreak were to occur, the annual monitoring program and intermittent transects will capture any sudden decline or change in the abundance of the population. The Navy will continue to minimize vehicle mortality collisions by enforcing speed limits and conducting roadside maintenance activities.

Anthropogenic factors are a well-documented source of fox mortalities, particularly vehicle strikes, but also, occasional accidental entrapment or drowning. Each year between 1993–2013, an average of 17 foxes have been killed by vehicles and two died of entrapment or drowning. In order to address these issues, several mitigation measures have been put in place including: improving signage, increasing educational and outreach efforts, and identifying ways to improve fox visibility on roads, as well as driver awareness.

It is important to have adequate management capacity for both early detection and quick response to population threats, particularly introduced diseases. From 2006–2009, a subset of island foxes were tracked as disease sentinels via radio-telemetry in order to gather baseline data on background mortality rates and causes. In light of the current population decline, in 2014, the sentinel program was re-established, with radio-collared foxes monitored weekly via aerial telemetry. This will serve to enhance the understanding of factors influencing the current population dynamics thereby improving management.

Management of the San Nicolas Island fox will continue to benefit from efforts to develop a Draft Candidate Conservation Agreement (CCA) between the Navy and the USFWS for the San Nicolas Island fox. Implementation of such an agreement would formalize education, monitoring, necropsy, and management. There also exists a need to have adequate management capacity to detect early and respond quickly to future threats to mammal populations such as an incident of disease outbreak. If such an incident were to occur there is a need to discover mortality events early. Questions remain as to the efficacy of using remote monitoring technology to monitor a mortality event to prevent a wildlife disease incident occurring in the San Nicolas Island fox population. Management will continue to follow the Channel Islands Fox Recovery Team guidelines by implementing a vaccination and disease control program that focuses on distemper and rabies.

Management Strategy

Objective: Maintain a viable population of the San Nicolas Island fox by reducing human impacts.

- I. Maintain a viable population of the San Nicolas Island fox.
 - A. Continue to monitor and study fox demographics and ecology through annual fox monitoring to determine population, age structure, and density.
 1. Determine current levels of reproductive success, disease, and causes of mortality.

2. Maintain vaccination cover for rabies and canine distemper virus in at least 50–100 island foxes.
 3. Using radio-telemetry, monitor a sample of foxes to detect mortalities.
 4. Any island foxes found dead should be scanned for PIT-tags and mortality data entered into master database. Specimens should be collected and shipped or frozen immediately for necropsy.
 5. Any island foxes appearing ill or acting in an abnormal manner should be reported immediately and monitored.
 6. Annually collect blood samples from a proportion of foxes evaluate ongoing disease risk.
 7. Develop an emergency response strategy for dealing with disease incidents relevant to island foxes.
- B.* Implement conservation measures to decrease the number of foxes killed by vehicles, to increase the visibility of foxes on roadsides, and to increase our knowledge of the distribution of island foxes in relation to various vegetation communities.
1. Continue prohibition of domestic dogs on SNI to protect foxes against transfer of infectious canine diseases.
- C.* Ensure working dogs and their handlers continue to adhere to guidelines established in NBVC Force Protection's K-9 Unit Standard Operating Procedures.
- D.* Continue implementing invasive non-native monitoring, control, and removal programs.
1. Develop a management strategy for responding to new introductions of non-native species to SNI.
 2. In the event that cat trapping is required in the future, trapping strategies and protocols that effectively target cats but avoid impacts to foxes, to the extent feasible, will be implemented.
- E.* Ensure that pest management practices minimize harm to island fox and deer mouse populations. Continue to restrict the use of rodenticides to avoid secondary poisoning of foxes and discourage habitation of buildings by mice through appropriate measures.
- F.* If specific locations are known to be used by trespassers that may bring dogs ashore, post signs in these locations stating that trespass is illegal and that the presence of dogs can threaten sensitive wildlife.
- II.* Reduce negative, human-caused impacts to foxes.
- A.* Maintain island speed limit at 35 mph or less.
 - B.* Adapt roadside mowing to increase visibility of foxes to drivers.
- III.* Maintain roadside signs warning of foxes.
- A.* Maintain fox exclusion devices at food waste disposal sites.
 - B.* Continue education of island personnel to fox issues and their role in helping to preserve the species.
- IV.* Remain an active participant with other agencies regarding island fox issues.
- A.* Maintain contact with regional specialists and regulatory agencies to stay updated on the listing status of the Island fox.

San Nicolas Island Deer Mouse – Endemic Species

Specific Concerns

- The status of the San Nicolas Island deer mouse population is unknown at this time, however, it is assumed they are common.
- A routine monitoring program that assesses the current status of the San Nicolas Island deer mouse population exists, however, it only monitors one small area of the island.

Current Management

The San Nicolas Island deer mouse population varies based on seasonal weather patterns affecting vegetation and predation by wildlife. The status of the population is unknown but is thought to oscillate based on rainfall. The management of the San Nicolas Island deer mouse is primarily accomplished through vegetation habitat management and minimizing human caused impacts through utilization of the SA/PRB process.

The pest management and control program at SNI also contributes to endemic terrestrial mammal management by restricting the use of poison rodenticide bait for rodent control. Prohibiting domesticated dogs from accessing the island also contributes to mammal management by avoiding harassment to endemic mammals and controlling a potential vector for wildlife disease.

Intermittent surveys have been conducted to assess the status of the San Nicolas Island deer mouse population by utilizing deer mice monitoring grids, which have been monitored by USGS. Previous university studies have also been conducted to study the San Nicolas Island deer mouse.

Assessment of Current Management

There is a potential need to add more sampling grids to the small mammal monitoring program at SNI. A standardized monitoring program ideally will conduct surveys either in the spring and/or fall. There is also a need to analyze, synthesize, and report on all the San Nicolas Island deer mouse studies that have been conducted at SNI.

Management Strategy

Objective: Determine the status of deer mouse populations.

- I. Determine the status of deer mouse populations.
 - A. Establish and implement a monitoring program to evaluate population status and overall health.
 - B. Survey various vegetation cover types to investigate habitat associations to better provide better management information.
- II. Establish a data base to store current and historical data series and survey information.
- III. Conserve and protect deer mouse habitat.
 - A. Continue to monitor for nonnative species that could compete with deer mice (house mouse).
 - B. Remove non-native predators (feral cats).
 - C. Use rodent control devices in structures and not rodenticides.
- IV. Remain an active participant with other agencies regarding deer mouse issues.

Island Night Lizard – Recently Delisted

Specific Concerns

- The island night lizard is the only endemic reptile species on SNI.
- The island night lizard is a species with low fecundity which makes it sensitive to disturbance and impacts from human activity.
- Argentine ants are an invasive terrestrial invertebrate species which represent a potential future threat to island night lizard populations at SNI.
- Removal of island night lizards by island personnel for pets or sale.

Current Management

Surveys have been and will likely be conducted by the USGS to monitor island night lizard populations post-delisting. As required in the post-delisting monitoring plan, surveys will occur every other year over a nine year period. On survey years, density and recruitment will be determined to analyze and monitor for changes in population status. On year three and year nine, habitat quality and quantity will also be determined, to monitor for changes in habitat availability.

When debris that may harbor island night lizards or appropriate island night lizard vegetation requires clearing, NBVC biologists attempt to capture island night lizards and relocate them to nearby habitats. This is usually done early morning when lizards are cold and easier to capture. Efforts to capture and relocate occurred in the past for any and all activities that occurred in night lizard potential habitats when species was federally listed. The Navy will continue its efforts to reduce mortality and capture and relocate, but efforts will likely be reduced, with efforts focused on capturing and relocating for activities and sites that are more likely to harbor or impact island night lizards.

High quality island night lizard habitats (cactus and boxthorn) are avoided and protected from any and all disturbance. At times habitats may be impacted if along a roadside, near culverts, or utility corridors, but all other sites are conserved for night lizard habitat protection.

NBVC has also began restoring habitat for night-lizards in 2013, by planting cactus and other species used by island night lizards in appropriate areas. With the continued development of the SNI nursery, efforts to out-plant for island night lizard habitat restoration will continue.

Impacts to island night lizard habitat are generally avoided and minimized through the NBVC SA/PRB process codified in NBVCINST 11010.1B. BMPs have also been developed and implemented to avoid and minimize impacts to island night lizard habitat.

Assessment of Current Management

Island night lizards and their habitats are appropriately managed to support their current population and to support a growing population. The island night lizard is affected by the actions of humans and predation. Construction activities pose the greatest threat to island night lizards by the removal of their habitat. Site specific surveys are conducted when development projects are being reviewed through the SA/PRB process. Habitat enhancement projects are also considered to support the viability and stability of the island night lizard population.

Management Strategy

Objective: Maintain a viable population of island night lizards on SNI.

- I. Continue to develop and implement protocols to resolve any baseline biological data gaps and to monitor distribution, population size, population trends, and habitat usage of the Island night lizard population.
 - A. Conduct site-specific surveys in known or suitable habitat prior to disturbance activities.
- II. Protect and maintain island night lizard habitat quality and integrity.
 - A. Conduct an invasive non-native control, monitoring, and removal program in Island night lizard habitat in order to reduce impacts upon the Island night lizard population.
 - B. Define and clearly mark work areas during road maintenance and other activities to prevent island night lizard mortality.
- III. Exclude high quality lizard habitat areas from the roadside-mowing regime.
 - A. Maintain a bare ground buffer zone around equipment and storage areas in high quality island night lizard habitat where practicable.
 - B. Site staging areas for storage of equipment and materials in areas with low island night lizard densities, whenever feasible.
- IV. Conduct relocation of island night lizards when activities occur in areas with high potential for night-lizards.
- V. Support studies to investigate the effectiveness of island night lizard management strategies.
 - A. Support scientific studies of competition relationships between alligator lizards and island night lizards.
 - B. If warranted based on results of current genetic study, continue to support additional genetic studies of isolated island night lizard populations to determine population structure and size.
- VI. Prepare a Navy instruction clearly stating the prohibition of taking night-lizards off island and educate island personnel on this restriction.
- VII. Support continued monitoring as required in the delisting monitoring plan, with monitoring to continue less frequently after nine year monitoring period.

4.6 Invasive Species

Specific Concerns

- Invasive exotic species are one of the leading causes of degraded ecological condition and ecosystem services (National Invasive Species Council 2001); climate change has the potential to interact with this stressor through multiple mechanisms (Fischlin et al. 2007; National Invasive Species Council 2008; EPA 2008).
- Experience elsewhere shows that ignoring an invasive exotic species often leads to a crisis situation where the species can no longer be eradicated and actions to limit the population become very expensive, if not impossible (Cohen and Carlton 1998).

- Exotic species invasion poses one of the most serious threats to the integrity of SNI's ecosystem, and the rate of local introduction is probably increasing, as has been shown on the nearby mainland coast (Crooks 1998).
- Very little is known about the effects on the SNI ecosystem.

Current Management

DoD management of invasive non-native species is guided by EO 13112 (03 February 1999).

A weed eradication plan for the island was developed by the environmental staff at SNI (Agri Chemical and Supply Inc. 2014b). Task orders have been developed to implement that plan by eradicating highly invasive non-native plant species. Initial non-native plant control treatments on SNI were carried out by Agri Chemical and Supply Inc. beginning in May 2001. This non-native plant control effort focused primarily on fennel and short-podded mustard, although several other target non-native species were treated in 2008, including: arundo, agave, cliff aster, smilo grass, and milk thistle (Agri Chemical and Supply Inc. 2009). Beginning in 2010, Sahara mustard was also mapped and treated (V. Vartanian, *pers. comm.*, 2010).

Assessment of Current Management

As an island ecosystem, SNI is particularly vulnerable to the introduction of invasive non-native (e.g. exotic) species. Plants and animals which evolved in other locations may have ecological advantages over native species which evolved without the presence of certain pathogens/parasites endemic to a species or without levels of competition and predation present elsewhere. If conditions are hospitable, newly introduced species can become established and out compete native species. The intensity of the interaction between native and invasive species could change with anticipated effects from global climate change such as changes to warming and drying scenarios in Mediterranean type ecosystems like that present at SNI. Warming and drying trends are likely to induce substantial species-range shifts, and imply a need for migration rates that will exceed the capacity of many endemic species (Fischlin et al. 2007). Vegetation structural change driven by dominant, common or invasive species may also threaten rare species (Fischlin et al. 2007). There is a difference between the potential for natural colonization of habitats that have undergone structural change due to global environmental change and colonization by invasive non-native species that results from human induced disturbance in the terrestrial or aquatic environment.

Management of invasive non-native species nationwide is focusing on those non-native species presently having obvious negative effects on native species populations. Studies of invasive non-native species have revealed that observed effects may range from "relatively large spatial (habitat-wide) and temporal-scale (decades) to small-scale interactions that take place in a matter of weeks" (Crooks 1998; Reusch and Williams 1998). To be effective, management actions need to understand non-native invasions in the context of the existing and historical natural systems. Some invasive non-native species have taken decades since introduction to become a "pest," showing that it is "potentially dangerous" to predict the future status of a non-native invader from its current status (Crooks 1998). Timing is of the essence, since delays in implementing appropriate control or extirpation measures can cause the measures to be ineffective if the invading non-native population grows too large.

Maintaining quality habitat should also help prevent or minimize invasions of non-native species. Anthropogenically disturbed sites, even when disturbed temporarily for restoration purposes, show an increased number of invasive non-native species (Crooks 1998). Altered hydrologic, soil, and fire regimes can also contribute to non-native plant germination and establishment.

Once invasive exotic species are established, at least five types of management controls can be used: (1) mechanical (through physical removal), (2) chemical (through conventional pesticides), (3) biological (through introduction of known natural predator or parasite), (4) harvest management (through promotion of a sport or commercial fishery for aquatic invaders) and (5) fire for terrestrial invaders. Biological controls are still in the experimental stage but hold promise. Each type has associated advantages and disadvantages, and combinations of more than one can be applied. Through adaptive management, managers can learn from experience to help identify the best tools for control of invasive non-native species. Targeting control of the most invasive, potentially ecosystem-damaging species in a timely fashion should also be a high priority because not all non-native species create serious problems.

4.6.1 Terrestrial Invasive Species

Specific Concerns

- Regional concerns for terrestrial invasive exotic species management on SNI include but are not limited to invasive terrestrial plants, invasive terrestrial invertebrates, invasive terrestrial birds, and invasive terrestrial mammals.
- Established populations of invasive exotic terrestrial plants are present in SNI, which include fennel, short-podded mustard, Sahara mustard, arundo, cliff aster, smilo grass, *Euphorbia terracina*, oyster plant, and milk thistle.
- Invasive exotic terrestrial invertebrate species that pose a potential threat to the integrity of SNI's terrestrial ecosystem include but are not limited to the Argentine ant, the European garden snail and the predatory decollate snail.
- Invasive exotic birds at SNI include but are not limited to chukar and European starlings.
- Established populations of chukar are present on SNI; although used for hunting on the mainland there is no hunting permitted on SNI so it may be considered an invasive bird species rather than a game species.
- Introduced terrestrial mammals pose a serious risk to the integrity of various avian, reptile, and mammal species.
- Future introductions of exotic terrestrial mammals such as rats may impact and compete with endemic mammals.

Current Management

Executive Order 13112 requires federal agencies to prevent the introduction of invasive non-native species and provide for their control (DoN 2005). Implementation of EO 13112 is covered by the National Invasive Species Council's 2008–2012 National Invasive Species Management Plan (National Invasive Species Council 2008). Management objectives and strategies in this INRMP build upon the framework discussed in the 2008–2012 National Invasive Species Management Plan. In addition to EO 13112, the Federal Noxious Weed Act (7 USC § 2801 *et seq.*) explicitly provides for the control and eradication of noxious (e.g. invasive) plants and weeds on land under the control of the federal government.

NBVC complies with the following OPNAVINST 5090.1D requirements:

- (a) Conduct surveys and manage natural resources in a way that prevents introductions of, reduces the spread of, or eradicates invasive species.
- (b) Plant native species in bare or erodible soils and use native species in all restoration and mitigation projects.
- (c) Address the potential to introduce or spread invasive species in all environmental planning analyses along with means for prevention and control.

- (d) Coordinate with states that maintain programs for controlling noxious plants and provide access for that control, provided access is consistent with installation security procedures. Only proven control measures that have been used on adjacent lands should be used.
- (e) Ensure aquatic invasive species are not introduced into nearshore environments or bodies of water on or adjacent to the installation. Measures to prevent introductions of aquatic nuisance species through ballast water or hull fouling, as mandated by references provided in OPNAV M-5090.1 *Chapter 35 (Environmental Compliance Afloat)*.

These requirements are implemented through the invasive species program and San Nicolas Island Weed Management Plan (Agri Chemical and Supply, Inc. 2014b). Treatments are recorded annually in a SNI geodatabase. Records date back to the 1980s.

Pesticide use in natural resources management programs must also comply with applicable requirements of Chapter 24 of OPNAVINST 5090.1D (DoN 2014a). Such programs must also allow for the conservation of federal and state listed plants and promote their delisting by maintaining or enhancing the ecosystem they depend upon. The control and eradication of non-native species, especially invasives, is of primary importance to natural resources management on SNI and is a fundamental step toward conservation of island ecosystems.

Annual risk assessments are developed by SNI staff familiar with invasive non-native plant species. Non-native plant control treatments on SNI were carried out by contractors through individual task orders and have been performed somewhat regularly since 2001. This invasive non-native plant control effort provides a continuous effort that identifies the status and trend of the most aggressive and threatening invasive non-native plants while supporting a mechanism for identifying new introductions.

SNI has a current IPMP within the NBVC IPMP (Appendix H of IPMP).

Management for the control and removal of non-native terrestrial mammals on SNI was identified as a recommended management action in the 2010 SNI INRMP for the protection and restoration of seabirds and other native wildlife on SNI, and was funded by the Trustee Council for the Montrose Settlements Restoration Program (USFWS 2009b). The Trustee Council for the Montrose Settlements Restoration Program selected the restoration of seabirds on SNI through the complete removal of feral cats as a priority project in their Montrose Settlements Restoration Program Final Restoration Plan (DoN 2007). Implementation of the feral cat control and removal program was accomplished from 2009–2010. It was determined through monitoring for feral cats using remote video and trapping at SNI that all feral cats have been removed from SNI (Hanson et al. 2010). If additional feral cats are detected, trapping may again be required. If non-native animal trapping occurs in the future, targeting feral animals such as cats, the Navy will coordinate with CDFW (South Coast Region) and USFWS to determine and discuss any appropriate measures to reduce any adverse impacts to island foxes.

Management of invasive exotic species is also accomplished through implementation of the NBVC SA/PRB process, codified in NBVCINST 11010.1B.

Assessment of Current Management

Terrestrial invasive exotic species management efforts need to be more strategic. Currently, all five strategic goals identified in the 2008–2012 NISMP are being implemented at SNI; however, a better job can be done at implementing all of those goals, especially for prevention efforts. If more funding is available to support implementation of these five goals then more results will be evident. There is a need to develop and enforce biosecurity measures for SNI. These biosecurity measures will help implement the goal of preventing new introductions of invasive non-native species. If more resources can be directed towards the implementation of prevention measures, in the long-term financial resources will be saved to implement measures that support the other four remaining goals. Prevention is the primary line of defense to avoid or minimize impacts from invasive non-native species introductions. If an invasive non-native species is introduced and becomes established the second line of defense is control and management. This prioritization

approach should be reflected in the amount of resources being requested to support invasive non-native species management at SNI.

There is also a need to evaluate the contributions of invasive non-native species to sensitive native species. For example, studies of chukar competition with San Nicolas Island fox populations showed that its impacts are negligible; the chukar is not competing with local species. However, as a result of the feral cat removal project, a presumed predator has been eliminated. An EPR has been developed that will consider post-cat removal monitoring to include birds and most likely chukar. Coordination with USFWS and CDFW in the removal of chukar from SNI may be needed due to their abundance.

Management Strategy

Objective: Minimize introduction of invasive non-native terrestrial species to SNI through prevention.

- I. Prepare and implement a biosecurity plan to prevent non-natives from entering SNI.
 - A. Prepare a plan that includes measures to prevent the introduction of invasive non-native species, detect early, and respond rapidly to new introductions, and control and monitor established populations.
 1. Enforce requirement that vehicles and equipment be cleaned prior to shipment to the island, and between uses at different island construction sites.
 2. Gravel and fill materials are brought to the island, then documentation is required to certify that it is “weed free.” Inspections of the material will be conducted to verify this requirement.
 3. Require that native plant species be used for landscaping unless a species is specifically approved by ED.
 4. Inspect barge and aircraft before they leave the mainland. For transport arriving directly from other ports or airports, inspect prior to disembarking on SNI.
- II. Prepare a Base Instruction and SOPs to support the implementation of the Biosecurity Plan.
- III. Prepare educational materials for the SNI military and civilian employees, contractors, and other visitors to prevent the introduction of non-native terrestrial species.

Objective: Enhance current early detection and rapid response management capabilities.

- IV. Ensure biosecurity plan establishes early detection protocol and rapid response options.
 - A. Establish adequate monitoring locations to detect invasive species introduction and spread.
 - B. Develop a communication network as a rapid response tool to quarantine specific invaders and identify the pathway.
 - C. Support rapid response by determining funding sources, contract vehicles, and cooperative mechanisms that can be accessed quickly.
 - D. Develop “spill kits” to address specific types of invasive species that may be detected.
- V. Prepare educational materials for the SNI military and civilian employees, contractors, and other visitors as a tool in early detection of non-native terrestrial species.

Objective: Evaluate control and management capabilities for established invasive non-native species populations and identify strategic gaps.

- VI. Revise and implement an invasive plant management plan based on current needs, information, and priorities.
- VII. Increase detection rates and management efficacy by monitoring the presence and absence of invasive non-native species populations.
- VIII. Map and prioritize terrestrial invasive non-native species populations.
 - A. Map the distribution of invasive species every five years.
- IX. Support studies that determine if there are impacts from invasive non-native species already present such as non-native snails, alligator lizards, and chuckar.
- X. Investigate and implement methods to control invasive non-native invertebrate species found on SNI.
 - A. Research control methods for Argentine ant and decollate snails.
 - B. Determine the distribution of Argentine ants on SNI.
- XI. Determine the distribution of decollate snails on SNI.
 - A. Prevent the spread of decollate snails and Argentine ants by restricting use of SNI Native Plant Nursery stock to landscaping projects in the living compound.
- XII. Address non-native species in NEPA and other ground disturbing project plans.
 - A. Ensure funding is secured for non-native removal during all phases (including post-project), if applicable.
 - B. Monitor projects to ensure personnel are following BMPs, conservation measures, and other guidelines and requirements.
- XIII. Manage roads, access routes, and new construction sites to minimize the spread of invasive non-native species and insure that new road or access routes are not created without authorization and project review approval.
 - A. Develop and implement Island Long-Term Road Maintenance Plan.
 - B. Require that maintenance or repair of existing roads stay within established footprints.
- XIV. Clean roadside mowing equipment of adhering dirt and vegetation between mowing cycles.
 - A. Schedule roadside mowing to minimize weedy species seed distribution.
- XV. Make project proponents pay for restoration projects that are used to compensate for development of habitat.
- XVI. Check project to make sure personnel are following guidelines.

Objective: Apply adaptive management principles and continue to evaluate the necessity for removal of other species.

- XVII. Continue investigating the best methods for removal, control, and timing of removal of invasive nonnative plants and ensure compliance with applicable regulations governing removal.
- XVIII. Complete the removal of the feral cat population on SNI. Assess and monitor the progress and success of the removal of feral cats.

- A. Survey and inventory the current status of species known to be impacted by feral cats to properly assess the recovery of those species upon the completion of the project.

XIX. Prepare an Instruction to support an adaptive management approach for terrestrial invasive exotic species management.

Objective: Promote cooperative interagency efforts to collect and analyze comprehensive monitoring data, including shared funding and staffing.

XX. Support the integration of SNI into the Invasive Species Task Force on Santa Cruz Island and other Channel Islands as opportunities arise.

4.6.2 Aquatic Invasive Species

Specific Concerns

- Aquatic invasive species are increasingly coming under the purview of regulatory and resource agency scrutiny, including ballast water and NPDES permits, total maximum daily loads (TMDLs) and impaired waters, economic consequences, and pesticide usage for control.
- Aquatic invasive species are used as biological indicators to measure ecosystem condition.
- Aquatic invasive species management in the context of climatic change requires increasing feedback to management in order to develop strategies for adapting their management to accommodate these environmental changes.
- Ability to monitor population densities of invasive non-native species to understanding any changes that take place in whole communities. Since impact assessments require thorough knowledge of the natural processes that influence community structure, further investigations into the relationship between hydrodynamics and resident fish and invertebrate assemblages may be central to the proper management of a healthy ecosystem.
- Specific vectors of aquatic invasive non-native species for SNI have not been identified; however, ballast water exchange from the provisioning barge may represent a potential vector.
- Uncontrollable vectors for aquatic invasive species introductions to SNI include the provisioning barge, planes, tall ship congregation, security vessels, commercial and recreational fishermen, and dogs that are brought onshore.
- Specific harm to native species and the ecosystem has not been identified for the invasive non-native species that occur in SNI waters.
- Killer algae (*Caulerpa taxifolia*) is not known from SNI waters but, given its growth capability, it can have devastating ecological and economic consequences. Observations of Japanese seaweed (*Undaria pinnatifida*) in waters of Santa Catalina Island and Port Hueneme, and attached to floats in Santa Barbara Harbor have alarmed marine biologists in southern California.
- A new non-native species of *Sargassum* (*S. horneri*) has been detected in southern California in 2003 and has spread rapidly throughout California and has been documented at several of the Channel Islands.

Current Management

The DoD supports implementation of federal aquatic invasive species laws including but not limited to EO 13112, the National Invasive Species Act (NISA) of 1996, and the Nonindigenous Aquatic Nuisance Prevention and Control Act of 1990.

NBVC supports CDFW as the lead agency for managing aquatic invasive species that occur in the nearshore waters of SNI and would collaborate with the CDFW Habitat Conservation Branch and the state invasive species coordinator. The CDFW conducts a number of programs related to aquatic invasive species, including serving as the lead agency in developing the statewide aquatic invasive species management plan, as well as a rapid response plan for invasions. The CDFW is responsible for enforcement of regulations concerning the aquaculture industry; recreational fishing; commercial fishing; the importation and transport of live wild animals, aquatic plants and fish into the state; and the placement of any such animals in state waters. Recent programs have focused on the aquarium plant *Caulerpa taxifolia*, the voracious fish northern pike, and the New Zealand mudsnail, among others. All species of *Caulerpa* are regulated in the State of California under CDFW Division 3, Chapter 3.5 Section 2300. Other state authorities and agencies with regulatory authority over the introduction and transport of aquatic invasive species include the California Department of Food and Agriculture through the California Food and Agriculture Code, California Department of Water Resources through the California Water Code, and the State Lands Commission through the Ballast Water Management Act and Marine Invasive Species Act of 2003.

Furthermore, NVBC is acting in compliance with EO 13112 by incorporating invasive non-native species prevention measures through contract language, BMPs, as well as existing operational and transportation policies and pest management plans.

In OPNAVINST 5090.1D, Navy installations are directed to prevent the introduction of invasive non-native species and provide for their control.

NBVC also prevents the introduction of aquatic invasive species by examining cargo, in-water construction materials, and amphibious training vehicles. Specifically OPNAVINST 5090.1D requires that amphibious vessels launching and recovering amphibious vehicles must ensure those vehicles, including their treads, are washed down after completion of operations. Ships shall also dispose of wash water before entering within 12 nm (22 km) of the next operating area.

Assessment of Current Management

Aquatic invasive species management efforts need to be more strategic. Currently, four of the five strategic goals identified in the 2008–2012 National Invasive Species Management Plan are being implemented at SNI: prevention, early detection and rapid response, control and management, and organizational collaboration. The role and responsibility of the Navy for aquatic invasive species management at SNI largely focuses on prevention and early detection and rapid response because the CDFW is the lead agency responsible for managing the nearshore waters surrounding SNI. It is the role and responsibility of the CDFW to control and manage any aquatic invasive species that are identified in the nearshore waters at the installation.

Aquatic invasive species prevention measures are guided by implementation of the NBVC SA/PRB process codified in NBVCINST 11010.1B and BMPs for in-water construction projects.

Early detection and rapid response efforts at SNI occur through the following mechanisms: ASBS compliance biological surveys, surveys to document existing conditions for in-water construction projects, and surveys to document Special Aquatic Sites such as eelgrass habitat.

Management Strategy

Objective: Prevent and manage invasive non-native invasions to minimize harmful ecological, economic, and human health impacts of aquatic invasive species in SNI waters.

I. Prevent the introduction of invasive non-native marine and coastal species into SNI waters.

- A. Promote ballast water management for all vessels entering Naval Installations.
 - 1. Support the continuation of the Navy's ballast water exchange policy for open ocean exchange and encourage the implementation of a ballast water management program that explicitly addresses the nonindigenous invasive species problem.
 - B. Identify methods to reduce or prevent the number of new invasive species.
- II. Develop a standardized monitoring system focused on early detection and rapid response for high priority aquatic invasive species.
- A. Provide for an early warning system for newly discovered species.
 - 1. Target locations with higher probability for newly arrived species (e.g. barge loading area settings and disturbed sites).
 - 2. Involve and educate Navy divers and marine scientists – who are frequently in the water and working on boats – in detection and management.
 - a. Develop a watch list for use by personnel who are frequently in the water that includes pictures to support the detection and management of aquatic invasive species.
 - b. Develop a means to educate personnel about the common aquatic invasive species pathways/vectors including barges, boats, and the recreational use of beaches.
 - B. Track all current monitoring of the state's coastal marine and inland waters for opportunities to incorporate early detection of aquatic invasive species. High priority aquatic invasive species for early detection for introduction or change in status include the, Northern Pacific seastar (*Asterias amurensi*), *Caulerpa*, *Hydrilla*, *Salvinia*, *Sargassum horneri*, and others.
 - 1. Map the existing problem areas and determine priority sites and control measures.
 - 2. Monitor progress, evaluate the effectiveness of measures, and revise as needed.
- III. Develop species- and/or location-specific rapid response plans in collaboration with CDFW and CDFA. These plans should include lead agencies, chain of command, specified lists of appropriate control measures (biological, chemical, and physical), methods to address the introduction pathways, and regular updates and drills to ensure the contingency plans remain current.
- A. To control new invasive non-native species with the potential to become problems, provide a rapid response, and respond at the appropriate spatial scale.
- IV. Promote cooperative interagency efforts to collect and analyze comprehensive monitoring data, including shared funding and staffing.

4.7 Prevention and Control of Wildlife Damage

4.7.1 BASH Program

Specific Concerns

- A Wildlife Hazard Assessment and BASH Plan has not been developed for SNI.

Current Management

Bird/Wildlife Aircraft Strike Hazard is defined as the threat of aircraft collision with birds during flight operations, particularly during take-off and landing and low-altitude training exercises. In general, the times of greatest threat during migratory bird activity are March, April, and August through November. While a safety hazard at SNI, bird-strikes occur infrequently.

Wildlife Hazard Assessment and BASH plans are required by DoD for military installations where there is a potential for a conflict between military activity and wildlife. Usually BASH plans contain installation specific guidelines to minimize collisions between aircraft and birds, such as ducks, geese, and raptors.

Generally such a plan requires the training of a staff biologist and review of the plan by the U.S. Air Force.

The BASH plan for SNI has had a focus on non-native birds such as removal of chukar and the trapping of starlings. To reduce the attractiveness of areas near the airfield for use as cover the environmental program has been managing grass height through mowing. Surveys have also been conducted around the airfield; horned larks have been commonly found during these surveys.

Efforts will need to be made to support Air Operations in securing funding to conduct a Wildlife Hazard Assessment for SNI and develop a BASH plan in coordination with the environmental program.

Assessment of Current Management

The BASH requirement for SNI has not been met. There is a need to develop a formalized Wildlife Hazard Assessment BASH plan for SNI.

Management Strategy

Objective: Reduce the potential for bird and other animal collisions with aircraft at the SNI airfield.

- I. Support Air Operations in conducting a Wildlife Hazard Assessment and preparing a BASH plan for SNI.
- II. Monitor and document bird strikes and carcasses adjacent to the SNI airfield.
- III. Survey and monitor avian species utilizing the SNI airfield for foraging and roosting and document responses to aircraft to evaluate the potential for aircraft impacts.

4.7.2 Pest/Predator Control

Specific Concerns

- Introduction and spread of pests (e.g. ants and rodents).
- Maintaining an effective early detection and monitoring pest program.

Current Management

SNI has a current IPMP (Appendix H of IPMP). For the purposes of this INRMP, a pest is defined as a domestic plant or animal (including insects) usually found in the urban (built) environment that if it escapes causes harm to humans or native ecosystems (V. Vartanian,

pers. comm., 2010). A biosecurity plan was developed for SNI (Tetra Tech, Inc. 2011) but needs to be revised to include plants and invertebrates.

Pest control on SNI is primarily concerned with the control or elimination of established pests and prevention of new pest species (invertebrates and vertebrates) introductions. All pests and predators on SNI in need of management actions were caught and removed by Environmental personnel. Snap traps are a commonly used method to capture pests in urban areas such as Nicktown.

Pest species known to occur on SNI include ants, deer mice, starlings, house sparrows, and the occasional rock pigeon (*Columba livia*). Other known vertebrates introduced to SNI in the last 20 years include the Virginia opossum (*Didelphis virginiana*), California ground squirrel, and dusky-footed wood rat (*Neotoma fuscipes*), but all have been successfully removed.

Assessment of Current Management

There is a need to control and actively manage pests and predators at SNI.

Management Strategy

Objective: Prevent the introduction of pests to SNI.

- I. Minimize, to the greatest practical extent, the introduction of pest species to SNI.
 - A. Continue the prohibition on bringing plants and pets to the island.
 - B. Require all barge and air cargo shipments (both contractor and government) be inspected for plant material, vertebrate, and invertebrate species before departing ports or airfields for SNI.
- II. Enforce the NBVC Biosecurity Instruction (NBVCINST 5090.14) for barge and air cargo shipment inspections.
 - A. Require gravel and soils to be pest-free (plant material and invertebrates).
 - B. Require refuse and shipping bins to be inspected before transportation to SNI.

Objective: Control pests around facilities while avoiding and minimizing impacts to non-target individuals.

- III. Implement IPMP to control and remove rodents.
 - A. Prohibit rodenticide use outdoors. Only allow use within buildings when mice are creating a health risk.
- IV. Determine presence or absence of non-native rodents.
 - A. Conduct a comprehensive island survey for rats and house mice.
- V. Establish and implement procedures to monitor for new arrivals of rodents.
 - A. Ensure revisions to the IPMP are addressed in the INRMP and support implementation of the IPMP.

4.8 Data Integration, Access, and Reporting

Specific Concerns

Managers concerned with ensuring the long-term health of the SNI ecosystem need to know what the long-term trends are in island populations and what is causing those trends. Some of these trends may be driven by drought, storm surges, El Niño-La Niña cycles, or climatic change rather than any local human activity. Populations fluctuate for a variety of reasons, and managers need to know what fraction of the variability is due to human influences.

There is a wealth of projects currently underway in the region which SNI could benefit from participating in. Conservatively, at least \$17 million is spent annually monitoring in the SCB (National Research Council 1990). However, the major regional time-series monitoring programs do not contain data specific to SNI. These include:

- Sport and commercial catch reported to CDFW, in which fishermen report the number and species caught (including lobster, sea urchin, and abalone), number of anglers fishing, area fished, and hours fished. However, no reporting is done specific to Island waters.
- The California Cooperative Oceanic Fisheries Investigation examines hydrology, primary production, zooplankton biomass, and larval fish distributions. It originated in response to the collapse of the California sardine fishery in 1947. It is unparalleled in its spatial extent, duration, and consistency through time of its study of the ocean and fisheries biology. Sampling occurs in offshore and coastal waters of the SCB. However, the data it collects is best suited to regional Bight questions rather than to management questions concerning the nearshore waters of SNI.
- Data is collected on sea surface temperature and other parameters from near the turn of the century at Scripps Pier, Scripps Institute of Oceanography in La Jolla, California. However, this long-term time series dataset does not directly pertain to management questions specific to SNI.
- During the last two decades, a CINP monitoring program has been developed to evaluate and predict the present and future State of ecological resources of the Channel Islands. Established in 1981, the project was designated the Vital Signs Monitoring Program and its objectives were to: determine the present and future ecosystem health; establish empirically normal limits of resource variation; provide early diagnosis of abnormal conditions; and identify potential agents of anthropogenic change (Davis 2005). This program has become a cost-effective and collaborative effort among numerous federal, state, and private interests. SNI could ensure that terrestrial monitoring is consistent with this program and share data across programs. Other programs with an emphasis on ecosystem monitoring in the marine environment have been established to help understand changes throughout California and could be adopted by the Navy for SNI marine ecosystem monitoring.
- Without access to long-term inventory or monitoring data, the Navy lacks the ability to make proper management decisions for this habitat, including the ability to identify concerns.

Current Management

Other agencies and universities support data collection and efforts are made to integrate, access, and report. The CINP shares information with SNI. SNI uses similar mapping strategies to be consistent with CINP.

As a starting point SNI has utilized an EMS program to track natural resources, coastal resources, and waste products. The EMS system is a compliance requirement for the environmental program and contributes to integration access and reporting.

Assessment of Current Management

The intent of developing an SNI archival database is to help organize data for use by SNI natural resource staff. The inventory and recordation of biological field data and the development of a computerized retrieval system, such as an archival database, for these data are ongoing efforts at SNI; the development of such an archival database system would be very useful when dealing with other federal and state agencies and efforts will continue to be applied toward its development. This is particularly important for those species that may be, or are being, considered for listing under provisions of the ESA. It is also equally important to provide this information, in a usable format; to other land managers since management of species can best be accomplished when all forms of potential impacts are considered for a species throughout its entire range. Ecosystem-wide resource management requires mutual cooperation of regional land managers, regulators, and scientific groups and facilitates regional planning efforts towards common goals. If researchers or scientific organizations want natural resource data, they are encouraged to contact and request data from environmental program staff. For example, data is shared with the Island Fox Recovery Team, but in a controlled manner.

Management Strategy

Objective: Ensure the technically sound, practical and appropriate use of library and computer technology to organize, analyze, and communicate natural resource information in support of management decisions.

- I. Set up a central clearinghouse for data, reports, and publications pertaining to the NBVC's EMS that addresses natural resources and that is accessible to staff.
 - A. Develop a plan that delineates the types of information to be included, accessible format, frequency for updating, and accessibility limits.
- II. Participate in data sharing, technology transfer, and communication as applicable.
 - A. Seek standardization of the approach to communicate research and monitoring results.
- III. Continue to develop and maintain SNI's data management capabilities.
 - A. Continue to support ongoing and new research, encouraging the use of specialists to facilitate recognition and discovery of previously unrecorded species or species occurring in previously unrecorded locations.
 - B. Direct specific attention towards locating and identifying rare, endemic, undescribed, and potentially new species.
- IV. Continue to update the GIS database by setting standards for periodic update thereby keeping GIS data current.
 - A. Provide appropriate data to the CNDDDB.

5.0 Sustainability and Compatible Use at San Nicolas Island

5.1 Sustainability of the Military Mission in the Natural Environment

Broadly speaking, sustainability takes a long-term view of natural resources stewardship, Navy mission accomplishment, social responsibility, and economic prosperity into the future. For this INRMP, the topic of sustainability encompasses:

- Sustainability of the Navy mission at SNI with respect to how natural resources support this mission.
- Resource-specific best practices, consistent with the Navy's EMS, for the use of renewable and non-renewable resources and how pollution and wastes are prevented and processed. The practices may address biosecurity, energy, water, water quality, air quality, greenhouse gas management, reducing threats both natural and human, and securing habitat for special status and indicator species into the future. This topic is also more fully developed in specific INRMP sections including *Section 4.2.1: Water Resources* and *Section 6.2: Water Quality, and Section Adaptive Management Annual Review and Metrics*.
- Preparing for climate change and regional growth.
- Resource use in the built environment.
- Indicators that help monitor progress toward sustainability objectives.

5.1.1 Integrated Military Mission and Sustainable Land Use Decisions

Background

A successfully implemented INRMP will meet two basic purposes:

1. It will ensure the sustainability of all natural resources at an installation; and
2. It will ensure no net loss of the capability of installation lands to support the DoD mission.

These two purposes are closely related and not mutually exclusive. Healthy ecosystems support realistic military training and testing needs by providing large open space, buffers, stable soils, clear air, clean water, and a range of natural conditions that are available for the indefinite future.

Disturbances that characterize SNI include:

- Facility sites
- Inactive target disturbance areas
- Active target disturbance sites
- Special use sites
- Test facilities
- Instrumentation sites
- Roads
- UXO operations

Map 5-1 shows locations of sensitive resources. The map is intended to show all areas on the installation where restrictions on training or mission occur due to natural resources related issues (listed species, soil erosion, invasive species, etc.).

Specific Concerns

- The concept of sustainability in the military and under the Sikes Act (under which this INRMP is a mandate) requires this INRMP to document “no net loss” to the military mission to comply with the Sikes Act. No benchmarks have been set up to monitor and evaluate whether this has been achieved; such benchmarks will help a natural resource manager assess sustainability at longer time scales.
- Management units are not defined that would allow for analyzing sustainability at a finer scale than all of the island and its surrounding waters at once. Management units help develop priorities and reconcile conflicts.
- Sustainability in siting and resource use is only beginning to be considered a metric of successful project design. To date, sustainability has been applied in military installations somewhat narrowly to the built environment and focused mostly on energy and recycling. It is beginning to be applied to storm water management such as with LID approaches, and to ecological sustainability of habitats, species, and ecological functions.

Current Management

Since most of SNI’s natural resources remain relatively undisturbed from current (as opposed to historic) land uses and provide a safety and security buffer zone for the RDAT&E activities, sustainable land use and a healthy ecosystem are mutually compatible. Most day-to-day activities at SNI have little potential to impact natural resources. Existing test sites are routinely re-used, taking advantage of existing instrumentation and infrastructure and avoiding environmental costs associated with establishing new areas. Most high value resource areas are in locations not intensively used for ground-related military activities. However, there is always the possibility of a change in mission which could lead to a degradation of the natural resources. Furthermore, because of the military mission some aspects of terrestrial habitat management, such as prescribed burns, cannot be utilized at SNI.

The SA/PRB process is also used to manage environmental compatibility with the military mission, and sometimes the natural resources staff provides on-site monitoring of a military operation in order to ensure environmental compliance.

Finally, each year the CO of NBVC must answer as part of the INRMP metrics review the following questions:

- Does the natural resources team consult with operators when making changes to the INRMP in order to keep it current? Coordination examples include: maps, signage, pamphlets, other communications, orientations, meetings, training, etc.
- To what level do natural resources compliance requirements support the installation’s ability to sustain the operational mission?
- Has there been a net loss of training lands?
- Does the INRMP process effectively consider current mission requirements?

Map 5-1 San Nicolas Island Natural Resources Constraints

Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan
Naval Base Ventura County San Nicolas Island

Assessment of Current Management

The Sikes Act guidance indicates the need to focus on improving the ties between natural resource management and military readiness. While the “no net loss” policy of the Sikes Act and DoD guidance is broadly accomplished by the Range Complex Management Plan and EIS, there remain unfulfilled opportunities to facilitate the connection between natural resources and the mission. More locally specific planning criteria could be used for site selection criteria (such as using landform, soil recoverability, plant community condition and sensitivity, and considering the timing and intensity of use).

Management Strategy

Objective: Achieve no net loss of military value by aligning current and future land and water use (location, extent, timing, and intensity) with environmental value protection into the future, while minimizing the cost of environmental conflict resolution and mitigation.

- I. Maintain and enhance existing land uses to support core RDAT&E, training, and mission-support capabilities through coordinating of all facilities siting, relocation, expansion, or change in use by continued use of the SA/PRB process.
- II. The placement of continuing and evolving military land uses, to the extent practicable, should be in previously disturbed areas to fully utilize existing operational areas and minimize potential effects to sensitive resources.
 - A. Locate new facilities within existing facility footprints or other previously disturbed areas to the extent practicable.
 - B. Withdraw from service any surplus facilities identified for retention (meet or exceed minimum codes/standards) and future reuse.
 - C. Demolish excess and/or substandard facilities and reclaim landscape to an applicable reclamation standard.
 - D. Review proposed new uses or alterations to existing buildings or structures, in consultation with a Navy Archaeologist, to determine the eligibility of affected structures for NRHP contributing elements. As needed, analyze for potential impacts in accordance with guidelines established for NRHP-eligible buildings.
 - E. Conduct appropriate environmental surveys on any proposed new land use within an undeveloped area to identify sensitive natural and cultural resources, environmental resources, and IRP (hazardous waste cleanups).
- III. Ensure compliance with statutes and regulations to protect sensitive natural and cultural resources, to maintain environmental quality and to exercise responsible stewardship of public lands.
- IV. Ensure the public health and safety of NBVC personnel and authorized visitors by maintaining a secure military operating environment on SNI administered lands.
- V. Maintain and enhance coordination and cooperation with neighboring communities, agencies, and organizations to ensure compatibility of off-island natural resource uses with the Navy’s mission.
- VI. Provide reasonable accommodation of compatible nonmilitary land use to the extent practicable.

- VII. Maintain healthy and intact habitats that self-recover from disturbance, using principles of ecosystem management and sustainability to balance short-term projects with long-term goals.
- A. Take an ecosystem approach to terrestrial and marine planning, rather than a species approach wherever possible. A habitat approach allows conservation of ecological linkages among species even when they are not understood.
 - B. Ensure the future of water that sustains the military presence is secure.
 - C. Manage land use compatibility by adopting management units that consider operational control.
 - D. Use management units to provide a finer spatial scale for analyzing military mission needs, and conserving high-value, scarce habitats and species.
 - E. Align infrastructure to contribute to the military mission, concentrating it in operations areas, and integrating it with the environment with proper siting and sustainability practices.
 - F. Use criteria in each management unit to define the resilience of the area to various types of use/disturbance patterns in order to set restoration priorities.
 - G. Address long-term threats to the stability of the natural environment, including, but not limited to, soil erosion, invasive exotic species, climate change, sea level rise, and habitat fragmentation by evaluating plant community composition, vegetation productivity, and soil health.
 - H. Avoid or minimize road proliferation which can promote plant invasions, or result in significant habitat fragmentation for animals.
- VIII. Continue to use NEPA documentation, including cumulative effects analysis, to guide specific projects and document choices.
- IX. Ensure the CO's preparedness to answer as part of the INRMP metrics review the following questions:
- A. Does the natural resources team consult with operators when making changes to the INRMP in order to keep it current? Coordination examples include: maps, signage, pamphlets, other communications, orientations, meetings, training, etc.
 - B. To what level do natural resources compliance requirements support the installation's ability to sustain the operational mission?
 - C. Has there been a net loss of training lands?
 - D. Does the INRMP process effectively consider current mission requirements?

5.1.2 Biosecurity

Specific Concerns

- Invasive species may be transported to SNI;
- Invasive species will likely have significant adverse effects to the island's ecosystem;
- New arrivals of invasive species may not be detected early enough after arrival;
- Proper planning and methods may not be in place to respond to introductions; and
- Species have been documented to leave the island.

Current Management

SNI has a Biosecurity Plan (Appendix I), which details potential threats and pathways for species to make it to island, as well as management actions to reduce potential introductions. Cargo is inspected before transported to the island, and shippers are instructed to ensure cargo is clean and free of stowaways. A Navy Instruction (NBVCINST 5090.14) is in place to enforce measures to not allow any cargo that may have invasive species be transported. Traps are in place on SNI to respond to any introductions and plant surveys occur regularly to search for arrival of new weeds.

Assessment of Current Management

The current management is a start to a good program, however it must continually develop. More detail is needed on the full suite of invasive species including plants, arthropods, diseases, and aquatic marine species. The biosecurity plan, implemented through the biosecurity instruction, must also be incorporated into all activities that have the potential to transport invasive species. For example ensuring all biosecurity requirements are placed within contracts during early phases of bidding, to ensure contractors incorporate costs to use “weed-free certified” or other costs associated with biosecurity protections. Outreach can also increase, so all personnel going to island are knowledgeable about the threats of invasive species to the Navy’s mission and SNI’s natural resources.

Management Strategy

Objective: Reduce potential of introductions of new species to SNI.

- I. Inspect cargo and do not allow any cargo to be transported if not clean.
- II. Routine trapping and control of rodents and mammals at cargo staging areas.
- III. Remove any weeds or rodent habitat at cargo staging areas.
- IV. Ensure biosecurity language is included in all contracts for work on island.
- V. Educate people visiting or working on island or work on shipping materials to island on threats.

Objective: Monitor SNI points of entry and areas of human activity for new arrivals.

- VI. Continue and develop methods to monitor for arrival of new animal species, such as cameras, traps, and personnel reporting.
- VII. Continue and develop methods to monitor for arrival of new plant species, such as regular plant surveys at sites more prone to introductions (barge and airfield, Nicktown).

Objective: Establish a rapid response protocol for any new invasive species detected by monitoring. Have traps and bait on hand to respond to any potential introductions.

- VIII. Develop a plan for control for species most likely to be introduced.
- IX. Have funding available or methods to ensure species is extirpated and does not become established.
- X. Develop a “spill kit” specific for types of invasive organisms placed strategically around the island.

5.1.3 Adapting to Effects of Climate Change

Specific Concerns

- Scientific research indicates that global warming will have long-term, irreversible, adverse consequences on natural resources, including terrestrial and aquatic habitats.
- The California Wildlife Action Plan (CDFW 2007) identifies climate change as one of four primary stressors affecting wildlife, along with growth and development, water management conflicts, and invasive species, and makes recommendations to include climate change science in restoration work.
- Models are the only way to project future changes for the SNI and the surrounding region, and to evaluate needed research, data collection, and potential management strategies. However the use of models to explore the potential implications of climate change is rife with uncertainty. A range of scenarios is possible using accepted models, and local data sets need to be developed and integrated through collaboration and consensus.
- The dynamic nature of information about climate change can be overwhelming to managers. The slow and deliberative process in which public agencies work can also be a barrier to swift implementation of strategic approaches, especially when multiple jurisdictions are involved.
- Key questions for NEPA analysis include whether the proposed action is expected to cause climate change effects, whether the proposed action combined with other past, present and reasonably foreseeable actions would cause such effects, and whether sufficient information is available to describe the nature and extent of the proposed action's effect. Developing mitigation for climate change is an emerging issue for NEPA analysis.
- Doing nothing will result in a decline to natural resources and increasing threat to infrastructure due to feedback loops from multiple causes, and a rising cost of addressing the problem. An example of a threat to natural resources that interacts through positive feedback loops is invasive species and related altered fire regime. Another could be impacts to kelp beds that cause trophic cascades that affect food web dynamics.

Current Management

The 2014 update to the DoD Climate Change Adaption Roadmap (Roadmap) fulfills the requirements of a Climate Change Adaptation Plan found in Executive Orders 13514 and 13653. Executive Order 13514 requires that all Federal Departments and Agencies evaluate climate change risks and vulnerabilities to manage both the short- and long- term effects of climate change on the agency's mission and operations, and include an adaptation planning document as an appendix to its annual Strategic Sustainability Performance Plan (SSPP). Executive Order 13653 notes that "building on these efforts, each agency shall develop or continue to develop, implement, and update comprehensive plans that integrate consideration of climate change into agency operations and overall mission objectives and submit those plans to CEQ and OMB for review." A table which cross references this Roadmap to the specific implementation requirements of EO 13653 is provided in Annex 1 of the Roadmap. The goals of the Roadmap are to:

Goal 1: Identify and assess the effects of climate change on the Department.

Goal 2: Integrate climate change considerations across the Department and manage associated risks.

Goal 3: Collaborate with internal and external stakeholders on climate change challenges.

The recently updated guidance for Navy INRMPs (OPNAVINST 4715.03 [DoD 2013]) added a requirement to address climate change in INRMPs. It states that "the evidence for climate change is extensive and has generated consensus in the scientific community. Addressing climate change poses a new challenge for natural resources managers who will need to understand

changes in ecosystem structure and function anticipated from climate change, in addition to understanding ecosystems as they function now and as they have in the past.”

The guidance continues with a framework for addressing climate change issues, and this is incorporated in the strategy outline below.

Assessment of Current Management

To date, the ability to analyze climate change implications is in early stages at SNI, including the ability to incorporate climate change analyses in NEPA documents in a consistent way. Increasingly, NEPA court challenges have resulted in a legal requirement to analyze climate change in certain cases, as well as develop mitigation measures for climate change impacts. Thus, agencies increasingly are expected to evaluate climate change impacts for a broad range of projects requiring federal approvals or permits. Many projects undergoing NEPA analysis will either directly or indirectly cause greenhouse gas emissions and strategies and techniques for analyzing these are needed. Many other projects will need to address climate change impacts onto the projects themselves (such as increased flash flood potential for a planned highway), or onto resources a project may impact (such as shifting habitat or species distributions due to increases in temperature).

Management Strategy

Objective: Adapt and mitigate the adverse impacts of climate change through goal setting based on science-based scenarios, targets, collaborative planning, and adaptive management.

- I. Anticipate shifts in species ranges and population abundances through monitoring.
- II. Identify data and research needs for ensuring an effective response to the consequences of climate change.
 - A. Identify species and communities that are either resilient or vulnerable to climate change impacts by conducting climate change vulnerability assessments.
 - B. Improve the application of models through data collection and validation (as feasible and needed) and for using such science based models in environmental and natural resource management planning.
 - C. Improve the graphical depiction of the potential impacts of climate change scenarios for SNI to address anticipated shifts in species ranges and population abundances in climate change vulnerability assessments.
- III. Adapt and mitigate the adverse consequences of climate change, including stresses on infrastructure, aquatic vegetation, erosion, and shifts in distributions of terrestrial endemic species and plant communities.
 - A. Ensure that species and community conservation priorities and expenditures reflect climate change risks, such as those on the margins of their distribution patterns.
 - B. Identify restoration projects to provide habitat elements for specific species which may be altered by climate change.
 - C. Provide for the management of threatened, endangered, and other special status species such that changes in distribution and abundance may be understood in the context of climate change.
- IV. Address the anticipated increase in extreme events by emphasizing preventative technologies.
 - A. Comply with guidelines on project siting.
 - B. Improve water conservation.
 - C. Improve storm water management through LID technologies.

- D. Improve coordination between natural resources and staff and development project proponents to ensure more energy efficient design features.
- V. Control and reduce greenhouse gasses, the pollution that causes global warming and climate change, by updating and implementing the SNI Renewable Energy Plan.
- VI. Improve and strengthen governance with respect to climate change.
 - A. Establish partnerships for collaboratively addressing climate change issues.
 - B. Analyze project impacts and cumulative effects through NEPA in a consistent way.
 - C. Incorporate climate change in Navy Encroachment Action planning.
 - D. Develop science-based agency coordination to protect, maintain, and restore at-risk habitats.
- VII. Ensure that base personnel have access to climate change education and outreach in order to help minimize the most dire forecasts for global warming through modification of individual behavior and lifestyle consumption patterns that contribute to global warming.

5.1.4 Sustainability in the Built Environment

Specific Concerns

- The true long-term cost of choices is not as visible to leadership as it could be because natural resources assets are not assigned a value, and thresholds or tipping-points of change in their value are not known.
- There is a need for those involved in executing development projects for education about costs and technologies to understand the difference in environmental approaches and choices. This uncertainty hampers the adoption of more projects that meet sustainability criteria.

Current Management

Sustainable development practices produce highly efficient and cost effective buildings that reduce the use of natural resources such as water and oil, decrease pollution, and provide a healthier indoor environment. Such development takes into account the full life cycle cost of a project, including broader concerns such as its effect on the environment and the community, not just the financial cost. Refer to the NBVC San Nicolas Island and Fort Hunter Liggett Activity Overview Plan for more information on current and future development projects that are based on the principles of sustainable planning and design.

In support of promoting sustainability in the built environment, a federal task force agreed to the following set of federally accepted principles for sustainability in the built environment (adapted from the WBDG, National Institute of Building Sciences¹):

1. Optimize siting potential. Avoid using undeveloped land, open space, water and soil conservation areas, existing natural wetlands, endangered species habitats, and floodplains. Promote compact/mixed-use development that minimizes the need to drive gas-powered vehicles and maximizes use of already developed land through infill, brownfields development, and preservation of natural, and cultural/historic resources.
2. Promote socio-economic development by involving local community residents in setting the vision for and developing plans and actions for their communities and regions, and making optimum use of existing assets in the adjacent communities. An open planning process ensures that development does not disadvantage communities in the siting of unattractive facilities.

¹Available online at: <http://www.wbdg.org/index.asp>.

3. Reduce the concentrations of carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases in the atmosphere by encouraging alternatives to the use of gas-powered vehicles.
4. Optimize operations and maintenance practices to maintain specified performance levels. Minimize energy consumption while maximizing use of renewable energy sources. Encourage pollution prevention by specifying land uses that minimize or eliminate the use of extracted underground substances; and by encouraging methods of landscape design and maintenance that use native vegetation and reduce or eliminate the use of pesticides, herbicides, and synthetic fertilizers.
5. Reduce the use of water through water conservation and recycling; re-using gray water on-site and employing innovative wastewater treatment.
6. Use environmentally preferable products.
7. Enhance indoor environmental quality.

In 1994, the USGBC developed the LEED Green Building Rating System² to evaluate sustainability for a project. The LEED program is one of several ratings systems for energy performance. The LEED rating system is a checklist of various “green” options for building design and construction, developed through a consensus by a consortium of industry groups. It evaluates environmental performance from a “whole building” perspective over a building’s life-cycle, providing a definitive standard for what constitutes a “green building.” The LEED rating system’s six credit areas for new construction are:

- Sustainable Sites (includes site selection, site resource protection, landscaping, and storm water management);
- Water Efficiency (water efficient landscaping, water conservation, and innovative technologies);
- Energy and Atmosphere;
- Materials and Resources;
- Indoor Environmental Quality; and
- Innovation and Design Process (includes exceptional performance beyond the LEED requirements).

Air quality is treated briefly, and as a subtheme only, under this topic of sustainability for this INRMP. Other topics that are mostly within the realm of the indoor environmental quality (e.g. built interiors) and therefore not addressed are: building systems, energy efficiency, building materials, waste and services, transportation, and use of historic properties.

Briefly in regards to energy efficiency, EO 13123 “Greening the Government through Efficient Energy Management” (superseding EO 12902) directs that the federal government significantly improve its energy management. It promotes energy efficiency through building design, construction, and operation; water conservation; use of renewable technologies; and fostering markets for emerging technologies. Refer to the SNI Renewable Energy Plan for more information on how SNI will increase energy efficiency through the development of wind turbines, facilities modernization, and energy conservation measures.

Many federal and state initiatives are in place for LEED certification that cover new construction and renovation, including most federal departments. California’s EO #S-20-04 (December 2004) requires the design, construction, and operation of all new and renovated state-owned facilities to be LEED Silver.

For sustainable water management, the EPA has developed a guide that includes a literature review, concepts, and case studies in LID³, and it is starting to be a requirement in storm water

²More information regarding the USGBC or the LEED program is available online at: <http://www.usgbc.org>.

³Available online at: <http://www.epa.gov/nps/lid.pdf>.

permits. On 20 January 2005, the SWRCB adopted sustainability as a core value for all California Water Boards' activities and programs, and directed California Water Boards' staff to consider sustainability in all future policies, guidelines, and regulatory actions.

Low Impact Development is a site design strategy with a goal of maintaining or replicating the pre-development hydrologic regime through the use of designs to create a functionally equivalent hydrologic landscape. Hydrologic functions of storage, infiltration, and ground water recharge, as well as the volume and frequency of discharges are maintained through the use of integrated and distributed micro-scale storm water retention and detention areas, reduction of impervious surfaces, and the lengthening of flow paths and runoff time (Coffman 2000). This contrasts with conventional approaches that typically convey and manage runoff in large facilities located at the base of drainage areas. Although traditional storm water control measures have been documented to effectively remove pollutants, the natural hydrology is still negatively affected (inadequate base flow, thermal fluxes or flashy hydrology), which can have detrimental effects on ecosystems, even when water quality is not compromised (Coffman 2000). Low Impact Development practices offer an additional benefit in that they can be integrated into the infrastructure and are more cost effective and aesthetically pleasing than traditional, structural storm water conveyance systems.

While standards exist for sustainable structures - "green buildings" and "water management" - there are no comprehensive guidelines and performance benchmarks for those who want to create and measure sustainable landscapes in the built environment (SSI 2010). The SSI⁴ is an interdisciplinary effort by the American Society of Landscape Architects, the Lady Bird Johnson Wildflower Center at the University of Texas at Austin and the U.S. Botanic Garden to create voluntary national guidelines and performance benchmarks for sustainable land design, construction, and maintenance practices (SSI 2010).

In the Navy, the first requirement of facilities is mission support; however, as stated in NAVFACINST 11010.45, "Sustainable development is required by law and policy, and is a requirement for the Navy." Sustainable planning is the application of sustainable development principles to the planning phase of project development in Navy terms, everything up to and including completion of project documentation (DD Form 1391). The Navy's goal is to exceed the LEED "certified" level where justified by life cycle costs (NAVFACINST 11010.45).

The Navy was the first federal agency to participate in the LEED program. The Navy continues to pursue sustainable development in its facilities requiring all applicable projects to meet the LEED Certified level, unless justifiable conditions exist that limit accomplishment of the LEED credits necessary. With the USGBC, the Navy supports development of the LEED for Homes Committee. Submission to the USGBC for certification is recommended for high visibility and to showcase projects. The Navy uses LEED as a tool in applying sustainable development principles and as a metric to measure the sustainability achieved.

In the Navy much of sustainability planning occurs within the Regional Shore Infrastructure Plan (RSIP) process, because this is the tool where facility needs are evaluated, and siting options are examined for fulfilling them. One of the stated Navy goals of the RSIP process pertaining to natural resources sustainability principles is (as stated in NAVFACINST 11010.45): "Recognizing the environmental association of all planning recommendations and providing ecologically sustainable solutions that support and enhance the regional shore establishment." Properly following the RSIP process means that a planner is already taking a longer-term approach (NAVFACINST 11010.45).

NAVFACINST 11010.45 adds the LEED and National Governors Association New Community Design checklist requirement to the RSIP process. The Navy's LEED checklist has the scoring shown in Table 5-1 (only elements related to natural resources are shown).

⁴More information on the Sustainable Sites Initiative is available online at: <http://www.sustainablesites.org>.

Table 5-1. Partial checklist (portion relating to natural resources) and scoring system for Navy LEED projects.

Erosion and Storm Water Control
Construction site sediment and erosion control plan that conforms to best management practices. No net increase in the rate or quantity of storm water runoff from existing to developed conditions, OR, if existing imperviousness is greater than 50 percent, new development will result in a 25 percent decrease in the rate and quantity of storm water runoff. Storm water treatment systems designed to remove 80 percent of the average annual post development total suspended solids, and 40 percent total phosphorous.
Site Selection
If the site is FREE from the following unfavorable conditions. Land whose elevation is lower than 5 feet (1.5 m) above the elevation of the 100-year flood as defined by Federal Emergency Management Agency. Within 100 feet (30.5 m) of any federal, state, or local wetland. Land that provides habitat for any species on the federal or state threatened or endangered list. If the site has any of these problems, strongly consider using another area.
Urban Redevelopment
Develop on a site classified as a brown field and provide remediation. Conserve water use through xeriscaping with native plants. Reduced Site Disturbance/Reduced Heat Islands Post development landscaping uses native plants that improve habitat for native species.
Light Pollution Reduction
Do not exceed Illuminating Engineering Society of North America foot candle level requirements, AND design interior and exterior lighting such that zero direct-beam illumination leaves the building site.
Water Use Reduction
Use only captured rain, graywater, or trenched wastewater to water landscape. Install non-potable water system for toilets, cooling towers, boilers, landscaping, vehicle washing, and other non-potable water needs. Employ strategies that in aggregate use 20 percent less water than the water use baseline after meeting Energy Policy Act of 1992 fixture performance requirements. Exceed the potable water use reduction by an additional 10 percent. Comply with the Department of Energy Performance Measured Protocol.

The National Governors Association Checklist for better land use “smart growth” approaches is the second set of standards used by the Navy. Their sustainability evaluation includes one criterion that addresses protection of open space, natural beauty, and critical environmental areas:

1. Does the project avoid fragmenting existing green space, especially natural habitats and forests?
2. Does the project design protect the local watershed? Water runoff and other factors should be examined to determine whether the development is harming the watershed. To minimize water runoff, the fraction of land paved over for streets and parking typically should not exceed 20 percent to 30 percent.
3. Does the project location avoid increasing the risk or negative impacts of natural disasters? Consideration should be given to what kinds of periodic natural hazards exist for the site and whether a specific location is vulnerable, for example, to flooding, wildfires, mudslides, beach erosion, or high winds.

The Engineering and Construction Bulletin 2014-02 also provides overall NAVFAC policy and guidance on sustainability and energy requirements.

Assessment of Current Management

Across nearly all sectors of environmental concern, there is unfulfilled potential to conduct operations that affect natural resources in a more sustainable manner. In addition, there are few yet emerging examples of projects that meet criteria as sustainable. Information sharing among agency practitioners with the work of professional societies in a range of resource areas is only

beginning. Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design is the best integrated into agency work due to the application of EO 13423 - Strengthening Federal Environmental, Energy, and Transportation Management (January 2007). However, further work is needed to integrate approaches advocated by the Sustainable Sites Initiative program into management practices at SNI.

Many opportunities also exist for the construction of infrastructure in a way that promotes the achievement of the Navy's mission in an environmentally integrated way. For example, the use of LID approved permeable surfaces and bioswales reduces storm-water runoff and reduces contaminants of concern in storm water runoff. Bioengineering techniques can promote favored wildlife while excluding undesirable species, such as rats. It is less expensive to design to prevent such impacts rather than to fix them after the fact.

Sustainability indicators for specific resources, such as water, energy, fisheries, wildlife, rangeland, soils, etc. are undergoing research and scrutiny for criteria and selection of the best indicators of sustainability. Professional societies collaborate in each specialty to develop Best Management Practices (BMPs), conceptual approaches at a hierarchy of scales, and position statements. Examples are "roundtable discussion forums" for water, energy, and soils. The resource roundtables, blogs, and discussion groups focus on each criterion, a category of conditions or processes that can be assessed nationally to determine if the current level of management will ensure sustainability. The indicators are developed through the expert opinions of scientists, management agency personnel, non-governmental organization representatives, practitioners, and other stakeholders. A suite of variables, when complemented with other sustainability indicators, produce a viable system to monitor at the national level the biophysical, social, and economic characteristics indicating trends of sustainability. There is a need to develop local indicators that tier off these.

The following objective and strategies are designed to improve sustainability of both development projects and natural habitats. Many are adapted from EO 13423.

Management Strategy

Objective: Sustain natural resources and the Navy institutional mission by enabling innovation in planning, design, project management, and implementation for development projects affecting the built environment.

- I. Ensure Navy leadership has visibility with respect to the total cost of mission sustainment, day-to-day operations, infrastructure and building development, and redevelopment. This should incorporate climate change scenarios and the projected value of the loss of habitat associated with the decision for No Action.
 - A. Natural resources asset valuation is needed to properly implement business decisions that affect resource capability, e.g. value of permitted air emissions, water quality permits, water resources availability. Identify those that sustain the mission. Assess their condition, quality, capacity, and value.
- II. Use the RSIP/master planning/site approval/NEPA processes to bring in interdisciplinary support to decisions early in the project planning phase that includes water, air quality, engineering, and natural resources professionals.
 - A. Improve the integration of Navy natural resources professionals into the sustainability planning through RSIPs, NEPA, site approval, and SAPs. Facilitate early, advance project review for storm water management, landscaping, shoreline and in-water structures.
 - B. Improve the integration of Navy water resources and water quality professionals into sustainability planning.
 1. Go beyond pollution prevention and compliance to sustainable operations.
 2. Expand the incorporation of sustainability principles into project scope and cost estimates, such as that reflected in DD Form 1391.

- III.* Apply sustainability principles to the management of habitats, species, and ecological functions on SNI by identifying resource-specific best practices similar to what has been done for energy and water in the built environment using LEED, LID, and SSI approaches.
- A.* Continue to comply with EO 13123 which tasks federal agencies with defining principles for implementing sustainable development in construction.
- 1.* Promote sustainable land use through avoiding the use of undeveloped land, open space, water and soil conservation areas, existing natural ecosystems, endangered species habitats, and floodplains (NAVFACINST 11010.45).
- a.* Select a site that preserves natural resources (Credit 1 under LEED Green Building Rating System)
- b.* Clean up and redevelop polluted sites (Credit 3)
- c.* Choose the project site to protect natural resources (NAVFACINST 11010.45):
- 1.* Consider the vegetation and topography of available sites and identify which would require the least amount of disruption in order to accommodate the project. Protect ecologically sensitive areas such as endangered species habitats, woodlands, meadows, wetlands, and water sources. Preserve culturally sensitive areas such as historic and archeological sites. Increase urban density rather than developing untouched areas. Maintain or increase the amount of green space, including planting trees, especially in densely developed areas where open parkland may not be possible.
 - 2.* Evaluate the topography of the possible sites. Accommodate topographically difficult terrain, avoiding disturbance of steep slopes where development could cause erosion. Avoid development of sites that would adversely affect watersheds or water sources. Accommodate natural watershed drainage patterns, and take advantage of water on a site in land use planning.
 - 3.* Plan for efficient use of water through use of natural drainage, drought tolerant landscaping, and recycling.
 - 4.* Reduce and manage storm water runoff from the site. This involves consideration of a storm water system layout and integration with existing utilities.
 - 5.* Minimize paved areas and maximize use of native vegetation that is selected from the plant palette included within the approved NBVC Landscape Plan.
 - 6.* Align proposed structures on the site to take advantage of positive, or minimize negative, climatic and weather factors such as sun angle and wind direction, thereby using passive measures to reduce energy consumption.
 - 7.* Minimize the footprint of the building and associated facilities on the site to retain open space. Bring the outside in, and the inside out, thereby connecting building occupants with nature.
 - 8.* Improve energy efficiency and reduce greenhouse gas emissions through a reduction of energy use.
 - 9.* Encourage methods of landscape design and maintenance that uses native vegetation and reduces or eliminates the use of pesticides, herbicides, and synthetic fertilizers as well as encouraging the use of compost and recycled rain or gray water (NAVFACINST 11010.45).
 - 10.* Reduce the consumption of petroleum fueled transportation and operations.
 - 11.* Prevent waste and encourage recycling to reduce the amount of trash, consistent with EO 13101.

- B. Implement LID practices for protecting water quality.
 - C. Use construction siting, materials, and methods that promote biotic communities to the fullest extent possible.
- IV. Use metrics (indicators) of sustainability that integrate environmental stewardship, mission accomplishment, social responsibility, and economic prosperity.
- A. Define and adopt standards, rating systems, and metrics.
 - B. Collaborate with tenants to develop an integrated, measurable, installation-wide sustainability effort.
 - C. Incorporate metrics and standards of success meaningful to SNI. Examples are:
 - LEED certification for all military construction (MILCON) starting in a fiscal year in the future.
 - National Governors Association Checklist, New Community Design.⁵
 - Habitat Indicators.
 - Global warming threat reduction through reduced carbon footprint and project design that incorporate planning for climate change.
- V. To develop sustainability indicators and best practices, monitor and integrate into SNI planning the work of professional societies, academic institutions, managers, business and government entities on the topic of sustainability with regard to specific disciplines and resource subsets.
- A. Select sustainability indicators that have the potential to turn the generic concept of sustainability into action.
 - B. Select indicators that improve the quality, regularity of dissemination, and accessibility to the public of sustainability achievement.
 - C. Identify appropriate spatial and temporal resolutions for reporting.
 - D. Consider Life Cycle Assessment as a "composite measure of sustainability." It analyzes the environmental performance of products and services through all phases of their life cycle: extracting and processing raw materials; manufacturing, transportation and distribution; use, re-use, maintenance; recycling, and final disposal
 - E. Consider an Environmental Sustainability Index (e.g. Yale Center for Environmental Law and Policy [YCELP], Center for International Earth Science Information Network [CIESIN] of Columbia University, and World Economic Forum and the Directorate-General Joint Research Centre [European Commission] 2004).
- VI. Develop a SAP at an organizational level meaningful to on-the-ground practice.
- A. Rank projects based on metrics that will help meet sustainability objectives.
 - B. Place top-tier projects in Implementation Table for action.
 - C. Assign natural resources valuation to support life-cycle cost analysis.
 - D. Integrate anti-terrorism considerations (NAVFACINST 10110.45).
- VII. Conduct training in sustainable design criteria in the Navy for engineers, construction and design specialists, water quality specialists, and biologists. This could be web-based training.
- VIII. Foster socially and environmentally responsible behavior through communication.

⁵Available online at: <http://www.nga.org/cda/files/072001NCDFULL.pdf>.

- A. Establish sustainability leadership awards for excellence in environmental, transportation, and energy management.

5.2 Construction and Facility Maintenance

Specific Concerns

- The military mission and preparedness at SNI could be impacted by ongoing erosion, as infrastructure and facilities are potentially threatened.
- Erosion control measures may be eliminated from a project as a cost-cutting measure.
- A concern associated with construction and facility maintenance projects is the introduction or spread of terrestrial invasive exotic plant species.
- Security lighting around buildings is for safety, such as lighting in uninhabited areas and in high asset locations like fuel stations. Night lighting may have environmental effects.
- Environmental Division is consulted from project inception to avoid delays in project schedule and minimize adverse environmental effects.

Current Management

By EO, the President has directed that federal agencies shall design, use, or promote construction practices that minimize adverse effects on the natural habitat where cost-effective and to the extent practicable (EO 13112). Routine maintenance activities that may affect drainages fall under the USACE authority from Section 404 of the CWA. Locations where roads cross drainages are most likely to require coverage by a permit. However, most SNI activities are covered under a Nationwide General Permit, so no specific application for a permit is required.

Assessment of Current Management

On occasion there is a need to build new facilities to shore up the SNI's ability to efficiently underpin military readiness. The DoD MILCON budget is a primary source of funds for construction. However, recent budget cuts have limited the MILCON project roster.

Management Strategy

Objective: Reduce conflicts and impacts to sensitive environmental resources by completing thorough environmental documentation requirements when conducting construction and facility maintenance and the, while ensuring full accomplishment of the military mission.

- I. Fish and wildlife conservation shall be considered in all site feasibility studies and project planning, design and construction. Appropriate conservation work and associated funding shall be included in project proposals and construction contracts and specification (DoD 4715.DD-R 1996). Funding to throughout building phases and post-construction to remove weeds, etc.
 - A. Develop or use proven BMPs for controlling soil erosion from construction and landscaping sites. Use the *California Storm Water Best Management Practices Handbook* (Caltrans 2000).
 - B. Ensure incorporation of BMPs in the preliminary engineering, design, and construction of facilities involving ground disturbance (OPNAVINST 5090.1D and OPNAV M-5090.1).
 - C. Vehicular traffic associated with the construction activities and operational support activities will remain on established roads to the maximum extent practicable. Areas with highly erodible soils will be given special consideration when designing the proposed project to ensure incorporation of various erosion control techniques, such as, straw bales, silt fencing, aggregate materials, wetting compounds, and rehabilitation, where possible, to decrease erosion. Rehabilitation may include revegetating or the distribution

- of organic and geological materials (i.e. rocks) over the disturbed area to reduce erosion while allowing the area to naturally vegetate. Additionally, erosion control measures and appropriate BMPs, as required and promulgated through the SWPPP and engineering designs, will be implemented before, during, and after construction activities.
- D. Native seeds or plants, which are compatible with the enhancement of protected species, will be used to the extent practicable, as required under Section 7(a)(1) of the ESA, to revegetate staging areas and other temporarily disturbed areas.
 - E. Construction equipment will be cleaned at the temporary staging areas, in accordance with BMPs, prior to entering and departing the project corridor to minimize the spread and establishment of non-native invasive plant species.
 - F. The MBTA requires that federal agencies coordinate with USFWS if a construction or site activity would result in the take of a migratory bird. If construction or clearing activities are scheduled during nesting season (February 15 through August 31), surveys will be performed to identify active nests. If construction activities would result in the take of a migratory bird, then coordination with USFWS and Navy will be undertaken and applicable permits would be obtained prior to construction or clearing activities.
- II. Promote the innovative and effective use of BMPs to prevent and control erosion and protect sensitive resources.
- A. Erosion from the following sources shall be addressed through plans and BMPs, based on the priorities cited above.
 - 1. Paved and secondary (unpaved) roads and culverts. Specific methods (BMPs) are cited in the *California Department of Transportation Statewide Storm Water Management Plan* (2003).
 - 2. Utilities, pipelines and underground cables.
 - B. Monitor resource condition and effectiveness of BMPs as mitigation.
 - C. Monitor and enforce compliance with BMPs.
- III. There is a long-term desire to underground as many utility lines as possible in order to avoid their use as perches by predators on federally protected species.
- IV. Encourage protocols for emergency repair of infrastructure so that human life, health and safety are given precedence, but sensitive resources are also protected. Emergency repairs need to be anticipated so environmental damage, which is typically worse in an emergency than during a planned repair, can be reduced.
- A. Investigate means to improve successful acquisition of funding for preventive repair of infrastructure, to avoid more environmentally damaging emergency repairs.

5.2.1 Road Maintenance

Specific Concerns

- Roadside maintenance can facilitate the spread of invasive plants.
- Timing of roadside maintenance may disturb nesting migratory birds.
- Of necessity, paved and unpaved roads and other infrastructure will traverse sensitive environmental and cultural areas. Routine maintenance may be hampered by the need to comply with requirements to protect sensitive habitat unless there is advanced early coordination. With proper planning, delays and impacts can be avoided or minimized.

Current Management

Road maintenance mowing activities often occur in grasslands habitat. Impacts from road development and maintenance are generally avoided and minimized through the SA/PRB process codified in NBVCINST 11010.1B. Management of roads also take into consideration and coordination with cultural resource management efforts focused on SNI's archeological resources. Surveys of mowed areas for bird nests occur to determine if or the frequency that birds may nest along mowed shoulder of road. In the event nests are found, management will occur to eliminate take.

Assessment of Current Management

Continued utilization of the SA/PRB process are necessary and sufficient to avoid and minimize impacts to sensitive natural and cultural resources associated with conducting road maintenance activities on SNI.

Management Strategy

Objective: Improve the soundness of road maintenance practices to avoid and minimize environmental impacts, to control non-native species, enhance biodiversity, and protect sensitive species, soil productivity, watershed functioning, and water quality.

- I. Develop a 5–10 year Long-term Road Maintenance Plan. Update and improve road maintenance best management practices. Continue to determine if migratory birds are nesting along shoulder that is mowed. Improve the way road shoulders are managed, such as managing the timing of mowing with respect to nesting migratory birds (if nesting occurring), and ensuring storm water is managed so as to protect wetlands.
- II. Comply with CWA Section 404 Permit and Section 401 State Water Quality Certification if a project may affect a floodplain, wetlands or watercourses.
 - B. A NPDES permit for storm water discharges from construction activities is required of owners/operators of construction sites where five or more acres of land will be graded or disturbed. They must apply for coverage under EPA's General Permit for storm water discharges associated with construction activities (effective 01 October 1992).
 1. Activities requiring a permit include construction where five or more acres will be graded or disturbed. A project cannot be phased to avoid permit compliance or application for a permit.
 2. A SWPPP must be prepared prior to the Notice of Intent is filed and records maintained of site inspections. The SWPPP is kept on site and not submitted to EPA or the RWQCB unless requested.
 - C. Actions that result in a discharge of dredged or fill material into waters of the U.S., including wetlands, most likely will require a Section 404 permit. Utility and road crossings, bridges, bank protection, boat launch ramps, sand and gravel mining, and fill associated with residential and commercial development are typical activities which require 404 permits.
 1. A project may qualify for a nationwide permit, an individual permit, or a Letter of Permission. Check with the Natural Resources Manager.
 2. Section 401 state water quality certification is required prior to issuance of 404 permits from USACE.
 3. Seek and obtain regional 404 permits (four months in advance) from USACE, if needed.
 4. Obtain a five-year regional permit for all routine maintenance practices.

- D. CWA Section 401 requires a review of federal permits, actions, and approvals that may result in a discharge to waters of the state (including wetlands and many washes) to ensure compliance with state water quality standards to restore and maintain the chemical, physical, and biological integrity of the Nation's waters. This permit is necessary whenever any other CWA permits are required.
 - E. Provide project proponents and the Facilities Manager direction on how to implement a USACE Nationwide permit, as well as direction on applying for CWA permits not covered by Nationwide permits.
 - F. Obtain the following concurrently with regional 404 permit: 401 permit from California RWQCB, CDFW Streambed Alteration Agreement, documentation of contact with State Historic Preservation Officer, and documentation of contact with USFWS.
- III. In order to comply with environmental requirements in a cost-effective manner, realign record-keeping on infrastructure to facilitate environmental documentation, permitting and mitigation planning.
- A. Keep specifications for each culvert, road structure, road, utility line, communication line, and other infrastructure in an electronic format so they can be reproduced at any scale, updated as needed, and in sufficient detail to assist in environmental compliance and monitoring.
 - B. Keep design and maintenance plans, protocols, procedures and other records on hand as required in the USACE permit application for wetlands disturbance to facilitate the SNI permitting and NEPA process for the projects.
- IV. Apply principles of “Integrated Vegetation Management,⁶” which are similar to the principles of grazing management, to meet multiple objectives for roadside maintenance to alleviate harmful environmental impacts and enhance possible benefits.
- A. Consider that roadside mowing strategy makes key decisions about time, space, and intensity that affect what flora and fauna grows after mowing.
 - 1. Mowing once or twice a year favors a richer plant palette than mowing more often, which favors a few tolerant species (Forman et al. 2003).
 - 2. The combination of seasonal timing and frequency of mowing has an even more major impact on plant diversity, and offers a many management choices to work with (Forman et al. 2003).
 - 3. Consider impacts to sensitive wildlife such as nesting birds, Island night lizard, and the San Nicolas Island fox when making decisions about time, space, and intensity of roadside maintenance activities.
 - B. Adopt a focus on improving the ecological condition of roadsides to enhance biodiversity, reduce non-natives, and control storm water pollutants, and provide cultural and natural resource education (Forman et al. 2003).
 - 1. Use a range of spatial and temporal techniques to broaden the range of native vegetation on roadsides, and reduce non-natives.
 - 2. Where possible, recuperate the natural surface heterogeneity to incorporate more diverse habitat elements.
 - C. Seek to reduce mowing frequency and intensity.
- V. Adopt a Mowing Instruction that provides roadside fire safety and minimizes detrimental environmental effects.

⁶For more information on Integrated Vegetation Management refer to the Integrated Vegetation Management Partners website at: <http://ivmpartners.org>.

5.2.2 Shoreline Construction

This section addresses construction activity and other disturbance in the shoreline environment. The types of activities addressed in this section include disturbance related to construction and maintenance of structures such as piers, docks, and wharves in the tidal zone, and roads, bridges, and buildings in the supratidal zone.

Specific Concerns

- Current engineering of shoreline structures does not effectively consider habitat values of alternative designs. Current “rule of thumb” guidance for construction buffer zones from the CCC may be inadequate for protecting habitat values, especially for nesting colonies. A need exists for optimal sizes and types of buffers that effectively prevent disturbance to different species of marine mammals or birds at critical time periods. Increased lighting may make otherwise high value habitat unusable for some species. Night lighting may increase vulnerability of nesting birds to predation. Sensitive plants may be affected by night lighting as it may disrupt photosynthetic processes. Effects of night lighting on wildlife are difficult to study and to prove, but the sensitivity of the resource merits further study and that a cautionary approach to use of lighting be taken.
- Effects of shoreline structures can go unmitigated due to lack of effects of the structures on adjacent habitats by modifying sediment transport currents. Construction of new or extended roads adjacent to the shore can cause loss of wetlands or wetland functions through sedimentation and blockage of tidal action. New or widened bridges can cause sedimentation of wetlands or alter the natural drainage patterns that affect wetlands.
- Shoreline areas have values that need protection: (1) high tide refugia for birds, (2) habitat for species that utilize beaches upland transition areas for pupping, (3) buffer zones between SNI habitats and the developed environment, and (4) sources of prey and juvenile nursery habitat for subtidal species. There are currently no regulatory or financial incentives to improve the habitat value of shoreline structures, to minimize their use, or to remove them in favor of a more natural shoreline.
- Construction associated with shoreline structures can generate turbidity, sedimentation, erosion, noise, and lighting that may hinder successful fish and wildlife use of SNI waters.

Current Management

Shoreline construction or maintenance activity in Waters of the U.S. is permitted under the CWA and also must comply with EFH conservation requirements under the Magnuson-Stevens Fishery Conservation and Management Act, ESA-related protection of federally listed species, CZMA consistency, as well as NEPA and CEQ. An environmental assessment requirements. In cases where listed species may be affected, mitigation is also required under the ESA. Above the mean higher high water line, construction activities must comply with provisions of the CCA and are permitted by the CCC. The Navy, for example, has a General Consistency Determination for periodic replacement of piers and shoreline structures dated 1998 (CD-070-98).

Permitting for riprap and other structures that result in a complete fill to upland habitat is primarily reviewed for the requirement for no net loss of jurisdictional waters of the U.S. (a balanced cut and fill must be part of the site plan). Mitigation for fill is required, as well as for impacts to marine resources or listed species. Typically, construction activities that generate noise or turbidity are restricted during the western snowy plover season to avoid impairing their foraging activities. However, there normally is no consideration of differences in habitat value because of designs or materials used in a structure, other than materials that may allow more light. Setback buffer requirements may be imposed by the CCC for construction not related to erosion control or vessel access. Current precedent for construction permitted by the CCC for buffer distances is 50 feet (15 m) in freshwater areas, and 100 feet (30 m) for the salt marsh. The CCC could adjust this requirement based on requests from commenting resource agencies.

Assessment of Current Management

Little scientific study has been conducted on the effects of noise or lighting on species and habitats of concern in this INRMP. Mitigation requirements are based on biologist judgment and experience.

Management Strategy

Objective: Ensure that shoreline construction activities do not increase erosion or adversely impact sensitive natural or cultural resources.

- I. Ensure that the Navy's Regional Shoreline Infrastructure Planning integrates the goal and objectives of this INRMP.
- II. Conserve existing habitat values by recommending setbacks for CCC permits for new construction that effectively protect habitat values, especially of sensitive habitats such as salt marsh and tidal flats.
- III. Discourage any Navy operations or construction that may impact the sensitive intertidal environment unless operationally necessary. Discourage construction of seawalls, revetments, breakwaters, or other artificial structure for coastal erosion control, unless each of the following criteria is met (California Coastal Coalition Policy for Shoreline Erosion Protection 14 September 1978):
 - A. No other nonstructural alternative is practical or preferable.
 - B. The condition causing the problem is site specific and not attributable to a general erosion trend, or the project reduces the need for a number of individual projects and solves a regional erosion problem.
 - C. It can be shown that a structure(s) will successfully mitigate the effects of shoreline erosion and will not adversely affect adjacent or other sections of the shoreline.
 - D. Any project-caused impacts on fish and wildlife resources will be offset by adequate fish and wildlife conservation measures.
- IV. Encourage the refitting of developed shorelines and existing structures to enhance habitat values.
 - A. Besides providing their engineered function, design shoreline structures to mimic the original habitat structure and function (this refers to situations where the native substrate is a hard one). Maximize benefit to native SNI species of fishes, birds, and invertebrates.
- V. Promote experimentation and application of alternative shoreline and underwater habitat structures.
 - A. Develop objective design criteria.
 1. Incorporate the best understanding about the attributes of the target habitat that promote the desired function.
 2. Designs should incorporate several options or variations of a particular attribute to constitute a legitimate test of the concept, and to provide an adaptive direction towards design modification.
 3. Incorporate contingency plans for each design element.
 - B. Monitor changes in invertebrate and algae populations that can result from alternative structural designs.
 - C. Identify and prioritize desired ecological function of artificial structures, including: (1) trophic support for native fishes and birds, (2) habitat for migratory birds, (3) nursery

and refugia for subtidal species, and (4) habitat for endangered and other special status species.

- VI. Promote experimentation and application of alternative LID and habitat-friendly landscaped areas adjacent to the shore.

5.3 Communications Towers, Wind Energy Facilities, and Power Lines

Specific Concerns

- There is concern about growing impacts from communications towers, power lines, and wind energy facilities to migratory birds protected under the MBTA of 1918, as amended. Communication towers may kill from 4-5 million birds per year. Collisions with power transmission and distribution lines may kill anywhere from hundreds of thousands to 175 million birds annually, and power lines electrocute tens to hundreds of thousands more birds annually. The avian risk assessment study for the SNI Wind Energy Project EA (NAVFAC SW 2010b) estimated 20.13 avian fatalities, including 0.07 raptors per year for the 11 proposed wind turbines.
- The construction of new towers creates a potentially significant impact on migratory birds, especially some 350 species of night-migrating birds. Communications towers are estimated to kill 4-5 million birds per year, which violates the spirit and the intent of the MBTA and the CFR at Part 50 designed to implement the MBTA. Some of the species affected are also protected under the ESA and Bald and Golden Eagle Act (16 USC 668-668c).

Current Management

Impacts associated with communications towers, wind energy facilities, and power lines are generally avoided and minimized through the SA/PRB process (NBVCINST 11010.1B). Guidance on communications towers from the USFWS such as the "Service Guidance on the Siting, Construction, Operation, and Decommissioning of Communications Towers" will also be used to manage these towers (USFWS 2000). The conservation, avoidance, and minimization measures outlined in the SNI Wind Energy Project BO (USFWS 2010) and Wind Energy Project EA (NAVFAC SW 2010b) were followed during the construction of the wind energy project on Skyline Drive. Guidance on wind energy facilities from the California Energy Commission (CEC) and the CDFW such as the "California Guidelines for Reducing Impacts to Birds and Bats from Wind Energy Development" (CEC and CDFG 2007) was referenced in the SNI Wind Energy Project BO (USFWS 2010) and the Wind Energy Project EA (NAVFAC SW 2010b). Management also refers to the guidance in Avian Power Line Interaction Committee - Reducing Avian Collisions with Power Lines (2012) and USFWS Land-based Wind Energy Guidelines (2012). Guy wires will be avoided whenever feasible and are required to be outfitted with bird deterrents (flappers) to reduce avian mortality.

Assessment of Current Management

The continued utilization of the SA/PRB process is necessary in order to avoid and minimize impacts associated with the planning, construction, and operation of communications towers, wind energy facilities, and power lines. Supplemental adherence to USFWS guidance for communications towers and CEC and CDFW guidance for wind energy facilities will provide a sufficient level of management to further avoid and minimize impacts associated with the planning, construction, and operation of such facilities.

Management Strategy

Objective: Safeguard military readiness by maintaining communications towers, powerlines, and wind energy facilities while avoiding and minimizing impacts to native wildlife and plants.

- I. Ensure siting criteria for communications towers, power lines, and wind farms are addressed through the SA/PRB process (NBVCINST 11010.1B).
- II. Use established protocols, such as the Service Interim Guidance on Avoiding and Minimizing Wildlife Impacts from Wind Turbines (USFWS 2003b) and the California Guidelines for Reducing Impacts to Birds and Bats from Wind Energy Development (CEC and CDFG 2007), to evaluate and rank potential sites proposed for wind development.
- III. Comply with California Energy Commission and CDFW guidelines for reducing impacts to birds and bats from wind energy development to the greatest extent possible (CEC and CDFG 2007).
 - A. Conduct mortality surveys at operational wind farms as described in Chapter 5 of "California Guidelines for Reducing Impacts to Birds and Bats from Wind Energy Development" (CEC and CDFG 2007).
- IV. Comply with avoidance and minimization measures during the operation phase of wind energy facilities as identified in the EA for the Development of Wind Energy Facilities on SNI (NAVFAC SW 2010b).
 - A. Comply with General Biological Resource Measures.
 1. Invasive pest plant species will be controlled through appropriately timed herbicide applications and/or physical removal.
 2. Air operations and maintenance program will be implemented to ensure the continued effectiveness of post-construction BMPs once construction is completed. Maintenance activities will vary depending on the BMPs in place, but will include the following:
 - a. Perform quarterly inspections of storm water drains, basins, and BMPs.
 - b. Clean and remove debris from BMP inlets, outlets, or catchments after major storm events (more than 2 inches [5 cm] of rainfall).
 - c. Maintain vegetated BMPs (e.g. maintaining swales and/or detention/retention systems to original cross-sections and infiltration rates).
 - d. Remove accumulated trash, debris, and/or sediment from BMPs before each wet season (i.e. September).
 - e. Repair or replace armor rock or stone aggregate that serves as scour protection (e.g. rip rap).
 - f. Repair erosion areas and stabilize repairs with additional erosion control protection.
 - g. Implement structural and nonstructural programs (i.e. routine procedures or practices) to prohibit the storage of uncovered hazardous substances in outdoor areas.
 3. All permanent and visiting personnel will be required to attend an environmental briefing that emphasizes Federal and Navy regulations pertaining to the protection of listed and rare species and their environment.
 - B. Comply with Avian and Bat Species Specific Measures.
 1. Ensure all wind energy facility operations are compliant with the MBTA. Active nests (i.e. nests with eggs and dependent chicks) are protected year-round by the MBTA. Project-related activities that will require disturbance, require removal of an active

- nest, or cause a breeding bird to leave the nest for prolonged lengths of time will not be permitted.
2. To the greatest extent feasible, vegetation clearing along the road and at the wind energy facility site should be scheduled to avoid the nesting season for birds from 15 December to 30 June.
 3. Trimming or removal of vegetation during the peak breeding season (15 December through 15 June) will require a pre-activity survey by the project biologist to determine that active nests will not be affected. If an active nest is found at any time, actions that could harm the nest will cease and a qualified Navy biologist will be contacted.
 4. A post-construction mortality study will be designed and implemented to determine mortality rates associated with wind turbine collision.
 5. Avian mortality estimates for the operation of the wind energy facility may not necessarily accurately account for estimates of potential mortality of nocturnal migrating passerines due to the lack of available data for this avian group (e.g. flight behavior and flight height). While research suggests that nocturnal migrants infrequently collide with operating turbines (Erickson et al. 2001), this scenario is not well studied. Avian mortality documented in post-construction mortality studies or observed incidentally will be reported to and discussed with the USFWS on an annual basis.
- C. Comply with water resources measures.
1. Once construction and of each wind turbine construction phase is completed, an effective operations and maintenance program will be implemented to ensure the continued effectiveness of post-construction BMPs. Maintenance activities would vary depending on the BMPs in place but would include the following:
 - a. Removing accumulated trash, debris, and/or sediment from BMPs before each wet season (i.e. September).
 - b. Repairing or replacing armor rock or stone aggregate that serves as scour protection (e.g. rip rap).
 - c. Seeding or sodding to restore or maintain ground cover where it has been previously been applied.
 - d. Repairing erosion areas and stabilizing repairs with additional erosion control protection.
 - e. Removing and replacing all dead and diseased vegetation as necessary to maintain vegetation coverage and minimize erosion.
 - f. Implementing structural and nonstructural programs (i.e. routing procedures or practices) to prohibit the storage of uncovered hazardous substances in outdoor areas.
- V. Comply with USFWS guidelines for reducing fatal bird strikes on communication towers, such as the Service guidance on the siting, construction, operation and decommissioning of communications towers (USFWS 2000), to the greatest extent practicable.

5.4 Beneficial Partnerships and Collaborative Resources Planning

Ecosystem conservation is best accomplished through cooperative ventures because habitats and species do not conform to administrative boundaries. “Preserving all the parts” with an emphasis on habitats is central to the ecosystem management approach mandated by DoD. The ecosystem approach involves going beyond addressing short-term approaches for a single species. Regional planning processes are a means to address natural resource management using an ecosystem approach. Partnerships among private, local, state, tribal, and federal interests are vital to help realize ecosystem management, which is the basis for management of Navy lands and waters. Cooperative management of terrestrial and marine flora and fauna at NBVC SNI is required under the federal Sikes Act and the Fish and Wildlife Coordination Act. Like NEPA, the Fish and Wildlife Coordination Act is essentially procedural, as no specific outcome is mandated. The USFWS and CDFW have a statutory obligation to review and coordinate on INRMPs.

Recognizing this three-way partnership, the DoD, U.S. Department of the Interior/USFWS, and state fish and wildlife agencies signed an MOU in January 2006. The CDFW and other state fish and wildlife agencies were represented by the International Association of Fish and Wildlife Agencies. By working together to prepare, review, and implement the INRMPs, all parties promote the “synchronization of INRMPs with existing fish and wildlife service and state natural resource management plans” and “mutually agreed-upon fish and wildlife service conservation objectives to satisfy the goals of the Sikes Act.”

It is Navy policy to encourage local and regional partnerships to implement an INRMP. Other potential DoD and non-DoD organizations that could provide support with INRMP implementation include Partners-In-Flight, Legacy Resource Management Program, USACE, Armed Forces Pest Management Board, EPA, Natural Resources Conservation Service, U.S. Department of Agriculture, U.S. Geological Survey, California Department of Water Resources, California EPA, California Biodiversity Council, colleges, universities, non-profits, and contractors.

Specific Concerns

- Increased partnerships with research institutions and the associated increase in foot access through sensitive areas could affect natural resources.
- Liability issues and a new requirement for Memorandums of Agreement, which are time consuming and may limit partnership opportunities.
- NBVC would be liable for any environmental violations by researchers

Current Management

INRMP coordination and metric reviews are a beneficial partnership mandated by the Sikes Act, for collaborative resource planning at NBVC SNI. Coordination and communication among Navy commands and personnel are vital for ensuring that site activities are implemented as planned under the INRMP. Navy policy also calls for its installations to expand involvement in regional ecosystem planning, management, and restoration initiatives.

NBVC Environmental Division is a member of Channel Islands working groups that coordinate with the National Park Service, The Nature Conservancy, and other non-profits to address management challenges and cooperative opportunities (e.g. sharing biosecurity inspection costs, co-authoring documents, information sharing, etc.). If the opportunity arises, NBVC would participate in any Landscape Conservation Cooperatives and Population Vulnerability Assessment (*Section 1.10: Integrating Other Plans*). Information on Landscape Conservation Cooperatives can be found at: <http://www.fws.gov/science/shc/>.

The Navy also sees partnerships as a means to manage encroachment pressure on the Navy mission. DoDINST 4715.03 defines encroachment to be any lack of action by the Navy to coordinate with local jurisdictions, monitor the development plans of adjacent communities, or adequately manage facilities and real property.

Assessment of Current Management

There is active cooperation and communication between NBVC and universities, local environmental groups, regulatory agencies, and selected land owners (environmental nonprofits).

The establishment of cooperative planning efforts with surrounding land agencies and individuals throughout the region will benefit natural resources at SNI. Cooperative planning can also reduce the costs of actions. For example, staff from NBVC, Channel Islands National Park (CINP), and CDFW used the same database to collect data for the vegetation classification and mapping effort; data collected from SNI was shared with CINP for their vegetation classification and with the CDFW for their California Classification and Mapping Program. Partnerships with universities and other natural resource agencies that are seeking research opportunities at SNI would support the natural resource management objectives for protection of resources. Effective communication about protecting environmentally sensitive periods and areas is critical to avoid impacts to resources during research activities.

Management Strategy

Objective: Continue to be proactive in cooperative resources planning partnerships to create regional conservation, ecosystem-based solutions of mutual benefit while also protecting the military mission.

- I. Continue to participate in the conservation and encroachment planning.
- II. Participate in regional conservation and ecosystem planning efforts, in collaboration with other government agencies.
 - A. SNI involvement on the following criteria:
 1. Evaluation of agreements that may encumber land or resources now or in the future. Emphasize the critical importance of ensuring continuation of the military mission and its unique attributes which cannot be replaced.
 2. Evaluation of the potential benefits to SNI natural resources.
 - B. Pursue pertinent DoD ecosystem management policies, including:
 1. Maintain and improve the sustainability and biological diversity of the island ecosystem at the local landscape and other relevant ecological scales.
 2. Promote development of the best available scientific and field-tested information for use in land management decisions.
 3. Support Navy and USFWS partnering efforts through active participation.
 4. Become a nonbinding partner in regional conservation planning.
- III. Seek planning partnerships for invasive species and feral animal removal with adjacent landowners if compatible with mission activities.
- IV. Meet annually with USFWS and CDFW to fulfill Sikes Act provisions and related inter-agency cooperative agreements.
 - A. Ensure compatibility with INRMP goals, objectives, and policies as well as internal consistency in future inter-agency agreements and plans.
 - B. Involve state and federal resources agencies in the implementation of INRMP objectives and policies when practicable.

- C. Promote information sharing and scientifically-based, coordinated data collection and management planning.
- D. Continue to participate in an SNI Natural Resources Partnering Team.
- E. Support California Wildlife Action Plan goals and objectives described below.
 - 1. Federal and state agencies should partner to advance marine stewardship in areas of jurisdictional overlap, especially with regard to marine protected areas. Multiple federal and state agencies, with varying mandates, have jurisdictional authority over marine waters off California. For example, NOAA manages fisheries via the PFMC and regulates the use of vast tracts of coastal ocean via the National Marine Sanctuaries program. Additionally, the NPS is charged with protecting and conserving marine species on land and in the nearshore marine environment. The BLM manages the CCNM, composed of more than 20,000 offshore rocks. On the state level, the CDFW manages and conserves marine resources within state waters; the CCC regulates and oversees development and use of the coastal zone; the California State Coastal Conservancy promotes public access to the coastline and protection and enhancement of marine resources; State Parks operates several coastal protected areas; and the SWRCB protects ocean water quality. To implement stronger, more well-coordinated and sustainable policies, all agencies with jurisdiction in California's coastal waters should promote and engage in multiagency partnerships where jurisdictions overlap and missions are complementary.
 - 2. The federal and state resource agencies should expand efforts to eradicate introduced predators from all seabird colonies. The state and federal resource agencies with authority to manage mainland areas and islands that support seabird colonies (NPS, CDFW, California State Parks, and the U.S. military) should expand their collective efforts to completely eradicate all introduced terrestrial predators (primarily rats and cats) from the seabird colonies and roosting areas. Control predators around mainland colonies of endangered species, such as beach-nesting colonies of western snowy plovers.
 - 3. Federal and state resource agencies and institutions should foster and facilitate interstate collaborative research on marine species whose ranges cross jurisdictional boundaries. Species like the gray whale and the black oystercatcher are good examples of broadly distributed species that warrant multistate collaborative research and cooperative management.
 - 4. Federal and state resource agencies should foster and facilitate interstate collaborative enforcement efforts on marine species whose ranges cross jurisdictional boundaries.
- F. Support USFWS Regional goals such as habitat conservation planning.

5.5 Public Access

Public Access and Recreational Use of SNI Offshore Areas

SNI personnel recreational activities occur exclusively in nearshore areas of SNI, particularly in areas adjacent to shore less than 300 feet. Common offshore recreational activities include sport fishing, Self-Contained Underwater Breathing Apparatus (SCUBA) diving, boating, and occasionally surfing.

Southern California is a leading recreational fishing area along the west coast but variable weather and sea conditions at SNI allow for challenging conditions at times. The coastline around SNI support robust kelp forests that provide optimal sport fishing opportunities, although exposure to prevailing winds and waves limit accessibility during much of the year. Commercial

passenger fishing vessels intermittently offer one to two day sport fishing excursions either from the Ventura or Port Hueneme harbor. SCUBA diving at SNI takes place on occasion and is most common in conjunction with the beginning of lobster season (Saturday preceding the first Wednesday in October). Offshore recreational activities are generally allowed around SNI, during periods of limited military activity. Restrictions are enacted to clear the appropriate Sea Range operational areas of non-participants before military operations are conducted (NAWCWD 2002).

Public Access and Commercial Use of SNI Offshore Areas

Commercial fishing occurs in the nearshore and open ocean waters within 30 miles of SNI and fishing vessels participating in these fisheries regularly use SNI anchorages while fishing on multi-day trips. Most types of fisheries common in southern California can occur in the nearshore waters of SNI. The primary nearshore fisheries at the island remain sea urchins and lobster (abalone fisheries are currently closed). These fisheries occur in less than 120 feet (37 m) of water around the island; fall and winter are the most heavily utilized seasons for these fisheries. Fisheries seasons and regulations are established and regulated by the CDFW.

Public Access and Use of SNI Onshore Areas

Unauthorized public access onshore at SNI is prohibited, primarily due to security and safety requirements associated with the island's weapons testing mission and associated equipment.

DoDINST 4715.03, Natural Resources Conservation Program (18 March 2011) states:

“The principal purpose of DoD lands, waters, airspace, and coastal resources is to support mission-related activities....DoD lands, waters, and coastal resources shall be made available to the public for the educational or recreational use of natural resources when such access is compatible with military mission activities, ecosystem sustainability, and with other considerations such as security, safety, and fiscal soundness.”

Specific Concerns

- The Navy is required to provide outdoor recreation and interpretive opportunities to the public where and when it is compatible with military needs; however, SNI is not open to the public due to reasons including the military mission, safety, security, and resource sensitivity.

Current Management

Outdoor recreation, as defined for the purposes of this section, is the active use of the installation's natural resources for recreation and physical exercise. There is no current authorized hunting on SNI by military personnel; however, recreational fishing by military personnel is allowed with a standard CDFW fishing license.

SNI is not open to the public due to reasons including the military mission, safety, security, and resource sensitivity.

Assessment of Current Management

SNI does not have the capability for an extensive public access and recreation program for several reasons, including the following.

- There are general security and liability issues.
- Any outdoor recreation that might be provided should be non-mechanized to provide fire safety, and day use only.
- Other islands are available for public access.

There is no special demand for use of SNI property for recreational access, neither by the public nor its DoD employees. The nearby islands provide public access.

Management Strategy

Objective: Ensure public access is compatible with NBVC SNI mission, natural resources responsibility, safety, and security.

- I. Maintain clear and coherent policies regarding public access to SNI.
 - A. Planning for public access shall consider, but not be limited to, the following topics (DoDINST 4715.03):
 1. Eligible users of installation resources and facilities, including the installation's method of determining user eligibility and priorities;
 2. Procedures required for the public to gain access;
 3. Accessible and off-limits resources, areas and facilities;
 4. Areas designated for special use;
 5. Points of access and egress;
 6. Periods of access;
 7. List of permitted and prohibited activities;
 8. Schedule of applicable fees and charges;
 9. Personal injury and property liability policy;
 10. Access agreements with agencies and organizations, including Native American access to traditional cultural sites; and
 11. Installation-established access quotas to reflect installation operational and wildlife carrying capacity.
 - B. Protect sensitive resources from incompatible public uses.
 - C. Provide access for agencies and others to conduct natural resources research on the installation to the extent it does not interfere with the military mission or resources sensitivity. Any studies or surveys must be approved by the CO.
- II. Take active measures to discourage trespass.
 - A. Ensure that maps and any other informational materials provided to the public clearly show the boundaries of and restricted areas of SNI.

5.6 Public Outreach

DoD installations are to provide for sustained public access and use of natural resources for educational or recreational purposes when such access is compatible with mission activities, and with other considerations such as security, safety, or resources sensitivity (DoD 1996).

Specific Concerns

- The community may not be aware of the intensive management efforts undertaken by the Navy to ensure compatibility of mission activities with natural resource protection.

Current Management

The Navy is committed to public outreach where and when it is compatible with military needs. SNI is not open to the public due to reasons including the military mission, safety, security, and resource sensitivity. Given this context, public outreach for natural resource activities that occur on SNI are limited.

Assessment of Current Management

There is no special demand for use of SNI property for public outreach. Channel Islands National Park provide an opportunity for the public to learn more about the California Channel Islands.

Management Strategy

Objective: Build a strong conservation ethic and personal commitment to natural and cultural resources stewardship through the promotion of education and awareness of the unique environmental setting and history of San Nicolas Island, as well as the SNI mission.

- I. Participate in Earth Day and annual science festivals on the mainland.
- II. Identify natural resource themes for public outreach. Examples are marine mammals, endemic plants, seabirds, and the kelp forest.

5.7 Consistency with Integrated Cultural Resource Management Plan

Specific Concerns

- Natural resources monitoring programs and the control and management of terrestrial invasive exotic plants have the potential to impact archaeological sites.
- Expanding pinniped populations cause the greatest impacts to archaeological sites that occur near marine mammal haul out locations.
- Cultural resources excavation may impact sensitive habitats.

Current Management

The SA/PRB process codified in NBVCINST 11010.1B provides the primary planning mechanism for projects conducted by the Natural Resource program to be reviewed by other programs such as Cultural Resources. An Integrated Cultural Resource Management Plan (ICRMP) for NBVC is was developed in 2010. The ICRMP includes SNI within its planning footprint and is intended to provide strategic guidance to NBVC to support a conservation and stewardship program for historic and archaeological resources present on property owned or controlled by the Navy. The cultural resource conservation and stewardship program enables NBVC and SNI to comply with DoD cultural resource Instructions such as DoDINST 4715.16 Cultural Resource Management, EOs such as EO 11593 Protection and Enhancement of the Cultural Environment, and cultural resource laws including but not limited to the American Antiquities Act, Archaeological Resources Protection Act, Archaeological and Historic Preservation Act, NHPA, and the Historic Sites Act. Cultural resource management activities encompassed within the ICRMP include access restrictions to archaeological sites and surveys of historic and archaeological resources.

Assessment of Current Management

In theory, the SA/PRB process will review all projects that may affect sensitive natural or cultural resources at SNI. However, in practice not all projects are submitted for review through the SA/PRB process. In particular, recurring projects such as invasive exotic plant control efforts are often not submitted each year to the SA/PRB because they are conducted on a recurring basis and the scope and purpose of these projects does not change. Even though the scope and purpose of a recurring project such as invasive exotic plant control efforts does not change, the actual locations where treatment efforts are applied do change on an annual basis. Although most other programs would not need to review such a recurring project, the Cultural Resource program should review the project because treatment efforts have the potential to impact sensitive cultural resource areas and known archeological sites. There is a need for the Natural Resource Program to be more diligent in ensuring that projects that may affect sensitive cultural resources go through the SA/PRB on an annual basis in order to ensure that archaeological sites are not impacted by natural resource management activities. Considerations should also be made to ensure that cultural resource briefings are conducted, GIS files and maps of sensitive cultural resources are provided, buffer distances encompassing sensitive cultural resource areas are adhered to, and cultural resource specialists are available to provide oversight in the field for those Natural Resource projects that are not able to provide site specific information to the SA/PRB process.

Management Strategy

Objective: Maintain continual coordination of management activities between the cultural and natural resource management programs.

- I. Continue to participate in the SA/PRB process to ensure communication and coordination between the natural and cultural resource management programs when either program's activities have the potential to impact sensitive resources.
- II. Coordinate with the Cultural Resource program when project proponents of natural resource projects that have the potential to impact sensitive cultural resources are not able to provide site specific information due to their need to identify unknown locations of plants or wildlife and subsequently monitor or control them.
- III. Coordinate with Cultural Resources staff to develop and implement a plan to manage wildlife impacts to cultural resources to address the management of expanding wildlife populations that impact cultural resources.

5.8 Regulatory Compliance

This INRMP supports NBVC's compliance with federal and state laws, such as those related to environmental documentation, wetlands, endangered species, and land and wildlife management. Table 5-2 presents an overview of federal laws and regulations that must be considered when managing NBVC natural resources. This table identifies the federal agencies and applicable laws guiding oversight of natural resource management. A law may appear more than once in Table 5-2 if it guides the management actions of more than one federal agency. The most relevant federal, state, and local laws and regulations that can pertain to projects that occur at NBVC are listed in Appendix B. Natural resources consultation requirements, including any current or planned consultations, consistency with ESA Recovery Plans, Wildlife Action Plans, RWQCB Basin Plans, and with EFH permit and consultation processes are all discussed below.

Table 5-2: Federal Regulations to be considered in NBVC San Nicolas Island natural resources management.

Federal Agencies and Applicable Laws	Authority and Activities
U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (USACE)	
Clean Water Act, Section 404	Responsible for issuing Section 404 permits for placement of dredge and fill material into waters of the U.S. (up to higher high water line in tidal waters) and into wetlands in compliance with EPA regulations.
Clean Water Act, Section 401	Provides state authority to issue certification that a proposed dredge and fill disposal activity will not violate applicable state water quality standards.
Rivers and Harbors Act of 1899, Section 10	Regulates construction, excavation, and deposition in navigable waters (up to mean high water in tidal waters).
National Environmental Policy Act	Commenting or lead agency authority for environmental review of proposed projects.
U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)	
Clean Water Act, as amended	Develops Section 404 regulations and may veto USACE Section 404 permits. Regulates waste disposal in coastal waters. Administers National Estuary Program.
National Environmental Policy Act	Commenting authority on proposed projects.
U.S. Department of the Interior, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS)	
Fish and Wildlife Coordination Act	Reviews/comments on federal actions that affect many habitat-related issues, including wetlands and waters considered under Clean Water Act Section 404 and Rivers and Harbors Act Section 10 permit applications.
Federal Endangered Species Act	Regulates, monitors, and implements programs for protecting the ecosystem on which freshwater and estuarine fishes, wildlife, and habitat of listed species depend. Enforces international treaties and conventions related to species facing extinction. Shares jurisdiction with NOAA/NMFS over listed sea turtles and some marine mammals.
Migratory Bird Treaty Act	Enforces prohibition against the taking of migratory birds, their eggs, or their nests.
National Environmental Policy Act	Commenting authority on proposed projects.
U.S. Department of Commerce, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS)	
Fish and Wildlife Coordination Act	Reviews and comments on federal actions that affect marine fishery resources and many habitat related issues, including Clean Water Act Section 404 and Rivers and Harbors Act Section 10 permit applications.
Federal Endangered Species Act	Jurisdiction over most threatened or endangered marine species and some anadromous fishes.
Magnuson-Stevens Fisheries Conservation and Management Act	Responsible for maintaining and conserving fisheries and rebuilding overfished stocks. Responsible for determining whether projects or activities adversely impact essential fish habitat (those waters and substrate necessary for spawning, breeding, feeding, or growth to maturity).
Marine Mammal Protection Act	Enforces protection provisions for marine mammals.
National Environmental Policy Act	Commenting authority on proposed projects.

A Strategic Action Plan (03 February 2005) was developed by the DoD, USFWS and CDFW, for improving the quality and consistency of INRMPs, and ensuring compliance with two amendments to DoD responsibilities under the MBTA and the ESA. Proposed projects, operations, or other actions are scrutinized for potential environmental impacts through a formal review process for NEPA compliance (the SA/PRB, codified in NBVCINST 11010.1B). The INRMP is used as a tool to identify at an early stage, the potential impacts of planned Navy action on natural resources and provide a basis for altering the action to prevent or minimize those impacts. Mitigation is the process of minimizing impacts to protected habitats or species. As defined by the Council on Environmental Quality in 1978, it includes measures to avoid, minimize, rectify, reduce, eliminate, or compensate for the impact. In most cases, mitigation is undertaken in that order or “sequence” of preference, that is, from avoidance as a first priority to compensation as a last resort. Most mitigation policies and measures are agreed to as a result of protection under the NEPA, ESA, or the Clean Water Act.

Current Management

All proposed projects for NBVC must be planned in accordance with the SA/PRB (NBVCINST 11010.1B, 04 June 2003). During the SA/PRB process, NBVC ED reviews project plans to determine if there are any regulatory issues regarding MBTA, ESA, MMPA, EFH, and other natural resource regulations. The SA/PRB guides NEPA implementation and permitting procedures; the primary responsibility for NEPA implementation is NBVC ED. The steps for the SA/PRB process are described below:

1. The project proponent must first submit all project plans, and a SA/PRB Request Form, to the Public Works Department which enters the project into e-Projects (a web-based tracking tool) and sends an announcement to the PRB Manager and Asset Management Branch.
2. The Asset Management Branch decides whether the plan is consistent with the Regional Master Plan and whether the proposed project requires a Safety Site Approval (Explosive Safety, Electromagnetic Radiation, or Airfield Safety Waiver).
3. The PRB Manager makes the proposed project available to an interdisciplinary team for review. Either the environmental coordinator for the proponent organization or an NBVC ED representative performs an initial review. The interdisciplinary team includes environmental specialists, security officers, safety officers, firefighters, and industrial hygienists. The PRB reviews the proposed project for compliance with NEPA, assesses potential project impacts to natural resources, and determines whether the proposed project is suitable for a Categorical Exemption, an Environmental Assessment, or an Environmental Impact Statement.
4. If a planned project is determined to have the potential to adversely impact the environment, the proponent will generate a request for formal environmental analysis by the NBVC ED.
5. The team will review the proposed project and fill out the PRB Checklist with applicable conditions related to their specific media or program area (i.e. air quality, water quality, cultural resources, etc.).
6. The PRB Manager will include all project conditions in the Categorical Exemption memorandum and forward the memorandum to the NBVC Commanding Officer for review and signature. The final signed Categorical Exemption will be returned to the requestor along with a "Statement of Understanding Form" which increases the project proponents' accountability for reviewing and complying with all conditions of the Categorical Exemption. The Statement of Understanding Form is signed and returned to the PRB Manager within two weeks of receipt. After the project has been completed, changed or cancelled, the requestor must complete and submit to the PRB Manager a Project Closure Form, which closes the start-to-finish loop for projects on NBVC.

NBVC ED's responsibilities for NEPA implementation include the following:

- Ensuring each action proposal is reviewed in a timely manner;
- Completing and forwarding documentation for Categorical Exemption and continuing action determinations to the action proponent;
- Coordinating consultation and document preparation with the proponent for actions requiring an Environmental Assessment or Environmental Impact Statement;
- Assisting action proponents in development of an Environmental Assessment or Environmental Impact Statement;
- Serving as a member of the SA/PRB process (NBVCINST 11010.1B);
- Forwarding Environmental Assessment and Environmental Impact Statement documents to Office of the Chief of Naval Operations via the chain of command;
- Serving as a single point of contact with regulatory agencies while engaged in the NEPA process; and
- Ensure communication and coordination between the natural and cultural resource management programs when natural resource management program activities have the potential to impact cultural resources.

Assessment of Current Management

NBVC ED effectively uses NEPA to ensure its activities (as described in this INRMP) are properly planned, coordinated, and documented. It also uses NEPA to identify issues associated with other organizations' projects that affect SNI's natural resources, when it has the opportunity to review such projects. Project and mitigation planning at NBVC will continue to avoid, minimize, rectify, reduce, eliminate, or compensate for any identified environmental impact while not impacting the Navy mission. In most cases at NBVC mitigation will continue to be undertaken in that order of preference, that is, from avoidance as a first priority to compensation as a last resort.

An important offshoot of proper NEPA implementation is that projects are often enhanced by the effort. When natural resources managers understand mission and project requirements in terms of land features and requirements, they often not only offer more potential site options to mission or project planners but also offer alternatives to avoid future environmental conflicts.

Management Strategy

Objective: Improve long-term planning of mission activities and reduce potential environmental effects by implementing applicable regulatory requirements. Continue to use NEPA documentation.

I. As far as possible, NEPA, BOs, and other environmental documentation should be programmatic.

For example, routine maintenance, in concert with the Programmatic BO would allow maintenance work to continue without delay.

II. Continue to analyze the environmental consequences of each proposed action that could affect the natural environment, and address the impacts through planning and avoidance.

A. Continue to implement the site approval process NBVCINST 11010.1B.

1. Determine a means to improve coordination between various budget processes and NEPA.
2. Both NEPA and other site approval processes should start concurrently.

3. Encourage consideration of indirect effects during project analysis. Effects beyond the immediate project footprint, such as lighting, noise, turbidity, increased truck traffic, etc., can negatively affect sensitive species.
 4. If federally listed species or designated critical habitat is known to occur in the project area the site approval should address direct and indirect impacts to these resources. A determination of no effect should be concurred upon by the USFWS or NMFS.
- III. The NEPA planning process should facilitate project planning and routine maintenance work, including the consideration of potential mitigation. It should integrate project-specific plans with overall land use and natural resource management plans.
- A. Integrate NEPA planning early with regular planning functions of each office.
 1. Technical assistance should be provided by staff to support other offices, when needed, *before* and after a proposed action is submitted for NEPA review, giving guidance on: project design, site selection, and scope of work; development of reasonable alternatives, including alternative sites; and selection of appropriate mitigations so the proposal integrates mitigation from the beginning.
 - C. Update NEPA forms for project proponents, including the Site Approval Checklist, periodically to ensure consideration of all issues.
 1. Provide list of pre-approved conservation measures or mitigation for project proponents to select from.
 2. Reference appropriate environmental protection and mitigation policies from this INRMP. Also provide for creative and flexible mitigations.
 3. Make available to project planners updated GIS maps of sensitive resources on the property to assist in evaluating potential impacts of proposed projects and in recommending appropriate mitigation opportunities.
 - D. Communicate directly with all affected parties during NEPA process to avoid misunderstandings and delays.
 1. Keep a stakeholder contact list. Contact off-site interested and affected agencies and parties as soon as possible on projects with potentially significant environmental impacts, particularly if controversial.
 - a. If possible coordinate with regulatory agencies in the early stages of the planning process, so project designs and construction schedules can be developed to have the least impact on sensitive species. This will assist in avoiding potential loss of project funding and project delays.
- IV. Use this INRMP as an initial screen for review of projects proposed on the installation from both Navy and outside interests. All proposals should provide the following information regarding natural resources:
- A. The acres of habitat currently present on the site based on the most current vegetation map for the installation.
 - B. The known sensitive species locations on or adjacent to the site which can be obtained from the ED GIS specialist.
 - C. A natural resource review should still only be one part of a project-by-project review conducted for each proposal.
- V. Provide clear direction on how to exercise a nationwide permit so that project work is facilitated. If a number of projects may be coming down the pike, treat them as a bundled group and get one permit with one public contact period. Best Management Practices would be described and if the project stayed within the guidelines, a simple letter would need to be

sent to the USACE notifying the Corps of the project, and no additional public notification would be necessary. This a way to streamline consultation.

- VI. Ensure consistency with Coastal Zone Plans. The CZMA requires that Navy installations ensure their operations, activities, projects, and programs in or on coastal lands or waters that affect coastal zones, comply with the coastal state's approved management program to the maximum extent practicable and shall cooperate in resolving concerns identified during the consistency review process (OPNAVINST 5090.1D and OPNAV M-5090.1).
- VII. Ensure that all necessary permits are obtained for restoration projects such as USACE Section 404 permit, Section 401, and possibly NPDES permits to discharge water into the wetland (RWQCB 2004).
- VIII. *Seasonal Avoidance Measures.* During the active growing and breeding season, many species and habitats are more sensitive to disturbance that may cause harm, harassment, or severe damage. Limitations on the timing of activities to avoid and minimize adverse effects can appear to leave little time for work. Wetland resources are most sensitive during and shortly after the rainy season when the ground is still wet (about November 1 – April 30; annual variation will occur and actual situation should be verified by a qualified biologist prior to actions). USFWS should be contacted early on in the planning process to help define other species and timing restrictions that may be necessary.
 - A. *Phasing of Work.* Often, careful planning can show that impacts to the differing resources can be phased or avoided. To assist project planners, a schedule of sensitivity periods will help. Where the conduct of activities cannot be planned to avoid sensitive periods, project specific authorizations and appropriate additional impact minimization measures should be planned for and expected from regulatory agencies.
- IX. *Standard Mitigation Measures.* The following mitigation measures should be planned for all proposed actions unless a determination can be made, in consultation with the ED, that they are not appropriate:
 - A. *Avoidance and Minimization First.* Proposed actions must include requirements for impact avoidance and minimization measures. Because the intent is to lessen the severity of an action, the first step should be avoidance of impacts. Once avoidance has been implemented to its fullest extent, remaining impacts should be minimized prior to consideration of off-site compensation for damaged resources as a last resort. This must be the first step in the mitigation planning process because numerous regulatory authorizations require demonstration of maximum impact avoidance and minimization before authorization may be given. Measures which should be considered, as applicable are: worker environmental protection briefings, signs, markers, protective fencing, biological monitoring, erosion and sedimentation prevention, noise baffling, and temporary impact restoration. These should be included as part of the environmental protection plan of the environmental protection requirements for all standard operating procedures, work requests, and contracts during planning.
 - B. *Consider Indirect Effects.* Indirect effects of a proposed action must be addressed. Indirect effects have an impact at some point later in time. This may be the case where use and maintenance of a new facility is likely to have an adverse effect beyond the building “footprint” following construction. For example, fencing may be necessary to prevent landscape maintenance and concentrated human foot traffic from damaging naturally occurring resources that were avoided by the construction of a building. Often, maintenance and safety considerations associated with new or reutilized facilities, such as wildfire fuel breaks, are overlooked by planners and are not realized until use is implemented. Such considerations must be treated as part of the initial project and mitigated accordingly.
 1. In addition to direct habitat loss, less tangible direct and indirect effects may result from a proposed action. Some examples of indirect effects can include: lights; noise;

- increased access by vehicles, off-road vehicles, humans, pets (increased pet use of natural areas [with housing]; invasive weed or exotic plant introductions; shading; need for fire suppressions or fuel modification (setbacks or clear zones); irrigation runoff; pesticides, herbicides and/or fertilizer overspray or runoff; oil, grease and gasoline runoff; erosion and sedimentation; and operation and maintenance of new facilities. Most common concerns are noise associated with construction and subsequent use that extends beyond the immediate work or activity area, outdoor lighting that may require shielding, visual harassment by human activities and equipment operation, changes to wetland hydrology, and sedimentation from construction sites to wetlands. Often the temporary effects that may result from construction are avoided by performing work outside the sensitive breeding and growing seasons as presented in this planning guidance. Potential effects must be evaluated. Effects that are likely to have a longer or permanent adverse effect must be mitigated.
- C. *Survey Protocols.* Federally threatened or endangered species presence or absence determinations must be made using, if available, survey guidelines developed by the USFWS or other means acceptable to them. Where no such guidelines or protocols exist, surveys must be conducted by qualified permitted persons (as defined below) using methods recognized and accepted by scientific experts in the professional consulting field. When making presence/absence determinations relative to a project, areas where indirect effects may affect species must be considered as well. If a habitat is used by a species for some important part of their life cycle, it is considered occupied regardless of the presence of the species at any one time. Corridors for animal movement, such as rivers and streams, are important considerations in the overall analysis.
- D. *Use of a Qualified Biological Monitor.* A biological monitor or qualified biologist should be retained, in coordination with the natural resources biologists, to educate workers, oversee and implement impact avoidance and minimization, document impacts, and guide revegetation efforts for all proposed actions that require active avoidance or actually will affect threatened or endangered species, wetlands (including vernal pools), require active revegetation, or habitat compensation. At a minimum, this individual must have: (1) a bachelor's degree with an emphasis in ecology, natural resource management or related science; (2) demonstrated local experience with resource(s) involved; and (3) a good understanding of the regulations regarding wetlands and state and/or federal threatened and/or endangered species. Section 10(a)1A permits under the ESA are required for biological monitors that check federally listed bird nests, conduct trapping efforts for federally listed species, or otherwise handle federally listed species. These permits are obtained from USFWS. Requests for these permits should be submitted to both USFWS Regional Office in Portland, Oregon and Carlsbad Field Office, USFWS, California.
- F. *Restoration Plans to Be Completed in Advance.* All actions that require active habitat restoration, enhancement, and/or compensation must have an appropriate plan developed prior to implementation. Such plans must discuss the site conditions, methods to be implemented, monitoring and maintenance (usually three–five years), success criteria, remedial actions if expected success is not being achieved, and reporting requirements. The plans must ensure that all applicable requirements of regulatory approvals are incorporated. Often, regulatory agencies require that they have an opportunity to review and approve plans where their authorization for resource impacts is provided. Regardless, review and approval of plans must be accomplished through the site approval process.
- X. *Catalog and Track Success of Measures Employed.* It is helpful to maintain a reference catalog of past avoidance, mitigation, and compensatory measures that have been used, and a system for ongoing evaluation of their effectiveness.
- XI. *Catalog and track restoration sites.* Maintain a record of all mitigation sites and the status and phases of each.

5.9 Storm Water Management

Background

While pollution entering the storm drains is usually from diffuse or nonpoint sources, the outfalls of storm drains represent a point source of discharge into the ocean. The federal CWA, as amended in 1987 (§ 402[p]), is the driving regulatory force in addressing nonpoint source pollution from urban and storm water runoff.

Storm water discharge to navigable waters is prohibited unless an NPDES permit is obtained. The EPA has delegated responsibility for the NPDES program to the State Water Resources Control Board (SWRCB). In turn, LARWQCB implements the program at the regional level.

A tiered approach is used by EPA and the State in implementing the storm water permit program. Phase I requires NPDES permits for municipal storm sewers serving large and medium sized populations (greater than 250,000 or 100,000 respectively) and for storm water discharges associated with industrial activity that is already permitted. Phase II addresses smaller municipalities and small construction sites, and became effective in 2002.

The use of storm water BMPs are recommended. EPA's management measures and BMPs for urban runoff address six source categories: developing areas; construction sites; existing development; onsite disposal systems; general sources; and roads, highways, and bridges (CCC 1997). Handbooks describing storm water BMPs applicable for California are available for municipal, commercial /industrial, and construction BMPs (Camp Dresser and McKee et al. 1993; CASQA 2003).

Island watersheds are identified in the Los Angeles Regional Basin Plan for the Channel Islands Watershed Management Area and the following Beneficial Uses of island watercourses are identified: municipal supply, groundwater recharge, contact and noncontact water recreation, warm water habitat, wildlife habitat, and preservation of rare and endangered species.

San Nicolas Island and Begg Rock are identified as being surrounded by an Area of Biological Significance by the State Water Board and is subject to SWRCB Resolution 2012-0031.

Specific Concerns

- Regulatory approach through storm water permits under the CWA has provided incentives for cooperative monitoring but also has required some expensive solutions.
- Runoff of pollution through storm water is the primary means of delivery to nearshore waters. Storm drains are not connected to sewers or a sewage plant. Unless natural or artificial filtering systems exist, every contaminant in the storm drains or creek systems is delivered into the nearshore waters. This problem is a significant storm water management issue. The impervious surfaces of developed areas, such as parking lots, roads, and buildings, reduce the natural filtering capability of the watershed and instead help pollutants wash off the "hardened" landscape (Center for Watershed Protection 2003).
- Waters surrounding SNI have been designated by the State as an ASBS for special water quality protection.

Current Management

The Navy (CNRSW) policy related to storm water management is: "Develop, implement, and maintain current storm water management plans, and comply with federal, state, and local regulations and permit conditions, as applicable." The Navy has coverage under two general storm water permits: the statewide General Industrial NPDES Storm Water Permit and the statewide General Construction NPDES Storm Water Permit.

The Navy has a SWPPP (MMEC Group 2015) for SNI. This SWPPP is written in accordance with requirements of the SWRCB Water Quality Order No. 2014-0057-DWQ and NPDES General Permit No. CAS000001 (General Industrial Permit) (NBVC 2015). The General Industrial Permit authorizes NBVC SNI to discharge storm water from the date the Navy submitted an NOI (17 March 1992). A revised NOI was submitted to the State Water Board on 30 June 2015.

The General Permit stipulates the essential elements that all facilities must consider and address in the SWPPP. The document contains two parts: (1) the SNI SWPPP, and (2) the Monitoring Implementation Plan. Both were updated to accommodate changes in industrial activities at the facility.

The storm water pollution prevention team at NBVC SNI is responsible for the following monitoring activities:

1. Non-storm water discharge visual observations to verify that non-storm water discharges have been eliminated;
2. Wet season sampling and observations to aid in evaluating the effectiveness of the SWPPP; and
3. Annual site inspections to assess compliance with the General Industrial Permit.

Dry season conditions are observed monthly to identify potential illicit discharges. Wet season conditions are observed during the sampling events. Sampling is conducted during two storms from July 1 to December 31 and two storms from January 1 to June 30. The storm water discharge visual observations visually evaluate the quality of storm water discharged from each drainage area at NBVC SNI. Storm water samples are collected from four outfalls and are analyzed for pollutant parameters listed in the permit. Pollutant parameters are selected based on their potential to enter the storm water system from industrial activities that drain to each sampling outfall. Typical pollutant parameters include oil and grease, total suspended solids, and pH. Analytical results are submitted to LARWQCB as part of an annual report. Numeric Action Levels are listed in the General Industrial Permit. The results of annual sampling are used to indicate whether the additional BMPs have had an impact on pollutant parameter concentrations over time.

Expectations are being built into the storm water permitting programs that "adaptive management" should occur - where feedback from annual monitoring results can be used to adapt the monitoring effort and the Storm Water Management program to be more useful. Municipal Permits, for example, requires co-permittees to collaborate with each other to develop a Long-Term Effectiveness Assessment. "Pollutants of Concern" can change over time, with some being dropped and others added as monitoring results indicate their importance.

The waters surrounding SNI are subject to SWRCB Resolution 2012-0031. NRSW participated in a regional monitoring program as described by Resolution 2012-0031, facilitated by the Southern California Coastal Water Research Project. Using standardized monitoring procedures, the project should help with certain monitoring and evaluation needs, though only on five-year increments (2008, 2013, etc.).

Assessment of Current Management

The present condition of the SNI's water appears to be good with no impairments identified (LARWQCB 2007).

San Nicolas Island evaluates the effectiveness of its storm water program by evaluating whether the overall monitoring program is (1) achieving its objectives, which include ensuring that storm water discharges are in compliance with the General Permit, (2) ensuring that management practices to control pollutants are evaluated and revised to meet changing conditions, (3) assisting in the implementation of the SWPPP, and (4) measuring the effectiveness of BMPs in preventing pollutants from entering storm water discharge.

The design of new development (or retrofitting existing development) to control storm water runoff is the subject of Low Impact Development (LID) practices, which are becoming increasingly popular in the U.S. and other countries. The SWRCB defines LID as "storm water management practices for land development that are conducted to minimize impacts on the natural environment; Low Impact Development techniques include conserving natural systems and hydrologic functions by managing rainfall at the source using design techniques that infiltrate, filter, store, evaporate, and detain runoff" (SWRCB 2010). SNI is subject to the Energy Independence and Security Act (EISA) LID requirements and the Department of Defense LID Unified Facilities Criteria. The EPA has developed a website⁷ for LID Strategies and Tools for NPDES Phase II Communities to assist storm water Phase II communities integrate LID strategies into their compliance programs. The NAVFAC Atlantic has a LID Design Manual developed in cooperation with the Low Impact Design Center.

Monitoring sites have tended to be selected for the purpose of compliance monitoring rather than for effectiveness monitoring of specific BMPs or for trend monitoring of different streams or their reaches over time. Information useful to detect storm water pollutant sources (e.g. forensic monitoring) and to evaluate runoff BMPs could be derived from expanding current monitoring programs from their compliance orientation.

Management Strategy

Objective: Reduce and minimize storm water pollutants harmful to the ocean ecosystem from entering SNI waters.

- I. Encourage the further development and implementation of new or existing storm water pollution prevention and water quality protection efforts throughout SNI watershed.
- B. Promote runoff BMPs that support storm water pollution prevention and reduction.
 1. Explore the opportunity for better use of natural and artificial wetlands as upslope filters to trap runoff sediment and pollutants.
 2. Support LID practices to mimic natural runoff patterns.
 - a. Facilitate opportunities to address runoff at the sub-basin scale rather than site or project scale.
 - b. Support educational tools such as webcasts and podcasts that teach about how communities can more effectively manage rainwater where it falls. "Green" streets and landscapes beautify, preserve water quality, minimize urban heat island effect, and reduce a community's carbon footprint. Other practices include rain gardens, curb cuts, bioswales, and green roofs to address storm water runoff. An example of an audio program is available from the Office of Wetlands, Oceans, and Watersheds.⁸
- C. Actively participate in the RWQCB's TMDL processes.
- D. Develop an improved training program for appropriate government employees.
 1. Support regular workshops on the need, design, and implementation of BMPs.
 2. Train selected employees to train others.
 3. Provide training on LID to maintain pre-development hydrologic conditions.
- E. Encourage agencies to improve relevant administrative and planning practices.
 1. Ensure that storm water quality controls are considered during the site planning and design phase and not tacked on after the fact.

⁷Available at: <http://www.lowimpactdevelopment.org/lidphase2>.

⁸Available online at: <http://epa.gov/owow/podcasts>.

2. Examine location and evaluate need to reposition outfalls in relation to effects on sensitive habitats.
- F. Target monitoring efforts to evaluate the effectiveness of BMPs and trends in water quality of sub-basins leading into the ocean. Perform adaptive management.
1. Position monitoring stations at key sites within sub-basins to better track "hot spot" sources of storm water pollution. Assess results of dry weather and wet weather monitoring.
 2. Evaluate the effectiveness of the applied urban runoff BMPs through the use of a targeted effectiveness and trend monitoring in the watershed.
 3. Continue identifying sources of improper discharges through dry season storm water monitoring.
 4. Implement a Biological Indicator Development Program to better evaluate the effects of runoff on the nearshore ecosystem.
 5. Re-evaluate the design and use of BMPs based on the results of the monitoring program.

5.10 Environmental Restoration Program

The Defense Environmental Restoration Program, created under the Superfund Amendments and Reauthorization Act, has two site cleanup programs: Installation Restoration Program (IRP), for sites with past releases of hazardous substances; and Munitions Response Program, for sites with munitions and explosives of concern. Information on Navy's Environmental Restoration Program is available at:

http://www.navfac.navy.mil/navfac_worldwide/specialty_centers/exwc/products_and_services/ev/erb.html

The installation recognizes that adverse impacts to natural resources addressed in this INRMP may result from the release of hazardous substances, pollutants, and contaminants into the environment. The Navy's Environmental Restoration Program is responsible for identifying releases; considering risks and assessing impacts to human health and the environment, including impacts to endangered species, migratory birds, and biotic communities; and developing and selecting response actions when a release may result in an unacceptable risk to human health and the environment (Navy 2006).

When appropriate, the regional or installation's natural resources management staff will help the Environmental Restoration Program Remedial Project Manager identify potential impacts to natural resources caused by the release of contaminants (Navy 2006).

Regional or installation natural resources staff will also participate, as appropriate, in the Environmental Restoration Program decision-making process by communicating natural resource issues on the installation to the Remedial Project Manager, attending Restoration Advisory Board meetings, reviewing and commenting on Environmental Restoration Program documents (e.g., Remedial Investigation, Ecological Risk Assessment), and ensuring that response actions, to the maximum extent practicable, are undertaken in a manner that minimizes impacts to natural resources on the installation (Navy 2006). When appropriate, the regional or installation natural resources staff will make recommendations to the Environmental Restoration Program regarding cleanup strategies and site restoration.

During initial monitoring protocols, the natural resources manager may suggest sampling and testing be accomplished so as to not impact sensitive or critical areas. Also during site restoration, the natural resources manager has the opportunity to recommend site restoration

practices that are outlined within the INRMP. The Navy Environmental Restoration Program is required to comply with the substantive provisions of applicable or relevant and appropriate requirements (ARARs) identified prior to performing remedial or removal actions. CERCLA Section 121(d) requires compliance with state and federal ARARs for wastes left on site at the conclusion of a remedial response. Overall, protection of human health and the environment and compliance with ARARs (unless a specific ARAR is waived) are threshold requirements that a remedial alternative must meet in order to be selected. In cases where removal actions will be performed, ARARs shall be attained to the extent practicable. ARARs are identified on a case-by-case site specific basis, considering but not limited to factors such as the hazardous substance present, the site's physical features and the actions being considered as remedies. Coordination with agencies regarding listed species and critical habitats during the normal CERCLA process through document review and agency input is sufficient to satisfy the substantive requirements of the ESA as well as the CERCLA/ National Oil and Hazardous Substances Pollution Contingency Plan requirements to coordinate with natural resource agencies.

5.10.1 Installation Restoration Sites

There are no active Installation Restoration Program (IRP) sites located on SNI. Per OPNAVINST 5090.1D, Navy policy relative to IRP sites requires every effort must be made to ensure that Navy projects are not constructed on contaminated sites. If contamination is discovered during the planning stages of a project or during construction, careful project controls must be in place to ensure proper investigation and clean-up procedures are followed (NOLF SNI 2003).

Although there are no active IRP sites, there are various petroleum products and hazardous materials that are currently used to support aircraft and vehicle maintenance that are performed on the Island.

Jet fuel (JP-5) and unleaded gasoline are the petroleum products that are stored in bulk at SNI (NOLF SNI 2006a). About 680,000 gallons (2.6 million liters) of jet fuel are shipped to the island by tanker barge every year (NAWCWD 2002). Unleaded gasoline is also shipped for use by ground vehicles in 15,000-gallon (56,781-liter) tanker trucks as needed (S. Schwartz, *pers. comm.*, 2010).

Propane (average 1,000 gallons [3,785 liters] or 1,300 pounds [590 kg]) and liquid oxygen (minimal - as needed) are the hazardous substances that are stored in bulk at SNI (NOLF SNI 2006a). Only the minimum amount of a hazardous material is obtained for a task order to prevent disposing excess material as hazardous waste (NAWCWD 2002). An inventory of hazardous substances is maintained by each activity storing or using the particular hazardous substance at SNI (NOLF SNI 2006a). In addition, the Public Works Environmental Division maintains an inventory of hazardous substances used at SNI. The inventory is updated annually and provided to the County of Ventura Department of Environmental Health for areas that could be affected by a release (NOLF SNI 2006a). None of the substances are considered to be Extremely Hazardous Substances. Site-specific spill response plans have been developed for each storage location that would require the highest levels of personnel protection in the event of a release (NOLF SNI 2006a).

Specific Concerns

- Contaminated sediment can also lead to bioaccumulation and biomagnification of sediment contaminants in organisms up the food chain. Bioaccumulation is the process in which biological uptake and retention of contaminants in the tissues of an organism results from feeding, contact with the sediments and overlying water, or some combination of these. In this process, concentrations of many contaminants can biomagnify in body tissue concentrations as they move up through the food web from small invertebrates to fishes, birds, and even to humans.

- The effects of bioaccumulation on migratory birds is a concern, including for listed species like the brown pelican and western snowy plover. Fish and wildlife can be affected by direct mortality, or at lower contamination levels by sublethal effects on reproduction and survivability of young.
- Certain sportfish species are known to accumulate PCBs and mercury at levels that could pose health risks for consumers.

Current Management

Cleanup or remediation of polluted sediment is regulated by several state and federal statutes. The primary laws that apply, or may apply in some instances, are summarized in Appendix B. The most important of these is the Porter-Cologne Water Quality Control Act, which forms part of the California Water Code.

Similarly, several different federal, state, and local governmental or regulatory agencies have official responsibility for issues involving contaminated sediments, as shown in Table 5-3. The lead agencies are the RWQCB, EPA, and USACE. The Navy has major roles in the process.

Table 5-3. Federal and State statutes affecting management of contaminated sediment.

Federal Statutes	State Statutes
Clean Water Act	California Water Code, Division 7
Rivers and Harbors Act of 1899	California Health and Safety Code
Marine Protection, Research, and Sanctuaries Act	California Fish and Game Code
National Environmental Policy Act	California Environmental Quality Act
Fish and Wildlife Act	California Food and Agricultural Code
National Historic Preservation Act	California Harbor and Navigation Code
Endangered Species Act	California Coastal Zone Management Act

The Navy’s policy on sediment cleanup where several responsible parties are involved is described in a statement from the CNO to the Commander, NAVFAC (Navy/Marine Corps Installation Restoration Policy on Sediment Investigations and Response Actions [08 February 2002]). The policy specifies that the source must be identified and controlled before cleanup, the cleanup must be risk-based and have site-specific cleanup goals, and the monitoring criteria for any monitoring plan must be established before the first sample is collected. All sediment investigations and response actions must be directly linked to Navy contaminated releases. Directly linked means that the sediment contamination is scientifically connected to a Navy Installation Restoration site. This Policy requires that:

1. All sources shall be identified to determine if the Navy is solely responsible for the contamination. Source identification is very important in determining the Navy’s cleanup responsibility and if a site will be recontaminated after cleanup is complete. The extent of the Navy responsibility shall be determined. Therefore, the project team will generate a Watershed Contaminated Source Document (not a watershed investigation) if there are potentially other non-Navy sources contributing to the contamination of the sediment. All sources of Navy and non-Navy contamination at the site should be identified.
2. All investigations shall primarily be linked to a specific Navy CERCLA/RCRA site. If it is established that only Navy activities contribute sources to a water body then investigating that water body using a watershed approach may be beneficial and cost effective. Investigating (collecting and analyzing samples) entire watersheds that contain non-Navy sources is not an appropriate use of cleanup funds. Any proposed broad watershed investigations with non-Navy sources and potential cost sharing with non- Navy entities must be approved by the CNO (N45) Office.

3. All sediment investigations and response actions shall be consistent with Navy polices on risk assessment and background chemical levels.
4. Sediment cleanup goals shall be developed based on site-specific information and shall be risk-based. If unacceptable risk to human health and/or the environment is identified, risk-based sediment cleanup goals shall be developed using site-specific information. The cleanup goal must be risk-based and achievable. Ecological screening values must not be used as cleanup goals nor shall cleanup values below background chemical levels be used. Development of cleanup goals should include, but not be limited to, land use and bioavailability.
5. The Navy shall not clean up contamination from a non- Navy source where the Navy has not contributed to the risk in sediments. The Navy will not clean up a site before the source is contained. Any potential re-contamination by non-Navy sources shall be documented. Only sediment sites with known contamination from Navy sources that demonstrate unacceptable risk will be remediated. All Navy sources shall be contained before sediment response actions are initiated. The information provided in these reports, documents that the Navy has cleaned up its responsibility.
6. A monitoring plan with exit strategies shall be developed before collecting the first monitoring sample.

As the lead regulatory agency, the LARWQCB fulfills its two primary functions in dealing with contaminated sediment issues:

- To ensure reasonable protection of beneficial uses; and
- To ensure the prevention of nuisance conditions resulting from excessive discharges of waste.

The SWRCB adopted a Statewide Consolidated Toxic Hot Spot Cleanup Plan on 18 June 1999. The Regional Board has the authority to take enforcement action against those who violate its waste discharge requirements or discharge prohibitions as they apply to sediment contamination. The three primary enforcement remedies available to the Board are: cease and desist orders; cleanup and abatement orders; and administrative civil liability monetary penalties.

The problems associated with remediation of contaminated sediment are obviously complex and most remediation methods themselves are costly. The following management objective and strategies are recommended to increase the efficiency of the remediation process.

Assessment of Current Management

The problems associated with remediation of contaminated sediment are obviously complex and most remediation methods themselves are costly. The following management objective and strategies are recommended to increase the efficiency of the remediation process.

Management Strategy

Objective: Avoid and minimize impacts from contaminated sediment to recreational and commercial water contact users.

- I. Collect and distribute data on sediment contamination.
 - A. Continue to participate in the Southern California Coastal Water Research Project's Bight sampling program.
 - B. The Navy should participate in RWQCB sediment workshops to discuss the means of determining clean levels or targets for sites.
 - C. The Navy should continue to update source control programs.
 - D. The Navy should update point-source pollution prevention plans for facilities.
- II. Minimize risks to recreational and commercial water contact users.

- A. Characterize bacteriological water quality at selected locations around SNI.
 1. Monitor indicator bacteria (total and fecal coliform) to determine compliance with state recreational water standards or other relevant criteria.
 2. Monitor and evaluate temporal trends in indicator bacteria at selected locations.
 - B. Minimize the exposure of recreational and commercial users to pathogens.
 - C. Design and implement management practices to prevent the introduction of pathogens to SNI waters.
- III. Minimize risks to the SNI's wildlife species.
- A. Conduct autopsies within 24 to 48 hours on birds found dead in the SNI area.
- IV. Support the protection of the public from health risks associated with consuming seafood harvested in SNI's nearshore waters.
- A. Support monitoring trends in contaminants determined to be present in seafood organisms at levels that may pose significant risks to human consumers.

5.11 Oil Spill or Hazardous Substance Prevention and Cleanup

Specific Concerns

- Marine terminal (fuel barge) operations at SNI include the routine transfer of between 200,000 and 250,000 gallons (760,000 and 950,000 liters) of jet fuel (JP-5) every fuel delivery. JP-5 jet fuel represents the largest quantity of hazardous materials stored at SNI and the associated fuel barge operations represent the highest potential for a release of a hazardous substance at SNI.
- Cumulative effects of small, medium, and large oil spills from boats, personal watercraft, and ships can contaminate SNI waters and affect natural resources.
- Coordinated planning for oil spill cleanup activities should be integrated with conservation priorities of this INRMP.
- The collection and maintenance of ecological information required by OPNAVINST 5090.1D and OPNAV M-5090.1 (Chapter 22) are essential to pre-incident planning on behalf of the Navy's Regional Environmental Coordinator.
- There is a need to incorporate planning for Natural Resources Damage Assessment (NRDA) under both federal and state oil spill prevention regulation, as well as to establish a quantitative baseline to support natural resources management decisions, habitat mitigation and enhancement planning, and sustainability planning.
- Oil spills most notably affects marine birds and marine mammals, but also exerts damaging effects on plankton and other organisms either directly or indirectly through habitat damage. The size of an oil spill doesn't necessarily correlate with the amount of damage it can do. Even small spills can have big consequences for birds if the oil contaminates an area where large numbers of seabirds are rafting or foraging (Bunn *et al.* 2008).

Background

Federal Regulatory Framework

The federal Water Pollution Control Act of 1972 (33 USC 1251, *et seq.*), as amended by the CWA of 1977, authorizes the President, in the case of an oil or hazardous substance release, to take any action necessary to mitigate damage to the public health and welfare; including, but not limited to fish, shellfish, wildlife, public and private property, shorelines and beaches. Natural Resource

Trustees are authorized to recover damages for injury to, destruction of or loss of natural resources resulting from a discharge or the substantial threat of discharge, of oil into navigable waters.

The CWA prohibits spills, leaks or other discharges of pollutants into waters of the U.S. in quantities that may be harmful, which includes discharges of pollutants that: (1) violate applicable water quality standards; (2) cause a film or sheen upon or discoloration of the surface of the water or adjoining shorelines; or (3) cause sludge or emulsion to be deposited beneath the surface of the water or upon adjoining shorelines.

The Oil Pollution Prevention Act of 1990 amended the CWA to expand oil spill prevention activities, improve preparedness and response capabilities, and ensure that companies are responsible for damages from spills. The USCG is the lead agency for oil spill prevention and response, and is authorized to direct state and local agencies in controlling pollution in bays and coastal waters.

Hazardous substances other than oil are addressed by the CERCLA (42 USC 9601, *et seq.*), which authorizes Natural Resource Trustees to recover damages for injury to, destruction of or loss of natural resources resulting from the release of a hazardous substance.

NOAA is assigned responsibility for NRDA from spills, and the Navy has adopted NOAA procedures for damage assessment (15 CFR 990). Similarly, the U.S. Department of Interior is in charge of damage assessment for hazardous substance spills under EO 12580. The baseline condition of the natural resources and services that would have existed had the oil or hazardous substance release not occurred is estimated using historical data, reference data, control data or data on incremental changes, alone or in combination, as appropriate. Navy guidance (OPNAVINST 5090.1D and OPNAV M-5090.1) suggests that this information may be obtained from INRMPS, NEPA Documents, or special studies.

NRDA and Ephemeral Data Collection Plan

Department of Defense guidance (DoDINST 4715.03) states that "All DoD Components shall develop and promulgate criteria and procedures for assessing natural resource damage claims in the event natural resources under DoD control are damaged [injured] by oil or a hazardous substance released by another party." Navy requirements (OPNAVINST 5090.1D and OPNAV M-5090.1), however, go beyond DoDINST 4715.03 and apply to natural resource injury occasioned by oil or hazardous substance releases from both DoD and non-DoD sources.

Where an oil spill, regardless of source or physical location, injures or threatens to injure natural resources within Navy management or control, NOAA NRDA procedures serve to guide Navy activities in the mitigation, assessment and collection of natural resource damages occasioned by the spill. In the case of other hazardous substance releases, the U.S. Department of Interior has established other types of natural resource damage assessment regulations. One method calculates resource damages called a Resource Equivalency Analysis (REA), also known as Habitat Equivalency Analysis, is the most common method used in NRDA cases nationwide. It has been endorsed by the courts on two occasions. The injury is assessed in terms of degree (percent of baseline injured), duration (years until recovery), and size (number of acres, stream miles, birds, etc.). A trajectory estimating the recovery to baseline is also estimated. The injury may be described in terms of lost acre-years or stream mile-years or bird-years of lost ecological services. The benefits of a restoration project are quantified in similar terms: degree of benefit (e.g. percent services per unit area), duration of the project, and trajectory of the benefits over time. With this information, the size of the project is scaled until the benefit of the project is equal to the injury. The final step is to cost out the project. This cost becomes the measure of damages.

The baseline assessment compiled prior to a spill becomes essential to both pre-incident planning for response, as well as this post-incident assignment of damages. This baseline ecological information is required under OPNAVINST 5090.1D and OPNAV M-5090.1, Chapter 22, on behalf of the Navy Regional Environmental Coordinator. Baseline data specifically includes this INRMP.

NAVFAC Southwest has developed an Ephemeral Data Collection Plan in support of NRDA (Robilliard et al. 1997). Immediately during and after a spill, data will be collected in order to evaluate the injury. Examples include macro invertebrate surveys, water and sediment samples, and vegetation surveys. Following federal guidelines, this is often done cooperatively with the responsible party, as well as with fellow trustee agencies. The NAVFAC plan identifies specific locations, methodologies, and responsibilities for data collection.

State Regulatory Framework

The OSPR is responsible for protecting California's natural resources by preventing, preparing for, and responding to spills of oil and other deleterious materials, and through restoring and enhancing affected resources. The OSPR was formed after the Exxon Valdez oil spill in 1989, and the spill off of Huntington Beach by the American Trader in 1990. These events inspired the California Legislature to enact legislation in 1990 called the Lempert-Keene-Seastrand Oil Spill Prevention and Response Act. The Act also gave the State Lands Commission certain authority over marine terminals. The OSPR's responsibilities under the Act are:

- Development of contingency plans for the protection of fish and wildlife
- Establishment of rescue and rehabilitation facilities
- Establishment and funding of a network of rescue and rehabilitation facilities, known as the Oiled Wildlife Care Network
- Assessment of injuries to natural resources from a spill
- Development of restoration plans to compensate for adversely affected wildlife resources and habitats.

Both the federal and state statutes (Oil Pollution Prevention Act 1990 and Senate Bill 2040) were enacted in consequence of the catastrophic oil spills of 1989, and both required contingency planning for both state and federal governments. The USCG and CDFW-OSPR agreed to joint preparation of contingency plans through co-chairing the three Port Area Committees for Contingency Planning: USCG Port Areas for San Francisco, Los Angeles/Long Beach, and San Diego.

The OSPR's Resource Assessment Program conducts NRDA of pollution events that result in significant injuries to wildlife and/or habitat. The goal of OSPR's NRDA program is to quantify the damages, to seek compensation from the responsible parties, and to both restore the injured resources and compensate the public for the lost interim ecological benefits and uses of these resources.

The OSPR have developed a California Wildlife Response Plan (CDFG and OSPR 2005) to augment the ACP. The California Wildlife Response Plan details the Wildlife Operations Branch purposes, goals, objectives, responsibilities, and structure. The Wildlife Operations Branch is in the Operations Section of the Incident Command System for oil spill response. The Wildlife Operations Branch structure needed in California and detailed in this plan is expanded beyond that described in the USCG Incident Management Handbook. The CDFW normally leads wildlife response during a spill in California.

The National Contingency Plan

The CWA and the Comprehensive Environmental Response, Compensation and Liability Act (CERCLA) of 1980, as amended, required that Federal agencies make plans for emergency response to spills of oil and hazardous substances for which they are responsible. To comply with these Acts, the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) has published Title 40 CFR Part 300, The National Oil and Hazardous Substances Pollution Contingency Plan, commonly referred to as the National Contingency Plan or NCP (NOLF SNI 2006a). The Final Rule for 40 CFR Part 300 was published on 15 August 1994 with an effective date of 17 October 1994.

Area Contingency Plan

The Oil Pollution Act of 1990 and EO 12777 require that *Area Spill Contingency Plans* be developed in accordance with the National Response Policy. The policy also requires that a pre-designated Federal On-Scene Coordinator (FOSC) be assigned to ensure effective and immediate removal of a discharge of oil or hazardous substances (NOLF SNI 2006a). The United States Coast Guard (USCG) designates FOSCs for the coastal zone of the U.S., and the EPA designates FOSCs for the inland zone. The Captain of the Port (COTP), Los Angeles-Long Beach, has been pre-designated to carry out the duties of the FOSC for the coastal areas of Southern California between San Louis Obispo and Orange County. San Nicolas Island operates within the guidelines of the USCG, EPA, and the State of California under the Los Angeles/Long Beach ACP published in January 2000 (NOLF SNI 2006a).

Spill Prevention Control and Countermeasure Plan

The EPA's Oil Pollution Prevention Regulations address non-transportation related facilities. Title 40 CFR Part 112 requires facilities to have a fully prepared and implemented SPCC Plan. These plans are to establish spill prevention procedures, methods, and equipment requirements for non-transportation related facilities with: (1) total aboveground, non-buried, oil storage capacity greater than 1,320 gallons (5,000 liters), including only those containers of oil 55 gallons (208 liters) or greater; or (2) underground, buried, oil storage capacity greater than 42,000 gallons (160,000 liters) (NOLF SNI 2006a). Facilities meeting these criteria and because of their location, that could reasonably be expected to discharge oil into navigable waters of the United States or adjoining shorelines, require SPCC plans (NOLF SNI 2006a). Based on these criteria and operations, SNI must have a SPCC Plan.

Federal Facility Response Plans

In response to the Oil Pollution Act of 1990, the EPA issued revised rules in 40 CFR Part 112, Oil Pollution Prevention and Response; Non-Transportation-Related Facilities. The Final Rules require a Facility Response Plan be prepared and submitted to the EPA Regional Administrator for any non-transportation-related facility that could reasonably be expected to cause substantial harm to the environment should a spill occur (NOLF SNI 2006a). The Facility Response Plan requirements in the EPA Final Rules apply to SNI because it transfers oil over water and has an oil storage capacity greater than 42,000 gallons (160,000 liters) and a discharge could be expected to cause substantial harm to fish and wildlife and sensitive environments on or around the facility (NOLF SNI 2006a). SNI is also classified as a Marine Transportation-Related (MTR) facility because it is capable of transferring oil to or from a vessel with a capacity of 250 barrels or more and it could be expected to cause significant and substantial harm to the environment by discharging oil into or on the navigable waters, adjoining shorelines, or exclusive economic zone of the United States (NOLF SNI 2006a). Therefore, the Final Rule issued by the USCG rules in 33 CFR Part 154, Facilities Transferring Oil or Hazardous Material in Bulk, applies to SNI and a response plan must be prepared to meet these requirements (NOLF SNI 2006a).

State of California Oil Spill Contingency Plan

Title 14 of the California Code of Regulations gave the Office of Oil Spill Prevention and Response (OSPR) authority to require marine facilities to submit oil spill contingency plans. San Nicolas Island must prepare and submit a contingency plan consistent with these requirements. The SNI ICP has been prepared to include requirements of the State of California and Title 14 CCR, Section 817 and Title 2 CCR, Division 3, Chapter 1, Article 5 regulations concerning Oil Spill Contingency Plans and Marine Facility Operations Manuals (NOLF SNI 2006a). The SNI Emergency Response Action Plan, also known as The Red Plan, provides the information for and serves as a Response Manual (NOLF SNI 2006b). Additional specific response information and procedures can be found in the various Annexes of the SNI Oil and Hazardous Substance Integrated Contingency Plan. In addition, Title 2 CCR, Division 3, Chapter 1, Article 5 requires an Operations Manual for the mooring where fuel is transferred at SNI. The Operations and Maintenance Manual, Final Revision 2, for Naval Base Ventura County was prepared to address this planning requirement (NOLF SNI 2006a). The Operations and Maintenance Manual, Final

Revision 2, for NVBC was submitted to the US Coast Guard and State of California and approved on 26 July 2005.

U.S. Navy Instructions

Government facilities must ensure compliance with the Oil Pollution Act of 1990 and Federal regulations in response to EO 12088 (compliance with applicable pollution control standards, 1978) and 12856 (planning, Emergency Planning and Community Right-to-Know Act [EPCRA], and pollution prevention requirements, 1991). San Nicolas Island is owned and operated by the Navy. In accordance with the OPNAVINST 5090.1D and OPNAV M-5090.1 (*Environmental Readiness Program and Manual*), Naval facilities will pursue the protection and enhancement of the quality of the environment by adhering to all applicable regulatory requirements (NOLF SNI 2006a). Facility Response Plans and SPCC Plans will be properly developed, submitted, and maintained by each installation required to do so. Any State requirements will also be met in facility response planning. San Nicolas Island is also expected to address Spill Contingency Planning as part of the Regional Environmental Coordinators Disaster Preparedness Plan for their geographical areas of responsibility (NOLF SNI 2006a). San Nicolas Island complies with the requirements in these Instructions.

Additional Emergency Response Planning

Facilities that handle or store hazardous substances, the release of which could endanger health and human safety and adversely impact the environment, must comply with additional Federal regulations that govern emergency planning, notification, and response. These requirements are part of the Resource Conservation and Recovery Act (RCRA), CERCLA, and EPCRA regulations contained in 40 CFR Part 264, 40 CFR Part 302, and 40 CFR Part 355, respectively. The Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) also has regulations governing emergency response and planning. Applicable requirements contained in 29 CFR Part 1910 are addressed in the SNI Oil and Hazardous Substance ICP (NOLF SNI 2006a).

Integrated Contingency Plan

On 05 June 1996, the National Response Team issued a Federal Register Notice on ICP Guidance (NOLF SNI 2006a). It intended to provide a mechanism for consolidating multiple plans that facilities prepare to comply with various regulations into one functional emergency response plan or ICP. The SNI Oil and Hazardous Substance ICP was prepared to meet all requirements as an ICP, as defined by the National Response Team (NOLF SNI 2006a). Specifically, the NOLF SNI ICP for Oil and Hazardous Substance Spill Prevention and Response is an operational, single-source document designed to meet the combined regulatory requirements for an EPA Facility Response Plan, and EPA SPCC Plan, a USCG Response Plan for Oil Facilities (Marine Transportation-Related Facility Response Plan), and a State of California OSPR Oil Spill Contingency Plan. The NOLF SNI ICP for Oil and Hazardous Substance Spill Prevention and Response also addresses the emergency planning, notification, and response actions directed by the RCRA, CERCLA, EPCRA, and OSHA. The NOLF SNI ICP for Oil and Hazardous Substance Spill Prevention and Response is also consistent with the NCP and the Los Angeles/Long Beach ACP.

In the event of an oil or a hazardous substance spill at SNI, the Emergency Response Action Plan, also known as the “The Red Plan,” serves as the initial plan to get the right response actions on track at the earliest possible time. The NOLF SNI ICP for Oil and Hazardous Substance Spill Prevention and Response reinforces “The Red Plan” and provides in-depth information on response, notification, organization, duties, containment, cleanup, and remediation procedures (NOLF SNI 2006a). The organizations to be involved in a spill response at SNI are identified in Figure 2-1.

“The Red Plan” is used in the early stages of a spill, and incident responders are expected to transition to the ICP for Oil and Hazardous Substance Spill Prevention and Response after appropriate notifications and response actions are underway.

Natural Resource program staff at SNI has coordinated with USCG and their partners in meetings and has provided geographic information system (GIS) layers of SNI's sensitive coastal areas during the revision of the *Los Angeles/Long Beach Area Contingency Plan* (M. Ruane, *pers. comm.*, 2010). Natural Resource Program staff will continue to provide current and updated information for inclusion into the *Los Angeles/Long Beach Area Contingency Plan*.

Current Management

San Nicolas Island's storage and transfer operations have the potential for a discharge of oil onto land or into navigable waters that could cause substantial harm to the environment, including injury to fish and wildlife and sensitive areas. Operational efficiency and safety of personnel and equipment, as well as Federal, State, and Navy regulations require that a plan exist to effectively respond to oil and hazardous substance spills. Oil and hazardous substance spill prevention and response planning requirements include the NCP, ACP, SPCC Plan, Federal Facility Response Plans, State of California Oil Spill Contingency Plan, Navy Instructions, Additional Emergency Response Planning, and an ICP.

Assessment of Current Management

Natural Resource program staff at SNI has coordinated with the USCG and their partners in meetings and has provided GIS layers of SNI's sensitive coastal areas during the revision of the Los Angeles/Long Beach ACP (M. Ruane, *pers. comm.*, 2010). Natural Resource Program staff will continue to provide current and updated information for inclusion into the Los Angeles/Long Beach ACP.

Recent SNI surveys could also be integrated into NRDA data collection study design, in order to improve the quantification of baseline status of natural resources in the event of a spill, and manage any Navy liabilities in such as case.

Management Strategy

Objective: Prevent spills of oil and other hazardous substances, and ensure the effectiveness of prevention and response planning.

- I. Continue to implement the SNI ICP for Oil and Hazardous Substance Spill Prevention and Response.
- II. Continually enhance oil and hazardous substances spill response capabilities through equipment procurement, training, and participation in drills and area exercises, and continue active membership in the Safety and Area Contingency Planning Committee.
 - A. Continue to test the local ACP with annual table-top exercises and periodic drills.
 - B. Continue spill response, regardless of its source, in partnership with the USCG in accordance with the existing MOU between the USCG and Navy.
- III. Continue to integrate the protection priorities of this INRMP into contingency spill response and NRDA planning.
 - A. Continue to update GIS layers of natural resources to support preparedness planning.
 - B. Continue to integrate baseline ecological surveys into preparedness planning.
 - C. Integrate invasive exotic species response planning with oil spill contingency plans.

5.12 Landscaping and Grounds Maintenance

Specific Concerns

- The Grounds Maintenance Contract needs to be evaluated for consistency with recent EOs or Navy policy.
- Recommendations of the Base Exterior Architecture Plan should be evaluated for consistency with respect to landscaping.
- Must meet the requirements in the Biosecurity Plan to ensure no new species are purposefully or accidentally introduced.

Current Management

Maintenance of semi-developed and developed grounds is accomplished at SNI with technical assistance from staff in NBVC Environmental Division. Landscaping and groundskeeping work occurs primarily within the Community Support area at SNI. It is anticipated that future native plant landscaping will be developed to accompany facility renovations and improvement around the Community Support Area. Future landscaping at SNI will follow the guidelines set forth in the "San Nicolas Island Landscaping Plant List" (see Appendix F).

SNI also maintains a plant nursery on island, this nursery provides native plants for habitat restoration project on island. Plants are used to restore or enhance habitat for listed species, sensitive plants, erosion control, and a variety of other needs. Plants are grown from seeds collected on SNI. The SNI plant nursery, if funded by the project proponent, can now provide a growing area and staff to care for plants. Funding is required to grow plants for base operational projects (such as erosion control or post-construction planting requirements).

The purpose of the San Nicolas Island Landscaping Plant List (Appendix F) is to provide a clear set of approved plants that are not known to be invasive to the island. All plant selections (outdoor landscape or indoor plants) for SNI must be approved by appropriate staff in NBVC ED. Specifically, landscape designs and plant lists shall be reviewed and approved by the Installation Natural Resource Specialist and the NAVFAC Landscape Architect in the planning stages of project design.

NBVC supports the goals of EO 13148 (21 April 2000) *Greening the Government Through Leadership in Environmental Management* and promotes the President's 26 April 1994 *Memorandum on Environmentally Beneficial Landscaping*. It is Navy policy to:

1. Use regionally native plants for landscaping.
2. Design, use and promote construction practices that minimize adverse effects on natural habitat.
3. Prevent pollution by reducing fertilizer and pesticide use, integrated pest management practices, recycling green waste (composting) and minimizing runoff.
4. Implement water-efficient practices, use efficient irrigation systems and recycled water, and use landscaping to conserve energy.
5. Create demonstration projects to promote awareness of environmental and economic benefits of these practices.

Water conservation is emphasized in landscaping and grounds maintenance at SNI through the use of xeriscaping practices. For example, watering is not included as part of landscaping and grounds maintenance efforts (S. Schwartz, *pers. comm.*, 2009). Xeriscaping, an important aspect of the water conservation program, is based on the use of native or drought-resistant plants and efficient irrigation practices that require less water. Principals of xeriscaping include the following:

- Using drought tolerant species of plants that require a minimum of maintenance;
- Using mulch as a ground cover to preclude weed growth and enhance water retention;
- Using plastic or rubber-based products to prevent the growth of undesirable species;
- Using species that accomplish a goal, such as using ground cover to prevent blowing dust and soil erosion;
- Watering using automatically controlled cycles during low evaporation periods; and
- Using drip irrigation whenever possible.

Xeriscaping can be both functional and aesthetic and will continue to be used to the extent possible at SNI.

Assessment of Current Management

Continued use of the San Nicolas Island Landscaping Plant List and adherence to the principles of xeriscaping are necessary and sufficient to maintain compliance with EOs and Navy policy. With the recent creation of the SNI plant nursery, plants can now be easily grown on island with appropriate funding.

Intact native ecosystems at SNI are easier to manage for long-term stability with the use of native plants for landscaping, as exotic non-native species have the potential to escape into natural areas. Native plants, especially successional species, are considered as a landscaping choice. Native plants provide extra resources for native pollinators and birds thus helping to buffer the edge effect on neighboring intact ecosystems. Land developments and road maintenance provide opportunities for plant salvage as ecologically appropriate and low cost landscaping resources.

It is vital that coordination with the Installation Natural Resource Specialist and the NAVFAC Landscape Architect occur early in the planning process to determine site-specific needs and constraints. Please note that other species may be used for landscaping but must be approved by Installation Natural Resource Specialist and the NAVFAC Landscape Architect prior to specifying on plans or scopes of work. These species must be screened through regional invasive plant lists. Only seed may be brought to the island at this time, no plants in soils. Contact Installation Natural Resource Specialist with any questions or requests for plants not on the approved San Nicolas Island Landscaping Plant List. This San Nicolas Island Landscaping Plant List is updated periodically. Prior to initiating a project, please obtain the most recent list from the Installation Natural Resource Specialist.

Management Strategy

Objective: Sustainably improve the visual and aesthetic environment for civilian and military personnel living, working, or visiting SNI, while maintaining the integrity and character of cultural resources.

- I. Comply with cultural and environmental laws, EOs, and Navy policies by considering environmental factors and their potential effects on cultural resources in landscape planning.
 - A. Continue to update the NBVC San Nicolas Island Landscaping Plant List.
 - B. Continue to operate and maintain the SNI plant nursery.
 - C. Consult with the Natural Resource Specialist for questions, comments, or concerns regarding landscaping before a project is submitted.
 - D. Develop an SNI Instruction that outlines an appropriate landscaping and grounds maintenance program consistent with EO 13123 and EO 13112.
 - E. Continue to update the Vegetation Management Plan every five years.

- F. Ensure mowing and other groundskeeping practices are consistent with USFWS BOs, terms of USACE permits, mitigation obligations agreed to in EISs, other legal agreements, IPMPs and natural resource management plans.
 - 1. Modify the Ground Maintenance Contract for the groundskeeping contract to comply with this INRMP.
 - 2. Ensure that these requirements are communicated to groundskeeping staff.
 - 3. Make sure Grounds Maintenance plans are consistent with the IPMP.
 - 3. Prohibit rodenticide use outdoors.
 - G. Consult with NBVC Cultural Resources Program Manager before starting any landscaping project to make sure no cultural resources will be negatively affected.
- II. Follow guidelines set forth in the SSI for planting site appropriate plants in a low impact and sustainable way.
- A. Use landscaping design to benefit the human working environment by moderating environmental influences (e.g. solar heat gain, glare, dust, and wind), conserving energy, protecting water quality, preventing soil erosion, reducing glare, buffering noise, improving visual aesthetics, providing wildlife habitat, and unifying exterior spaces.
 - B. New lawns are discouraged except where functionally essential. Lawns require frequent watering and should be restricted to: formal areas such as for ceremonies, family housing, recreation fields, and children's playgrounds. Replacing turf with native and drought tolerant plants in combination with rocks or gravel over bare areas will save large amounts of water. Turf replacement can also be done in a very aesthetically pleasing manner and can equal turf in terms of dust control.
 - C. Implement new technology to reduce water usage whenever possible.
 - D. Utilize xeriscaping to the maximum extent possible.
- III. Consider landscaped areas and storm water systems as continuous with the wetland system and ensure compatibility with natural resource objectives.
- IV. Use island native plants whenever possible. If native plants are not available or do not suit the project objective, the CNRSW Natural Resources Office Botanist may grant permission for the use of non-native plants with other beneficial attributes such as drought-tolerance, fire resistance or other special purpose species. Remove and eliminate the use of invasive exotic plants in landscaping. Favor natives over exotics using good maintenance practices.
- A. All SNI contracts related to grounds maintenance should include language that promotes implementation of the INRMP.
 - B. All plants should be from native seed or plant material collected on SNI.
 - C. Eliminate the use of invasive exotic plants in landscaping.
 - D. Incorporate historically appropriate plants in areas with existing architecture.
 - 1. Provide a coordinated landscape color scheme for the housing and administration areas which will enhance the existing architecture.
 - E. Provide weed control.
 - 1. Use mulches to reduce evapotranspiration and control weeds.
 - 2. Apply herbicides on an as-needed basis only.
 - F. An approved mowing schedule/map should be incorporated into this Instruction, as well as the groundskeeping contract.

- V. Minimize the use of pesticides and herbicides in landscape management by following the NBVC IPMP. Continue to develop an Integrated Pest Management approach to dealing with pest problems at SNI.
 - A. Be consistent with existing NAVFACINSTs on Integrated Pest Management guidance (OPNAVINST 6250.4B 1998).
 - B. Prohibit rodenticide use outdoors. Only allow use within buildings when mice are creating a health risk.
- VI. Perform regular maintenance of any irrigation system and upgrade when appropriate.
 - A. Check the irrigation system often and repair leaks, broken sprinklers and clogged emitters.
 - B. Upgrade manual systems and hand watering to automatic "smart" systems.
- VII. Unless there is an identified conflict with the military mission, avoid groundskeeping practices that may affect sensitive species.
 - A. Comply with the MBTA for migratory and resident birds during tree trimming, pruning, or removal.
 - B. Check timing and location of mowing in natural areas to avoid impacts to sensitive species.
- VIII. Augment goals of force protection by incorporating landscaping into physical barriers surrounding buildings and visual protection barriers between the SNI and public waters or between high security areas.
 - A. Use landscape planters to create a physical barrier between vehicles and structures at the specified distance as required under new security restrictions following the September 11, 2001 terrorist attack.
 - B. Use trees and shrubs to block all undesirable views, noise, and lights and provide privacy.
- IX. Prioritize landscape improvement projects while using the following guidelines for implementation.
 - A. Ensure that all new projects and contracts follow the guidelines and any implementation Instructions.
 - B. Give high priority to areas that serve as important gathering places or highly used areas.
 - C. Implement projects that will reduce water usage and help meet water conservation goals.
 - D. Plant a demonstration conservation garden of regionally native plants for education of personnel.

5.13 Outdoor Recreation

Specific Concerns

- There are limited outdoor recreational opportunities at SNI that must be compatible with military safety and security needs.

Current Management

The Sikes Act requires each military service to provide outdoor recreation and interpretive opportunities to the public where and when it is compatible with military safety and security needs. DoD installations are to provide for sustained public access and use of natural resources

for educational or recreational purposes when such access is compatible with mission activities, and with other considerations such as security, safety, or resources sensitivity. Recreational access at NBVC SNI complies with the requirements associated with the provisions of the Americans with Disabilities Act of 1990, as amended, and the Disabled Sportsman Access Act of 1998, as amended. Recreation-related projects that result in ground disturbance are managed through the SA/PRB (NBVCINST 11010.1B) to avoid and minimize potential impacts.

Implementation of the outdoor recreation management program is the responsibility of the Commanding Officer of NBVC SNI. The Natural Resources Manager oversees the outdoor (natural resource) recreation program and ensures that, where applicable, programs are developed in coordination with appropriate state and federal agencies. The Natural Resources Manager also coordinates with and informs MWR of projects and operations related to outdoor OPNAVINST 5090.1D and OPNAV M-5090.1, states that military lands and waters shall be made available to the public for recreational usage to the extent it is appropriate and consistent with the military mission, and that the natural resources will support such usage. Since SNI is the site of weapons testing and sensitive equipment, public access is prohibited in the interest of security and safety. This precludes recreational use of the island by the general public.

Outdoor recreational opportunities are available to island personnel, and are regulated by the installation for the protection of cultural and natural resources. Land-based recreational activities are not allowed on the south side of the island. This INRMP does not regulate offshore recreational activities, other Navy requirement such as safety and security do.

Outdoor recreational activities at SNI include hiking, biking, fishing, wildlife observation, diving, surfing, kayaking, and boating. Interested individuals periodically suggest the potential for chukar hunting on the island. Safety, security, cultural resource protection, and natural resource management concerns make hunting on the island infeasible. Bird hunting programs have a significant potential to negatively impact the Island fox population. Introduction of a canine disease via hunting dogs could jeopardize the existence of the population, and hunting would result in reduction of an important prey resource of the fox.

The two categories of outdoor recreation opportunities recognized for Island personnel are concentrated area activities and dispersed area activities.

Concentrated Outdoor Recreation Areas and Activities - Cissy Cove, Corral Harbor, and Daytona Beach are popular sites for outdoor recreational pursuits (NAVFAC SW 2010a). Personal watercraft to be used for recreational fishing are launched from Cissy Cove. Corral Harbor is favored for snorkeling and diving. Daytona Beach is the popular fishing spot. Surfing, boat use, and recreational diving are all popular activities on the Island. All of these activities have been restricted to specific areas on the Island to preserve natural and cultural resources and ecologically sensitive areas (NAVFAC SW 2010a).

Dispersed Outdoor Recreation and Activities - Fishing is probably the most popular dispersed recreational activity on SNI. The island is surrounded by lush kelp forests, exhibits an upwelling of nutrient, and has numerous fishing spots along the shoreline. Many of the better areas to fish are identified by fishing signs (NAVFAC SW 2010a). Some of the more common species include cabezon, California sheephead, rock bass, white bass, and calico bass. Fishermen must have a California ocean-fishing license to fish on SNI and abide by bag and size limits. The CDFW is responsible for the enforcement of fishing regulations on the Island, although among the small SNI community, peer pressure to abide by the rules and regulations appears to foster self-regulation of fishing laws (NAVFAC SW 2010a). Fishermen must also abide by SNI area closures due to environmental laws protecting certain wildlife and respect cultural resources areas, such as Native American middens located near coastal areas. Environmental personnel post flyers regarding fishing on SNI, including specific information on different species of fish and catch limits, in obvious locations (NAVFAC SW 2010a).

Assessment of Current Management

Continued use of signs to raise awareness of marine mammal haul out locations is needed. Various signs have been posted to protect marine mammal haulout and breeding sites. Interpretive brochures are available at the airfield. Natural resources staff routinely provide briefs to Navy personnel and contractors regarding precautions around sensitive wildlife. The planned development of a future SNI Outdoor Recreation Plan will address recreational access for Navy staff and island personnel that ensure that any planned recreational access is compliant with the requirements associated with the provisions of the American with Disabilities Act of 1990 as amended and the Disabled Sportsman Access Act as amended.

Management Strategy

Objective: Enhance quality of life for military personnel by promoting compatible, sustainable outdoor recreation opportunities.

- I. Continue to limit public access and outdoor recreation for reasons that include general security and liability issues, the presence of federally endangered and threatened species, and fire safety. Limit recreational access to sensitive intertidal environments when those activities may impact sensitive resources.
- II. Develop an updated outdoor recreation plan that includes military personnel components where possible. Seek opportunities for natural resources-based outdoor recreation to improve quality of life for Navy personnel and improve knowledge of the natural world and the Navy's stewardship of natural resources.
 - A. Identify major themes from Navy point of view. Identify and evaluate suitable outdoor recreation opportunities for installation personnel in developed areas.
 - E. The outdoor recreation plan should include wording for a Navy Instruction on outdoor recreation that includes maps of where outdoor recreation is allowed and not allowed, and whether it is permitted for military personnel, dependents, DoD civilians, contractors, and approved guests.
 - F. Cooperative agreements with NPS, in conjunction with the INRMP, are the mechanism for a program of planning, development, maintenance, and coordination of outdoor recreation on Navy lands.
- III. Identify and evaluate suitable outdoor recreation opportunities for installation personnel in undeveloped areas that do not contain or have the potential to impact sensitive species.
 - A. Seek strategies for compatible use and overall protection of outdoor recreation resources.
 - G. Provide interpretive material about native habitats, sensitive species, and areas to avoid because of the presence of sensitive resources.
 - H. When appropriate, develop brochures, on-site interpretive signage, and a field guide for wildlife viewing.
 - I. Continue to ban all hunting, for reasons of security.
 - J. Provide, where possible and compatible with the mission, development and enhancement of fishing, and other outdoor uses of natural resources for the disabled.
 - K. Off-road vehicle use for recreation is an incompatible activity at SNI, for reasons of security, safety, fire, and the presence of threatened and endangered species.
- IV. Maintain recreational opportunities on SNI consistent with the military mission.
 - A. Periodically review appropriateness of instituting new outdoor recreation activities.
 - L. Investigate development of designated hiking trails.

- M. Periodically review and update recreational policies to ensure compliance with environmental management regulations.
- N. Prepare and annually update maps of recommended and prohibited diving, surfing, kayaking and boating locations.

5.14 Environmental Education

Specific Concerns

- Selected environmental awareness brochures are distributed by housing and MWR staff, and for various reasons, may cease to occur because of the printing effort, time, and money to maintain copies for distribution.
- Staff turnover may impede communication about the natural resources of NBVC, environmental regulations, protocols for responding to trapped, injured, or unwelcome wildlife.
- Habitats and species may be harmed when people do not follow environmental rules and regulations.

Current Management

The Sikes Act requires each military service to support environmental education for personnel and for the public where and when it is compatible with military safety and security needs. Conservation awareness on NBVC is implemented by multiple basewide environmental programs. The conservation effort on site will continue to expand as this INRMP and subsequent natural resource management programs are undertaken to ensure efficient and thorough management of the natural resources on base. Specifically, conservation efforts at NBVC SNI address energy, water resources, recycling, pollution prevention, and public outreach and education. The following conservation programs are currently in place on NBVC SNI:

Indoctrination program for newly stationed military personnel, presenting an overview of the Environmental Program, from hazardous waste to wetlands and endangered species. Natural resource brochures are made available on sensitive and natural resources at SNI. New housing residents are given natural resources brochures and information on how to live with wildlife in the housing area. Signs are placed in appropriate places that indicate closure areas and provide environmental education. Through the EMS, contractors and federal employees are required to review a presentation on the natural resources. Brochures for NBVC SNI biosecurity are available at the SNI and SNI air terminals and provide information on the importance of not introducing invasive species to the island.

Assessment of Current Management

There is currently an effective environmental education program, with information on sensitive resources readily available to most personnel. Regular coordination must continue with MWR and the housing administrator to ensure environmental education continues to be distributed. The indoctrination program should continue to instruct personnel, civilian staff, and housing residents on the natural resources of NBVC. Topics covered should include protocols for responding to trapped or injured wildlife and birds nesting in base facilities. Applicable goals and directives of this INRMP should be communicated to new staff in indoctrination materials and through personnel training programs. Natural resources education information, including rules and regulations, should be posted in MWR facilities. Adequate signage should alert personnel to environmentally sensitive areas. General conservation awareness and education could be enhanced through projects such as a demonstration water conservation garden using native or low water usage plants, or a demonstration bioswale.

Management Strategy

Objective: Objective: Increase natural resources outreach to military and civilian staff and contractors.

- I. Continue to support and develop the indoctrination program for new staff.
- II. Identify opportunities on base for enhanced natural resource education and awareness of military and civilian staff and contractors.
 - A. Ensure that adequate signage is posted in environmentally sensitive areas, and closure areas.
 - B. Develop and post environmental educational materials and rules and regulations in community housing areas and MWR facilities.
 - C. Ensure all housing residents receive information on the natural resources of NBVC SNI, emphasizing the importance of following regulations.
 - D. Promote environmental awareness at all applicable large base functions.

5.15 Natural Resources Law Enforcement

DoD police have the authority of the Installation Commander and of the Sikes Act (16 U.S.C. 670a *et seq.*) to enforce all federal laws relating to the management of natural resources at NBVC, including the ESA, Clean Water Act, and MBTA. NBVC law enforcement activities are addressed in the Programmatic Biological Opinion (USFWS 2001b). NBVC Force Protection is responsible for enforcing beach closures designed to protect listed species. They are on continuous patrol, 24 hours per day.

NBVC is closed to the public because of security protocols for the military mission. The NBVC police patrol the base to prevent trespassers from entering SNI.

Specific Concerns

- Instances when NBVC Force Protection may not be aware of areas used by nesting birds or marine mammals, when they should coordinate access with NBVC ED to not disrupt and to minimize disturbance to listed species.
- Gaps in communication between NBVC ED and NBVC Force Protection, related to enforcement of closure areas or other areas requiring special protection.
- The Sikes Act, as amended, requires a Natural Resources Law Enforcement Program.
- There is currently no formal program to enforce federal laws relating to natural resources management at NBVC.

Current Management

Protection of natural resources at NBVC is currently provided through NBVC Force Protection in regards to enforcing closed areas. CDFW game wardens help enforce fishing and hunting regulations when they come aboard the installation. No Wildlife/Natural Resources Law Enforcement Program is currently in place at NBVC SNI. Navy police enforce closures to protect nesting areas for listed species. NBVC ED provides NBVC Force Protection maps of closure areas. Navy biologists work closely with NBVC Force Protection when trespassers are observed and access to nesting areas is required. Newly assigned NBVC staff are provided indoctrination education that contains information on environmental closures and sensitive species.

Assessment of Current Management

Natural resources are sufficiently protected under the current program. Force Protection is aware of all the closed areas and enforce the closures. Improvements may be made in communication of protocols in regards to responding in emergency situations in which sensitive areas must be accessed. Natural resource management activities (restoration, area closures, etc.) should be continually communicated to NBVC Force Protection, to ensure successful management and protection of resources.

Staff from the USFWS Division of Law Enforcement should train Navy police staff to enforce management guidelines and ensure compliance with the ESA and its regulations. Procedures for enforcing ESA regulations should be developed so that enforcement is consistent regardless of the personnel on duty. Additional training should be provided for new Navy police if no member of the force has completed the program presented by USFWS. Written materials should also be made available as obtained from the USFWS Division of Law Enforcement.

Management Strategy

Objective: Objective: Reduce unauthorized access, activities, or other disturbances that may cause adverse impacts to sensitive habitats or species.

- I. Ensure NBVC Force Protection is informed of special closures due to listed or sensitive species presence, nesting, or habitat restoration activities.
- II. Maintain regular communication between NBVC Force Protection and NBVC ED, to inform on sensitive area closures, areas that require regular patrol, and protocols for reporting trapped or injured wildlife and marine mammal strandings.
- III. Ensure closure areas are appropriately signed.

6.0 Implementation Strategy

6.1 General Considerations

A successfully implemented INRMP will:

- Ensure the sustainability of all habitats in NBVC SNI.
- Ensure no net loss of the capability of NBVC SNI lands to support the DoD mission.

The INRMP is considered implemented if the installation:

1. Actively requests, receives, and uses funds for all Level 4 projects and activities;
2. Ensures that sufficient numbers of professionally trained natural resources management staff are available to perform the tasks required by the INRMP.
3. Coordinates annually with all cooperating offices; and,
4. Documents specific INRMP action accomplishments undertaken each year.

Formal adoption of an INRMP by a Commanding Officer or Officer-In-Charge constitutes a commitment to seek funding and execute, subject to the availability of funding, all Environmental Readiness Level (ERL) 4 projects and activities in accordance with specific timeframes identified in the INRMP. For a description of “Level 4” projects and activities and budget programming hierarchy for this INRMP (both DoD and Navy), see *Section 6.3: Budget Considerations*.

Successful implementation of this INRMP will depend upon not only the guidelines set up and projects described, but how well these are translated into performance work statements (who will do what and with what money), project lists and scopes of work, and a workload plan. It must fit into the formal EMS established at NBVC for integrating environmental considerations into day-to-day activities across all levels and functions of Navy enterprise (see *Section 1.8: Ecosystem Approach*). To accomplish this, NBVC SNI will need to take advantage of funding opportunities outside normal program boundaries, consistent with authority to receive and use any such funds.

6.1.1 Federal Anti-Deficiency Act

NBVC intends to implement recommendations in this INRMP within the framework of regulatory compliance, national Navy mission obligations, anti-terrorism and force protection limitations, and funding constraints. All actions contemplated in this INRMP are subject to the availability of funds properly authorized and appropriated under federal law. Nothing in this INRMP is intended to be nor must be construed to be a violation of the Anti-Deficiency Act (31 U.S.C. 1341 et seq.).

6.1.2 Staffing

The Sikes Act specifically requires that there be “sufficient numbers of professionally trained natural resources management and natural resources enforcement personnel to be available and assigned responsibility” to implement an INRMP. The NBVC ED is responsible for identifying personnel requirements to accomplish INRMP goals and objectives. The NBVC ED is also responsible for providing input into this process by allocating existing budgetary and personnel resources and then identifying staffing needs based on any additional current and future projects. Personnel assigned to natural resources management are the core staff responsible for implementing the INRMP. These personnel ensure that a consistent conservation program is carried out by using strategies outlined in this plan to support the Navy mission and achieve INRMP goals and objectives. Staff coordination includes both planning teams for initiating projects and staffing teams to manage and run projects. Some of the projects described in this plan will depend on coordination with the Public Works Department and other installation personnel.

The following staffing is required to implement this INRMP at NBVC SNI. These positions are currently funded and no additional positions are needed:

- Terrestrial Ecologist
- Marine Ecologist
- Biological Technician
- Environmental Protection Specialist (NEPA)

Professional Development and Natural Resources Training

Adequate training of natural resource personnel is important to the success of military sustainability and land management. OPNAVINST 5090.1D *Environmental Readiness Program* and *Manual* (OPNAV M-5090.1) require that Navy commands develop, implement and enforce the management plan through personnel with professional training in natural resources. “Natural resources programs shall support military readiness and sustainability and commands shall assign specific responsibility, provide centralized supervision and assign professionally trained personnel to the program. Natural resources personnel shall be provided an opportunity to participate in natural resource management job-training activities and professional meetings.” The Sikes Act (Section 670g) and DoDINST 4715.03 (18 March 2011) also addresses this need.

Properly trained personnel are required to achieve objectives and guidelines of this INRMP. Environmental staff members entrusted with this work must have a thorough knowledge and understanding of biology and natural resources, and administrative duties such as project management, reporting, and contracting. Periodically, additional training is needed to keep personnel updated on the current practices and advances in knowledge of these topics. This training may be obtained from a variety of sources, including universities, regulatory agencies, professional societies, and other Navy or military organizations. These training opportunities may be offered in the forms of structured courses or conferences, workshops, and symposia. Professional development and the sharing of information with natural resource experts ensure the maximum benefits of adaptive management and research efforts is derived. NBVC ED will evaluate the following annual workshops or professional conferences for attendance depending on funding available for travel and training:

- National Military Fish and Wildlife Association annual workshop;
- North American Natural Resources Conference;
- Wildlife Society – Western Section; Partners-In-Flight national, regional, and state meetings (generally in conjunction with other listed meetings); and
- Working groups for species of concern on the installation.

Other conferences and workshops will be evaluated for their usefulness, and decisions will be made based on appropriateness to ongoing projects and funding availability. Conferences, which are especially useful, include those that address invasive species biology and control, wetland restoration and management, shorebird management, and endangered species management. The Wildlife Society, Society for Ecological Restoration, and National Military Fish and Wildlife Association are among the professional societies applicable to meeting the needs of NBVC's natural resources managers. Membership in these societies is encouraged. The Wildlife Society has some of the best scientific publications in the profession, and literature review is a necessary commitment to maintain standards. Attending meetings of these societies provides excellent opportunities to communicate with fellow professionals and maintain professional standards.

6.2 Adaptive Management: Annual Update, Review and Metrics

DoD policy requires installations to review INRMPs annually in cooperation with the two primary partnering parties to the INRMP: USFWS and the state fish and wildlife agency. Annual reviews facilitate “adaptive management” by providing an opportunity to review the goals and objectives of the plan, and establish a realistic schedule for undertaking proposed actions. Section 101(b)(2) of the Sikes Act (16 U.S.C. 670a[b][2]) requires that INRMPs be reviewed for operation and effect regularly (no less than every five years) by the installation, the USFWS, the state fish and wildlife agency (CDFW), and the NMFS. The DoD and Navy have provided specific guidance on the joint review and coordination process and timeframe (Deputy Under Secretary of Defense for Installations and Environment 2002; OPNAVINST 5090.1D). As part of the review, NBVC should invite annual feedback from the USFWS, NMFS, and the CDFW on the effectiveness of the INRMP, and inform the agencies about those INRMP projects and activities that are required to meet current natural resources compliance needs. INRMP updates are in Appendix J.

According to Chief of Naval Operations guidance, (DoN 2006), INRMPs must also be reviewed by installations at least once per year to verify the following:

- Current information on INRMP conservation metrics, as described in the Navy Conservation Website;
- All “must fund” projects and activities have been budgeted for and implementation is on schedule;
- All required trained natural resources positions are filled or are in the process of being filled and the number of positions is based on natural resource recommendations;
- Projects and activities for the upcoming year have been identified and included in the INRMP—an updated project list does not necessitate INRMP revision;
- All required coordination has occurred and all significant changes to the installation's mission requirements or its natural resources have been identified.

Chief of Naval Operations guidance requires installations use the Navy Conservation Website to facilitate annual review of the INRMP by the Navy, the USFWS, NMFS, and the CDFW (DoN 2006). The web-based program is used to evaluate the effectiveness of the INRMP and installation natural resources management as a whole through the following seven performance areas (DoN 2006): (1) INRMP Implementation; (2) Partnerships/Cooperation and Effectiveness; (3) Team Adequacy; (4) Status of Federal Listed Species and Critical Habitat; (5)

Ecosystem Integrity; (6) Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use; and (7) INRMP Impact on the Installation Mission. Each focus area has three to seven criteria that are used to determine the status of a given functional area within Natural Resources. An annual report is prepared during the annual review and is provided to the regulatory agencies upon completion.

Neither NEPA analysis or public review are necessary if an existing INRMP requires only limited revisions that are not expected to result in significant environmental effects other than those anticipated for the existing INRMP (DoN 2006). If the parties determine that substantial revisions to an INRMP are necessary, public comment shall be invited in conjunction with any required NEPA analysis. Public review requirements may be met by providing the public a meaningful opportunity to comment on the Draft Revised INRMP. After soliciting public comments, NBVC must afford the USFWS, NMFS, and the CDFW the opportunity to review all public comments (DoN 2006).

6.3 Budget Considerations

Formal adoption of an INRMP by a Commanding Officer or Officer-in-Charge constitutes a commitment to seek funding and execute, subject to the availability of funding, all "must fund" projects and activities in accordance with specific time frames identified in the INRMP. Under the Sikes Act, as amended, and Secretary of the Navy memorandum (12 August 1998), any natural resources management activity that is specifically addressed in the INRMP must be implemented (subject to availability of funds). Failure to implement the INRMP is a violation of the Sikes Act and may be a source of litigation. Since the Sikes Act requires implementation of the INRMP, there is a clear fiscal connection between INRMP preparation, revision, implementation, and funding. Funding to implement natural resources management will largely come from program sources (through Navy Region Southwest). Accordingly, it is vital that budget personnel understand and participate in the INRMP process.

The following sections address budget considerations for funding INRMP implementation.

6.3.1 Natural Resources Management Priorities and Funding Classifications

The DoD programming and budgeting priorities for conservation programs are detailed in DoDINST 4715.03 (*Natural Resources Conservation Program*, 2011). The Instruction divides programming and budget requirements into two categories: Recurring and Non-recurring. Compliance activities are in the Recurring category and the Non-recurring Current and Maintenance Compliance categories. Stewardship activities are in the Enhancement Actions Beyond Compliance category.

The following is the description of funding designations from the DoDINST 4715.03:

“1. RECURRING NATURAL RESOURCES CONSERVATION MANAGEMENT REQUIREMENTS

A. Administrative, personnel, and other costs associated with managing the DoD Natural Resources Conservation Program that are necessary to meet applicable compliance requirements in Federal and State laws, regulations, EOs, and DoD policies, or in direct support of the military mission.

B. DoD Components shall give priority to recurring natural resources conservation management requirements associated with the operation of facilities, installations, and deployed weapons systems. These activities include day-to-day costs of sustaining an

effective natural resources management program, as well as annual requirements, including manpower, training, supplies, permits, fees, testing and monitoring, sampling and analysis, reporting and recordkeeping, maintenance of natural resources conservation equipment, and compliance self-assessments.

2. NON-RECURRING NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT REQUIREMENTS. DoD Components shall prioritize non-recurring requirements using these classifications:

A. Current Compliance. Includes installation projects and activities to support:

- (1) Installations currently out of compliance (e.g., received an enforcement action from an authorized Federal or State agency or local authority).
- (2) Signed compliance agreement or consent order.
- (3) Meeting requirements with applicable Federal or State laws, regulations, standards, EOs, or DoD policies, including those listed in Enclosure 1.
- (4) Immediate and essential maintenance of operational integrity or military mission sustainment.
- (5) Projects or activities that will be out of compliance if not implemented in the current program year. Those activities include:
 - (a) Environmental analyses for natural resources conservation projects, and monitoring and studies required to assess and mitigate potential impacts of the military mission on conservation resources.
 - (b) Planning documentation, master plans, compatible development planning, and INRMPs.
 - (c) Natural resources planning-level surveys.
 - (d) Reasonable and prudent measures included in incidental take statements of biological opinions, biological assessments, surveys, monitoring, reporting of assessment results, or habitat protection for listed, at-risk, and candidate species so that proposed or continuing actions can be modified in consultation with the USFWS or NOAA Fisheries Service.
 - (e) Mitigation to meet existing regulatory permit conditions or written agreements, such as those required in chapter 26 of Reference (ai), and included in documents required by the DoD Chesapeake Bay Strategic Action Plan (Reference (ap)).
 - (f) Nonpoint source pollution or watershed management studies or actions needed to meet compliance dates cited in approved State coastal nonpoint source pollution control plans, as required to meet consistency determinations consistent with Coastal Zone Management.
 - (g) Wetlands delineation critical for the prevention of adverse impacts to wetlands, so that continuing actions can be modified to ensure mission continuity, as required by chapter 26 of Reference (ai).
 - (h) Compliance with missed deadlines established in DoD executed agreements (e.g., Reference (ap)).

B. Maintenance Requirements. Includes those projects and activities needed to meet an established deadline beyond the current program year and maintain compliance. Examples include:

- (1) Compliance with future deadlines.

- (2) Conservation, GIS mapping, and data management to comply with Federal, State, and local regulations, E.O.s, and DoD policy.
- (3) Efforts undertaken in accordance with non-deadline specific compliance requirements of leadership initiatives.
- (4) Wetlands enhancement to minimize wetlands loss and enhance existing degraded wetlands as required in chapter 26 of Reference (ai).
- (5) Conservation recommendations in biological opinions issued pursuant to the ESA.

C. Enhancement Actions Beyond Compliance. Includes those projects and activities that enhance conservation resources or the integrity of the installation mission, or are needed to address overall environmental goals and objectives, but are not specifically required by law, regulation, or E.O., and are not of an immediate nature. Examples include:

- (1) Community outreach activities, such as International Migratory Bird Day, Earth Day, National Public Lands Day, Pollinator Week, and Arbor Day activities.
- (2) Educational and public awareness projects, such as interpretive displays, oral histories, Watchable Wildlife areas, nature trails, wildlife checklists, and conservation teaching materials.
- (3) Restoration or enhancement of natural resources when no specific compliance requirement dictates a course or timing of action.
- (4) Management and execution of volunteer and partnership programs. (DoD 2011)."

The Navy funding programming hierarchy of recurring and non-recurring projects consists of four ERLs. Navy policy requires funding of all compliance driven (ERL 3 or 4) projects. ERLs enable capability-based programming and budgeting of environmental funding, and facilitate capability versus cost trade-off decisions. Projects recommended in this INRMP have been prioritized based on ERLs (DoN 2006, 2014a, 2014b). ERL 3 & 4 projects are compliance driven. ERL 4 is considered the absolute minimum level of environmental readiness capability required to maintain compliance with applicable legal requirements. ERL 1 & 2 projects are under the stewardship category. Funding is routinely programmed three years in advance of project implementation. All projects and activities in the Appendix C Implementation Table are assigned an ERL or entered into EPR-Web, but many actions are completed using on-site personnel (listed in Appendix C as "NBVC In-House") and are not part of the program budget. For example, natural resources personnel lead bird walks for the public or staff informational booths at public events.

ERL levels, as defined in the 2006 INRMP Guidance (DoN 2006, 2014a, 2014b) are:

Environmental Readiness Level 4:

- Supports all actions specifically required by law, regulation or EO.
- Supports all DoD Recurring Natural Resources Management requirements as they relate to a specific statute such as hazardous waste disposal, permits, fees, monitoring, sampling and analysis, reporting and record keeping.
- Supports recurring administrative, personnel and other costs associated with managing environmental programs that are necessary to meet applicable compliance requirements.
- Supports DoD policy requirement to comply with overseas Final Governing Standards and Overseas Environmental Baseline Guidance Document.

- Supports minimum feasible Navy executive agent responsibilities, participation in Office of Secretary of Defense sponsored inter-department and inter-agency efforts, and Office of Secretary of Defense mandated regional coordination efforts.

Environmental Readiness Level 3:

- Supports all capabilities provided by ERL 4.
- Supports existing level of Navy executive agent responsibilities, participation in Office of Secretary of Defense sponsored inter-department and inter-agency efforts, and Office of Secretary of Defense mandated regional coordination efforts.
- Supports proactive involvement in the legislative and regulatory process to identify and mitigate requirements that will impose excessive costs or restrictions on operations and training.
- Supports proactive initiatives critical to the protection of Navy operational readiness.

Environmental Readiness Level 2:

- Supports all capabilities provided under ERL 3.
- Supports enhanced proactive initiatives critical to the protection of Navy operational readiness.
- Supports all Navy and DoD policy requirements.
- Supports investments in pollution reduction, compliance enhancement, energy conservation and cost reduction.

Environmental Readiness Level 1:

- Supports all capabilities provided under ERL 2.
- Supports proactive actions required to ensure compliance with pending or strong anticipated laws and regulations in a timely manner or to prevent adverse impact to Navy mission.
- Supports investments that demonstrate Navy environmental leadership and proactive environmental stewardship.

It is the Navy's policy to fully fund compliance with all applicable federal, state and local laws; EOs; and associated implementing rules, regulations, DoDINSTs and DoDDIRs, and applicable international and overseas requirements (OPNAVINST 5090.1D [DoN 2014a]). Budget priorities for threatened and endangered species management, especially compliance with BOs, receive the **highest possible** budgeting priority, and support NBVC SNI's need to avoid critical habitat designations under Section 4(b)(2) of the ESA (ERL compliance levels 1 and 2), or Section 4(a)(3)(B)(i) of the ESA (exclusion from critical habitat designations for national security reasons).

Environmental Readiness Program Assessment Database

Environmental Program Requirements (EPR) covers multiple subject matter or "business lines" aside from natural and cultural resources. EPR-Web is an optimized online database used to define all programming for the Navy's environmental requirements, and is the tool for providing the four ERL capabilities used in fiscal planning. All natural resources requirements are entered into EPR-Web and are available for review/approval by the chain of command by the dates specified in the Guidance letter provided annually by Chief of Naval Operations (N45). EPR-Web records data on project expenditures, and provides immediate, web-based access to requirements entered by the multiple Navy environmental programs, including Environmental

Compliance, Pollution Prevention, Conservation, Radiological Controls, and Range Sustainment as related to environmental costs on military ranges.

Implementation Schedule

This INRMP will become effective upon the acceptance and signatory release at the front of this document, indicating mutual agreement among the INRMP signatories. Current projects, activities, and plans have been incorporated into the INRMP, as the plan serves as a formal structuring and integration of the existing natural resources management program.

Future work identified herein will be implemented as funding becomes available. Priorities identified in this INRMP will generally determine the order of implementation. The NBVC ED will determine what projects and activities are appropriate to initiate, given funding, at any particular time. The INRMP is meant to be flexible, dynamic, and adaptable to the immediate concerns and needs of natural resources management and the Navy mission.

Program Monitoring

The NBVC ED will be responsible for oversight and monitoring of the overall program identified in this INRMP. Cooperative projects among different Navy organizations will be monitored by the originating or controlling office as specified prior to project implementation.

6.3.2 External Assistance

Opportunities for external assistance with natural resource programs at NBVC SNI are identified below.

Other Agencies

NBVC recognizes the importance of cooperating with federal and state agencies in addition to private organizations. *Section 1.0: Introduction* and *Section 5.4: Beneficial Partnerships and Collaborative Resources Planning* identify other agencies and organizations with which NBVC has cooperatively worked in recent years. These organizations, particularly INRMP signatory partners (USFWS, NOAA and CDFW), will continue to assist with implementation of various aspects of this INRMP.

Volunteers

Volunteers are a potential valuable source of personnel assistance at NBVC SNI. NBVC ED uses volunteers for marsh clean-up events, beach clean-up events, California least tern colony monitoring, and invasive species control. NBVC ED will continue to pursue the use of volunteers.

University Assistance

Universities are an excellent source of assistance for research and provide resource specific expertise, as well as assistance with implementation of restoration activities. Collaborative investigations performed in conjunction with installation biologist provide the most likely and cost effective sources of assistance with implementation of this INRMP. Local and regional universities, such as UC Los Angeles, UC Santa Barbara and California State University Channel Islands should continue to be coordinated with for potential sources of graduate and undergraduate assistance with implementation of projects discussed in this INRMP.

Contractors

Selected projects can be carried out with Navy biology staff. Many projects, such as invasive species control, wetland restoration, targeted surveys or time-sensitive surveys and monitoring requires contractor services or other federal agency services, because of a need for expertise or for necessary personnel. Therefore, funding is required to perform these actions, as installation biologists cannot accomplish all of the INRMP management goals without external assistance. In accordance with Circular Number A-76, the federal government is mandated to use commercial sources to supply the products and services the Government needs. Contractors are able to provide a wide variety of specialties to aid NBVC ED with implementation of this INRMP. Specialties range from NEPA documentation, vegetation surveys, vertebrate and invertebrate surveys, vegetation surveys, water quality surveys, production of management plans, and similar activities. Contractor supported projects require preparation of a request for proposal to acquire services, which should be considered during project planning, to ensure appropriate funding can be obtained.

6.4 Funding Sources

To implement the various research, surveys, and programs necessary to fulfill the mission of the NBVC ED, funding must be identified and acquired. The NBVC ED, under the direction of the Commanding Officer, NBVC, is responsible for coordinating efforts and funding for natural resource and environmental programs. NBVC ED receives funding, program, and policy support and guidance from the Navy Region Southwest, San Diego. The Region is the Commander Navy Installations Command local agent for ensuring that environmental programs are effectively managed. The Region is supported by NAVFAC SW who provides assistance to many local installations.

There are several avenues of funding available to the NBVC ED, beyond the typical Naval operational budget, that allow the inclusion of additional projects to assist the NBVC ED in their mission-related and stewardship endeavors. The NBVC ED must continually assess the priority and level of budgetary needs to fulfill Navy and regulatory requirements and to sustain overall program goals. These funding sources are discussed below in general terms, as this process is dynamic and is dependent on the INRMPs continuously developing program.

These programs will be implemented using Navy personnel and program resources as much as possible; however, it is likely that contractors will accomplish many projects. NBVC ED will identify projects that would be accomplished using contract vehicles, with existing contracts being used where possible and appropriate.

For large projects that involve different Navy organizations, representatives of these organizations would coordinate budgeting and scheduling to ensure that the project can be accomplished in the planned timeframe. Large-budget projects may not be completely funded in a fiscal year, requiring incremental funding over the term of the project.

In some cases, smaller, lower-priority projects may be conducted using unspent funds from other tasks or year-end fallout funding. Some projects may be accomplished with little or no funding required, such as those requiring only a change of policy or coordination and effort from volunteer labor. These tasks can be implemented virtually as soon as planning is performed.

6.4.1 Department of Defense Funding Sources

The costs of executing INRMP actions may be funded from a variety of DoD sources. Funding sources should be reviewed carefully to identify qualifying projects. Execution of this plan by the federal government is contingent on the availability of funds properly allocated to the plan in accordance with applicable law. The primary funding sources to Navy natural resources programs include:

1. **Operations and Maintenance Funds.** Funding sources for the natural resources program are derived from General and Administrative, Operations and Maintenance Navy, Major Range Test Facility Base, and input into the Navy EPR system for funding. This primary budgetary source is the basis for maintaining the personnel and core programs inherent to the natural resources program. It is the responsibility of ED to manage the natural resources program budget and funding. Once Operations and Maintenance Navy funds are appropriated for core personnel and the program, funding can be justified for other project requirements.
2. **Agricultural Outlease Funds.** Funds accumulated through the outleasing of agricultural lands on many installations are directed back into the natural resource program and reallocated throughout the Navy by NAVFAC Headquarters. These are the broadest use funds available exclusively to natural resource managers. These funds are available to all installations to offset the costs of preparing and implementing INRMPs.
3. **Recycling Funds.** Installations with a Qualified Recycling Program may use proceeds for some types of natural resource projects.
4. **Navy Working Capital Fund.** Many natural resource projects may be funded with the Navy Working Capital Fund. All projects submitted for funding through the Navy Working Capital Fund must be included in the INRMP, or a clear justification for their omission must be provided. Navy Working Capital Fund funds are generally not available for Navy Level 2-5 projects. The Navy Working Capital Fund is a revolving fund that is generated by fees for services and used to pay expenses.

Other DoD funding sources are described below.

Sikes Act Funds

Sikes Act funds are collected via sales of licenses to hunt or fish (Navy 2005a). They are authorized by the Sikes Act and may be used only for fish and wildlife management on the installation where they are collected. No generates Sikes Act funds are collected at NBVC SNI.

Legacy Funds

The Legacy Resource Management Program was enacted in 1990 to provide financial assistance to military natural and cultural resources management. The program assists with protection and enhancement of natural resources while supporting military readiness. Legacy projects may involve regional ecosystem management initiatives, habitat preservation efforts, archaeological investigations, invasive species control, and/or monitoring, and predicting migratory patterns of birds and other animals.

6.4.2 Use of Cooperative Agreements and Partnerships

Cooperative agreements are legal relationships between the Navy and states, local governments, institutions of higher education, hospitals, non-profit organizations or individuals. The principal purpose of the relationship is to transfer a thing of value to the state, local government, or other recipient to carry out a public purpose of support or stimulation authorized by a law of the U.S. instead of acquiring (by purchase, lease, or barter) property or services for the direct benefit or use of the U.S. Government. Cooperative agreements may be entered into for inventories, monitoring, research, minor construction and maintenance, and public awareness, to provide for the maintenance and improvement of natural resources or conservation research on DoD installations (DoDINST 4715.03). To use a cooperative agreement, substantial involvement is expected between the Navy and the state, local government, or other recipient when carrying out the activity contemplated in the agreement. Cooperative agreements provide a mutually beneficial means of acquiring, analyzing, and interpreting natural resources data, which can then be used to inform natural resources management decisions. Cooperative agreements are funded by the Navy and produce information that can be used to help resource managers achieve project-specific compliance with environmental laws. Authorization for cooperative agreements is arranged through NAVFAC.

NBVC recognizes the importance of cooperating with federal and state agencies, in addition to private organizations. No cooperative agreements are in place other than this INRMP's signatory partners (USFWS, NOAA, and CDFW) and NAVFAC SW, who will continue to assist with implementation of various aspects of this INRMP. Cooperative agreements may provide future funding opportunities for the Resources Management Program at NBVC SNI, and should be pursued.

Cooperative Ecosystem Studies Units

The Cooperative Ecosystem Studies Units program is a working collaboration among federal agencies, universities, state agencies, non-governmental organizations, and other nonfederal institutional partners. The Cooperative Ecosystem Studies Units National Network provides multidisciplinary research, technical assistance, and education to resource and environmental managers. Although the overall program is overseen by USDI, one of the participating agencies is DoD. For more information regarding the Cooperative Ecosystem Studies Units program, refer to the following website: <http://www.cesu.psu.edu>.

6.4.3 Research Funding Requirements

Environmental program funding in the Navy is primarily based upon federally mandated requirements. Program managers are encouraged to seek outside funding for projects consistent with the INRMP, such as research, that will benefit natural resources on installations, but that are not directly related to federal mandates.

New funding sources should be sought from federal, state, local, and nonprofit organizations with an interest in achieving the goals and objectives of this INRMP in partnership with NBVC. Any such funding would need to be consistent with authorization to receive and use such funds. These will often require cost-sharing. This funding opportunity should be sought for projects that are not ERL 3 or 4 "must fund" items, tied directly to immediate regulatory compliance. Examples are watershed management, habitat enhancement, or wetland restoration.

6.4.4 Non-DoD Funding Sources

There are a number of grant programs available for natural resource management projects such as watershed management and restoration, habitat restoration, and wetland and riparian area restoration. When federally funded, these programs typically require non-federal matching funds. However, installations may be able to partner with other groups to propose eligible projects. One example grant program is listed below, but many more are available.

The National Association of Counties, National Association of Service and Conservation Corps, National Fish and Wildlife Foundation, and Wildlife Habitat Council sponsor the Five Star Restoration Challenge Grants program, in cooperation with EPA, NMFS and other sponsors. This program provides modest financial assistance (\$5,000 to \$20,000) on a competitive basis to support community-based wetland and riparian restoration projects that build diverse partnerships and foster local natural resource stewardship. Installations would need to partner with other groups to be eligible for this type of program. Applications are due in March. Information is available on the web at <http://www.epa.gov/owow/wetlands/restore/5star/>.

6.5 INRMP Implementation Summary and Schedule

The objectives and strategies that support INRMP implementation are identified in this section. Detailed natural resource management prescriptions and a list of projects are in Appendix C. The Sikes Act requires implementation of this INRMP; however, INRMP implementation is also subject to the provisions of the Federal Anti-Deficiency Act. Some INRMP projects are accomplished with installation staff; others involve contracting work to specialists. The implementation schedule identified in Appendix C, Table C-3 is suggested for long-term planning purposes; however, the schedule may be modified based on need, resources, and seasonal requirements.

7.0 References

- Agri Chemical and Supply, Inc. 2009. Invasive Plant Control on OLF San Nicolas Island- 2008 Report. Prepared for Natural Resources Office, Commander Navy Region Southwest, Under Contract with Southwest Division, Naval Facilities Engineering Command, Contract N-8711-04-D-3604, Task Order 0059.
- Agri Chemical and Supply, Inc. 2014a. Final Report Exotic Pest Plant Species Eradication at Naval Base Ventura County, California. Prepared for Naval Facilities Engineering Command Southwest, Contract N-62473-10-D-0802/0056. June.
- Agri Chemical and Supply, Inc. 2014b. 2013 San Nicolas Island Weed Management Plan, Naval Base Ventura County, California. Prepared for Naval Facilities Engineering Command Southwest, Contract N-62473-10-D-0802/0900. December.
- Ainley D.G., W.J. Sydeman, and J. Norton. 1995. Upper trophic level predators indicate interannual negative and positive anomalies in the California Current food web. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 118: 69-79.
- Ainley, D.G, and R.J. Boekelheide. 1990. Seabirds of the Farallon Islands: ecology, dynamics, and structure of an upwelling system community. Stanford University Press, Stanford, CA. 450 pages.
- Allen, M.J. 2006. "Continental Shelf and Upper Slope." In: L.G. Allen, D.J. Pondella II, and M.H. Horn, editors. *The Ecology of Marine Fishes: California and Adjacent Waters*. Berkeley, California: University of California Press. Pages 167-202.
- Anderson, D.W. and Gress F. 1983. Status of the northern population of California brown pelicans. *Condor* 85: 79-88.
- Anderson, D.W., F. Gress F., M.F. Mais. 1982. Brown pelicans: influence of food supply on reproduction. *Oikos* 39:23-31.
- Anderson, D.W., J.R. Jehl, R.W. Risebrough, L.A. Woods, L.R. DeWeese, and W.G. Edgecomb. 1975. Brown pelicans: improved reproduction off the southern California coast. *Science* 190: 806-808.
- Anderson, T.W. 1994. Role of macroalgal structure in the distribution and abundance of a temperate reef fish. *Marine Ecological Progress Series* 113: 279-290.
- Andres, B. A., and G. A. Falxa. 1995. Black Oystercatcher (*Haematopus bachmani*). In *The Birds of North America*, No. 155. A. Poole and F. Gill (Eds.). The Birds of North America, Inc., Philadelphia, PA.
- Azevedo, J. and D.L. Morgan. 1974. Fog precipitation in coastal California forests. *Ecology*, 55, 1135-1141.
- Baldwin, B.G. et al. 2012. *The Jepson Manual: Vascular Plants of California*, second edition. University of California Press. Berkeley, California.

- Barlow, J., Boveng, P., Lowry, M.S., Stewart, B.S., Le Boeuf, B.J., Sydeman, W.J., Jameson, R.J., Allen, S.G., and C.W. Oliver. 1993. Status of the northern elephant seal population along the U.S. west coast in 1992. Administrative Report LJ_93_01. Southwest Fisheries Science Center, National Marine Fisheries Service, La Jolla, CA. 32 pages.
- Barlow, J., Forney, K.A., Hill, P.S., Brownell Jr., P.S., Carretta, J.V., DeMaster, D.P., Julian, F., Lowry, M.S., Ragen, T., and Reeves R.R. 1997. U.S. Pacific Marine Mammal Stock Assessments: 1996. NOAA Technical Memorandum NMFS-SWFSC-248. Southwest Fisheries Science Center, National Marine Fisheries Service, La Jolla, CA.
- Barnard, J.L. 1963. Relationship of benthic Amphipoda to invertebrate communities of inshore sublittoral sands of southern California. *Pacific Nature* 3:439-467.
- Barnes RSK, Hughes RN. 1988. An introduction to marine ecology. 2nd ed. Oxford: Blackwell, 351 pages.
- Benton, N., J.D. Ripley, and F. Powledge (Editors). 2008. Conserving Biodiversity on Military Lands: A Guide for Natural Resource Managers, 2008 Edition. Nature Serve: Arlington, Virginia. <http://www.dodbiodiversity.org>.
- Bezy, R.L., G.C. Gorman, G.A. Adest, and Y.J. Kim. 1980. Divergence in the island night lizard *Xantusia riversiana* (*Sauria: Xantusiidae*). Pages 565-583. In: D.M. Power (Ed.), *The California Islands: Proceedings of a Multidisciplinary Symposium*. Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History, Santa Barbara, California.
- Blecha, J.B., Steinbeck, J.R., and D.C. Sommerville. 1992. Aspects of the biology of the black abalone (*Haliotis cracherodii*) near Diablo Canyon, central California. Pages 225-236 in S.A. Shepherd, M.J. Tegner, and S.A. Guzman del Proo (Eds.), *Abalone of the world: Biology, fisheries, and culture*. Proceedings of the 1st International Symposium on Abalone. Blackwell Scientific Publications Ltd., Oxford, U.K.
- Bleitz, D.E. 1993. "The Prehistoric Exploitation of Marine Mammals and Birds at San Nicolas Island, California." Pages 519-536 in: *The Third California Islands Symposium: Recent Advances in Research on the California Islands*, F.G. Hochberg (Ed). Santa Barbara, CA: Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History.
- Bodkin, J.L. 1988. Effects of kelp removal on associated fish assemblages in central California. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 1 (17): 227-238.
- Bonnell, M.L. and M.D. Dailey. 1993. Marine mammals. In M.D. Dailey, D.J. Reish, and J.W. Anderson, editors. *Ecology of the Southern California Bight: A synthesis and interpretation*. Berkeley: University of California Press. Pages 604-681.
- Bonnell, M.L., and R.G. Ford. 1987. California sea lion distribution: A statistical analysis of aerial transect data. *Journal of Wildlife Management* 51(1): 13-20.
- Bretagnolle, V. 1990. Effect of moon on activity of petrels (Class Aves) from the Selvagen Islands (Portugal). *Canadian Journal of Zoology* 68: 1404-1409.
- Brown, S., Hickey, C., Harrington, B., and R. Gill (Eds.). 2001. *The U.S. Shorebird Conservation Plan*, 2nd edition. Manomet Center for Conservation Sciences, Manomet, MA.

- Browne, D.R. 1994. Understanding the oceanic circulation in and around the Santa Barbara Channel. The Fourth California Islands Symposium: update on the status of resources (ed. by W.L. Halvorson and G.J. Maender), pages 27-34. Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History, Santa Barbara.
- Bunn, D., A. Mummert, M. Hoshovsky, K. Gilardi, and S. Shanks. 2007. California Wildlife: Conservation Challenges, California's Wildlife Action Plan. Prepared by the U.C. Davis Wildlife Health Center for the California Department of Fish and Game, Sacramento, CA.
- Bureau of Land Management (BLM). 2005. California Coastal National Monument Resource Management Plan. U.S. Department of the Interior, Bureau of Land Management, California State Office, September 2005.
- Burgess, S.S.O., and Dawson, T.E. 2004. The contribution of fog to the water relations of *Sequoia sempervirens* (D. Don): foliar uptake and prevention of dehydration. *Plant Cell and Environment*, 27, 1023-1034.
- Burnham, W., F. Kunkel, W. Hofmann, and W. Peterson. 1963. Hydrogeologic reconnaissance of San Nicolas Island, California. U.S. Geological Survey Water Supply Paper 1539-O. U.S. Government Printing Office, Washington, D.C. 43 pages.
- Butler, J., DeVogelaere, A., Gustafson, R., Mobley, C., Neuman, M., Richards, D., Rumsey, S., Taylor, B., G. VanBlaricom. 2009. Status Review Report for Black Abalone (*Haliotis cracherodii*, Leach, 1814). National Marine Fisheries Service, Southwest Region, Long Beach, CA.
- Butler, J., Neuman, M., Pinkard, D., Kvittek, R., and G. Cochrane. 2006. The use of multibeam sonar mapping techniques to refine population estimates of the endangered white abalone (*Haliotis sorenseni*). *Fishery Bulletin* 104: 521-532.
- California Coastal Commission (CCC). 1997. California Coastal Commission Strategic Plan, June 1997.
- CCC. 2010. Public Resources Code, Division, 20, California Coastal Act - 2010. <http://www.coastal.ca.gov/ccatc.html>. Accessed 1 June 2010.
- California Department of Fish and Game (CDFG). 1974. Cruise Report 74-KB-15 and 74-M-3 Abalone-Lobster Investigations. Prepared by R. Burge for the State of California - The Resources Agency, Department of Fish and Game, Marine Resources Region, Long Beach, California.
- CDFG. 2002. Nearshore Fishery Management Plan. Prepared by the California Resources Agency, Department of Fish and Game, Marine Region, August 2002.
- CDFG. 2005. Final Abalone Recovery and Management Plan. Prepared by the California Resources Agency, Department of Fish and Game, Marine Region, 09 December 2005.
- CDFG. 2006. News Release. <http://www.dfg.ca.gov/OSPR/organizational/admin/news/2006news/brownpelicans-nr-060606.pdf>.
- CDFG. 2008a. California Marine Life Protection Act: Master Plan for Marine Protected Areas. Prepared by the California Resources Agency, Department of Fish and Game, January 2008.

- CDFG. 2008b. California Aquatic Invasive Species Management Plan.
- CDFG. 2008c. California Bird Species of Special Concern.
- CDFG. 2010. State and Federally Listed Endangered and Threatened Animals of California.
- CDFG and Office of Spill Prevention and Response (OSPR). 2005. California Wildlife Response Plan for California.
- California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW). 2007. California Wildlife Action Plan. Available at: <http://www.dfg.ca.gov/wildlife/WAP/>
- CDFW. 2014. Kelp Coverage for the California Coast. Developed by NAVAIR, Ocean Imaging, and the California Department of Fish and Wildlife. Data available online at: <https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Conservation/Marine/GIS/Downloads>. Last accessed August 8, 2015.
- California Department of Transportation (Caltrans). 2000. Construction Site Best Management Practices (BMPs) Manual. State of California, Department of Transportation, November 2000.
- California Department of Transportation. 2003. Statewide Storm Water Management Plan. CTSW-RT-02-008. California Department of Transportation, Division of Environmental Analysis, Sacramento, CA.
- California Energy Commission (CEC) and CDFG. 2007. California Guidelines for Reducing Impacts to Birds and Bats from Wind Energy Development. Commission Final Report. California Energy Commission, Renewables Committee, and Energy Facilities Siting Division, and California Department of Fish and Game, Resource Management and Policy Division.
- California Mission Resource Center (CMRC). 2010. <http://www.missionscalifornia.com/stories/lone-woman-san-nicolas-island.html>. Accessed 2 August 2010.
- California Resources Agency (CRA) and California Environmental Protection Agency (CalEPA). 2004. Protecting Our Ocean: California's Action Strategy.
- California Stormwater Quality Association (CASQA). 2003. California Stormwater BMP Handbook. <http://www.cabmphandbooks.com/Documents/Construction/SE-5.pdf>.
- California Stormwater Quality Task Force. 2003. California Stormwater Best Management Practice Handbook, Construction Activity, Industrial, Commercial, Municipal, New Development and Redevelopment. Hayward, California: January 2003.
- Camp Dresser & McKee et al. 1993. California Stormwater Industrial/Commercial Best Management Practice Handbook. Stormwater Quality Task Force, Sacramento, CA.
- Capitolo, P.J., Davis, J.N., Henkel, L.A., Tyler, W.B., Carter, H.R., and Kelly P.R. 2007. Monitoring cormorant populations in Southern California in 2005-2006: Asilomar, California, Pacific Seabird Group Annual Meeting, Abstracts: 53-54 (www.pacificseabirdgroup.org).

- Caplan, R.I. and R.A. Bootllootian. 1967. Intertidal Ecology of San Nicolas Island. Proceedings of the Symposium on the Biology of the California Islands. Santa Barbara, California.
- Carr, M.H. 1991. Habitat selection and recruitment of an assemblage of temperate zone reef fishes. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 146: 113-137.
- Carr, M.H. 1994. Effects of macroalgal dynamics on recruitment of a temperate reef fish. *Ecology* 75:1320-1333.
- Carretta, J.V., Forney, K.A., Lowry, M.S., Barlow, J., Baker, J., Johnston, D., Hanson, B., Muto, M.M., Lynch, D., and L. Carswell. 2009. U.S. Pacific Marine Mammal Stock Assessments: 2008. U.S. Department of Commerce, NOAA Technical Memorandum: NOAA-TM-NMFS-SWFSC-434.
- Carretta, J.V., Forney, K.A., Lowry, M.S., Barlow, J., Baker, J., Hanson, B., and M.M. Muto. 2007. U.S. Pacific Marine Mammal Stock Assessments: 2007. U.S. Department of Commerce, NOAA Technical Memorandum, NMFS-SWFSC-414. 320 pages.
- Carretta, J.V., Lowry, M.S., Stinchcomb, C.E., Lynn, M.S., and Cosgrove, R.E. 2000. Distribution and abundance of marine mammals at San Clemente Island and surrounding offshore waters: Results from aerial and ground surveys in 1998 and 1999. Southwest Fisheries Science Center Administrative Report LJ-00-02. La Jolla, California: National Marine Fisheries Service.
- Carretta, J.V. et al. 2013. U.S. Pacific Marine Mammal Stock Assessments: 2012. U.S. Department of Commerce, NOAA Technical Memorandum: NOAA-TM-NMFS-SWFSC-504.
- Carter, H.R., G.J. McChesney, D.L. Jaques, C.S. Strong, M.W. Parker, J.E. Takekawa, D.L. Jory, and D.L. Whitworth. 1992. Breeding Populations of Seabirds in California, 1989-1991. Vol. 1 - Population Estimates, Unpublished Final Report, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Northern Prairie Wildlife Research Center, Dixon, California.
- Carter, H.R., T.A. Ames, P.J. Capitolo, G.J. McChesney, T.W. Keeney, and G. Smith. 2014. Status of the Western Gull at San Nicolas Island, California, 1850-208. Unpublished report, Carter Biological consulting, Victoria, British Columbia; and Humboldt State University, Department of Wildlife, Arcata, California. 55 pages.
- Center for Watershed Protection. 2003. Impacts of Impervious Cover on Aquatic Systems. Ellicott City, MD.
- Channel Islands National Park (CINP). 2005. Seabird Monitoring Annual Report, National Park Service, Department of the Interior, Washington, D.C.
- CINP. 2010. <http://www.nps.gov/chis/parkmgmt/partners.htm>. Accessed 30 July 2010.
- Clifford, D.L., Mazet, J.A.K., Dubovi, E.J., Garcelon, D.K., Coonan, T.J., Conrad, P.A., and L. Munson. 2006. Pathogen exposure in endangered island fox (*Urocyon littoralis*) populations: Implications for conservation management. *Biological Conservation* 131: 230-243.
- Coffman, Larry. 2000. Low-Impact Development Design Strategies, An Integrated Design Approach. EPA 841-B-00-003. Prince George's County, Maryland. Department of Environmental Resources, Programs and Planning Division.

- Cohen, A. N., and J. T. Carlton. 1998. Accelerating invasion rate in a highly invaded estuary. *Science* 279: 555-558.
- Cole, E.S. 2005. Root and whole plant growth responses to soil resource heterogeneity in coastal dune shrubs of California. PhD Dissertation, Department of Ecology, Evolution, and Marine Biology, University of California, Santa Barbara.
- Collins, P.W. 1991a. Interaction between Island foxes (*Urocyon littoralis*) and Indians on islands off the coast of southern California: I. Morphological and archaeological evidence of human assisted dispersal. *Journal of Ethnobiology* 11(1):51-81.
- Collins, P.W. 1991b. Interaction between Island foxes (*Urocyon littoralis*) and Native Americans on islands off the coast of southern California: II. Ethnographic, archaeological, and historical evidence of human assisted dispersal. *Journal of Ethnobiology* 11(2):205-229.
- Coonan, T.J. 2003. Recovery strategy for island foxes (*Urocyon littoralis*) on the northern Channel Islands. National Park Service, Channel Islands National Park, Ventura, CA. 81 pages.
- Corbin, J.D., Thomsen, M.A., Dawson, T.E., and D'Antonio, C.M. 2005. Summer water use by California coastal prairie grasses: fog, drought, and community composition. *Oecologia*, 145, 511-521.
- Council on Environmental Quality (CEQ) et al. 1995. Memorandum of Understanding between CEQ, U.S. Department of Agriculture, U.S. Department of the Army, U.S. Department of Commerce, U.S. Department of Defense, U.S. Department of Energy, U.S. Department of Housing and Urban Development, U.S. Department of the Interior, U.S. Department of Justice, U.S. Department of Labor, U.S. Department of State, U.S. Department of Transportation, Environmental Protection Agency, Office of Science and Technology Policy to Foster the Ecosystem Approach.
- Crooks, J.A. 1998. Habitat alteration and community level effects of an exotic mussel, *Musculista senhousia*. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 162: 137-152.
- Cross, J.N., and Allen L.G. 1993. Fishes. In M.D. Dailey, D.J. Reish, and J.W. Anderson (Eds.). *Ecology of the Southern California Bight, A Synthesis and Interpretation*. University of California Press, Berkeley, CA. Pages 459-540.
- Dailey, M.D., D.J. Reish, and J.W. Anderson (Eds.). 1993. *Ecology of the Southern California Bight: A Synthesis and Interpretation*. University of California Press, Berkeley/Los Angeles.
- Dale, Virginia H. and Suzanne C. Beyeler. 2001. Challenges in the development and use of ecological indicators. *Ecological Indicators* 1:3-10.
- Davis, G.E. 2005. National Park stewardship and 'vital signs' monitoring: a case study from Channel Islands National Park, California. *Aquatic Conserv. Mar. Freshw. Ecosyst.* 15:71-89.
- Dawson, T.E. 1998. Fog in the California Redwood forest: ecosystem inputs and use by plants. *Oecologia*, 117, 476-485.
- Dayton P.K. 1985. Ecology of kelp communities. *Annu Rev Ecol Syst* 16:215-45.

- De Violini, R. 1974. Climate handbook for Point Mugu and San Nicolas Island, Part I, surface data. Technical Publications PMR-TP-74-1, Pacific Missile Range, Point Mugu, CA. 139 pages.
- DeMartini, E.E. and D.A. Roberts. 1990. Effects of giant kelp (*Macrocystis*) on the density and abundance of fishes in a cobble-bottom kelp forest. *Bulletin of Marine Science* 46: 287-300.
- Deysher, L.E., Dean, T.A., Grove, R.S., Jahn, A. 2002. Design considerations for an artificial reef to grow giant kelp (*Macrocystis pyrifera*) in Southern California. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 59: S201-S207.
- Dotson and Charter. 2003. Trends in the Southern California Sport Fishery. CalCOFI Rep., Vol 44 94-106 pages.
- Douros, W.J. 1985. Density, growth, reproduction, and recruitment in an intertidal abalone: Effects of intraspecific competition and prehistoric predation. Master's Thesis. University of California Santa Barbara, Santa Barbara, CA.
- Drost, C.A. and G.M. Fellers. 1991. Density cycles in an island population of deer mice, *Peromyscus maniculatus*. *Oikos* 60:351-364.
- Dugan, J.E., Hubbard, D.M., Engle, J.M., Martin, D.L., Richards, D.M., Davis, G.E., Lafferty, K.D., and R.F. Ambrose. 2000. Macrofauna communities of exposed sandy beaches on the Southern California mainland and Channel Islands. Fifth California Islands Symposium, OCS Study, MMS 99-0038: 339-346.
- Ehrlich, P.R., D.S. Dobkin, and D. Wheye. 1988. *The Birders Handbook*. Simon and Schuster, New York. 785 pages.
- Ellison, W.H. (editor). 1937. *The life and adventures of George Nidever [1802-1883]: the life story of a remarkable California pioneer told in his own words, and none wasted*. University of California Press, Berkeley.
- Engle, J.M. 1979. Ecology and growth of juvenile California spiny lobster, *Panulirus interruptus* (Randall). Ph.D. Dissertation, University of Southern California.
- Engle, J.M. 1994. Perspectives on the structure and dynamics of nearshore marine assemblages of the California Channel Islands. *The Fourth California Islands Symposium: update on the status of resources* (ed. by W.L. Halvorson and G.J. Maender), pages 13-26. Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History, Santa Barbara, CA.
- Engle J.M. and K.A. Miller. 2003. Distribution and morphology of eelgrass (*Zostera marina L.*) at the California Channel Islands. In: Garcelon D.K. and Schwemm C.A. (Eds.). *Proceedings of the Sixth California Islands Symposium*. Institute for Wildlife Studies, Arcata, pages 405-414.
- Erickson, W.P., G.D. Johnson, M.D. Stickland, D.P. Young, Jr., K.J. Sernka, and R.E. Good. 2001. *Avian Collisions with Wind Turbines: A Summary of Existing Studies and Comparisons to Other Sources of Avian Collision Mortality in the United States*. The National Wind Coordinating Committee.

- Estes, J.A. and J.L. Bodkin. 2002. Otters. In *Encyclopedia of Marine Mammals* (W.F. Perrin, B. Wursig, and J.G.M. Thewissen editors). Academic Press, San Diego, California. Pages 842-858.
- Estes, J.A. and R.J. Jameson. 1988. A double-survey estimate for sighting probability of sea otters in California. *Journal of Wildlife Management*. 52: 70-76.
- Estes, J.A. Hatfield, B.B., Ralls, K., and J. Ames. 2003. Causes of mortality in California sea otters during periods of population growth and decline. *Marine Mammal Science* 19: 198-216.
- Estrada, D. 1985. Soil Survey of Channel Islands Area, California: San Nicolas Island. Interim Publication, National Cooperative Soil Survey. Soil Conservation Service, Washington, D.C.
- Farlinger, S. and A. Campbell. 1992. Fisheries management and biology of northern abalone, *Haliotis kamtschatkana*, in the northeast Pacific. In: *Abalone of the World Biology, Fisheries, and Culture* (Eds: S.A. Shepherd, M.J. Tegner, and S.A. Guzman del Proo). University Press: Cambridge. 608 pages.
- Fellers, G.M., Drost, C.A., Muntz, W.J., and T. Murphey. 1998. Ecology of the Island Night Lizard, *Xantusia riversiana*, on San Nicolas Island, California. U.S. Navy, Point Mugu and Biological Research Division, U.S. Geological Survey, Point Reyes National Seashore, California.
- Fischer, D.T., C.J. Still, and A.P. Williams. 2008. Significance of summer fog and overcast for drought stress and ecological functioning of coastal California endemic plant species. *Journal of Biogeography*. Blackwell Publishing Ltd.
- Fischlin, A., Midgley, G.F., Price, J.T., Leemans, R., Gopal, B., Turley, C., Rounsevell, M.D.A., Gallo-Reynoso, J.P. and Rathbun, G.B. 2007. Status of sea otters (*Enhydra lutris*) in Mexico. *Marine Mammal Science* 13(2): 332-340, 1997.
- Foreman, R. 1967. Observations on the flora and ecology of San Nicolas Island. Report USNRDL-TR-67-8 U.S. Naval Radiological Defense Laboratory, San Francisco, CA.
- Forman, R. T. T., D. Sperling, J. A. Bissonette, A. P. Clevenger, C. D. Cutshall, V. H. Dale, L. Fahrig, R. France, C. R. Goldman, K. Heanue, J. A. Jones, F. J. Swanson, T. Turrentine, and T. C. Winter. 2003. *Road Ecology: Science and Solutions*. Island Press, Washington, D.C.
- Foster, M. & Schiel, D.R. 1985. The ecology of giant kelp forests in California: a community profile. US Fish and Wildlife Service Biological Report 85 (7.2), USA: 152 pages.
- Foster, M.S., A.P. De Vogelaere, C. Harrold, J.S. Pearse, and A.B. Thum. 1988. "Causes of Spatial and Temporal Patterns in Rocky Intertidal Communities of Central and Northern California." *Memoirs of the California Academy of Sciences* 9:1-45.
- Friedman, C.S., Andree, K.B., Beauchamp, K.A., Moore, J.D., Robbins, T.T., Shields, J.D., and R.P. Hedrick. 2000. '*Candidatus Xenohaliotis californiensis*', a newly described pathogen of abalone, *Haliotis* spp., along the west coast of North America. *International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology* 50: 847-855.

- Gallo-Reynoso, J.P. 1994. Factors affecting the population status of Guadalupe fur seal, *Arctocephalus townsendi* (Merriam, 1897) at Isla de Guadalupe, Baja California, Mexico. Ph.D. Dissertation, University of California, Santa Cruz, CA. 199 pages.
- Garcelon, D. 2009. Personal communication as cited in USFWS 2009. President. Institute for Wildlife Studies, Arcata, CA.
- Garcelon, D.K. and B.R. Hudgens. 2009. Island Fox Monitoring and Demography on San Nicolas Island–2007. Unpublished report prepared by the Institute for Wildlife Studies, Arcata, California.
- Garcelon, D.K. and G.A. Schmidt. 2005. Island Fox Monitoring and Demography on San Nicolas Island–2004. Unpublished report prepared by the Institute for Wildlife Studies, Arcata, California. 24 pages.
- Gaston, A.J., and S.B.C. Dechesne. 1996. Rhinoceros auklet (*Cerorhinca monocerata*). In: The Birds of North America, No. 212. A. Poole and F. Gill (Eds.). The Academy of Natural Sciences, Philadelphia, PA, and the American Ornithologists' Union, Washington, D.C.
- Gerard, V.A. 1976. Some aspects of material dynamics and energy flow in a kelp forest in Monterey Bay, California. Ph.D. dissertation, University of California Santa Cruz, Santa Cruz, California. 173 pages.
- Gill, A.E. 1980. Evolutionary genetics of California Islands *Peromyscus*. In: Power, D. M. (ed.), The California Islands: Proceedings of a multidisciplinary symposium. Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History, Santa Barbara, CA.
- Goldberg, S.R., and R.L. Bezy. 1974. Reproduction in the island night lizard, *Xantusia riversiana*. *Herpetologica* 30:350-360.
- Goldfarb, W. 1984. Water Law. Butterworth Publishers, Boston. 233 pages.
- Graham, M.H. 2004. Effects of local deforestation on the diversity and structure of southern California giant kelp forest food webs. *Ecosystems* 7:341-357.
- Graham, M.H., Dayton PK, Erlandson JM. 2003. Ice ages and ecological transition on temperate coasts. *Trends Ecol Evol* 18:33-40.
- Gress, F., Risebrough, R.W., Anderson, D.W., Kiff, L.F., and J.R. Jehl Jr. 1973. Reproductive failures of double-crested cormorants in southern California and Baja California. *Wilson Bull.* 85: 197-208.
- Grossman D.H., Faber-Langendoen D., Weakley A.S., Anderson M., Bourgeron P., Crawford R., Goodin K., Landaal S., Metzler K., Patterson K.D., Pyne M., Reid M., and Sneddon L. 1998. International classification of ecological communities: terrestrial vegetation of the United States. Volume I, The National Vegetation Classification System: development, status, and applications. The Nature Conservancy: Arlington, VA.
- Haaker, P.L., Henderson, K.C., and D.O. Parker. 1986. California abalone. California Department of Fish and Game, Marine Resources Division, Long Beach, CA.
- Haaker, P.L., Karpov, K., Rogers-Bennett, L., Taniguchi, I., Friedman, C.S., and M.J. Tegner. 2001. Abalone. In Leet, W.S., Dewees, C.M., Klingbeil, R., and E.J. Larson (Eds.).

California's Living Marine Resources: A Status Report. California Department of Fish and Game. SG01-11. Pages 89-97.

- Haaker, P.L., Parker, D.O., Togstad, H., Richards, D.V., Davis, G.E., and C.S. Friedman. 1992. Mass mortality and withering syndrome in black abalone, *Haliotis cracherodii*, in California. Pages 608 in S.A. Shepherd, M.J. Tegner, and S.A. Guzman del Proo (Eds.). Abalone of the world: Biology, fisheries, and culture. Proceedings of the 1st International Symposium on Abalone. Blackwell Scientific Publications Ltd., Oxford, U.K.
- Halvorson, W.L. and G.J. Maender, G. J. (Eds.). 1994. The Fourth California Islands Symposium: Update on the Status of Resources. Santa Barbara, CA: Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History.
- Halvorson, W.L., S. Junak, C. Schwemm, and T. Keeney. 1996. Plant communities of San Nicolas Island, California. Technical Report 55. National Biological Service, Cooperative Park Studies Unit, University of Arizona, Tucson, AZ.
- Hamilton, J. A. 2004. Kelp bed variability and fish population dynamics in Kachemak Bay, Alaska. M.S. thesis, 57 p. Univ. Alaska Fairbanks, Fairbanks, AK.
- Hamilton, J., and B. Konar. 2007. Implications of substrate complexity and kelp variability for south-central Alaskan nearshore fish communities. Fish. Bull. 105:189-196.
- Hanan, D.A. 1996. Dynamics of Abundance and Distribution for Pacific Harbor Seal, *Phoca vitulina richardsi*, on the Coast of California. Ph.D. Dissertation, University of California Los Angeles, Los Angeles, CA. 158 pages.
- Hanson, C.C., J.E. Bonham, K.J. Campbell, B.S. Keitt, A.E. Little, G. Smith. 2010. The Removal of Feral Cats from San Nicolas Island: Methodology.
- Harrold, C. and D.C. Reed. 1985. Food availability, sea urchin grazing, and kelp forest community structure. Ecology 66: 1160-1169.
- Harthill, M.P., D.M. Long, and B.D. Mishler. 1979. Preliminary List of Southern California Mosses. Bryologist 82(2).
- Harvey, J. T., and D. Goley. 2011. Determining a correction factor for aerial surveys of harbor seals in California. Marine Mammal Science 27(4):719-735.
- Hatfield, B. 2007. Spring 2007 Mainland California Sea Otter Survey Results. U.S.G.S. Western Ecological Research Center, San Simeon, CA.
- HDR. 2013a. Rare Plant Surveys, Naval Base Ventura County, San Nicolas Island, California. Prepared by HDR for Naval Facilities Engineering Command Southwest.
- HDR. 2013b. Bird Point Count Surveys, Naval Base Ventura County, Point Mugu, Port Hueneme, and San Nicolas Island, California. Prepared by HDR for Naval Facilities Engineering Command Southwest.
- HDR. 2014. Vegetation Classification and Mapping, Naval Base Ventura County San Nicolas Island, California. Prepared by HDR for NAVFAC SW. December.

- Heath, C.B. 2002. California, Galapagos, and Japanese sea lions *Zalophus californianus*, *Z. wolfebaeki*, and *Z. japonicus*. Pages 180-186 in W.F. Perrin, B. Wursig, and J.G.M. Thiewissen (Eds.). Encyclopedia of marine mammals. Academic Press.
- Herder, M.J. 1986. Seasonal movements and hauling site fidelity of harbor seals, *Phoca vitulina richardsi*, tagged at the Russian River, California. MS Thesis. Humboldt State University. 52 pages.
- Hierl, Lauren A., J. Franklin, D. H. Deutschman, H. M. Regan, and B. S. Johnson. 2008. Assessing and Prioritizing Ecological Communities for Monitoring in a Regional Habitat Conservation Plan. Environmental Management, Volume 42, Issue 1, pages 165-179.
- Hillinger, C. 1958. The California Islands. Academy Publications, Los Angeles, CA.
- Hobday, A.J. and M.J. Tegner. 2000. Status Review of White Abalone (*Haliotis sorenseni*) Throughout Its Range in California and Mexico. NOAA Technical Memorandum NMFS: NOAA-TM-NMFS-SWR-035.
- Hochberg, F.G. (Ed). 1993. The Third California Islands Symposium: Recent Advances in Research on the California Islands. Santa Barbara, CA: Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History.
- Holbrook, S.J., Carr, M.H., Schmitt, R.J., Coyer, J.A. 1990. Effect of giant kelp on local abundance of reef fishes: the importance of ontogenetic resource requirements. Bulletin of Marine Science 47: 104-114.
- Holston, K.C. and M.E. Irwin. 2005. Revision of the Nearctic *Thereva*: (Diptera: Asiloidea: Therevidae). Studia Dpterologica, Supplement 13, page 107. Halle: Ampyx-Verlag. 10 March.
- Honma, L. 2008. Personnel Observations made during ASBS monitoring on San Nicolas Island in the Fall of 2008.
- Horn, M.H. 1980. Diversity and ecological roles of non-commercial fishes in California marine habitats. California Cooperative Oceanic Fisheries Investigations Reports 21: 37-47.
- Horn, M.H., Allen, L.G., and R.N. Lea. 2006. Biogeography. In Allen, L.G., Pondella, D.J. II, Horn, M.H. editors. The Ecology of Marine Fishes: California and Adjacent Waters. Berkeley, California: University of California Press. Pages 3-25.
- Howorth, P.C. 1978. The abalone book. Naturegraph Publishers, Inc., Happy Camp, CA.
- Huber, H.R. 1991. Changes in the distribution of California sea lions north of the breeding rookeries during the 1982-1983 El Nino. In Pinnipeds and El Nino: response to environmental stress. F. Trillmich and K.A. Ono (Eds.). p. 129-137. Springer-Verlag, Berlin and Heidelberg, Germany.
- Hudgens, B.R. and D.K. Garcelon. 2014. Island Fox Monitoring and Demography on San Nicolas Island- 2013, Final Report. Unpublished report prepared by the Institute of Wildlife Studies, Arcata, California for Naval Base Ventura County Environmental Division. March. 28 pages.
- Hudgens, B.R., K. McHarry, and D.K. Garcelon. 2015. Island Fox Monitoring and Demography on San Nicolas Island- 2014, Final Report. Unpublished report prepared by the Institute

of Wildlife Studies, Arcata, California for Naval Base Ventura County Environmental Division. July. 39 pages.

Ingraham, N.L. and Matthews, R.A. 1995. The importance of fog-drip water to vegetation - Point Reyes Peninsula, California. *Journal of Hydrology*, 164, 269-285.

Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Working Group II. 2007. *Climate Change 2007 - Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability: Contribution of Working Group II to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Fourth Assessment Report. I. P. o. C. Change. Cambridge, U.K., Cambridge University Press.

Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). 2007. *IPCC Fourth Assessment Report: Climate Change 2007*.

http://www.ipcc.ch/publications_and_data/publications_and_data_reports.htm.

International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN). 2010. *IUCN Red List of Threatened Species*. Version 2010.1. <<http://www.iucnredlist.org>>. Accessed 2 June 2010.

Jacobs, D.F., Cole, D.W., and McBride, J.R. 1985. Fire history and perpetuation of natural Coast Redwood ecosystems. *Journal of Forestry*, 83: 494-497.

Jehl, J. R., Jr. 1985. Hybridization and evolution of oystercatchers on the Pacific Coast of Baja California. *Neotropical Ornithology*, A.O.U. monograph 36: 484-504.

Johansen, J.R., L.L. St. Clair, D. Evans, V. Flechtner, J. Balczon, and B.L. Webb. 1998. *Resilience of Microbiotic Species to Military Training Pressures: Natural and Stimulated Recovery Following Disturbance*. Technical Report (Contract DACA88-95-C-0015) USACERL. 210 pages.

Johnson, C.K., Tinker, M.T., Estes, J.A., Conrad, P.A., Staedler, M., Miller, M.A., Jessup, D.A., and J.A.K. Mazet. 2009. Prey choice and habitat use drive sea otter pathogen exposure in a resource limited coastal ecosystem. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 106(7): 2242-2247.

Jolley, W.J., K.J. Campbell¹, N.D. Holmes, D.K. Garcelon, C.C. Hanson, D. Will, B.S. Keitt, G. Smith, A.E. Little. 2012. Reducing the impacts of leg-hold trapping on critically endangered foxes by modified traps and conditioned trap aversion on San Nicolas Island, California.

Jorgensen S.J., N.S. Arnoldi, E.E. Estess, T.K. Chapple, M. Ruckert, S.D. Anderson, B.A. Block. 2012. Eating or Meeting? Cluster Analysis Reveals Intricacies of White Shark (*Carcharodon carcharias*) Migration and Offshore Behavior. *PLoS ONE* 7(10).

Junak, S. 2003. Sensitive Plant Survey, Outlying Landing Field, San Nicolas Island, California, Final Report. Prepared by the Santa Barbara Botanic Garden Technical Report No. 5. Prepared for Department of the Navy, Southwest Division, Naval Facilities Engineering Command and Environmental Planning and Management Department, Naval Air Weapons Station, China Lake, California, Letter of Agreement No. N68711-99-LT-90039.

Junak, S. 2008. *A Flora of San Nicolas Island, California*. Santa Barbara, CA: Santa Barbara Botanic Garden. 235 pages.

Junak, S. and J. Vanderweir. 1990. "An Annotated Checklist of the Vascular Plants of San Nicolas Island, California." Pages 121-145 in: *Proceedings of the Fifth Biennial Mugu*

lagoon/San Nicolas Island Ecological Research Symposium. Naval Air Station, Point Mugu, CA.

- Junak S., T. Ayers, R. Scott, D. Wilken, and D. Young. 1995. *A Flora of Santa Cruz Island*. Santa Barbara Botanic Garden and California Native Plant Society, Santa Barbara and Sacramento, CA. 397 pages.
- Junak, S., Halvorson, W.L., Schwemm, C., and T. Keeney. 1996. Sensitive Plants of San Nicolas Island, California, Phase 2, Technical Report No. 57. United States Geological Survey, Cooperative Park Studies Unit, University of Arizona, Tuscon, AZ.
- Juola, F.A., G.A. Schmidt, P.B. Sharpe, and D.K. Garcelon. 2002. Island Fox Monitoring and Demography on San Nicolas Island-2001. Institute for Wildlife Studies, Arcata, California. 34 pages.
- Karpov, K.A., Haaker, P.L., Taniguchi, I.K., and L. Rogers-Bennett. 2000. Serial depletion and the collapse of the California abalone fishery. Pages 11-24 in A. Campbell, editor. Workshop on rebuilding abalone stocks in British Columbia. Canadian Special Publications, Fish and Aquatic Sciences.
- Keitt, B., R.W. Henry, A.A. Munoz, C. Garcia, L.L. Mendoza, M.A. Hermosillo, B. Tershy, and D. Croll. 2005. El efecto de los gatos introducidos (*Felis catus*) en el ecosistema de Isla Guadalupe. In *Isla Guadalupe restauracion y conservacion*. K. S. d. Prado, and E. Peters (editors). Pages 219-230. Instituto Nacional de Ecologia, Mexico City.
- Kennedy, P.G., and Sousa, W.P. 2006. Forest encroachment into a Californian grassland: examining the simultaneous effects of facilitation and competition on tree seedling recruitment. *Oecologia*, 148:464-474.
- Kenner, M.S, J.A. Estes, M.T. Tinker, J.L. Bodkin, R.K. Cowen, C. Harrold, B.B. Hatfield, M. Novak, A. Rassweiler, D.C. Reed. 2013. A multi-decade time series of kelp forest community structure at San Nicolas Island, California (USA). *Ecological Archives*. 94 (11): 2654.
- Keystone Center. 1996. Keystone Center Policy Dialogue on a Department of Defense (DoD) Biodiversity Management Strategy. T. K. Center. Keystone, Colorado.
- Knudsen, K. and T. Wheeler. 2015. Lichens of San Nicolas Island. To be published on University of California Riverside Herbarium website: <http://herbarium.ucr.edu/>
- Koski, W.R., J.W. Lawson, D.H. Thomson, and W.J. Richardson. 1998. Point Mugu sea range technical report. Rep. by LGL Limited, King City, ON and Ogden Environmental Energy Services, Santa Barbara, CA for U.S. Navy Naval Air Warfare Center, Weapons Division, Point Mugu, CA and Southwest Division Naval Facilities Engineering Command, San Diego, CA. 281 pages.
- Kreuder, C., Miller, M.A., Jessup, D.A., Lowenstine, L.J., Harris, M.D., Ames, J.A., Carpenter, T.E., Conrad, P.A., and J.A.K. Mazet. 2003. Patterns of Mortality in Southern Sea Otters (*Enhydra lutris nereis*) from 1998-2001. *Journal of Wildlife Diseases* 39(3): 495-509.
- Kushlan, J.A. et al. 2002. Waterbird conservation for the Americas: The North America waterbird conservation plan, version 1. Waterbird Conservation for the Americas, Washington, D.C., USA.

- Lafferty, K.D. and A.M. Kuris. 1993. Mass mortality of abalone *Haliotis cracherodii* on the California Channel Islands: tests of epidemiological hypotheses. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 96: 239-248.
- Lafferty, K.D., Behrens, M.D., Davis, G.E., Haaker, P.L., Kushner, D.J., Richards, D.V., Taniguchi, I.K., and M.J. Tegner. 2004. Habitat of endangered white abalone, *Haliotis sorenseni*. *Biological Conservation* 116: 191-194.
- Le Boeuf, B.J., Crocker, D.E., Costa, D.P., Blackwell, S.B., Webb, P.M., and Houser, D.S. 2000. Foraging ecology of northern elephant seals. *Ecological Monographs* 70(3): 353-382.
- Lee, W.S., C.M. Dewees, R. Klingbeil, and E.J. Larson (Editors). 2001. California's living marine resources: A status report. California Department of Fish and Game.
- Lerma, D. 2009. Personnel observation 2009, Observations taken during brine discharge surveys January 2009.
- Lerma, D., and D.V. Richards. 2000. Sand Beach and Coastal Lagoon monitoring, Santa Rosa Island, 1997 Annual Report. Technical Report CHIS-2000-01. Channel Islands National Park, Ventura, CA.
- Lever, C. 1985. Naturalized mammals of the world. Longman, London, NY.
- Lindberg, D.R., K.I. Warheit, and J.A. Estes. 1987. Seasonal predation and prey preference by oystercatchers on limpets at San Nicolas Island, California, USA. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 39:105-113.
- Littler, M.M. and S.N. Murray. 1975. "Impact of sewage on the distribution, abundance, and community structure of rocky intertidal macro-organisms." *Mar. Biol.* 30: 277-91.
- Los Angeles Regional Water Quality Control Board (LARWQCB). 1994. Basin Plan for the Coastal Watershed of Los Angeles and Ventura Counties. Los Angeles, CA.
- LARWQCB. 2007. 2005-2007 Triennial Review for the Channel Islands Watershed Management Area.
- Lowe, S., Browne, M., Boudjelas, S., and M. De Poorter. 2000. 100 of the world's worst invasive alien species. A selection from the global invasive species database. The Invasive Species Specialist Group (ISSG) Species Survival Commission (SSC) of the World Conservation Union (IUCN), Auckland. 11 pages.
- Lowry, M. S., P. Boveng, R. J. DeLong, C. W. Oliver, B. S. Stewart, H. DeAnda, and J. Barlow. 1992. Status of the California sea lion (*Zalophus californianus californianus*) population in 1992. Admin. Rep. LJ-92-32. Southwest Fisheries Science Center, National Marine Fisheries Service, La Jolla, CA 92038. 34 pages
- Mann K. H. 1973. Seaweeds: their productivity and strategy for growth. *Science* 182:975-81.
- Lowry, M.S., Carretta, J.V., and K.A. Forney. 2005. Pacific harbor seal, *Phoca vitulina richardsi*, census in California during May-July 2004. Administrative Report LJ-05-06, available from Southwest Fisheries Science Center, La Jolla, CA. 38 pages.
- Lowry, M.S., Carretta, J.V., and K.A. Forney. 2008. Pacific harbor seal census in California during May-July 2002 and 2004. *California Fish and Game* 94(4): 180-193.

- Lowry, M.S., Stewart, B.S., Heath, C.B., Yochem, P.K., and J.M. Francis. 1991. Seasonal and annual variability in the diet of California sea lions *Zalophus californianus* at San Nicolas Island, California, 1981-1986. *Fishery Bulletin* 89: 331-336.
- Mad River Biologists. 2002. California Coastal National Monument Literature Search and Summarization of Key Biological Resources of the Monument - Seabirds and Marine Mammals. Prepared for Bureau of Land Management California Coastal National Monument.
- Manley, S.J. and D.K. Garcelon. 2013. Survey and Testing of Trapping Techniques for Chukar (*Alectoris chukar*), on San Nicolas Island, California, 2012-2013. Unpublished report prepared by the Institute for Wildlife Studies, Arcata, California. June. 15 pages.
- Mann, K.H. 1973. Seaweeds: their productivity and strategy for growth. *Science* 182: 975-981.
- Manuwal, D.A., Thorensen, A.C. 1993. Cassin's Auklet (*Ptychoramphus aleuticus*). In *The Birds of North America*, No. 50. A. Poole and F. Gill (Eds.). The Academy of Natural Sciences, Philadelphia, PA, and the American Ornithologists' Union, Washington, D.C.
- Martz, P.C. 2003. Prehistoric Settlement and Subsistence on San Nicolas Island. *Proceedings of the Sixth California Islands Symposium*. December 1-3.
- McCann, T.S. 1985. Size, status and demography of southern elephant seal (*Mirounga leonina*) populations. In J.K. Ling and M.M. Bryden (Eds.). *Studies of Sea Mammals in South Latitudes*. South Australian Museum. 132 pages.
- McChesney, G.J., Carter, H.R., Parker, M.W. 2000. Nesting ashy storm-petrels and Cassin's auklets in Monterey County, California. *Western Birds* 31: 178-183.
- McRoy, C.P., and C. McMillan, C. 1977. Production ecology and physiology of seagrasses. In: P.C. McRoy and C Helfferich (eds.) *Seagrass ecosystems: A Scientific Prospective*, Marcel Dekker, New York, pages 53-87.
- Mearns, A.J., M.J. Allen, M.D. Moore, M.J. Sherwood. 1980. Distribution, abundance, and recruitment of softbottom rockfishes (*Scorpaenidae: Sebastes*) on the southern California mainland shelf. *California Cooperative Oceanic Fisheries Investigations Reports* 21: 180-190.
- Melin, S.R. and R.L. DeLong. 1999. Observations of a Guadalupe Fur Seal (*Arctocephalus townsendi*) Female and pup at San Miguel Island, California. *Marine Mammal Science*. 15: 885-888.
- Merkel and Associates, Inc. 2007a. Naval Base Ventura County, San Nicolas Island, Area of Special Biological Significance, Exception Application Package. Prepared for Division of Water Quality State Water Resources Control Board and Los Angeles Regional Water Quality Control Board.
- Merkel and Associates, Inc. 2007b. Naval Base Ventura Country San Nicolas Island: Area of Special Biological Significance, Historical Assessment of Brine Waste Effluent and Storm Water and Compliance History. Prepared for NAVFAC Southwest.
- Miller, S.E. and A.S. Menke. 1981. Entomological Bibliography of the California Islands. *Occasional Papers, Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History*. 11: 1-78.

- Miner, C.M., J.M. Altstatt, P.T. Raimondi, and T.E. Minchinton. 2006. Recruitment failure and shifts in community structure following mass mortality limit recovery prospects of black abalone. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 327: 107-117.
- Mishler, B.D. 1978. The mosses of the Channel Islands, California. *Madroño* 21: 435-438.
- Moody, A. 2000. Analysis of plant species diversity with respect to island characteristics on the Channel Islands, California. *Journal of Biogeography* 27(3): 711-723.
- Morrin, J.G., J.E. Kastendiek, A. Harrington, and N. Davis. 1988. Organisms of a subtidal sand community in southern California. *Bulletin of the Southern California Academy of Sciences* 87: 1-11.
- Morris, R.H., Abbott, D.L., and E.C. Haderlie. 1980. *Intertidal Invertebrates of California*. Stanford University Press, Palo Alto, CA.
- Nabhan, G.P. 1998. *Cultures of Habitat: On Nature, Culture, and Story*. Counterpoint; Washington, D.C.
- National Invasive Species Council. 2001. *Meeting the Invasive Species Challenge: Management Plan*, National Invasive Species Council, 2001.
- National Invasive Species Council. 2008. *National Invasive Species Management Plan 2008–2012*. Department of the Interior. 35 pages.
- National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS). 2001. Endangered and threatened species: Endangered status for white abalone. *Federal Register* 66(103):29046-29055.
- NMFS. 2006. *Biennial Report to Congress on the Recovery Program for Threatened and Endangered Species - October 1, 2004 - September 30, 2006*. N. M. F. S. Office of Protected Resources, Silver Springs, MD: 185 pages.
- NMFS. 2008. *White Abalone Recovery Plan (Haliotis sorenseni)*. National Marine Fisheries Service, Long Beach, CA.
- NMFS. 2009. <http://www.nmfs.noaa.gov/pr/species/invertebrates/whiteabalone.htm>. Accessed 29 December 2009.
- NMFS—Northwest Region. 2004. *Pacific Groundfish Fishery Management Plan Essential Fish Habitat Preliminary Draft Environmental Impact Statement*. Seattle Washington.
- National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA). 1997. *Magnuson-Stevens Act Provisions; Essential Fish Habitat (EFH)*. *Federal Register* 62(244): 66531.
- NOAA. 2001. Endangered and threatened species: endangered status for white abalone. *Federal Register* 29046-29055.
- National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA). 2003. Harbor seal (*Phoca vitulina richardsi*): California Stock.
- NOAA. 2007a. California sea lion (*Zalophus californianus californianus*): U.S. Stock.
- NOAA. 2007b. Northern Elephant Seal (*Mirounga angustirostris*): California Breeding Stock.

- NOAA. 2009. Channel Islands National Marine Sanctuary Management Plan.
- NOAA. 2010. Marine Mammal Protection Act (MMPA) of 1972.
<http://www.nmfs.noaa.gov/pr/laws/mmpa/>. Accessed 30 March 2010.
- National Park Service (NPS). 1985. Channel Islands National Park General Management Plan.
- NPS. 2003. Channel Islands National Park Recovery Strategy for Island Foxes on the Northern Channel Islands.
- National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL). 2008. San Nicolas Island, California Renewable Community Plan Outline, Baseline Development, and Initial Renewable Assessment.
- National Research Council. 1990. Monitoring Academy Press, Washington, D.C.
- National Weather Service. 2007. NWS Detroit/Pontiac weather glossary. Available at <http://www.crh.noaa.gov/dtx/glossary.php>.
- Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS). 2010. Watershed Protection and Flood Prevention. <http://www.nrcs.usda.gov/programs/watershed/>. Accessed 22 March 2010.
- Nature Serve. 2009. Nature Serve Explorer. <http://www.natureserve.org/explorer>.
- Naval Air Warfare Center Aircraft Division Weapons Division. 2008. Naval Air Warfare Center Aircraft Division / Weapons Division Strategic Plan: Charting Our Course.
- Naval Air Warfare Center Weapons Division (NAWCWD). 2002. Final Environmental Impact Statement/Overseas Environmental Impact Statement for Point Mugu Sea Range. Prepared by U.S. Department of the Navy, Naval Air Systems Command, Naval Air Warfare Center Weapons Division, Point Mugu, CA.
- NAWCWD. 2004. <http://www.navair.navy.mil/nawcwg/weather/climatology/sni/sniclima.htm>.
- NAWCWD. 2014. Environmental Assessment for UAS Expansion on San Nicolas Island. Prepared by U.S. Department of the Navy, Naval Air Systems Command, Naval Air Warfare Center Weapons Division. October.
- Naval Air Weapons Station China Lake. 2002. Environmental Assessment for Construction of Supply Pier at San Nicolas Island.
- Naval Base Ventura County (NBVC). 2015. Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan, San Nicolas Island, Naval Base Ventura County, California. Prepared by MMEC Group for NAVFAC Southwest. Contract No. N62473-12-D-2012. June.
- Naval Facilities Engineering Command Southwest (NAVFACSW). 2009. Final Range Condition Assessment (RCA) Decision Point 1 Recommendations Report for Naval Base Ventura County (NBVC), California: Point Mugu, San Nicolas Island, and San Miguel Island. July.
- NAVFAC SW. 2010a. NBVC San Nicolas Island and Fort Hunter Liggett: Activity Overview Plan. Prepared by KTU+A under Naval Facilities Engineering Command Southwest Contract # N62473-08-D-8623 Delivery Order 09.
- NAVFAC SW. 2010b. Final Environmental Assessment for the Development of Wind Energy Facilities on San Nicolas Island, Ventura County, California. Prepared for U.S.

Department of the Navy, Naval Facilities Engineering Command Southwest, 1220 Pacific Highway, San Diego, California 92132-5190. Contract Number N62473-09-D-2602, Delivery Order 0003. August.

Naval Outlying Landing Field (NOLF) San Nicolas Island (SNI). 2003. Master Plan: Nicktown and Public Works Areas.

NOLF SNI. 2006a. Naval Outlying Landing Field (NOLF) San Nicolas Island (SNI) Oil and Hazardous Substances Pollution Contingency Plan.

NOLF SNI. 2006b. Naval Outlying Landing Field (NOLF) San Nicolas Island (SNI) Emergency Response Action Plan - The Red Plan.

Noblet J.A., E.Y. Zeng, R. Baird, R.W. Gossett, R.J. Ozretich, and C.R. Phillips. 2003. Southern California Bight 1998 Regional Monitoring Program: VI. Sediment Chemistry. February 2003. Southern California Coast Water Research Project, Westminster, CA.

Nogales, M., Martin, A., Tershy, B.R., Donlan, C.J., Veitch, D., Puerta, N., Wood, B., and J. Alonso. 2004. A review of feral cat eradication on islands. *Conservation Biology* 18: 310–319.

North, W.J. 1971. The biology of giant kelp beds (*Macrocystis*) in California: introduction and background. *Nova Hedwigia* 32: 1–68.

North, W.J. 1994. Review of *Macrocystis* biology. In: Akatsuka, I. (Eds.). *Biology of economic algae*. The Hague: Academic. Pages 447–527.

Oberbauer, T. 2002. Analysis of vascular plant species diversity of the Pacific Coast islands of Alta and Baja, California. Pages 201-211 in: D. Browne, K Mitchell, and H Chaney. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the fifth California Islands symposium*. 2 volumes. Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History, Santa Barbara, CA.

Odell, D.K. 1974. Seasonal Occurrence of the Northern Elephant Seal, *Mirounga angustirostris*, on San Nicolas Island, California. *J. Mammal.* 55:81-95.

Oliver, J.S., P.N. Slattery, L.W. Hulberg, and J.W. Nybakken. 1980. Relationships between wave disturbance and zonation of benthic invertebrate communities along a subtidal high energy beach in Monterey, California. *U.S. National Marine Fisheries Service Fishery Bulletin* 78: 437-454.

O'Malley, P.G. 1994. "Animal Husbandry on the Three Southernmost Channel Islands: A Preliminary Overview, 1820-1950." Pages 157-164 in: *The Fourth California Islands Symposium: Update on the Status of Resources*, W.L. Halvorson and G.J. Maender (Eds). Santa Barbara, CA: Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History.

Orr, R.T. and C. Helm. 1989. *Marine mammals of California*, revised edition. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press. 93 pages.

Orrock, J. L. and B.F. Allan. 2008. Sin Nombre Virus infection in deer mice, Channel Islands, California. *Emerging Infectious Diseases* 14:1965-1966.

Pacific Fishery Management Council. 2011a. *Fishery Management Plan for U.S. West Coast Fisheries for Highly Migratory Species, As Amended through Amendment 2*. July. 122 pages.

- Pacific Management Fishery Council. 2011b. The Coastal Pelagic Fishery Management Plan. PFMC, Portland. As Amended through Amendment 13, September 2011.
- Pacific Fishery Management Council. 2014. Pacific Coast Groundfish Fishery Management Plan for the California, Oregon, and Washington Groundfish Fishery. May. 158 pages.
- Page, G.W. and L.E. Stenzel (Editors). 1981. The breeding status of the snowy plover in California. *Western Birds* 12(1):1-40.
- Page, G.W. and P.E. Persons. 1995. The snowy plover at Vandenberg Air Force Base: population size, reproductive success and management. Point Reyes Bird Observatory, Stinson Beach, CA. 24 pages plus appendices.
- Page, G.W., L.E. Stenzel, D.W. Winkler, and C.W. Swarth. 1983. Spacing out at Mono Lake: breeding success, nest density, and predation in the snowy plover. *The Auk* 100: 13-24.
- Parr, T. and J. Shrake. 1989. Benthic habitat characterization survey for POCS lease blocks 0514 (Cicero Northwest), 0515 (Tamora), 0516 (Tamora East) and 0517 (Iago). Kinnetic Laboratories Inc., Carlsbad, CA.
- Parry, M. 1990. *Climate change and world agriculture*. Earthscan Publications Limited, London.
- Paton, P.W.C. 1994. Survival estimates for Snowy plovers breeding at Great Salt Lake, Utah. *Condor* 96: 1106-1109.
- Philbrick, R.N. (Ed). 1967. Proceedings of the symposium on the biology of the California Islands. Santa Barbara, CA: Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History.
- Phillbrick, R. and J. Haller. 1977. The Southern California Islands. Pages 893-906 in M. Barbour and J. Major (Eds.). *Terrestrial vegetation of California*. John Wiley and Sons, New York, NY.
- Pilsbry, H.A. 1921. *Manual of Conchology: Volume XXVI, Pupillidae*. Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia. Philadelphia, PA.
- Pondella, D.J. II, Gintert, B.E., Cobb, J.R., and L.G. Allen. 2005. Biogeography of the nearshore rocky-reef fishes at the southern and Baja California islands. *Journal of Biogeography* 32: 187-201.
- Powell, A.N. and C.L. Collier. 1994. The status of western snowy plovers (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*) in San Diego County, 1994. Report to California Department of Fish and Game, Sacramento, CA, and U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Portland, OR. 28 pages.
- Powell, A.N., J.M. Terp, C.L. Collier, and B.L. Peterson. 1997. The status of western snowy plovers (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*) in San Diego County, 1997. Report to the California Department of Fish and Game, Sacramento, CA, and U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Carlsbad, CA and Portland, OR. 34 pages.
- Powell, J. and C. Hogue. 1979. *California Insects*. University of California Press.
- Powell, J. 2005. Lepidoptera Recorded on San Nicolas Island, CA. *Essig Museum of Entomology, University of California*. December.

- Power, D.M. (Editor). 1980. The California Islands: Proceedings of a Multidisciplinary Symposium. Santa Barbara, CA: Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History.
- Raimondi P.T., R.F. Ambrose, J.M. Engle, S.N. Murray, and M. Wilson. 1999. Monitoring of rocky intertidal resources along the central and southern California mainland. 3-Year Report for San Luis Obispo, Santa Barbara, and Orange Counties (Fall 1995- Spring 1998). OCS Study, MMS 99-0032, U.S. Bureau of Energy Management, Regulation, and Enforcement, Pacific OCS Region.
- Ralls, K. and D.B. Siniff. 1990. Time budgets and activity patterns in California sea otters. *Journal of Wildlife Management* 54(2): 257-259.
- Ralls, K., B. Hatfield, and D.B. Siniff. 1995. Foraging patterns of California sea otters based on radiotelemetry. *Canadian Journal of Zoology*.
- Ralph, C.J., G.R. Geupel, P. Pyle, T.E. Martin, and D.F. DeSante 1993. Handbook of Field Methods for Monitoring Landbirds. U.S. Dept. of Agri. For. Ser. Gen. Tech. Rep. PSW-GTR-144.
- Ramsey, D., J.P. Parkes, D. Will, C.C. Hanson, and K.J. Campbell. 2010. Quantifying the success of feral cat eradication, San Nicolas Island, California.
- Raven, P. 1967. The floristics of the California Islands. Pages 57-67 in: R. Philbrick. (ed.) Proceedings of the symposium on the biology of the California islands. Santa Barbara Botanic Garden, Santa Barbara, CA.
- Raven, P.H., and D.I. Axelrod. 1978. Origin and relationships of the California flora. University of California Publications in Botany 72. University of California Press, Berkeley, CA.
- Reeves, R.R., B.S. Stewart, and S. Leatherwood. 1992. The Sierra Club Handbook of Seals and Sirenians. San Francisco, CA: Sierra Club. 359 pages.
- Reeves, R.R., B.S. Stewart, P.J. Clapham, and J.A. Powell. 2002. National Audubon Society guide to marine mammals of the world. New York: Alfred A. Knopf.
- Regional Water Quality Control Board (RWQCB). 1994. Water Quality Control Plan, Los Angeles Region, Basin Plan for the Coastal Watersheds of Los Angeles and Ventura Counties.
- Reusch, T.B.H. and S.L. Williams. 1998. Variable responses of a native eelgrass *Zostera marina* to a non-indigenous bivalve *Musculista senhousia*. *Oecologia* 113: 428-441.
- Rich, T. D., C. J. Beardmore, H. Berlanga, P.J. Blancher, M.S.W. Bradstreet, G.S. Butcher, D.W. Demarest, E.H. Dunn, W.C. Hunter, E.E. I-igo-Elias, J.A. Kennedy, A.M. Martell, A.O. Panjabi, D.N. Pashley, K.V. Rosenberg, C.M. Rustay, J.S. Wendt, T.C. Will. 2004. Partners in Flight North American Landbird Conservation Plan. Cornell Lab of Ornithology. Ithaca, NY. http://www.partnersinflight.org/cont_plan/ (VERSION: March 2005).
- Richards, D.V. 2004. Sand Beach and Coastal Lagoon monitoring, Santa Rosa Island, 2004 Annual Report. Technical Report CHIS-2004-05. Channel Islands National Park, Ventura, CA.
- Richards, D.V. and G.E. Davis. 1993. Early warnings of modern population collapse in black abalone *Haliotis cracherodii*, Leach, 1814 at the California Channel Islands. *Journal of Shellfish Research* 12: 189-194.

- Ricketts, E.F., J. Calvin, J.W. Hedgpeth, and D.W. Phillips. 1985. *Between Pacific Tides*. Stanford, CA, Stanford University Press.
- Riedman, M.L., and J.A. Estes. 1990. The sea otter (*Enhydra lutris*): behavior, ecology, and natural history. U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Biological Report. 90(14). 126 pages.
- Robilliard, G.A., Boehm, P.D., and M.J. Amman. 1997. Ephemeral Data Collection Guidance Manual, With Emphasis on Oil Spill NRDAS. In Proceedings from the 1997 International Oil Spill Conference p. 1029-1030.
- Rodriguez, S., A.R.T. Santiago, G. Shenker. 2001. A public-access GIS-based model of potential species habitat distribution for the Santa Barbara Channel and the Channel Islands National Marine Sanctuary, Donald Bren School of Environmental Science and Management: 130 pages.
- Roemer, G.W., Coonan, T.J., Munson, L., and R.K. Wayne. 2004. Island fox, *Urocyon littoralis*. Canid action plan for the Island fox. In *Canids: foxes, wolves, jackals, and dogs. Status Survey and conservation action plan*. In C. Sillero-Zuiri, M. Hoffman, and D.W. Macdonald (Editors.). Pages 97-105. IUCN/SSC, Canid Specialist Group, IUCN Publications Services Unit, Cambridge, United Kingdom.
- Rogers-Bennett, L., Haaker, P.L., Huff, T.O., and P.K. Dayton. 2002. Estimating baseline abundance of abalone in California for restoration. *CalCOFI Reports* 43: 97-111.
- Saul, S.M. 1982. Clam diggers and snowy plovers. *Washington Wildlife* 32(1): 28-30.
- Sawyer, J.O., T. Keeler-Wolf, and J. Evens. 2009. *A Manual of California Vegetation, Second Edition*. California Native Plant Society, Sacramento, CA.
- Schmidt, G. A., and D. K. Garcelon. 2003. Island Fox Monitoring and Demography on San Nicolas Island–2002. Unpublished report prepared by the Institute for Wildlife Studies, Arcata, California. 22 pages.
- Schmidt, G. A., and D. K. Garcelon. 2004. Island Fox Monitoring and Demography on San Nicolas Island–2003. Unpublished report prepared by the Institute for Wildlife Studies, Arcata, California. 24 pages.
- Schmidt, G. A., B. R. Hudgens, and D. K. Garcelon. 2006. Island Fox Monitoring and Demography on San Nicolas Island–2005. Unpublished report prepared by the Institute for Wildlife Studies, Arcata, California. 24 pages.
- Schmidt, G.A., Hudgens, B.R., and D.K. Garcelon. 2007. Island fox monitoring and demography on San Nicolas Island - 2006. Institute for Wildlife Studies, Arcata, California. 26 pages.
- Schwartz, S.J. 1994. "Ecological Ramifications of Historic Occupation of San Nicolas Island." Pages 171-180 in: *The Fourth California Islands Symposium: Update on the Status of Resources*, W.L. Halvorson and G.J. Maender (Eds.). Santa Barbara, CA: Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History.
- Seagars, D.J. 1984. The Guadalupe fur seal: a status review. Administrative Report SWR-84-6. Southwest Region, National Marine Fisheries Service, Terminal Island, CA.

- Seapy, R.R. and M.M. Littler. 1980. Biogeography of rocky intertidal macroinvertebrates of the southern California islands. In: D.M. Power (ed.) *The California Islands: Proceedings of a Multidisciplinary Symposium*. Haagen Printing, Santa Barbara, CA. Pages 307-324.
- Sibley, D. 2001. *The Sibley Guide to Bird Life and Behavior*. Chanticleer Press, Inc., New York, NY.
- Smith, G.G. 1993. *Special Plants and Animals at Naval Air Weapons Station, Point Mugu, California*. 117 pages.
- Smith, R.I., and J.T. Carlton (Eds.). 1975. *Light's Manual: Intertidal invertebrates of the central California coast*. Third Edition. University of California Press, Berkeley, CA. 716 pages.
- Southern California Coastal Water Research Project (SCCWRP). 2008. *Regional Monitoring Journal Articles, Annual Reports, and Technical Reports*.
http://www.sccwrp.org/view.php?action=quick_publications&id=95.
- State Water Resources Control Board (SWRCB). 1976. *Areas of Special Biological Significance*. California Environmental Protection Agency, State Water Resources Control Board.
- SWRCB. 2001. *Water Quality Control Plan for Ocean Waters of California: California Ocean Plan*. California Environmental Protection Agency, State Water Resources Control Board.
- SWRCB. 2003. *State Water Resources Control Board Marine State Water Quality Protection Areas - Areas of Special Biological Significance*. California Environmental Protection Agency, State Water Resources Control Board.
- SWRCB. 2004. *Policy for Implementation and Enforcement of the Nonpoint Source Pollution Control Program*.
- SWRCB. 2010. *Water Words - Glossary and Definitions - A Compilation of Technical Water, Water Quality, Environmental, and Water Related Terms: Low Impact Development*.
http://www.swrcb.ca.gov/publications_forms/available_documents/water_words/words_1.pdf.
- SWRCB and California Regional Water Quality Control Boards (RWQCB). 1970. *SWRCB and California RWQCB's Administrative Procedures, September 24, 1970, Section XI, Miscellaneous (Rev. 7-9/1/1972), Designation of Areas of Special Biological Significance*.
- Stebbins, R.C. 2003. *A Field Guide to Western Reptiles and Amphibians*. New York, New York. Houghton Mifflin Company.
- Steneck, R.S., M.H. Graham, B.J. Bourque, D. Corbett, J. M. Erlandson, J. A. Estes, and M. J. Tegner. 2002. Kelp forest ecosystems: biodiversity, stability, resilience, and future. *Environ. Cons.* 29:436; 459.
- Stenzel, L.E., Warriner, J.C., Warriner, J.S., Wilson, K.S., Bidstrup, F.C., and G.W. Page. 1994. Long-distance breeding dispersal of snowy plovers in western North America. *Journal of Animal Ecology* 63: 887-902.
- Stewart, B.S. 1997. "Ontogeny of differential migration and sexual segregation in northern elephant seals." *Journal of Mammalogy* 78(4): 1101-1116.

- Stewart, B.S. and P.K. Yochem. 1984. Seasonal abundance of pinnipeds on San Nicolas Island, California, 1980-1982. *Bulletin of the Southern California Academy of Sciences* 83: 121-132.
- Stewart, B.S. and P.K. Yochem. 1994. Ecology of harbor seals in the Southern California Bight. In W.L. Halvorson and G.J. Maender (Eds.), *The Fourth California Islands Symposium: Update on the status of resources*, p. 123-134. Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History, Santa Barbara, CA.
- Stewart, B.S., and H.R. Huber. 1993. *Mirounga angustirostris*. *Mammalian Species* 449: 1-10.
- Stewart, B.S., and R.L. DeLong. 1989. The Ecology and Population Biology of the Northern Elephant Seal, *Mirounga angustirostris* Gill 1866, on the Southern California Channel Islands. Ph.D. Dissertation, University of California Los Angeles, Los Angeles, CA. 195 pages.
- Stewart, B.S., and R.L. DeLong. 1995. Double migrations of the northern elephant seal, *Mirounga angustirostris*. *Journal of Mammalogy* 76(1): 196-205.
- Stewart, J.G. and B. Myers. 1980. "Assemblages of algae and invertebrates in Southern California Phyllospadix-dominated intertidal habitats." *Aquatic Botany* 9:73-94.
- Suckling, K. and Garcelon, D.K. 2000. Petition to list four island fox subspecies as Endangered. Petition submitted to the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, 1 June 2000. Center for Biological Diversity, Tuscon, Arizona, and Institute for Wildlife Studies, Arcata, California, USA.
- Sustainable Sites Initiative. 2010. The Sustainable Sites Initiative. <http://www.sustainableites.org/>. Accessed 12 August 2010.
- Tetra Tech, Inc. 2011. San Nicolas Island Biosecurity Plan, Naval Base Ventura County, California. Prepared for Naval Facilities Engineering Command Southwest and Naval Base Ventura County. May.
- Tetra Tech, Inc. 2015. 2014–2015 Bat Survey Report, Naval Base Ventura County, Point Mugu and San Nicolas Island, California. Prepared for Naval Facilities Engineering Command Southwest and Naval Base Ventura County. August.
- Thatcher, T. 1990. Understanding interdependence in the natural environmental: some thoughts on cumulative impact assessment under the National Environmental Policy Act. *Environmental Law* 20(3):611-647.
- Thom R.M., D.K. Shreffler, and K.B. Macdonald. 1994. *Shoreline armoring effects on coastal ecology and biological resources in Puget Sound. Coastal Erosion Management Studies, Volume 7. Shorelands and Coastal Zone Management Program*, Washington Department of Ecology, Olympia, Washington.
- Tierra Data, Inc. (TDI). 2009. Vegetation Condition Evaluation Report, Outlying Landing Field, San Nicolas Island, San Nicolas Island, California. Prepared for Naval Base Ventura County, San Nicolas Island Environmental Division.
- Trask, L.B. 1900. Dying San Nicolas. *Land of Sunshine* 13(2):95-100.

- U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (USACE). 2013. Delineation of areas within Corps jurisdiction at Naval Base Ventura County Point Mugu and Port Hueneme, conducted November 2011. Los Angeles District Regulatory Branch.
- U.S. Department of Defense (DoD). 2008. Department of Defense Instruction Number 4715.16, Cultural Resources Management. 18 September 2008.
- DoD. 2011. Department of Defense Instruction Number (DoDINST) 4715.03, Natural Resources Conservation Program. 18 March.
- DoD. 2013. Department of Defense Office of the Under Secretary of Defense Memorandum: Department of Defense Manual 4715.03, Integrated Natural Resource Management Plan (INRMP) Implementation Manual. 25 November.
- U.S. Department of the Navy (DoN). 2005. Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan for San Nicolas Island, California, 2006-2010. 135 pages.
- DoN. 2006. Department of the Navy Office of the Chief of Naval Operations Integrated Natural Resources Management Plant Guidance for Navy Installations: How to Prepare, Implement, and Revise Integrated Natural Resource Management Plans (5090 N456K/6U838101 10 April 2006), April 2006.
- DoN. 2007. San Nicolas Island Seabird Restoration: Project Plan for Cat Eradication April 2007. Prepared by Island Conservation for U.S. Navy Environmental Department, Outlying Landing Field, San Nicolas Island, Ventura County, CA and Naval Facilities Engineering Command, Southwest, San Diego, CA, and Montrose Settlements Trustee Council under Cooperative Agreement N68711-05-LT-A0039.
- DoN. 2014a. Chief of Naval Operations Instruction Number 5090.1D (OPNAVINST 5090.1D) Environmental Readiness Program. 10 January 2014.
- DoN. 2014b. Chief of Naval Operations Manual 5090.1 (OPNAV M-5090.1) Environmental Readiness Program Manual. 10 January 2014.
- DoN Pacific Fleet. 2008. United States Navy Pacific Fleet Southern California Range Complex Environmental Impact Statement /Overseas Environmental Impact Statement.
- U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA). 2008. Climate Change on Aquatic Invasive Species and Implications (Final Report Feb. 2008).
- EPA. 2010a. Federal Insecticide, Fungicide, and Rodenticide Act (FIFRA). <http://www.epa.gov/agriculture/Ifra.html>. Accessed 22 March 2010.
- EPA. 2010b. History of the Clean Air Act. http://www.epa.gov/air/caa/caa_history.html. Accessed 22 March 2010.
- EPA. 2010c. Summary of the Resource Conservation and Recovery Act. <http://www.epa.gov/lawsregs/laws/rcra/html>. Accessed 23 March 2010.
- EPA. 2010d. Comprehensive Environmental Response, Compensation, and Liability Act (CERCLA). <http://www.epa.gov/superfund/policy/cercla.html>. Accessed 23 March 2010.
- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS). 1976. Proposed Endangered or Threatened Status for 32 U.S. Snails. Federal Register 41(83): 17742-17747.

- USFWS. 1984. Recovery Plan for the Endangered and Threatened Species of the California Channel Islands. U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Portland Oregon. 165 pages.
- USFWS. 1987a. Endangered and Threatened Wildlife and Plants; Establishment of an Experimental Population of Southern Sea Otters; Final Rule. Federal Register. Department of Interior USFWS. 52: 29754-29784.
- USFWS. 1987b. Final Environmental Impact Statement: Translocation of southern sea otters. O. o. S. O. C. Prepared by U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Sacramento, California, and Institute of Marine Sciences, University of California, Santa Cruz, California.
- USFWS. 1988. Endangered and Threatened Wildlife and Plants; Technical Amendments to the Sea Otter Translocation Regulations. Federal Register. Department of Interior USFWS. 53: 37577-37581.
- USFWS. 2000. Service guidance on the siting, construction, operation and decommissioning of communications towers. Division of Habitat Conservation and Division of Migratory Bird Management, Fish and Wildlife Service, Arlington, Virginia
<http://migratorybirds.fws.gov/issues/towers/comtow.html>.
- USFWS. 2001. Biological Opinion (BO) for Activities on San Nicolas Island, California.
- USFWS. 2001. United States Shorebird Conservation Plan.
- USFWS. 2002. North American Waterbird Conservation Plan.
- USFWS. 2003a. Final Revised Recovery Plan for the Southern Sea Otter (*Enhydra lutris nereis*). Portland, Oregon. xi + 165 pages.
- USFWS. 2003b. Service Interim Guidance on Avoiding and Minimizing Wildlife Impacts from Wind Turbines.
- USFWS. 2004a. North American Waterfowl Management Plan.
- USFWS. 2004b. Endangered and threatened wildlife and plants; listing the San Miguel Island fox, Santa Rosa Island fox, Santa Cruz Island fox, and Santa Catalina Island fox as Endangered. 69 FR 10335.
- USFWS. 2005. Regional Seabird Conservation Plan Pacific Region.
- USFWS. 2006. News Release: SERVICE INITIATES REVIEW OF ISLAND NIGHT LIZARD TO DETERMINE IF REMOVAL FROM ESA PROTECTION IS WARRANTED. U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service Carlsbad Fish and Wildlife Office 6010 Hidden Valley Road, Carlsbad, California 92011. http://www.fws.gov/carlsbad/NR/Inl_delisting_findings_nr.pdf. Accessed 21 February 2010.
- USFWS. 2007a. Recovery Plan for the Pacific Coast Population of the Western Snowy Plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*). In two volumes. California/Nevada Operations Office, Sacramento, California. Xiv +715 pages.
- USFWS. 2007b. Listed distinct population segment of the brown pelican (*Pelecanus occidentalis*), 5 Year Review: Summary and Evaluation.
<http://www.fws.gov/arcata/es/birds/brnPelican/documents/2007>.

- USFWS. 2008. Birds of Conservation Concern 2008. United States Department of Interior, Fish and Wildlife Service, Division of Migratory Bird Management, Arlington, Virginia. 85 pages. <http://www.fws.gov/migratorybirds/>.
- USFWS. 2009a. 2009 Summer Window Survey for Snowy Plovers on U.S. Pacific Coast with 2005-2008 Results for Comparison. <http://www.fws.gov/arcata/es/birds/WSP/documents/2009%20Pacific%20Coast%20breeding%20SNPL%20survey.pdf>
- USFWS. 2009b. Final Environmental Assessment for the Restoration of San Nicolas Island's Seabirds and Protection of other Native Fauna by Removing Feral Cats. Report on behalf of the Montrose Natural Resources Trustee Council and U.S. Navy.
- USFWS. 2010. Biological Opinion for the San Nicolas Island Wind Energy Project, Ventura County, California (8-8-10-F-35).
- USFWS and National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS). 1998. Endangered Species Consultation Handbook, Procedures for Conducting Consultation and Conference Activities Under Section 7 of the Endangered Species Act, March 1998, Final.
- U.S. Geological Survey (USGS). 2003. USGS WERC Fact Sheet, Rare Plants in Channel Island National Park. <http://www.werc.usgs.gov/fs/rareplants.pdf>. Accessed 2 September 2009.
- University of California Santa Cruz (UCSC) California Institute of Environmental Studies (CIES). 2006. More signs of return for California brown pelicans. UCSC Currents Online, Volume 10, Number 41, June 12-18 2006. <http://currents.ucsc.edu/05-06/06-12/pelicans.asp>.
- VanBlaricom, G.R. 1978. Distribution, predation, and resource allocation in a high-energy sand-bottom ecosystem; Experimental analysis of critical structuring processes for the infaunal community. Ph.D. Dissertation, University of California San Diego. 328 pages.
- VanBlaricom, G.R. 1993. Dynamics and distribution of black abalone populations at San Nicolas Island, California. Pages 323-334 in F. G. Hochberg, editor. Third California Islands Symposium: recent advances in research on the California Islands. Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History, Santa Barbara, CA.
- VanBlaricom, G.R. 2008. Unpublished Data. January through November 2008 long term black abalone population monitoring program data.
- Vantuna Research Group (VRG). 2009. Fisheries Inventory and Utilization of San Diego Bay, San Diego, California for Surveys Conducted in April and July 2008.
- Vedder J. and D. Howell. 1980. Topographic evolution of the southern California borderland during late Cenozoic time. Pages 7-31 in: D.Power (ed.) The California Islands: proceedings of a multi-disciplinary symposium. Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History, Santa Barbara, CA.
- Vedder, J. and R. Norris. 1963 Geology of San Nicolas Island, California. U.S. Geological Survey Professional Paper 369, U.S. Government Printing Office, Washington D.C. 65 pages, maps.
- Von Bloeker, J.C. 1967. The land mammals of the southern California Islands. In: Philbrick, R. N. (ed.), Proceedings of the symposium on the biology of the California Islands. Santa Barbara Botanic Garden, pages 245-263.

- Wallace, E.A.H and G.E. Wallace. 1998. Brandt's Cormorant. In *The Birds of North America: Life Histories for the 21st Century*. No. 362. A. Poole and F. Gill (Eds.). The Academy of Natural Sciences, Philadelphia, PA and the American Ornithologists' Union, Washington, D.C.
- Wallace, G. 1985. Vascular plants of the Channel Islands of southern California and Guadalupe Island, Baja California, Mexico. *Natural history Museum of Los Angeles County, Contributions in Science* 365:1-136.
- Warriner, J.S., J.C. Warriner, G.W. Page, and L.E. Stenzel. 1986. Mating system and reproductive success of a small population of polygamous snowy plovers. *Wilson Bulletin* 98(1): 15-37.
- Wayne, R.K. S.B. George, D. Gilbert, and P.W. Collins. 1991a. The Channel Island fox (*Urocyon littoralis*) as a model of genetic change in small populations. Pages 639-649 in Dudley, E.C., (ed.), *The Unity of Evolutionary Biology: Proceedings of the Fourth International Congress of Systematic and Evolutionary Biology, Vol II*. Discorides Press, Portland, Oregon.
- Wayne, R.K., S.B. George, D. Gilbert, P.W. Collins, S.D. Kovach, D. Girman, and N. Lehman. 1991b. A morphological and genetic study of the Island fox, *Urocyon littoralis*. *Evolution* 45(8): 1849-1868.
- Wehtje, W. 2000. Status, Distribution and Habitat Associations of Six Breeding Land Bird Species on San Nicolas Island. Prepared for NAWS/CL by the Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History.
- Weseloh, C.V.C, C. Pekarik, and H. Blokpoel. 1999. Breeding populations of cormorants, gulls, and terns of the Canadian Great Lakes in 1997/1998. *Bird Trends (Canadian Wildlife Service)* 7:30-34.
- Western Regional Climate Center (WRCC). 2010.
<http://www.wrcc.dri.edu/cgi-bin/cliMAIN.pl?ca7870>. Accessed 20 August 2010.
- Wharton, W.G. and K.H. Mann. 1981. Relationships between destructive by the sea urchin *Strongylocentrus droebachienisi*, and the abundance of the American lobster *Homarus americanus* on the Atlantic coast of Nova Scotia. *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Science* 38: 1339-1349.
- Whittaker, R.J. 1998. *Island Biogeography: Ecology, Evolution, and Conservation*. Oxford University Press, Oxford; New York, NY.
- Wicksten, M.K. 1980. "Mainland and insular assemblages of benthic decapod crustaceans of southern California." In: D.M. Power, e.d. *The California Islands: Proceedings of a Multidisciplinary Symposium*. Haagen Printing, Santa Barbara, CA. Pages 357-367.
- Widrig, R.S. 1980. Snowy plovers at Leadbetter Point: An opportunity for wildlife management? Prepared for the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Willapa NWR, Ilwaco, WA. 14 pages.
- Wilson, D.E., M.A. Bogan, R.L. Brownell, A.M. Burdin Jr., and M.K. Maminov. 1991. Geographic variation in sea otters, *Enhydra lutris*. *J. Mamm.* 72(1): 22-36.
- Wilson, R.A. 1980. Snowy plover nesting ecology on the Oregon coast. MS Thesis, Oregon State University, Corvallis. 41 pages.

- Wilson-Jacobs, R. and G.L. Dorsey. 1985. Snowy plover use of Coos Bay north spit, Oregon. *Murrelet* 66(3):75-81.
- Wolf, S.G. 2002. The relative status and conservation of island breeding seabirds in California and northwest Mexico. M. Sc. Thesis. University of California, Santa Cruz, California.
- Wyda, J.C., L.A. Deegan, J.E. Hughes, and M.J. Weaver. 2002. "The response of fishes to submerged aquatic vegetation complexity in two ecoregions of the Mid-Atlantic Bight: Buzzards Bay and Chesapeake Bay," *Estuaries* 25, 86-100.
- Zobell, C.E. 1971. Drift seaweeds on San Diego County beaches. *Nova Hedwigia* 32:269-314.